

Risk avoidance, opportunities, economic development, global governance, peace, Reclassify social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives

Reclassify social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives

----- Novel Strategies for Maintaining Durable Global Peace-12

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Abstract

Marx etc. identified and planned six social systems. However, this article believes that the social systems identified by Marx and their progress and classification are too simple and abstract, making it difficult to accurately describe the social systems of some countries, and also lead to ideological confrontations between some countries, increasing the risk of war. Moreover, more importantly, the concepts of leadership in different countries are different. Leadership selection methods in different countries are different. The interest classes represented by the leadership in different countries are different. The moral levels of leadership in different countries are different. Leadership empathy in different countries is different. The philosophies followed by leadership in different countries are different. The political and economic theories followed by leaders in different countries are different. Perhaps there are controlling groups behind the leadership of some countries. The controlling groups behind the leadership of different countries are different. The purpose of formulating policies by leadership in different countries are different. The concepts of people in different countries are different. The moral levels of people in different countries are different. The empathy of people in different countries is different. The life logics followed by people in different countries are different. The religious logics followed by people in different countries are different. The biological or genetic differences of people in different countries are different. Regional and climatic differences in different countries are different. The customs of people in different countries are different. The ways of accumulating wealth in different countries are different. Some countries are inclined to carry out large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, live organ harvesting, massacre, plunder, and live burial when opportunities arise, or use national government agencies, local administrative agencies, local armed forces or national armies to protect these anti-human criminal acts. The people of some countries like to commit crimes across the board and support and encourage the army to carry out large-scale massacres of civilians and plunder of wealth. The ways in which different countries implement democracy are different. The degree of discourse power

that people in different countries have is different. The degree of freedom that people in different countries have is different. The level of punishment for heinous crimes in different countries is different. The level of fairness and justice in law enforcement varies from country to country. The level of assistance to vulnerable groups also varies from country to country. This makes there be obvious differences in the construction of social systems in different countries. Therefore, human social systems must have more detailed subdivisions.

Social systems are closely linked to economic development. The Ronald Coase theorem can explain institutional changes from a specific perspective, but it cannot answer the basic question of "what is an institution." Douglass North tried to construct a complete set of institutional change theories and use them to explain the evolution of European history. But he also faced the same challenge and could not precisely define or describe institutions. Until his later years, North was still constantly trying and hoping to introduce a variety of emerging economic theories to define institutions. He tried many methods, such as evolutionary game theory, behavioral economics, and neuroeconomics, but the results were not very successful. Based on the shortcomings of past definitions of social systems, this article redefines social system.

The current social system in the United States is similar to the system in the late Tang Dynasty and can be regarded as the 4.0 version improved from the system of the late Tang Dynasty. This is manifested in private monopolies over land and the financial sector, with a pronounced trend towards asset consolidation leading to highly concentrated social wealth and severe inflation problems. Currency issuance is controlled by private banks, and U.S. debt has spiraled out of control. While taxation is nominally under national control, it is effectively influenced by private companies. Despite being the world's largest economy, the United States is forced to rely on China to buy U.S. Treasury bonds to sustain itself, clearly demonstrating the extreme self-interest of the U.S. system and government. Unless the United States achieves a fair distribution of land ownership, it will inevitably fall into the cycle of historical periodicity, facing threats of decline, disintegration, frequent financial and economic crises, and even war.

However, an absolutely idealized socialist system also does not exist; only a relatively equal socialist system is realistic. **The current socialist system with Chinese characteristics can be seen as an improved version 4.0 of the equal-field system (均田制) of the early Tang Dynasty.** In China, land is either state-owned or collectively owned, with core assets under state control, and a market-oriented economy serves as a supplementary model to prevent private monopolies. This system is relatively fair, conforms to historical laws, and is conducive to breaking free from historical cyclical patterns. The continuous improvement of the equal-field system from the early Tang Dynasty is undoubtedly a common aspiration and goal of human progress.

Marx's naming of the socialist social system brought great difficulties and differences in understanding and cognition to later practitioners, and provided opportunities for those who create ideological confrontations between the East and the West. As a similar practice to the communist system, the kibbutz in Israel, a capital-dominated country, has achieved remarkable results in the past 100 years or so,

indicating that the implementation of a communist-like distribution system according to needs is feasible on a local scale and may reduce ideological opposition. Today, there has been a serious setback in global ethics. Conflicts and wars continue, and the whole world is in a dilemma. This highlights the urgent need for humanity to choose at least one empathetic social system and establish a negative feedback mechanism to effectively govern, prevent the emergence of evil forces, promptly combat criminal acts, reduce wars, restore world peace and stability, and get rid of humanity's chaotic predicament. Therefore, considering the complexity and diversity of human society from philosophical, methodological and historical perspectives and reclassifying human social systems will help the public identify the advantages and disadvantages of social systems and help eliminate this ideological opposition in the hearts of people around the world. At the same time, according to different characteristics, moral levels and whether they are pirate-plundering countries, the public can quickly identify the systems of these countries and choose, avoid, change or eliminate the social systems of some countries. Finally, this article reclassifies human social systems like an encyclopaedia from historical and philosophical perspectives.

It should be emphasized that, the reclassification of human social systems is hoped to help just - minded and well - meaning merchants, investors and entrepreneurs quickly choose suitable partners, be vigilant against unexpected heavy losses in business activities and huge traps following sweet - sounding offers. It is also helpful for politicians with a sense of justice and conscience and countries to conduct government activities and choose long - term cooperation partners, to be vigilant against and prevent evil countries from launching wars, and to establish the concept of warvigilance (war-vigilance, WV). Eliminating criminals who commit large-scale crimes and their protectors, and reconstructing human society and some inferior criminal countries will inevitably bring huge business opportunities, economic development, and peace and stability.

Keywords: philosophy · world peace · conflict · strategy · civilization · global governance · national governance ethics · global consensus · religion · history · religious ethics · fabricate · sustainable development · politics · political ethics · fictional · World War II · US economic system · universal values · human rights · equal-field system · 均田制 · socialism · communist system · Tang Dynasty · historical cyclical pattern · **social system** · Marx · sex slave · Rape · gang rape · ideology · financial oligarch · financial magnate · plutocrat · Huang Chao uprising · economic crisis · Methodology · Jesus · Jehovah · Savior · Catholicism · Judaism · Yahweh · Christianity · God · primitive society · slave society · feudal society · capitalist society · empathy · marketization · United Nations conventions · capitalization · self-discipline · marketization · **kibbutz** · constitutions · market-oriented economy · Soviet Union · **civilized society** · **National Democracy** · **Country's Democracy** · **Democratic Country** · **Warvigilance** · telecom fraud · kidnap · torture · organ harvesting · massacre · rape · gang rape · atomic bomb · psychological warfare · **Hiroshima** · **Nagasaki** · **defense behavioral economics** · **military behavioral economics** · **war behavioral economics** · **rural behavioral economy** · conscience · party

behavioral economics (political -party behavioral economics) · government behavioral economics · **politician behavioral economics** · political vigilance (political vigilance) · institutional economics · Coase theorem · **super-large criminal country-type underworld society** ·

34.1. As a system name, socialist society leads to difficulties in cognition and understanding

Marx's selection and definition of the name of the socialist society's system are inappropriate. First, the name of "socialist society" itself lacks salience and intuitiveness. Even many Chinese national leaders had long had difficulty in truly understanding the concept of socialism from engaging in socialist movements in the 1920s to 40 years after the founding of the People's Republic of China, resulting in many cognitive confusions and disputes about the conceptual extension of this society and how this society should develop. Similar confusions also occurred in the former Soviet Union.

Second, among the six different institutional societies designed by Marx, all have names for societies. "Socialist" is similar and repetitive to the noun "society." Therefore, "socialist" is not suitable to be used as the name of a social system. The socialist society understood by Marx is a state capitalist system in which the state controls all land resources and means of production. The socialism understood by China is that the ownership of land belongs to the state and peasant collectives, and peasants have a certain degree of farming rights. In today's China, the arable land owned by peasants does not need to be taxed, and basic family housing does not need to be taxed annually.

Given that this term has been used for a long time, if different countries have a purely socialist system, some attributives should be added before it to distinguish the real social system of that country. If the government, army or people of a country like to massacre the people of other countries on a large scale, rape the people or their descendants of other countries or plunder the property of descendants of other countries after obtaining assistance or when the country encounters a crisis, even if the country's system is nominally called socialism and the ruling party is the Communist Party, it is obviously deceptive. That country is simply using the Communist Party to deceive its own people or the people of other countries and should be classified as a pirate-like, fraud-type, massacre-type, rape-type or without empathy country.

Third, Karl Marx never came to China and did not conduct in-depth research on Chinese history. He lacked understanding and awareness of the changes in social systems that China has experienced. In fact, in Chinese history, there were dynasties that had implemented a socialist-like system. In the Xin Dynasty founded by Wang Mang after the end of the Western Han Dynasty in China, in some social systems and methods, there even appeared an equal socialist system similar to that of today in the 20th - 21st century. For example, at that time, in terms of political and economic policy reforms, Wang Mang vigorously promoted the reform of state ownership of land. He nationalized a large amount of land in the hands of local tyrants, officials and religious

institutions, prohibited private land transactions, and redistributed it according to the local population, striving to achieve an ideal state where everyone has land to cultivate. Second, he nationalized the management rights of important materials such as salt, iron, and wine, and used state power to balance prices and prevent businessmen from obtaining high profits. These thoughts were very avant-garde at that time. In the new policies implemented by Wang Mang, he introduced a system of interest-free loans and low-interest loans by the government, which is very rare in China's thousands of years of history. The land system of Wang Mang's Xin Dynasty laid the foundation for the implementation of the equal-field system in the later Northern Wei Dynasty, Sui Dynasty, and Tang Dynasty in China. Today's socialist system in China may be renamed an improved version of the Wangtian system or an improved version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty or the 4.0 version of the new equal-field system.

Perhaps Marx could not find a good name for the society between capitalist society and communist society at that time. Therefore, he adopted a very abstract, vague and difficult-to-identify word "socialism." To a certain extent, this has provided material for ideological opposition between eastern and western countries. In the future, the naming of socialist society may be cancelled, or retained for historical reasons.

34.2. The composition of human society

From a historical perspective, both Marx and past sociological theories have overlooked the composition of human society. This neglect has resulted in the prolonged inability of human society to eradicate groups that commit large-scale crimes. Instead, a series of systems have been established to protect such criminal groups, harming victims, kind-hearted individuals, and those with a sense of justice. This has resulted in a blurring of the lines between justice and evil in human society, resulting in the continued occurrence of large-scale heinous crimes and wars of aggression.

Human society is composed of humans and evil humanoid creatures that can speak the human language. Further speaking, human society is made up of kind-hearted people, people with a sense of justice, neutral humans, people lacking empathy, groups that fabricate and invent religious beliefs to commit large-scale crimes (including manufacturing drugs such as opium and trafficking drugs such as opium), evil people, evil races, and groups of humanoid criminals with an appearance just like that of humans. The human social system is inevitably formed in the struggle where some groups commit injustices, plunder wealth, massacre kind-hearted groups and commit evil crimes, while other groups pursue justice, fairness, power, wealth and resist evil.

The process of the evolution of human social civilization is a process of mutual struggle between kind-hearted people and those with a sense of justice on one hand, and groups of evil criminals on the other. It is a process in which kind-hearted people, those with a sense of justice, and neutral people are enslaved, defrauded, kidnapped, tortured, plundered, raped, gang-raped, poisoned with drugs, buried alive, and massacred by people lacking empathy, evil people, evil races, and criminal humanoid creatures. It is a process in which kind-hearted and justice-minded people, after

awakening, strive to protect themselves and their kind, and resolutely eliminate and wipe out evil people, evil races, criminal humanoid creatures that look like humans, criminal races, or criminal countries. It is also a process in which kind-hearted and justice-minded people continuously guide the moral evolution of neutral people and those lacking empathy, and constantly combat and reform evil people. Reducing and eliminating evil humanoid creatures that commit heinous crimes is not a crime, nor is it anti-human; rather, it is a process of purifying human society. Conversely, protecting and tolerating these evil humanoid creatures, as well as the groups or nations formed by them, constitutes a grave crime against victims, kind-hearted individuals, and those with a sense of justice.

34.3. Redefining the Social System

Social systems are closely linked to economic development. The Ronald Coase theorem can explain institutional changes from a specific perspective, but it cannot answer the basic question of "what is an institution." Douglass North tried to construct a complete set of institutional change theories and use them to explain the evolution of European history. But he also faced the same challenge and could not precisely define or describe institutions. Until his later years, Douglass North was still constantly trying and hoping to introduce a variety of emerging economic theories to define institutions. He tried many methods, such as evolutionary game theory, behavioral economics, and neuroeconomics, but the results were not very successful. Based on the shortcomings of past definitions of social systems, this article redefines social systems.

The author of this article believes that the definition of the social system can be determined in the following way. The social system refers to the general term for one or more systems that reflect and maintain a certain social form or social structure and achieve the inevitable results of that society. It includes the economic, political, legal, cultural, educational and other systems of society. **If the social system is elaborated in ecological and vivid language, the following definitions can be made: A vivid description of the definition of the social system: the general term for one or more systems that lead to what the trunk, branches, leaves and flowers of a society look like and what kind of fruit will inevitably be borne.**

34.4. The current land system in China continues and reforms the land system of the early Tang Dynasty to a certain extent.

The early Tang Dynasty's equal-field system (均田制) was an important land system, with its core being the redistribution of land to ensure that every farmer had a certain amount of land to sustain their livelihood and production. According to this system, most of the land belonged to the imperial court, effectively belonging to the state.

The establishment of this land ownership system was intended to ensure that the State could control land resources and safeguard its interests in agricultural production and taxation. In addition, it aimed to safeguard the rights of the farmers and prevent social instability caused by excessive land concentration. By transferring ownership of land to the State, farmers were provided with more security in using the land and were

less likely to lose it, thus enhancing their stability and dependency on land.

The Equal-Field System of the Tang Dynasty was an important land system in the history of Chinese feudal society. It advocated the equal distribution of State land to farmers according to certain standards and the collection of corresponding taxes and levies. As a system with universal values, the Equal-Field System emphasized social fairness and stability, trying to balance the distribution of social resources and prevent excessive wealth disparity.

"Valuing farming as the foundation" was one of the important values in ancient Chinese society. The implementation of the Equal-Field System ensured, to a certain extent, that farmers had the basic means of production—land—and safeguarded their rights to subsistence and development. This policy achieved considerable success in the early Tang Dynasty, helping to prevent excessive concentration of land and ensure the livelihood of the common people, thereby promoting social and economic stability and development.

However, over time, the Equal-Field System in the Tang Dynasty gradually fell into disuse due to bureaucracy, hereditary family systems, and warfare. Land started to be accumulated by the powerful and landlords, resulting in farmers losing their land and forming a large population of landless or land-poor peasants. This intensified social contradictions and eventually became a major factor in the social collapse of the later Tang Dynasty.

In modern China's rural land system, the basic framework of collective ownership is retained, with the implementation of the household contract responsibility system. To a certain extent, today's peasants' land system can be seen as a continuation of the equal-field system of the Tang Dynasty, which similarly emphasized the guarantee of the broad peasantry's land use rights, trying to avoid the extreme concentration of land resources to maintain social stability and harmony.

Despite new demands posed by the development of the market economy for the commercialization of the land, if China were to fully marketize the land (**market-oriented**), capitalizing most of it, there might be a risk of a collapse scenario similar to the late Tang Dynasty. Once the land excessively flows into the hands of capital-controlled enterprises, the rural areas would lose the safety net that safeguards the basic subsistence of farming households, leading to rural impoverishment, the solidification of social classes, and even triggering social conflicts due to inequality.

Therefore, maintaining a certain level of state intervention and regulation is necessary in the process of advancing land system reforms. Policy design adjustments for land use rights, ensuring the interests of farmers and social equity, are one of the potential principles to follow. It is possible to explore a balance between marketization and social equity to avoid the excessive land concentration and social unrest of the late Tang Dynasty.

From this, it is clear that history offers us a mirror. **The current non-fully capitalized land system in China is not an institution created by Marx,** and it poses no threat to **America's land or financial system.** China **innovatively continues the principles of asset system management from the early Tang Dynasty more than a thousand years ago,** with sufficient historical and philosophical justification. This

model obviously respects the ethics of history, economics, politics, and management to a large extent, and **the United States has no reason whatsoever to dictate that China must follow an American capitalist or market-oriented model.** However, the author believes that while summarizing historical experiences, not only does China need to cautiously consider the market-oriented reform of its land and financial systems in line with its current national conditions and changes of the times, but the United States and other countries around the world should also deal with such issues with care. In pursuing economic development and activating land resources, it is crucial to be vigilant against the potentially disruptive impact of marketization on the existing social structure, thus ensuring long-term stability of society and global sustainable development. Excessive marketization, which results in the government losing its ability to regulate, is essentially a poison that can create extreme societies and lead to societal breakdown. According to Western economic theory, the economic results of social operation dominated by the liberal economy must conform to the 2/8 law. In a society with vast territory and serious inequality of resources, it will inevitably lead to social unrest or war and repeat the historical cycle of the country.

34.5. The current economic situation formed by the political and economic system in the US is similar to the economic situation in the later period of the Tang Dynasty in China. The equal-field system (均田制) in the early Tang dynasties can be regarded as the 1.0 version of the socialist system.

From a historical perspective, the current market-oriented political, economic, and financial system in the United States is similar to the political, economic, and financial system of the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China. If land resources in China were highly concentrated and monopolized like in the United States, and if China were no longer ruled by the Communist Party of China, then China would inevitably experience an uprising similar to that of Huang Chao. Almost all the tycoons and officials in the country would be slaughtered. The number would surely exceed eight million people as in the Tang Dynasty. Moreover, it would spread globally, and basically all tycoons and officials around the world could die. Then wealth redistribution would take place. This system obviously cannot be superior to the political and economic system and management system of China's state-owned assets improved by the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. In other words, the current Chinese socialist system is essentially an improved version of the equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty. Looking at it from another angle, **the equal-field system in the Northern Wei, Sui, and early Tang dynasties can be regarded as the 1.0 version of the socialist system.** The socialist system has existed in the long river of history for more than a thousand years. Do the United States and Europe need to be afraid of China's equal field system? If the U.S. is afraid of China's new equal field system, is it still a society with universal values?

From this, it is evident that the dominant perspective dominating the economic and political arenas of the United States is deeply flawed. Demanding the capitalization and marketization of China's assets based solely on the interests of individuals and interest groups is bound to plunge China back into historical catastrophes and pitfalls,

an approach that clearly does not align with universal values. The author feels compelled to argue that the United States needs to enhance the learning ability and moral standards of mainstream politicians, economists, and financial experts. They should broaden their horizons rather than come up with outrageous governance plans at random to capture public attention or garner votes. This is similar to the various approaches taken by the U.S. during the COVID-19 pandemic, which not only failed to prevent infections effectively, but also led to the most extensive spread worldwide. Actions have led to avoidable COVID-19 deaths, propelling the U.S. death toll to the second highest globally, presumably after India. If the U.S. continues to excessively promote the capitalization and marketization of critical resources like land, concentrating assets in the hands of a few magnates, it could lead to a scenario resembling late Tang Dynasty China, where the U.S. population could rise against these tycoons and possibly overthrow them. Clearly, the establishment of a kind, relatively equal, justice-filled, and vibrant American society is in line with the future development direction of the United States, as opposed to the current situation where many instances of unpunished supermarket theft and drug abuse occur, while individuals and organizations provide even more legal drugs. If this continues, the U.S. could face decline and collapse.

Ahead of this year's Spring Festival, the Chinese people provided selfless assistance to drivers and passengers stranded on the highways of Hubei and Anhui, a level of public benevolence that might be rare in other countries. This fully reflects the connotation, kindness, quality, and spirit of the nation's people, even though those who offered aid were not rich. It wouldn't hurt U.S. politicians and financial figures to also watch the relevant videos, as China-U.S. cooperation is even more important.

34.6. New continuously evolving equal-field system should be the ultimate system for Chinese society, Communist society is a religious belief.

Marx's socialist theory is too idealistic and lacks an understanding of global practice and history. Marx believed that human society could enter the socialist stage only after passing through the capitalist stage. This is a rigid view. In fact, human social systems are changing dynamically. They can progress and also regress under the influence of interests. Historically, China did not enter the socialist system through capitalist society. Instead, it eliminated Qing Dynasty society with centralized imperial power, the prefecture-county system, and partial slavery. After a series of anti-aggression wars and anti-secession wars, China established a New China in a basically unified new democratic society.

Moreover, Marx's judgment of the main social groups constituting socialist society is also incorrect, as he believed that it was mainly composed of workers, whereas in China it was mainly composed of farmers and workers. The education of university students and intellectuals in China is part of the new type of intelligent farmers and workers. Not everyone has to work in state-owned enterprises or collective enterprises, as even farmers or workers are allowed to become private entrepreneurs and become part of society. Regarding private enterprises, as long as they employ a certain number of workers, have a fair and equal distribution

mechanism, pay regular taxes, do not avoid taxes through trusts or charitable funds, and do not mass layoffs during crises, the author believes that they can be regarded as 60-80% collective enterprises. As far as state-owned enterprises, as long as their distribution mechanism is fair and they employ a large number of workers, they can to some extent be considered as 40-70% collective or private enterprises. **State-owned enterprises can become a reservoir function to take on more employees when an economic crisis occurs, regardless of short-cycle earnings. It must be pointed out that social benefits are also a kind of economic benefits.**

The increasingly perfect socialist system in China with its own characteristics will inevitably implement a **new system of equal fields**, where land resources are owned by the state and collectives, allowing the existence of private enterprises.

China's socialist system aims to promote social fairness and economic development while respecting the individual's private property rights, encouraging and supporting the development of private enterprises to create more employment opportunities and increase national income. **However, under this system, private enterprises must operate legally, uphold the legitimate rights of their employees. This system respects the autonomy of private business owners while also protecting the labor rights of employees, achieving the mutual development of the state, enterprises and employees.**

When China perfects its system for preventing and punishing corruption, improves the appointment and dismissal system for civil servants, opens up most of the positions for government officials, and allows for fairness and justice in various fields, achieves universal medical insurance, free university education and a complete pension system, punishes criminals in a timely manner, and continuously optimizes the developing socialist system with Chinese characteristics to make it one of the models of the ultimate social system for human society. Humanity will continually adjust the details of governing various social problems and improve the corresponding system in accordance with the beautiful wish for communism. Other countries can refer to the Chinese system to establish their own corresponding social systems, although it may be difficult for some countries and internal conflicts or wars are unavoidable.

Only through formulating United Nations conventions and incorporating relevant conventions into the constitutions of various countries can the governance of major crimes and public officials in a country be effectively achieved. Countries that do not implement a new equal-field system and countries that lack empathy, especially major countries, find it difficult to avoid war. These countries are usually the main bodies that create chaos, conflict or start wars.

Marxist communism is a kind of religious belief.

It needs to be pointed out that in 1938, Chairman Mao Zedong said in front of the cave dwellings in Yan'an that there could never be absolute fairness in the world, no matter what time. Clearly, this means that Chairman Mao Zedong has always regarded the realization of the communist system as an ideal or a religious goal to strive for. Chairman Mao Zedong's practical experience in difficult environments far exceeds that of Marx, Engels, and Lenin. In the 1950s, the system established by Chairman Mao Zedong in China was significantly different from that of the Soviet Union, and more in

line with the reality of China. However, the realization of communism is a goal, because only by striving for a just society can people be inspired to develop the greatest enthusiasm, and only then can society be relatively fair and just. Just like calculus, the ideal system of fairness and justice can only be infinitely approached, after all, as a biological entity, differences will always exist, and people also need a certain level of motivation. Absolute equality is not conducive to activating biological entities.

Therefore, the constantly improving equal-field system with Chinese characteristics will be one of the ultimate beautiful system for human society. Marx never experienced a relatively equal equal-field system in Europe, his knowledge usually came from missionaries who transferred Chinese history to Europe, and he further idealized the relatively equal social systems of multiple dynasties in Chinese history and renamed it socialism, especially drawing on both Mozi's ideas and Wang Mang's proposed system of nationalization after the Western Han, giving a new name to a social system according to Western logic. If we apply Marx's definition of a social system, the equal-field system with Chinese characteristics is actually the socialist system with Chinese characteristics, which will inevitably be continuously improved in the development process.

Marx's lack of relevant historical depth comparative analysis between socialist and capitalist systems has led to famous Chinese leaders even being unable to articulate what socialism, Marxism, and capitalism are, causing ideological confusion and unclear direction. Now, by reviewing and comparing history, it is not difficult to find that **China's former capitalist social system** is roughly equivalent to the system of the late Tang Dynasty. Land and other means of production are highly privatized, land and asset mergers and monopolies, finance is highly monopolized, and tax policies squeeze the middle and lower classes, causing many people to lose resources and social security. However, all land in current China is owned by state-owned or rural collectives, and there have been no serious land mergers and monopolies affecting national security and social stability. The current socialist system with Chinese characteristics is roughly equivalent to the 4.0 version of the improved equal-field system of the early Tang Dynasty. After more than 70 years of infrastructure construction, **it will inevitably develop into versions 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, and 8.0 in the future**, although the process will inevitably be somewhat tortuous.

According to the US FDA's inspection standards for process authenticity, only records with credible time records in historical documents can be considered true. Historical documents without credible time marks cannot be considered true history. China is the only country in the world whose ancient historical documents have real-time historical records.

Because the laws of history have proved that a dynasty similar to the late Tang Dynasty, which is plagued by inflation, fiscal difficulties, uncontrolled currency issuance, uncontrolled taxation, excessive marketization, self-interest, and relies on war or financial means to harvest wealth and social unrest, will inevitably be put to an end in history and enter the garbage dump of history. On the other hand, a continuously improving system that prevents excessive marketization, similar to the early Tang Dynasty, is like the vibrant sun at 7-8 in the morning, even if it's not sunny

every day. If China, like the Western political and economic systems, re-enters the stage of capital-controlled free markets in the late Tang Dynasty under the strong promotion of the West, social wealth will inevitably tend strongly towards **an about 9:1 distribution**. After wealth is highly concentrated, a revolt similar to the Huang Chao Uprising will inevitably break out, demanding that the equal-field system be implemented again in society. This war of wealth redistribution triggered by disasters or famines will not only affect China, but will also have a widespread impact on the whole world. All the plutocrats who have relations with China and the plutocrats who affect the world economy will not escape bad luck. In the future, **at least 30 to 60 million plutocrats and officials and their entire families will be slaughtered globally** before a new dynasty with the equal-field system can enter again.

The human social system does not necessarily have to go through capitalist society first before entering socialist society. It may also experience a repeat cycle of the socialist (the new Equal-field system) and capitalist system.

34.7. Karl Marx's erroneous views on the State or Country or Nation

Karl Marx had a mistaken viewpoint, believing that after the development of the social system into communism, the state or Country or nation would disappear. This viewpoint is erroneous. Even if there is a convergence of thinking globally in the future, it is impossible for there not to have differences of viewpoints. Just as the body requires various organs and organizations to coordinate and direct its functions and life activities, it needs to organize production and various activities of life, and to resolve various conflicts. **The efficient operation of different institutions and factories in the same area, and the efficient coordination and operation of organizations in different areas are usually managed by multiple powerful and efficient administrative institutions.**

Even if the ideological and moral level of human beings in the future is extremely high, and people with low efficiency enjoy the same benefits, reaching the level of a highly civilized society of democratic equality, communism and sharing, there are usually some differences in systems or distributions between organizations in different regions. For a large country, all the income and distribution of the whole country cannot be completely the same, and there must be certain administrative institutions to manage it.

Even in a family, the smallest social structure, where the thoughts of two individuals are highly aligned, conflicts and the need for coordination and resolution of conflicts are inevitable, requiring motivation to keep the family moving forward. However, when a system and its environment become completely identical, it is thermodynamically equivalent to death. Clearly, Marx's viewpoint is incorrect. A well-preserved national structure, one after another, benefits the stability and normal operation of the global system.

34.8. Classification of human social systems based on empathy and morality status

Marx identified and planned six social systems. However, the author believes that

the social systems and their progress and classification identified by Marx are too simple and abstract. At least human social systems can be classified into multiple social systems according to empathy, as follows:

Table 1. Classification of human social systems based on empathy and morality status

Reclassification of Human social systems		
First level classification	Second level classification	Third level classification
Society with empathy	Tribal Empathy Society	Tribal Empathy Society
	Emperogenic Empathy Society	A society with imperial centralization and morality above all.
		A society with imperial decentralization and morality above all.
		A society with imperial centralization, decentralized power in prefectures and counties, and morality above all.
		A society with imperial decentralization, the equal-field system in prefectures and counties, and morality above all.
		Imperial decentralized and county equal-field system empathetic society.
		A society with imperial centralization where evil forces can be severely punished.
		A society where the emperor decentralizes power and where evil forces can be severely punished.
		A society where imperial power is decentralized and morality is supreme, and where evil forces can be severely punished.
		Party based Empathy Society
Party decentralized new equal-field system empathetic society.		
The new equal-field system version: A society of empathy with the new equal-field system version 3.0 or above optimized and improved from the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty, or a society with socialism with Chinese characteristics. For short, it is called the society of the new equal-field system version 4.0,4.5,5.0,6.0,7.0,8.0,9.0, X.etc.		

		When X approaches infinity or a certain number, at this time, in a society with highly abundant material supply and a very equalized material distribution, and where people's moral characters are all very noble, it may be called a communist society.
		A society with morality above all under the political party system.
		A society with morality above all under the multi-party system.
		A society with democracy and morality above all under the political party system.
		A society with democracy and morality above all under the multi-party system.
		An empathetic society of peaceful win-win.
		An empathetic society of peaceful win-win and friendship.
	Empathy Society Without Party or Emperor or Non-political party and non-imperial empathetic society	Empathy Society Without Party or Emperor or Non-political party and non-imperial empathetic society: Social systems that may exist in the future when the moral level, cognitive level, self-discipline level of the public in the whole world or a continent or some countries are in line with the national governance level.
	Civilized society	The standards of a civilized society are as follows: Definition of Civilization or Civilized Society: Respect life and severely punish criminals. Let the weak not be fearful, the strong not be arrogant, power not be haughty. Let the incompetent voluntarily step aside. Let the immoral occupy fewer public offices. Let the mediocre make fewer decisions. Let the virtuous and capable not waste their talents. Let the wicked be afraid to do evil. Let the kind people be safe. Make society fairer and more just. Make society full of vitality and let people have inner peace. Let there be education in childhood, learning in adolescence, medical care when sick, support and guarantee when unemployed, support for the elderly. Basic family housing does not need to be taxed. Everyone

		respects each other. Let the operation of the government be based on a negative feedback mechanism.
Society with little or no empathy	Tribal-type society without empathy.	Tribal-type society without empathy.
	slave society	Slave society
	Society dominated by nobles with little or no empathy.	A society dominated by nobles in a feudal system.
		A society dominated by nobles in a semi-feudal system.
	Imperial-type society with little or no empathy.	Society of imperial centralization with brutal slaughter.
		Society of imperial centralization with oppression.
		Imperial centralization society of aggression and expansion without empathy.
		Imperial centralization society of external plunder.
		Imperial centralization society that protects large-scale fraud, or and torture, raping, gang-raping, human trafficking and massacre.
	Warlord-type society with little or no empathy.	Warlord-type society without empathy.
	Party-type society with little or no empathy.	Multi-party extremely evil, bloody, slaughtering, brutal and plundering, fake polite and fake civilized society.
		Multi-party bloody, brutal and plundering society.
		Multi-party fraudulent, bullying and evil society.
		Multi-party fraudulent, brutal, slaughtering and evil society.
		Multi-party fraudulent, cruel, brutal, slaughtering and evil semi-slave society.
		Multi-party society that protects large-scale fraud, or and torture, live organ harvesting, human trafficking or and massacre.
		A society that indulges in raping and gang-raping women.
		A multi-party society with a preference for mass rape and gang rape of women from other ethnic groups or countries

		Political party-type with a preference for mass rape and gang rape of women from other ethnic groups or countries
		A multi-party society where citizens commit rape and gang rape of women but are almost innocent
		Political party-type society with large-scale rape and gang rape of women.
		Party-type semi-feudal society.
		Multi-party hegemonic and violent suppression society.
		Multi-party immoral auxiliary violent system society.
		Multi-party society with little or no empathy.
		Party-type aggressive and expansionist society with little or no empathy.
		Party-type external plundering society.
		Party-type external wealth fraud society.
		A party-type society that subtly takes the wealth of people in the poor class.
		A multi-party society that is falsely democratic and oppresses internally and wages wars externally.
		A party-type society that is falsely democratic and oppresses the people internally and starts wars.
		A society of party warlords who oppress the people internally and start wars.
		Shameless pirate society
		A complex society with a strong internal nature of rape and predation (SIRP C-society).
		A society that is inclined to force women to be sex slaves. What evil politicians do is often to give a beautiful name "comfort women". Could their own wives and daughters also enjoy the treatment of becoming "comfort women"?
		A complex society with a false democratic system that pretends to be kind but is actually brutal and predatory. They know minor proprieties but lack righteousness. They are meticulous about trifles but lack great virtue. They attach importance to minor matters but despise integrity. They are afraid of the strong and dare not resist. When strong, they are invaders and thieves. When weak, they are humble and submissive.

		<p>A society of the underworld type under the cover of multi-party and democracy.</p> <p>In this society, the ethnic group with a large population oppresses the ethnic minorities belonging to the indigenous people in the country, resulting in the extremely low status of the indigenous ethnic minorities in the region.</p>
		<p>A society of the underworld type under the cover of multi-party.</p> <p>In this society, the ethnic group with a large population oppresses the ethnic minorities belonging to the indigenous people in the country, resulting in the extremely low status of the indigenous ethnic minorities in the region.</p>
		A society of the underworld type under the cover of political party-type.
		A society that is ungrateful or shows little gratitude.
		A society of political parties that like to defraud wealth from outside.
		A society of multiple political parties that like to defraud wealth from outside (SMP-DW).
		A society composed of multiple political parties where the people have long liked to obtain the wealth of other countries through fraud or telecom fraud.
		A society without morality.
		A society where evil forces are rampant.
		Caste discrimination society
		<p>A society that disguises itself as being led by a ruling party with noble morality but massacres the people or descendants of the assisting country and plunders wealth:</p> <p>Under the guise of a ruling party with the noble ideal of achieving human equality, it greedily asks for assistance from another country without gratitude. In turn, at a certain time, it is bound to appear and massacre the descendants of the assisting country or people of other countries, plunder wealth or forcibly occupy the territory of other countries.</p>
		A society that uses multi-party and democracy as a guise and where the people have long enjoyed obtaining the wealth of other countries through fraud or telecommunications fraud. In this society,

		the country's politicians do not consider defrauding money a crime.
		<p>A society with a special system: A society with an outwardly sunny appearance but an internally evil system. It has long - term mobilized the strength of its national people, manipulated the media and public opinion of both its own country and the globe, deceived the world, the United Nations, and the Nobel Peace Prize Committee by falsely claiming that the country was bombed by atomic bombs twice, obtained huge benefits, ignored the mistakes of its ally who has been helping its economy develop rapidly from the bottom, continuously and skillfully misled its ally, which have been helping its economic development, to invest seven trillion US dollars, but only produced atomic - bomb - related products that are bound to be scrapped in the future, causing the ally to produce economic crises continuously and seriously harming the interests of the ally and the global public.</p>
		<p>A social system that supports lawyers to reduce the sentences of criminals who deserve severe punishment, turning guilty criminals into innocent ones through a flood of words and evil evidential logic.</p>
		<p>On October 20, 2023, local officials appointed by the Myanmar government organized relevant armed personnel. When attempting to transfer a large number of telecom fraudsters, they buried four Chinese undercover police officers alive who had identified themselves as being involved in combating telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, and rape crimes. What kind of social system does Myanmar have?</p>
		<p>As early as 1946 during the trial of Japanese war criminals by the International Military Tribunal for the Far East, in order to search for evidence of Japan's aggression against China, the inspectors of the Nationalist Government accidentally discovered that the Japanese army actually displayed the heads of Chinese soldiers as exhibits in exhibition halls for the public. Among them was the head of Major - General Liu Guiwu of the Army. However, when the news was relayed back to China and the Chinese Nationalist Government demanded that the Japanese Government return the heads of these anti - Japanese heroes, this extremely cunning nation had already moved these "trophies" in their eyes, and the</p>

		<p>heads of martyrs like Liu Guiwu disappeared. Later, someone once saw General Liu's head in an exhibition hall in Japan, soaked in formalin and still on display in Japan today.</p> <p>What kind of evil social system does Japan have? It is a nation that is good at using immigration to infiltrate China on a large scale and cannot be assimilated, a nation that launches aggressive wars, massacres civilians on a large scale, and carries out mass rapes and gang rapes whenever it finds an opportunity.</p>
		<p>Dogs don't defecate in their own dens. Wild boars don't defecate in their own dens either. However, the Japanese actually dump a large amount of nuclear contaminated water that can cause disease and be fatal into the ocean, which is the living place for all human beings.</p> <p>The harm of nuclear contaminated water to the human body and the earth is extremely serious, with nuclear wastewater posing a greater threat to the human body. It contains 64 kinds of radioactive materials, including tritium, carbon-14, iodine-129, strontium-90, and cobalt-60. The most harmful to human beings and marine organisms are carbon-14 and iodine-129, with a half-life of over 5000 years for carbon-14 and an even longer half-life for iodine-129. Carbon-14 can accumulate in the bodies of marine organisms, such as fish, with an abundance or concentration possibly 50 times that of tritium.</p> <p>What kind of social system does the nation have?</p>
		<p>A society or country that fabricates illness and forcibly sends normal people to mental hospital.</p>
		<p>An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that likes to commit large-scale heinous crimes and does not compensate all the losses of the victims and severely punish criminals, or a criminal country or evil criminal society that protects those who commit large-scale heinous crimes, does not compensate all the losses of the victims and severely punishes the criminals.</p>
		<p>An evil criminal society or An evil criminal country has long been fond of deliberately fabricating lies about companies in other countries' tax arrears or tax evasion, seizing most of the property of these companies, or robbing them of control or equity.</p>
		<p>An evil criminal country or evil criminal society</p>

		that will carry out large - scale heinous crimes when the opportunity arises.
		An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that likes to carry out or protect heinous crimes such as large - scale telecom fraud.
		An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that likes to carry out large - scale heinous crimes or a country that protects criminals who carry out such crimes.
		An evil criminal society or An evil criminal country that commits large - scale heinous crimes such as rape, gang - rape, burying people alive, massacring, and plundering the property of victims, or protects those who carry out such large - scale crimes. This evil criminal country or evil criminal society has never fully compensated the victims for their losses or severely punished the criminals.
		An evil criminal country or An evil criminal society that commits any of the heinous crimes on a large scale, such as telecom fraud, kidnapping, plunder, torture, rape, gang rape, forced organ harvesting, human trafficking, massacre, or protects those who commit such large - scale heinous crimes.
		An evil criminal country or An evil criminal society that commits heinous crimes such as large-scale fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape or forced organ removal, or protects those who commit such heinous crimes on a large scale.
		A criminal country or An evil criminal society controlled by an evil race that likes to carry out large - scale heinous crimes or protect criminals who commit such crimes.
		A society formed by deceiving the public with religion based on fictional history and thus gathering a large number of believers.
		Establish an evil fictional religion by fabricating history, deceive the public, make them gather to form a large number of believers, and thereby establish a society of a specific so - called ethnic group.
		By fabricating history, an evil fictitious religion is established to deceive the public and make them gather to form a large number of believers, thus

		establishing a specific so-called ethnic society.
		By fabricating history, a fictitious religion is established to deceive the public and make them gather to form a large number of believers, thus establishing a specific so-called ethnic society.
		A fictitious religion based on fabricated history, used to deceive the public, gather them to form a large number of believers, and defraud money from these believers, thus establish a society of a specific religious group.
		A society with a cult system that uses fabricated history to establish an evil religion, fools the public, induces them to believe in this religion, tells believers that this religion must be their only faith, and labels those who don't as heretics.
		A society with a cult system fabricates a religion, induces the public to believe in it, tells believers that it is the only belief that can be followed, and labels those who don't believe as pagans.
		Criminal countries sold a large amount of opium drugs to other countries, poisoning the people of those countries. However, evil politicians and merchants regarded it as "free trade." When the victimized country destroyed the opium, the criminal countries that sold opium launched wars against the victimized country, forcing the victimized country to sign unequal treaties and demanding indemnities. The criminal countries that sold opium have long enjoyed the social welfare brought about by the sale of opium drugs. It can be seen that the criminal countries that sold opium established an extremely evil social system.
		An evil country engaged in opium manufacturing or selling exports opium drugs to other countries, poisoning the people of those countries. However, this country itself, its community of interests, or its allies consider the trafficking of opium as free trade. Such a social system is one created by an extremely evil criminal race.
		A society with an evil and heartless system that supports or protects acts of large-scale heinous crimes (such as large-scale telecommunications fraud, or kidnapping, or torture, or rape, or gang rape, or forced organ harvesting, or burying alive, or massacres, or plundering of civilian property) and yet does not bear full civil and criminal

		responsibilities.
		A sinful society constructed by evil humanoid creatures who like to protect, support or enjoy the slaughter, plunder, rape, gang rape, torture, forced organ harvesting, or large-scale telecommunications fraud of human beings.
		A society with so-called religious beliefs constructed by humanoid objects that shamelessly enjoy the pleasure of slaughtering, raping, gang-raping, or large-scale telecommunications fraud, plundering kind victims, or deprive these victims of their wealth or value.
		A so-called society or country with religious beliefs where the government subsidizes and rewards its people for raping or gang-raping a large number of women in large quantities, criminals are not cracked down on, punished, and executed, and victims cannot receive full compensation.
		A society that destroys the legal housing on which civilians rely for survival but does not promptly crack down on and severely punish criminals to protect the rights and interests of the victims.
		A society where customs officers habitually extort money from inbound and outbound travelers.
		An evil criminal society that often kidnaps the people of other countries.
		A sinful society constructed by evil humanoid creatures who like to protect, support or enjoy the slaughter, plunder, rape, gang rape, torture, forced organ harvesting, or large-scale telecommunications fraud of human beings.
		A society with so-called religious beliefs constructed by humanoid objects that shamelessly enjoy the pleasure of slaughtering, raping, gang-raping, or large-scale telecommunications fraud, plundering kind victims, or deprive these victims of their wealth or value.
		A society with usury where the annual interest rate of loans exceeds 6%.
		A society where the mainstream media likes to spread rumors and tell lies but does not bear civil and criminal responsibilities.
		A society where politicians like to tell lies during elections or while in power but do not bear civil and criminal responsibilities.
		A society where politicians or officials use their power to oppress kind-hearted people or those who dare to reveal the truth but do not bear full civil and criminal responsibilities.
		A society where voters support the perpetration or protection of large-scale heinous crimes—such as mass telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, live burials, massacres, or the plundering of civilian property—yet bear no civil or criminal liability, is an evil society.
		A society where citizens support the perpetration or protection of

		large-scale heinous crimes—such as mass telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, live burials, massacres, or the plundering of civilian property—yet bear no civil or criminal liability, is an evil society.
		A society that supports the perpetration or protection of large-scale heinous crimes—such as mass telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, live burials, massacres, or the plundering of civilian property—yet bears no civil or criminal liability, is an evil society.
		A society in which the government fails to promptly crack down on and severely punish the crimes of destroying the legal housing on which civilians depend for their livelihoods, and fails to protect the rights and interests of the victims.
		A racial society constructed by people who fabricate religion and religious beliefs.
		A society constructed by people and ethnic groups who control the mainstream media and often create fake news to deceive the public.
		A society in which extremely wrong policies are formulated and implemented, resulting in the death of kind-hearted people and the deprivation of their rights, interests and properties, and in which these evil groups of people are not severely punished.
		A society that bullies or ignores kind and vulnerable groups. A society constructed by officials, those with vested interests and a plutocracy that bullies kind and vulnerable groups or those with a sense of justice.
		A society constructed by people or ethnic groups who often fabricate history or historical cultural relics, beautify interest relationships, and deceive the public.
		A so-called racial society or country with religious beliefs formed by fabricating a large number of cultural relics and books, fabricating history, and inventing a religion.
		A so-called racial society or country with religious beliefs formed by stealing a large number of books, forging a large number of cultural relics and books, fabricating history, and inventing a religion.
		It steals and transfers a large number of cultural and scientific and technological books of ancient China, forges a great deal of cultural relics and books, fabricates history and religion. It uses the fabricated religion to form religious groups, defrauds the money of believers, and thus forms the so-called racial society with religious beliefs. Vatican.
		A society where the police are rather lenient towards a large number of theft and robbery crimes within their jurisdiction, do not

		carry out severe crackdowns, and are not proactive in recovering the losses for the victims. This is the case in Italy and France.
		A society where thieves and robbers run rampant, but politicians and the judicial authorities are quite lenient towards these two types of crimes, rarely take the initiative to retrieve the losses for the victims, and are accustomed to receiving their salaries without effectively cracking down on or controlling crimes.
		A hypocritical society where thieves and robbers run wild, politicians and the judicial authorities are very lenient towards these two types of crimes, seldom taking the initiative to recover the losses for the victims. Meanwhile, politicians and the media often brag that the country has democracy, freedom and human rights, and civil servants and politicians are used to getting their salaries without bothering to control crimes.
		A society with a hierarchical system where the social status and treatment differences between officials and ordinary people are quite obvious.
		The sons and daughters of citizens of a country were killed by criminals from an evil criminal country that commit large-scale crimes. The victimized citizen and his relatives angrily denounced and exposed the crimes of this evil criminal country. However, instead of receiving the sympathy of some people in their home country, the victims and their relatives were actually blamed by some of the country's people. The museums in this country refused to exhibit the photos taken by the victims' relatives as evidence of the crimes committed by the criminal country that carried out large-scale heinous crimes. On the contrary, they accused the victims and their relatives of damaging the relationship with the evil criminal country that committed large-scale heinous crimes. Such people have no empathy or sense of justice, and the victims are in a society with such an evil system! For example, France.
		A judicial system that assigns defense lawyers to criminals (who are not mute) or criminal countries that commit heinous crimes, and uses the powerful defense skills and wisdom of lawyers to enable criminals to try to reduce their charges or evade legal punishment, instead of having the criminals themselves disclose the crime process and details in court. Isn't this a society with an evil system?
		A society that formulates or implements extremely wrong policies or judicial systems, harms kind-hearted people or those with a sense of justice, and where the victims do not receive adequate compensation, while the groups of evil people who formulate or implement these extremely wrong policies or judicial systems are not severely punished.
		A society where the government protects government officials who

		have committed serious misdeeds or serious illegal acts, or who bully civilians or vulnerable groups, more than it protects the interests of the common people.
		A society that protects the wealthy or the plutocracy who have committed serious illegal acts or severely bullied civilians or vulnerable groups more than it protects the interests of the common people.
		A society where the judicial system tends to protect those in power, the plutocracy, or the wealthy groups.
		A society that has lost its public credibility.
		A society that supports or tacitly approves of the creation of viruses or bacteria with mass destructive power to harm humanity.
		A society in which politicians or officials use their power to oppress kind-hearted people or those who dare to reveal the truth, but do not bear full civil and criminal responsibilities.
		Selling a large amount of opium drugs to other countries and poisoning the people of those countries, evil politicians and merchants regard it as free trade. When the victimized country destroys the opium, the country that sells opium launches a war against the victimized country, forcing the victimized country to sign unequal treaties and demanding indemnities. The country that sells opium has long enjoyed the social welfare brought by the sale of opium drugs. It can be seen that the evil country that sells opium has established an extremely evil social system.
		The criminal country sells a large amount of opium drugs to other countries and poisons the people of those countries. Evil politicians and merchants consider it as free trade. When the victimized country destroys the opium, the criminal country that sells opium initiates a war against the victimized country, compelling the victimized country to sign unequal treaties and extorting indemnities. The criminal country that sells opium has long reaped the social benefits from the sale of opium drugs. Evidently, the criminal country that sells opium has constructed an extremely evil social system.

34.8.1. Doubts about the Current Social System in Japan

The public of the whole country has been deceived by Japan, which pretends to be the victim of atomic bomb explosions. Japanese society is a deceptive society that deceives the world in an uneventful manner. **It is a society, the only one in the world that fakes a desire for world peace but builds a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " or [the**

Unified Universe Tower(八纎一宇塔). to suppress the souls and national fortunes of other countries. It invaded China, massacred at least 51.80–89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people, raped and gang - raped at least 31.45–54.40 (61.20) million Chinese women, looted at least 700 million cubic meters of wood (usually worth at least \$420 billion) and plundered at least 1.06 billion tons of coal (usually worth \$114.4 billion). Japan is a society that has not only failed to compensate for China's losses and the harm suffered by the Chinese people, but also still exhibits the head of the Chinese army general Liu Guiwu as a trophy in Japan, and makes people believe their fictional stories.

The Japanese used a large number of so - called victim documents composed of written and fabricated facts signed by supposed victims of the Hiroshima - Nagasaki atomic bombs. **Through more than 70 years of repeated deceptive propaganda by the Japanese media, Japan has successfully deceived world peace organizations and the Norwegian Nobel Committee, and won the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize. The Japanese have no sense of remorse at all. Japan plundered as much as 500,000 kg of natural diamonds from China, worth about \$132.55 - 280.5 billion**, and has not compensated the Chinese for their losses up to now. The Japanese have always been greedy for both big and small sums of money. Just like when Japan invaded China, Japanese soldiers carried a pair of pliers with them and pulled out the gold teeth of the victims at any time during the Nanjing Massacre. It's the 21st century. Although the Nobel Peace Prize money is not much, the Japanese still want to steal it instead of publicly announcing to the world that Japan has been perjuring itself and giving up the Nobel Peace Prize. From October 11th to 28th, it has been 17 days, and the Japanese Prime Minister is also celebrating Japan's award without any sense of shame. The Japanese consider themselves the smartest people on earth. Basically, the whole Japanese population should know that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are fictional. **However, instead of remaining silent, they claim that they or Japan were the victims of atomic bomb explosions. Japanese politician has even threatened to retaliate against the United States by dropping 500 hydrogen bombs on it. During Japan's aggressive wars**, the number of Japanese deaths is far lower than the number of Chinese victims. The entire Japanese population are war criminals and criminals, and countless criminals have not been sentenced to death. What kind of social system does Japan have today?

What kind of social system does Japan have today? Please test the length of time it takes for you to be 100% sure that the Japanese are actually conducting false propaganda when you hear that the atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki are fictional or psychological warfare related.

34.8.2. Whether Hiroshima and Nagasaki experienced atomic bombings can serve as an assessment criterion for assessing people's thinking abilities

Whether Hiroshima and Nagasaki experienced atomic bomb explosions may be used as an evaluation criterion for examining people's thinking abilities in Western society, or it may be used as a recruitment topic for employees or a rough test of students' judgment before the truth is fully revealed.

When someone in front of you mentions that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are false or fabricated and that the U.S. military did not drop atomic bombs on Japan, your thinking and judgment abilities may be assessed in the following ways.

Table S01. Evaluation criterion for examining people's thinking abilities	
1	<p>If you are a top military strategist or academician - level figure or top entrepreneur or top - level statesman with global leadership or top economist or top scientist or top management expert or top marketing specialist, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 30 - 60 seconds, and then, after retrieving and studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 5 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military (Starting from the end point of 30 or 60 seconds, including the time for subsequent literature review, it is regarded as five minutes.).</p> <p>Or you don't need to do any verification and directly make a completely accurate judgment within 60 seconds, confirming that the US military did not really drop atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki. At a high level, a response every ten seconds reflects a level difference.</p>
2	<p>If you are a first - class professor, a management expert, or a member of the Senate or the House of Representatives, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 90 seconds, and then, after studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 7 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.</p>
3	<p>If you are a PhD in Natural Science or Engineering Science, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 120 seconds, and then, after studying the relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 10 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.</p>
4	<p>If you are a PhD in Social Sciences or Arts, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 180 seconds, and then, after studying the relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 15 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.</p>
5	<p>If you are an undergraduate graduate with a university science or engineering background, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 2 - 5 minutes, and then, after studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 30 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.</p>

6	If you are an undergraduate graduate with a liberal - arts background from a university, you should generally be able to judge that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are suspected within 6 - 8 minutes, and then, after studying relevant literature, you should be able to judge within 30 minutes that the atomic bombings in Japan suffered were definitely psychological warfare of nuclear explosions fabricated by Japan and the U.S. military.
7	You can also test whether you really don't understand that the U.S. military didn't drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, or you just pretend not to understand.

34.8.3. The Japanese invaders placed the head of General Liu Guiwu, an anti - Japanese hero, in an exhibition hall, and it is still there for tourists to see. What kind of society is Japan?

In April 1938, during the Japanese invasion of China, the Japanese Army listed Liu Guiwu's 6th Cavalry Division as a key target for attack. In this battle, the Japanese army not only dispatched more than 100 vehicles, more than 50 tanks and armored vehicles carrying thousands of Japanese soldiers, but also had 33 planes for support, along with highly mobile motorized troops. Surrounded and intercepted by the heavy forces of the Japanese army, although the 6th Cavalry Division had very poor equipment and was deeply trapped with heavy losses, in order to cover the retreat of Ma Zhanshan's headquarters, Liu Guiwu led his troops to fight back bravely. Eventually, being outnumbered, he was unfortunately shot and died for the country at the age of only 36.

After Liu Guiwu's sacrifice, the evil Japanese army cut off his head and took it back in a wooden box, leaving only a headless corpse on the battlefield. In order to snatch the general's body, a fierce bayonet fight broke out between the two sides. Liu Guiwu's wife, single - handedly, fought her way out of the enemy's encirclement. Despite the danger, she managed to retrieve her husband's body from the Japanese siege and then rode away, leaving the Japanese soldiers on the side dumbfounded. In this battle, almost all of the 6th Cavalry Division sacrificed, and our army killed more than a thousand Japanese and puppet soldiers.

The Japanese army took General Liu Guiwu's head back to Japan, soaked it in formalin solution, and placed it in an exhibition hall for tourists to view. How crazy and shameless the dirty and despicable psychology of the Japanese is! Japan is strongly demanded to return General Liu Guiwu's head! He is one of the 300 revolutionary martyrs announced by the Ministry of Civil Affairs.

As early as 1946 during the trial of Japanese war criminals by the International Military Tribunal for the Far East, in order to search for evidence of Japan's aggression against China, the inspectors of the Nationalist Government accidentally discovered that the Japanese army actually displayed the heads of Chinese soldiers as exhibits in exhibition halls for the public. Among them was the head of Major - General Liu Guiwu of the Army. However, when the news was relayed back to China and the Chinese Nationalist Government demanded that the Japanese Government return the heads of these anti - Japanese heroes, this extremely cunning nation had already moved

these "trophies" in their eyes, and the heads of martyrs like Liu Guiwu disappeared. Later, someone once saw General Liu's head in an exhibition hall in Japan, soaked in formalin and still on display in Japan today.

What kind of evil social system does Japan have? It is a nation that is good at using immigration to infiltrate China on a large scale and cannot be assimilated, a nation that launches aggressive wars, massacres civilians on a large scale, and carries out mass rapes and gang rapes whenever it finds an opportunity.

If Hollywood wants to invest in filming real heroic female characters, the wife of Liu Guiwu, a major general and division commander of the 6th Cavalry Division, is a good subject. **She was able to single - handedly inspire the blood of other soldiers, ride bravely into battle, kill the ferocious Japanese invaders with superior forces and equipment, and retrieve her husband's body, which is rare in world history.** If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in making this film, it is believed that it can achieve high box - office revenues in China. Each screening and dissemination of the film is equivalent to holding several World Peace Conferences, and it will inevitably cultivate a large number of peace fighters around the globe in subtle ways, promote nuclear disarmament, and reduce wars between countries. This fully complies with the four concepts proposed by Nobel. However, the screenwriter, director, lighting engineer, and costume designer must be the right people.

The international community must deal with the issue of immigration with caution. During Japan's war of aggression against China, **Japanese immigration to China became the fuse for continuously plundering China's wealth and initiating and expanding the war.** Otherwise, after lurking in other countries for decades, a hundred years, or even several hundred years, once Japan's military power becomes strong, even if Japanese immigrants have integrated into that country for many years, they will still inevitably become Trojan horses, stir up trouble at any time, and become excuses for creating conflicts and starting wars.

At the beginning of the last century, in order to occupy China, Japan dispatched hundreds of thousands of immigrants to the three northeastern provinces of China. Under the threat of Japanese invaders, they forced farmers to sell their land at low prices and then established the so - called Manchukuo in the region, attempting to plunder China's territory through piecemeal encroachment. When the Japanese emperor was defeated, he said that he underestimated China. At that time, only hundreds of thousands of Japanese immigrants were involved. Now, the number of organized Japanese immigrants in Brazil is close to three million. According to Japan's plan of Hakkō ichiū formulated a thousand years ago to annex the world, Japan continuously launched wars of aggression against China. Only at the beginning of the last century did it occupy most of China. The Japanese can be patient for a thousand years and quietly accumulate military strength. **There are often strikingly similar scenes in history. The global public should pay attention to warvigilance and safeguard world peace.**

Fig 1. When the evil Japanese invaders were aggressing against China, they cut off the head of General Liu Guiwu, a Major General of the Chinese Army who was shot and sacrificed, and transported it to Japan. It is still placed in an exhibition hall for tourists to see. What an evil society Japan is! What an evil society system Japan is! Such an evil country has repeatedly attempted to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council. Has not the ethics, morality, and human conscience of the contemporary world regressed by two thousand years?

[The head of 36-year-old anti-Japanese martyr Liu Guiwu appeared in old photos of the Japanese army, and the head is still in Japan today. May 26, 2023. https://www.bilibili.com/read/cv23942767/?jump_opus=1]

If the Japanese nation is not really a people who do not love peace, how can they tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still serving as a trophy for tourists to watch???

If Japan is not really a country that does not love peace, how can it tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still serving as a trophy for tourists to watch???

If the Japanese emperor was not really a peaceless emperor, how could he tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still treating it as a trophy for tourists to watch???

If Japan is really not a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized country without proper religious beliefs or a cult nation, why would they still tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head since the end of World War II, and even display it as a war trophy for tourists to admire???

If the Japanese nation is really not a nation that believes in cults, how can it tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to observe???

Fig2. When the evil Japanese invaders were aggressing against China, they cut off the head of General Liu Guiwu, a Major General of the Chinese Army who was shot and sacrificed, and transported it to Japan. It is still placed in an exhibition hall for tourists to see. What an evil society Japan is! **What an evil society system Japan is!**
<https://www.douyin.com/video/7426402313545256231>

Such an evil country has repeatedly attempted to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council. Has not the ethics, morality, and human conscience of the contemporary world regressed by two thousand years?

Do you know how cruel the Japanese are, who appear very polite on the surface and

how to everyone they meet? These pictures are proof. The atrocities committed by Japanese immigrants in Jinan and Shanghai were even more serious. They were the vanguard of Japan's aggression against other countries. A French diplomat said that every Japanese person in China was a spy.

If the international community does not establish evaluation standards for social systems based on ethics, morality and conscience, the tragic situation of China in the last century will be the future of your country.

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

If Japan is not truly a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized country, how can it tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

If Japan's emperor is not truly a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized leader of the yakuza, how can he tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

If the Japanese people are not really a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized nation, how can they tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see?

If the Japanese government is not really a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized government, how can it tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see???

If Japan really regards the invasion of China during World War II and the massacre of tens of millions of Chinese people as a serious crime that requires acknowledgement and repentance, how can they tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of the Second World War and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to see???

If the Japanese nation is not really a people who do not love peace, how can they tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still serving as a trophy for tourists to watch???

If Japan is not really a country that does not love peace, how can it tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still serving as a trophy for tourists to watch???

If the Japanese emperor was not really a peaceless emperor, how could he tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head after World War II and still treating it as a trophy for tourists to watch???

If Japan is really not a barbaric, evil, or uncivilized country without proper religious beliefs or a cult nation, why would they still tolerate not returning General Liu Guiwu's head since the end of World War II, and even display it as a war trophy for tourists to admire???

If the Japanese nation is really not a nation that believes in cults, how can it tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the

end of World War II and is still displayed as a war trophy for tourists to observe???

If the Japanese emperor is really not a cult leader, how can he tolerate the fact that General Liu Guiwu's head has not been returned since the end of World War II and is still being displayed as a trophy for tourists to see???

The laws you've created have failed to protect victims. So why should you be the one making the laws?

Since the inferior legal system you created did not protect victims and instead allowed criminals to continue to harm new people and turn them into new victims, shouldn't you be severely punished?

Shouldn't you be put to death? Are you nobler than the victims? Why can't victims make laws? Aren't the victims equal human beings?

Can't victims make laws to sentence these criminals who committed heinous crimes to death? If you insist on such extremely stupid views, you must let the victims use the same means as the criminals to make all members of your family experience the process of being victimized with similar intensity and for a similar length of time, and end up in a similar situation of being victimized. If anyone in your family dies or loses all their property as a result, wouldn't that be caused by your ignorance?

Since you are ignorant, you should not be involved in law-making at all. You shouldn't be able to work in any government agency or engage in any government affairs.

Would it would be legal to rob the national treasury and banks of your country, plunder all the gold and currency, and pass them on to the next generation for ownership? The next generation of criminals, knowing full well that these properties were obtained through robbery and are illegal gains, continue to hide and consume them. Aren't they criminals?

If not, wouldn't it be legal to send a few people or an army to rob any bank in the United States of its gold, diamonds, jewels and dollars, kill all the security personnel, and then pass the gold, diamonds, jewels and dollars on to the next generation?

Don't you think that's absurd? If you don't think it's absurd, what qualifications do you have to be involved in law-making? Aren't you just a pig's head that can't produce any grain?

Fig 3. Great Anti-Japanese Hero: Xu Rumei

Xu Rumei, born in Wenchang, Hainan, was captured and injured during an escape attempt in the autumn of 1943. In order to obtain information from the anti-Japanese guerrilla forces, **the Japanese devils cut off her breasts with a knife, smashed her foot bones with a hammer, inserted sugarcane into her lower body, branded her chest with a red-hot iron, cut off her tongue, nailed her to a tree with 11 steel nails, stripped her naked and smeared her body with the bait that wolves love to eat, and let the wolves tear her body apart to expose her bones.** Despite the cruel torture, she remained steadfast and refused to disclose any information about the anti-Japanese guerrilla forces. In a fit of rage, the devils used a wooden stick to penetrate her vagina, leading to her sacrifice. She died a heroic death at the age of only 21. **It was later discovered that the tree under which she was nailed miraculously grew into a human-like shape.**

[\[https://v.douyin.com/ijjHwbjX/\]](https://v.douyin.com/ijjHwbjX/)

Japanese spies are very rampant in China. After several months, they managed to delete the link to the picture, fearing that the crimes of the Japanese invaders would be exposed. Are Japanese invaders making long - term preparations for the next war?

Do you know how cruel the Japanese are, who appear very polite on the surface and bow to everyone they meet? These pictures are proof. The atrocities committed by Japanese immigrants in Jinan and Shanghai were even more serious. They were the vanguard of Japan's aggression against other countries. A French diplomat said that every Japanese person in China was a spy.

If the international community does not establish evaluation standards for social

systems based on ethics, morality and conscience, the tragic situation of China in the last century will be the future of your country.

Fig 4. Chinese infants dissected alive using formalin soaking in Japanese 731 Biological War unit. [Dogs can never change their habit of eating feces. Those who say China Japan is friendly are actually traitors and traitors. Don't forget blood and tears, don't forget national shame.2023-05-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAbhGbx/>]

Do you know how cruel the Japanese are, who appear very polite on the surface and bow to everyone they meet? These pictures are proof. The atrocities committed by Japanese immigrants in Jinan and Shanghai were even more serious. They were the vanguard of Japan's aggression against other countries. A French diplomat said that every Japanese person in China was a spy.

If the international community does not establish evaluation standards for social systems based on ethics, morality and conscience, the tragic situation of China in the last century will be the future of your country.

Fig 5. Japanese invaders looted a bank in northeast China, where there were 160,000 taels of gold and tens of millions of silver dollars.

The Japanese must have made huge profits from these hard currencies, but they have not compensated the Chinese for their losses until now. Those who kill and plunder property must be sentenced to death, and murderers must return the property of the victims. The Japanese emperor and his family are the world's largest criminals and war criminals, yet they have not been killed or punished. This is the evil of the law - makers. Otherwise, anyone could kill the Japanese people now and plunder all their property and pass it on to the next generation. Most of Japan's wealth was plundered from China.

Lawyers, peace - loving people, groups, and countries around the world should unite to sue the Japanese government and force it to compensate the Chinese for their losses, and they will receive rich rewards.

Fig 6. [After the Japanese invaders occupied Datong coal mines, they plundered the resources frenziedly. Under the bloody rule of the Japanese army, large numbers of miners who were battered to death or left to die were discarded in abandoned mine shafts. Among them, there were a total of 14 pits of ten thousand corpses, each with a level of over 10,000 individuals, with the largest containing the remains of 60,000 people – all with missing limbs, some with only their heads remaining. The silent bones stand as ironclad evidence that cannot ever erase the heinous crimes committed by the Japanese military in China. #Remember History #Never Forget National Humiliation. 2022-01-08. <https://v.douyin.com/iNA4eX1M/> 12/20 b@N.wS VLJ:/]

Fig. 7. **One of the tortures of the Evil, shameless, cruel, despicable I Japanese Evil Staphylococcus aureus Japanese Biological War Unit 731** The Japanese Biological War Unit 731 vivisection: a so-called comfort woman (**Sex slave**) was raped by evil Japanese soldiers and then subjected to a live dissection, during which her breasts were removed, and her left eye was excised to be preserved as a specimen. [In the living experiment of Japanese Unit 731, a sex slave was unscrewed and his breasts were cut off..... <https://v.douyin.com/iXu4h6e/>]

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If the international community does not establish evaluation standards for social systems based on ethics, morality and conscience, the tragic situation of China in the last century will be the future of your country.

Fig. 8. Chinese military and civilians provide international assistance to 64 US pilots.

To rescue the 64 U.S. crew members of the 13 planes led by Doolittle, 250,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians sacrificed their lives. This ratio of tremendous sacrifice to success is unprecedented in world history.

It is hoped that Hollywood will turn these challenging rescue operations into a movie. With a talented director and enough funding, it could surely become an extraordinarily thrilling and successful blockbuster, potentially reaching unrivaled viewership ratings.

[Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250,000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

The Japanese biological warfare unit released a large amount of bacterial viruses and carried out massacres in Zhejiang and Anhui provinces of China, where 64 American pilots were rescued. Countless civilians were killed, with at least 250,000 people sacrificed.

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in producing a film about Chinese people risking their lives to save 64 Allied pilots with 250,000 Chinese losing their lives in the process, it may create a box office of \$1 billion in China. This will enable more people around the world to understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments, and at the same

time further expanding the scale of the Nobel Fund.

Do you know how cruel the Japanese are, who appear very polite on the surface and bow to everyone they meet? **These pictures are proof. The atrocities committed by Japanese immigrants in Jinan and Shanghai were even more serious.** They were the vanguard of Japan's aggression against other countries. **A French diplomat said that every Japanese person in China was a spy.** In the 21st century, Japanese teachers in a city kindergarten in China have been constantly using children's parents to spy on different entrances to various government institutions and other sensitive units, with such meticulous work. It is just like during the Japanese invasion of China in the last century. The maps held by the Japanese army were much more accurate than those of the Chinese army. They even knew the names of almost every platoon leader in the Chinese army in Shanxi, which is astonishing. The Japanese government should give bonuses to encourage these spies. **If the international community does not establish evaluation standards for social systems based on ethics, morality and conscience, the tragic situation of China in the last century will be the future of your country.**

Fig. 9. For the 50th and 70th anniversaries, the Doolittle Association invited the Chinese people who rescued them to participate in the events.

[In order to save 64 Americans, the Chinese have attracted Japan's crazy retaliation, with 250,000 soldiers and civilians sacrificed.] June 21, 2017.

<https://www.toutiao.com/article/6433939830006088194/>

Do you know how cruel the Japanese are, who appear very polite on the surface and bow to everyone they meet? These pictures are proof. The atrocities committed by Japanese immigrants in Jinan and Shanghai were even more serious.

The Japanese Nobel Prize winner not only acts as the head of spies, but is also warlike. The Japanese Nobel laureate and professor shouted: Japan has long

infiltrated China and can still defeat China if a war breaks out.

Last year, the Japanese Nobel Prize winner and professor at Kyoto University, Tasuku Honjo, said: "Even if a war breaks out between China and Japan again, Japan still has the ability and strength to defeat China. Even though China has emerged at present, Japan has infiltrated in many fields and has the strength to disintegrate its interior. We not only affect their future direction; even if no conflict breaks out, I think our influence on them will continue to rise so that Japan can obtain more long-term benefits."

Mr. Nobel established the Nobel Prize with the hope of peace, but it was awarded to Japan, a war criminal country that did not fully compensate for its crimes and victims.

I believe that this university professor is by no means talking nonsense or making casual remarks; a Nobel Prize winner can enumerate infiltration in all aspects of China like counting family treasures and firmly believes that he has mastered our development direction and future.

This is a terrible result of the failure to severely punish war criminals and all the criminals of the Second World War.

日本教授本庶佑，公开声称有信心从内部瓦解中国！

就在最近，日本京都大学高级研究所有一位名叫本庶佑的特别教授。他威胁说，如果中日战争开始，日本完全有能力打败中国，因为我们已经全面渗透到中国的各个领域，对中国的一举一动了如指掌。我们完全有能力肢解中国内部。

Fig 10. Japanese Professor Motosuke Honjo, a Nobel laureate: Japan has fully penetrated into various fields of China. 2023-11-02.

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/IIIU26V10528AOT4.html>

Japanese academicians should generally know that the US military did not drop atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki at all. The so - called nuclear bombing of

Japan is just nuclear psychological warfare between Japan and the US military. However, the Japanese people and Japanese academicians use the fictional atomic bomb explosions in Hiroshima and Nagasaki to deceive the global public, gain the public's tears and sympathy, continuously develop military power, and prepare for the next war. They even secretly processed 4.7 million sets of various Chinese military uniforms in Wuhan. What are the evil Japanese trying to do? This reflects in particular that if standards for the evaluation of social systems based on ethics, morality and conscience are not established, the tragic situation of China in the last century will be the future of your country.

Do you know how cruel the Japanese are, who appear very polite on the surface and bow to everyone they meet? These pictures are proof. The atrocities committed by Japanese immigrants in Jinan and Shanghai were even more serious. They were the vanguard of Japan's aggression against other countries. A French diplomat said that every Japanese person in China was a spy.

Warvigilance:

If Japan is truly a peace-loving country, then in the 21st century after World War II, would a peace-loving country still be so thoroughly infiltrating and preparing for war???

If Japan is truly a peace-loving country, then in the 21st century after World War II, would a peace-loving medical academician still be so familiar with the all-round infiltration of Japanese spies into China and the preparation for war with China???

As of today in the 21st century, how many Japanese medical academicians have joined Japanese spy organizations???

How many Japanese medical academicians are core members of Japanese spy organizations???

In general, only core members of spy organizations are familiar with the infiltration of another country. How many Japanese academicians have joined Japanese spy organizations???

How many of Japan's academicians and medical academicians have not joined Japanese spy organizations???

A French diplomat named Casseville once said that almost every Japanese person in China is a spy.

Do you know how many Japanese expatriates were in China during the Second World War? In 1945, there were as many as 1.1 million people in the three northeastern provinces of China alone.

Japan's immigration program is a long-term major means of implementing espionage activities, waging aggressive wars, and annexing other countries. There are often strikingly similar scenes in history. Today, there are nearly three million Japanese immigrants in Brazil and they have purchased land three times the size of Japan's territory. What are they trying to do? Don't people know to be vigilant?

A letter from Major Casseville, military attaché of the French Embassy in China, to the French Ministry of Defense: The Japanese are arrogant, suspicious and stingy.

They don't trust Europeans. They are keen on espionage activities and are also good at lying.

The culture, beliefs and values of a country determine the social system of a country.

Warvigilance:

据悉，最近在武汉我们的武警官兵，查获了一批日本人制造的**中国军服**，各种各样的**军服**都有。共查获了470万套，为什么日本人要偷偷的做这么多军服呢？他们要干啥呢？武汉的武警查封了一家纺织厂，当时日本人正在偷偷的制作中国各种各样的军服。国内混进这么多日本人，搞这么多军服意欲何为？给谁做的？他们穿中国军服又想干嘛呢？

Fig 11. In recent years, in Wuhan, China, armed police officers and soldiers have seized a batch of Chinese military uniforms made by the Japanese. There are all kinds of military uniforms. **A total of 4.7 million sets were seized. Why did the Japanese secretly make so many military uniforms? What are they going to do?** Armed police in Wuhan have sealed off a textile factory. At that time, the Japanese were secretly making all kinds of Chinese military uniforms. Japan is a country of war criminals. Almost all Japanese people, including Japanese children, serve the aggression against China, the Asia-Pacific region and the United States and are all war criminals. Now there are so many Japanese in China. What is the intention of making so many Chinese military uniforms? What do they want to do by wearing Chinese military uniforms? Japan has a population of 126 million and can rapidly expand its military to 2-3 million. **It is said that every student in Japanese schools in Brazil undergoes gun training, just like during World War II.**

[The Japanese are making trouble in our country again. As a result, they were caught red-handed. **December 28, 2022.**

<https://m.163.com/dy/article/HPKR2V3D05531ZD7.html>]

It can be seen from this that Japan's social system determines that they have been preparing to launch aggressive wars again.

Fig.12. Survivor of the bacterial warfare in Zhegan Bacterial Massacre
Victim of **Japanese biological warfare**: Mao Xiaowei, an 80-year-old man, has wounds that have not healed for 70 years, with his skin infested with countless maggots. There has been no cure for decades, and one of his legs has rotted away, leaving only one tendon.

The evil Japanese Army airdropped fleas infected with the plague virus in the city of Quzhou.

[World War II Japan # Remembering History and Remembering National Shame # Remembering History and Strengthening Our Generation # World Peace. <https://v.douyin.com/iJmvg5mp/>]

Fig. 13. The invading Japanese army carried out bacterial warfare in Quzhou, and now the victims are all old and have passed away one after another.

[The 90th anniversary of the September 18th Incident. The invading Japanese army carried out bacterial warfare in Quzhou, and now the victims are all old and have passed away one after another. What else should we do# Don't forget national shame<https://v.douyin.com/iJuGeXt9/>]

1945年5月，日军进入极为被动的境地，日本天皇的表兄建议为应对严重的粮食危机，应该用身体强壮的健康中国小孩为食物。为此日军各部应该在中国**掳掠12岁以下孩童运往日本**，以作为抽血、兵员和食物之用。
其实早在1941年开始，八路军主办的《抗日旬刊》就已经揭露，日军大肆在中国抢夺和收购儿童，他们以每个儿童10块钱的价格买走，用轮船运往日本。日军将这些儿童作为战略资源，这些儿童的命运可想而知。

Fig 14. In May 1945, the Japanese army entered an extremely passive situation, and the cousin of the Japanese Emperor suggested that in response to the serious food crisis, **strong and healthy Chinese children should be used as food.** For this reason, **various Japanese military departments should kidnap children under the age of 12 in China and transport them to Japan for blood collection, soldiers, and food.**

[A terrifying page in the Japanese military archives: The Japanese enjoy eating and their cruel behavior is outrageous2023-01-17. http://www.360doc.com/content/23/0117/17/9305059_1064008699.shtml#google_vignette]

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.

Fig. 15. [Saving 64 Americans and sacrificing 250000 Chinese: the most cinematic feat of World War II. February 8, 2018. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/DA44MGF70523GE20.html>]

To rescue the 64 U.S. crew members of the 13 planes led by Doolittle, 250,000 Chinese soldiers and civilians sacrificed their lives. This ratio of tremendous sacrifice to success is unprecedented in world history.

The Japanese biological warfare unit released a large amount of bacterial viruses and carried out massacres in Zhejiang and Anhui provinces of China, where 64 American pilots were rescued. Countless civilians were killed, with at least 250,000 people sacrificed.

Business opportunities:

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood jointly invest in producing a film about Chinese people risking their lives to save 64 Allied pilots with 250,000 Chinese losing their lives in the process, it may create a box office of \$1 billion in China. This will enable more people around the world to understand the evil of war and the hard - won nature of peace, which is conducive to cultivating more peace advocates, reducing nuclear weapons and armaments, and at the same time further expanding the scale of the Nobel Fund. However, the screenwriter, director, performer, lighting engineer, and costume designer must be the right people.

Fig 16. **No compensation**

[Is this a civilized era? Is today's society a civilized society? Are the Japanese civilized or barbaric? Or are they despicable? The Japanese military used bacteria that caused people's feet to rot and become infested with maggots. **Wang Xuan has been suing Japan for 25 years on behalf of the victims.** 2022-11-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iN6Kk6aX/06/27B@t.RkgoD:/>]

The Japanese invaders slaughtered at least seven million people with bacterial and viral biochemical warfare in China, and 30 million people were infected. Chinese victims even had to spend large sums of money to file lawsuits in Tokyo. After dozens of legal proceedings, Japan only admitted that biochemical warfare had occurred, but never compensated the victims. Isn't it obvious that the evil Japanese carried out biochemical warfare? Do we still need criminals to admit it? Isn't this the most absurd law, the most absurd country, **and the most absurd social system in the world?** **Japan must be prohibited from serving as a permanent director of any international organization for seven million years.**

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

Fig 17. The bones accumulated more than three meters thick in the collective burial pit discovered during the Nanjing Massacre.

2023-04-03. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAG1KXH/s@e.oq02/01qRK/>

The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all.

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

“日本人是
有史以來我
見過的最卑
鄙、最無耻
的民族。”

——富蘭克林·羅斯福（美國第32任總統）

Fig 18. "The Japanese are the most despicable and shameless people I have ever seen in history." - Franklin D. Roosevelt (32nd President of the United States) [The evaluation of Japan by celebrities from various countries: "Every generation has a reason to resist Japan!"2023-10-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iFv519Qm/> 12/28 LI:/B@T.yT]

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."

“日本，這是一個陰險與狡詐的殘忍民族，這個民族非常勢利，其瘋狂嗜血程度类似于歐洲中世紀的吸血鬼德庫拉，你一旦被它看到弱點，喉管立即會被它咬破，毫無生還可能”

——戴高樂（法蘭西第五共和國首任總統）
头条 @那些段子

Fig 19. "Japan, this is a treacherous and cunning cruel nation, this nation is very mercenary, its crazy bloodthirsty level is similar to vampire Dracula in medieval Europe, once you are seen weak by it, your throat will be bitten immediately, there is no possibility of survival." – Charles de Gaulle (President of the French Fifth Republic)

[The evaluation of Japan by celebrities from various countries: "Every generation has a reason to resist Japan!" 2023-10-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iFv519Qm/> 12/28 LI:/B@T.yT]

“日本人的性格是非常變態的。在歐洲人看來，日本是一個血腥變態嗜殺成性的民族。日本人頑固不化、任性作爲、剛愎自用、愚昧無知，對上級奴顏卑膝，對下級凶狠殘暴。日本人動不動就殺人，動不動就自殺。不把自己的生命放在心上，更不把別人的生命放在心上。所以，日本充滿了混亂和仇殺。”

——孟德斯鳩（法國偉大思想家）

头条 @那些段子

Fig 20. "The character of the Japanese is extremely twisted. In the eyes of Europeans, the Japanese are a bloody and perverse nation with a penchant for killing. They are stubborn, capricious, self-willed, and ignorant, groveling to their superiors and cruel and brutal to their inferiors. The Japanese are quick to kill and quick to commit suicide. They do not value their own lives, let alone the lives of others. Therefore, Japan is full of chaos and enmity."

-Montesquieu (Great French philosopher)

[The evaluation of Japan by celebrities from various countries: "Every generation has a reason to resist Japan!"2023-10-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iFv519Qm/> 12/28 LI:/B@T.yT]

Fig. 21. Professor Dai Jinhua of Peking University collaborated with professors from universities in Japan for five years, during which they explored various topics. This cooperation revealed the distorted personalities or bases, shameless rhetoric and logical confusion present in the Japanese academic circle's debates. It's not impossible that Japan could initiate a third world war, as Dr Kissinger warned. Here is a partial English translation of her video:

By chance, I took part in a five-year academic activity with Japanese scholars, focusing on researching war, discussing war, and exploring issues of peace. This five-year endeavor turned out to be probably the most negative experience of my entire academic life. It was profoundly negative because every time we discussed issues of the war, I felt forced into the role of a nationalist. Whenever this happened, I despised myself and others, because these Japanese scholars—mostly so-called left-wing academics who are considered top-notch—refused to discuss Japan's war

responsibilities. As soon as you bring up the Nanjing Massacre, they shift their focus to Hiroshima and Nagasaki, regardless of whether you intended to challenge them. Whenever you point out that Japan was an aggressor in the war, they portray themselves as victims of that very war. Then, if you try to examine the historical process of the war as a cause-and-effect relationship, they respond by describing it as the convoluted path of Japan's modernization. After that, they would, quite politely but in a very impolite manner, challenge me by asking, "Professor Dai, how old are you? Did you live through the war? How can you understand war without having experienced it? Who told you that?" Implicitly, they are suggesting, "Aren't you just reciting textbooks?" Haven't you been indoctrinated? Aren't you being manipulated?" They say they are the post-war generation that doesn't know and doesn't bear responsibility for the war.

[Don't forget national shame, remember history. 2022-09-18.
<https://v.douyin.com/iN4GU1ue/QXZ:/E@H.li> 08/14]

Fig. 22. **President George H.W. Bush** flew a military aircraft to bomb the Japanese during World War II. After being shot down, he narrowly escaped being captured by

the Japanese. Unfortunately, some of his fellow soldiers who were also shot down were captured and brutally dismembered by the evil Japanese, their flesh sliced into sashimi or raw meat slices and consumed by the enemy soldiers. As a result, when President Bush saw sashimi and raw meat slices on the Japanese Prime Minister's banquet table, he experienced a psychogenic vomiting response.

Although most of the universities ranked in the top 100 in the world in medicine, philosophy, political science, economics, journalism and media, management, and military science are in the United States, and Americans' cognitive level should be leading globally, at that time, not all of the top - level American experts and leaders came forward to explain to the public that President George H. W. Bush just had neurogenic vomiting and give the people correct guidance, so as to guide the American people to carry out healthy presidential election activities. Although it was an obvious transient neurogenic vomiting, the mainstream U.S. media did not all stand by President George H.W. Bush, either. Instead, the public mistook President George H.W. Bush for having poor physical health, resulting in his final loss in the election. This reflects that most of the mainstream U.S. media lack a sense of justice and has not widely reported President George H.W. Bush's transient vomiting from a positive perspective. Voters lack a sense of justice and conscience, and have a lack high - level recognition and respect for President George H.W. Bush's brave and just actions in the war against Japan.

President George H.W. Bush's transient vomiting was because when he saw Japanese sashimi and raw meat slices, he suddenly had to think of his comrades - in - arms who had been eaten by the Japanese as raw meat slices. President George H.W. Bush had deep empathy and was missing his comrades - in - arms at that moment. However, most American voters lack empathy, and their cognitive level is worth discussing. They could not understand President George H.W. Bush. In the United States, which is made up of various interests, the blindly - following mentality of the voters is too strong. These reasons intertwined, resulting in the decrease of President George H.W. Bush's vote — getting rate and losing the election. In China, the IQ of 1.2 billion Chinese is higher than that of the author. The author can tell at a glance that President Bush had transient neurogenic vomiting. If the author of this article were an American and had the right to vote, he would definitely vote for President George H.W. Bush, and it is believed that most Chinese would do the same if they had the right to vote.

However, it can be seen that many Americans believe that they are good people just because they believe in religion. It seems that those who have religious beliefs are good people. **In fact, many Americans lack true beliefs in their hearts.** Is a religion that does not spread the idea that empathy is one of the highest qualities of human beings a cult or a religion? **This is the fundamental problem of American society, and it is the root cause of all legal systems. The foundation on which the American social system is established is worth discussing.**

日军丧心病狂害我儿童把孩子当血库，抗战湖南抢救难童工作艰巨！

访古湖湘 2018-06-08 13:09

湖南战时儿童保育院

作者：陈先枢

Fig. 23. The evil Japanese regarded Chinese children as blood banks to supply blood for Japanese soldiers.

[The Japanese army, in their insane cruelty, have turned our children into blood banks. The task of rescuing child laborers in the Anti-Japanese War in Hunan is arduous. 2018-06-08.

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1602679724264864504&wfr=spider&for=pc>

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

It can be seen from the above that the hearts of the evil Japanese are extremely cruel. However, in daily life, their outwardly polite behavior is very misleading. **And the social system is constructed based on the inner essence of such people.**

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.

日本在侵华期间不但在中华大地上烧杀淫掠，无恶不作，甚至冒天下之大不韪，毫不顾忌的将罪恶的双手伸向了中华民族的未来，少不更事的儿童，有资料统计，侵华日军仅在广东一省就通过强行劫掠，拐骗等方式抓去上千名儿童。

Fig. 24. During its invasion of China, Japan not only committed atrocities such as burning, killing, pillaging, and raping on Chinese soil, but also, without any regard for the consequences, extended its evil hands to the future of the Chinese nation, targeting innocent children. According to available data, the invading Japanese army in Guangdong province alone forcibly abducted and abducted more than 1,000 children through various means.

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Table S1. Questioning the international community and judges	
1	Sexual assault on minors should indeed be subject to lifelong accountability!
2	Rape and gang rape should be subject to lifelong accountability!
3	Murder should be subject to lifelong accountability, isn't it?
4	Isn't Japan a nation where its citizens and the state are collectively responsible for crimes?
5	Why don't justice-oriented lawyers in the United States seize this historic opportunity to accomplish something great that could change the world?
6	Japan destroyed most of the evidence of crimes committed in China, covering up war crimes, and is suspected of bribing the top commander of the U.S. occupation forces, interfering with judicial independence. Japan, the Japanese

	people, and the Japanese Emperor, who committed murder and engaged in crimes against humanity through bacteriological and chemical warfare, should not the United States and international courts reconsider the trial of the criminals and the criminal nation?
7	If Japan is not retried, would it not imply that anyone or any country could think that there is no justice or fairness in this world, and that the Japanese can lie, kill, rape, or rob without facing legal consequences?
8	If Japan is not retried, would it not imply that anyone or any country could think that there is no justice or fairness in this world, and that anyone can kill, rape, or rob without facing legal consequences?

日军将这些中国儿童劫掠过去绝不仅仅只是为了运往日本培养成将来侵华的牺牲品，更令人发指的是把这些孩子当做“行走的血袋”，为日本伤兵输血。

Fig. 25. The Japanese military's abduction of these Chinese children was not just for transporting them to Japan to be groomed as future sacrifices for further invasions of China. What's even more appalling is that **these children were used as "walking blood bags" to provide blood transfusions for the wounded.**

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the

world.

日本对中国儿童的劫掠即便就在日军投降以后也丝毫没有收敛。1945年9月16日下午，一辆载有10名日本士兵的汽车在广州凤安桥边遭中国警察拦截，在进行检查时发现在车上的行李里隐藏着3名中国儿童。日军辩称这3名儿童是在日军部队里从事煮饭等杂役，因没钱回家，准备将他们带到日军驻地后给予钱粮遣散。中国警察在给了3名儿童米粮后让他们自行离开。

Fig. 26. Even after the surrender of the Japanese military, the looting of Chinese children by Japan did not stop. On the afternoon of September 16, 1945, a car carrying 10 Japanese soldiers was intercepted by Chinese police at Feng'an Bridge in Guangzhou. During the inspection, three Chinese children were found hidden in in the car's luggage. The Japanese military argued that the three children were engaged in menial tasks such as cooking in the Japanese army and, having no money to return home, they were planning to take them to the Japanese garrison and provide them with money and food before sending them away. After giving the three children rice, the Chinese police allowed them to leave on their own.

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

同样是在广州，一辆日军军车在撞伤一名人力车夫后被迫停下，日军一反常态的主动提出愿意以3袋大米来赔偿车夫。围观群众及警察在查看日军随车货物的时候，发现有三个麻袋在晃动。打开一开，每个麻袋里竟然都装着一名儿童，日军在被带回警局后承认，这三名儿童是他们抓回来的杂役，准备蒙混过关，带入看管日军的战俘营，以便在日本投降后继续供他们驱使奴役。

日军劫掠中国儿童的目的除了供他们驱使成为奴役之外，当时国民政府调查表明日本还计划将这些儿童训练后用于将来驾驶自杀式飞机进行“特攻”作战，或做为秘密细菌实验的牺牲品。

战后日本为了掩盖这一段极为不光彩的历史，刻意的将关于劫掠中国妇女儿童的材料进行了销毁，也使得日军的罪行至今鲜为人知。

Fig. 27. In Guangzhou, a Japanese military vehicle struck and injured a rickshaw puller and was forced to stop. In a rare move, the Japanese military voluntarily offered to compensate the rickshaw puller with three bags of rice. When the onlookers and police inspected the goods accompanying the Japanese military vehicle, they found three sacks shaking. Upon opening them, each sack was found to contain a child. The Japanese military admitted, after being taken back to the police station, that these three children were kidnapped laborers, intended to be smuggled into the prisoner of war camp where the Japanese military was held, in order to continue to serve as forced labor after Japan's surrender.

The purpose of the Japanese military looting Chinese children was not only to serve as forced labor, but also, according to investigations by the Nationalist government at the time, Japan planned to train these children for future use in piloting suicide planes for "kamikaze" operations or as sacrificial victims for secret bacteriological experiments. After the war, Japan deliberately destroyed materials related to the looting of Chinese women and children in order to cover up this extremely disgraceful period of history, making the atrocities committed by the Japanese military still relatively unknown to this day.

[The invading Japanese army **once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers**, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Evil Japanese soldier invading China

关于日军劫掠拐骗中国儿童的事实，著名的左翼女作家，北京师范大学教授彭慧曾在1938年写下了著名的《怀念被敌船载去的孩子们》一诗，曾使许多读者流下了眼泪。

“如今，白白地，看着你们成了强盗的俘虏！如今，空望着，万恶不赦的倭寇，在黄浦江上，将你们一船船载走！……午夜，我怕听到孤雁的哀鸣。那令我忆起，在日本海峡的那边，那强盗们的巢穴里，正睡着哀哀啼哭的叫不应妈妈的你们！……他要教你们成小小的强盗，他要教你们背叛祖国，他要唆使你们来残杀自己的同胞，专听他们的征调。你们幼小的心灵要牢牢紧记：你们是黄帝的子孙，是诚实耐劳的大中华民族的世裔，你们身在扶桑，心不要忘了祖国！你们不要甘心作奴隶！……到最后胜利的那天，我们还要过海洋，来寻找你们的踪迹，把

Fig. 28. Regarding the fact that the Japanese army looted and abducted Chinese children, a famous writer and professor at Beijing Normal University, wrote the famous poem "Remembering the Children Taken Away by Enemy Ships" in 1938, which brought tears to many readers' eyes.

"Now, I see you, innocent and pure, become captives of bandits. Now, I gaze into the distance, as the unforgivable Japanese pirates, on the Huangpu River, take you all away in boat after boat. ... At midnight, I fear hearing the lonely geese's mournful cries. It reminds me of you, on the other side of the Japan Sea, in the bandits' nest, sleeping with tearful cries, calling for your mothers. ... They want to teach you to be little bandits, to betray your motherland, to incite you to kill your compatriots, and obey their commands. Your young hearts must remember: you are descendants of the Yellow Emperor, descendants of the honest and hardworking Chinese nation, you are in Japan, but do not forget your homeland. Do not be willing slaves. ... On the day of final victory, we will cross the ocean to find your traces and bring you back to our motherland."

[The invading Japanese army once plundered Chinese children and transfused blood to wounded Japanese soldiers, known as walking blood bags. Love history. 2016-12-10. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1553242880051228&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

1945年，日本在中国掳走数万名儿童，至今77年时间仍然是个谜

阿七说史 2022-10-05 18:47 河南

在《国际联盟盟约》中，曾有着这样一条规定，禁止任何国家以任何手段贩卖、掳掠妇女和儿童，而这项准则几乎是现代战争中，所有国家必须遵守的人道主义铁律之一，日本在这份盟约的最后，也信誓旦旦地署上了自己的名字。

但是随着日军侵华脚步的全面兴起，他们却将这条规定抛诸脑后，做出了一系列违背人道主义原则的恶性，他们在中国扔下了数不尽的炮弹，将城市炸成了一片废墟，他们将大量的劳力抓捕起来，通过不光彩的手段，偷偷运到工地上，没日没夜的进行工作。

日本臭名昭著的731部队，更是以非人的手段，用中国民众进行实验，而最恶劣的是，他们仅仅用了几年时间，就从我国掳掠走了上千名儿童，至今不知去向。

迄今为止，日本仍未承认他们的恶性，对于曾经的恶行更是闭口不谈，甚至不断地美化他们的侵略行为。

Fig. 29. In 1945, Japan abducted tens of thousands of children in China, which remains a mystery for 77 years. Aqi talks about history. October 5th, 2022. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1745844307445724066&wfr=spider&for=pc>

Fig 30. Oracle bone fragments, with 13,000 stolen to evil and despicable Japan. How Japan plundered China's wealth. February 26, 2018. https://www.sohu.com/a/224186891_100011719

Fig 31. The Guanyin Monkey and Crane Painting, collected in a Japanese museum, was looted by evil Japan and listed as a national treasure. How Japan plundered China's wealth. February 26, 2018. https://www.sohu.com/a/224186891_100011719

Fig 32. The baby's eyes were gouged out by the fierce Japanese invaders. [After Japan's surrender, the US military discovered a laboratory in Qingdao where Japanese people stored baby specimens, unexpectedly exposing Japan's heinous crimes # 731

Unit # World War II # 731 Bacterial Warfare.2023-04-27.
<https://v.douyin.com/iNAXQGxq/> OKj:/ 06/27 e@B.gB]

Why is Japan so despicable, evil, cruel, and vicious? Genes?

Table S2. Questioning the international community and judges	
1	What is a royal army?
2	Isn't the royal army the Japanese Emperor's army?
3	Since it was the Japanese military that referred to itself as the Imperial Army during World War II, isn't the Japanese Emperor the biggest war criminal in Japan?
4	Japan destroyed most of the evidence of crimes committed in China, covering up war crimes, and is suspected of bribing the top commander of the U.S. occupation forces, interfering with judicial independence. Japan, the Japanese people, and the Japanese Emperor, who committed murder and engaged in crimes against humanity through bacteriological and chemical warfare, should not the United States and international courts reconsider the trial of the criminals and the criminal nation?
5	If Japan is not retried, would it not imply that anyone or any country could think that there is no justice or fairness in this world, and that the Japanese can lie, kill, rape, or rob without facing legal consequences?
6	If Japan is not retried, would it not imply that anyone or any country could think that there is no justice or fairness in this world, and that anyone can kill, rape, or rob without facing legal consequences?
7	The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

Fig 33. The priceless skull of the Beijing people mysteriously disappeared after being occupied by the Japanese army. There are reports that it is in Japan. How Japan plundered China's wealth. February 26, 2018. https://www.sohu.com/a/224186891_100011719

Fig. 34. Warvigilance: Photos taken by Kyodo News Agency on May 12, in the 21st century, it showed Japanese Prime Minister Abe, wearing a flight suit, sitting in the T-4 trainer aircraft of the Self- Defense Forces' "Blue Shock Wave" air show team,

smiling, stretching out his right hand and giving a thumbs- up. **Aircraft number 731.** The move drew fierce criticism from South Korean media. The South Korea's Chosun Ilbo said Abe was endlessly provocative; According to the Central Daily News, Abe revived the terror of **Japan's 731 biochemical forces**. During the Japanese War of Aggression against China, Unit 731 conducted bacteria experiments with living people in Northeast China, which was notorious (What human experiments have been done in the top ten dehumanizing experiments of the Japanese Unit 731, Time.: June 8, 2020; <http://www.52qixiang.com/m/view.php?aid=49778>)

Abe, the prime minister of Japan in the 21st century, is still openly nostalgic for the **731 Japanese biological warfare troops** who use living people to carry out large-scale experiments and eat living people. This is not an occasional phenomenon, which shows that the Japanese army worships the 731 biochemical troops in World War II. At present, Japan's naval strength ranks fourth in the world, indicating that Japan will inevitably wage war again in the future, and the weapons used must include chemical, biological or nuclear weapons and other special weapons. If Japan cannot gather the U.S. military to fight together, it will inevitably find ways to eliminate or disintegrate the U.S. military nearby, and the large number of U.S. troops in sight do not even need to fly to Pearl Harbor.

Logical and Historical analysis of Contemporary Japan and Japanese:

According to Western standards, Japan has a freely elected government. The Prime Minister elected by the Japanese people must represent the will and thoughts of the Japanese people in the 21st century. Since the Prime Minister elected by the Japanese people has a great fondness for the evil Unit 731, a biological warfare army that once slaughtered countless lives, and even drive its symbolic Unit 731 - related aircraft, doesn't it reflect that most of the Japanese people in modern society are an evil, malicious nation with a penchant for killing people using bacteria and viruses? The social system of a country is determined and chosen by the people, political leaders, and their political parties in that country. Doesn't this mean that Japan's social system today is an evil one? If you don't think so, don't you think that Western democratic elections are very hypocritical? If you are not a hypocritical or evil person, and you believe that you are a person with a sense of justice and conscience, don't you want to change the bad Western political systems? Or are you going to become a slave to the so - called Western democratic selection systems? Wouldn't you then be in a slave society or a semi - slave society? Doesn't this imply that Karl Marx made many mistakes in his classification of human social systems in the past? Can you still claim that your country's liberal democratic system is superior?

Marx's simple classification of social systems is clearly unable to quickly identify Japan's social system. Obviously, the evil Japanese and the Japanese nation as a group have demonstrated the complexity and cruelty of human social systems to the world.

Fig 35. [Australian soldier George Leonard, who resisted the Japanese, remained steadfast despite being captured and tortured by Japanese forces for half a month before ultimately being brutally beheaded. 2023-12-22. <https://v.douyin.com/iNkkpn37/TYz:/09/17 W@z.tr>]

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig 36. The baby's head was cut in half by the Japanese. [Japanese atrocities. The hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten. Don't forget national shame, remember history# Never forget national shame#2023-09-08.<https://v.douyin.com/iNkAyV2H/HVY:/d@a.aA04/02>]

Why is Japan so despicable, evil, and vicious? Genes?

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig 37. The Japanese invaders tossed infants into boiling pots of oil, frying them until golden brown, and then placed them on trays to be eaten. [Japanese atrocities. The hatred engraved in the bones will never be forgotten. Don't forget national shame, remember history# Never forget national shame#2023-09-08 <https://v.douyin.com/iNkAyV2H/HVY:/d@a.aA04/02>]
Why is Japan so despicable, evil, cruel, and vicious? Genes?
Japan must be named SRM-Japan or SR-Japan
The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?
Which nation is the most evil, cruel, and despicable in the entire universe?

Fig 38. [In 1946, millions of Japanese POWs were repatriated on aircraft carriers, taking with them not only large and small parcels but also arrogant demeanor. #History #True Event #Precious Footage #Never Forget National Humiliation.2023-02-15. <https://v.douyin.com/iNkBbTdL/S@l.cn> 04/05 pDU:/]

Look at the arrogant and excited demeanor of these Japanese prisoners of war; how could Japan be considered a defeated nation? Japan did nothing more than sign a single A4-sized document of surrender, which excited the utopian nerves of kind-hearted people around the world. The biggest war criminal even openly bribed the occupying commander, General MacArthur, with beauty, and was not only spared the death penalty, but was astonishingly not sentenced at all. Where are human rights? Where is empathy? Where is freedom? Where is democracy?

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

侵华日军罪恶实录： 731部队拿婴儿做标本 历史珍贵图片

731部队除了细菌战

Fig. 38-1. Crimes of the Japanese Invading China: Photos of **Chinese pregnant women's live infants taken by the extremely malicious and evil 731 Japanese Army as specimens**. {Are Japanese individuals? I don't think even my cats and dogs can bear to do this! Do you think whitening is useful? Do you think changing the textbook is enough? The matter is in front of us, an unforgettable history! Never change# Remembering history # Cultural invasion # War without gunpowder # Punishing scumbags severely # Forgetting history means betrayal. 2022-10-02. <https://v.douyin.com/idrd5t88/>}

Fig 39. Bacterial Warfare Massacre [The invading Japanese army admitted to bacterial warfare, but refused to compensate or plead guilty. Do you know why? 2023-12-10. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAV89sJ/j@c.aa10/08iPx:/>]

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?
The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?
The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

美军发现青岛实验室 意外揭开日本滔天罪行 简直就是恶魔

Fig 40. After Japan's surrender in 1945, U.S. troops in Qingdao began to sweep the battlefield. As they entered a club established by the Japanese, they discovered a hidden cellar. When they opened door to the cellar, they were greeted by a pungent smell of antiseptics, and the dank and dark basement emitted the same harsh odor, giving everyone a sense of foreboding. Suddenly, they found three tubs in the corner, each containing the body of an infant soaked inside. Although American soldiers were accustomed to seeing dead bodies, such a sinister scene still made their skin crawl. After a search, they found that each infant had a strange sequence of numbers marked on them: 33, 35, and 99. One soldier speculated that it might have been a biochemical base of the Japanese army and that the children were pitiful test subjects. Hearing this, everyone on-site got chills down their spines, and they immediately contacted the police. The authorities arrived at the scene promptly after receiving the report and found that the tragic infants were all less than a year old, with evident signs of abuse on their bodies, eyes gouged out, and abdomens dissected. According to the codes on the infants' bodies, at least 99 babies were tortured to death by the Japanese. Before Japan's surrender, many Japanese had fled back to their country, with only a few still

staying temporarily in China. The police brought them all to the station for questioning, hoping to learn something. However, these Japanese doctors denied the killings and claimed that the Yamato people would never harm infants, insisting that it was definitely a conspiracy by the Americans to frame the Japanese. However, it wasn't long before the police received another report; another vat was found in another Japanese stronghold, filled with the corpses of Chinese children. People who had lived nearby reported that the Japanese army had secretly conducted human experiments there and abducted many people.

[After Japan's surrender, the US military discovered a laboratory in Qingdao where Japanese people stored baby specimens, unexpectedly exposing Japan's heinous crimes # 731 Unit # World War II # 731 Bacterial Warfare.2023-04-27. https://v.douyin.com/iNAXQGxq/OKj:/06/27_e@B.gB]

Fig. 41. The evil and inhumane Japanese turned living Chinese babies into baby specimens. Do you know why Chinese people like to call Japanese people "Japanese locusts"? How far apart are the genes of Japanese individuals from those of hyenas and wolves?

Do the Japanese have a little bit of humanity?

Are Japanese people not human?

Are Japanese people human?

Are Japanese a species of people on this planet?

Seeing the cruel behavior of the Japanese, one instinctively asks: Are the Japanese really still a race of humans?

[Too many unborn babies have been cruelly deprived of their lives. The Japanese people who have lost their sense of humanity deserve to be punished severely. #Trueevents #History #We must strive for self-improvement #Rememberhistory #Japaneseatrocities. <https://v.douyin.com/iJjnK9Lf/>]

Fig. 42. Specimens made from live infants by the 731 unit of the invading Japanese army in China

The evil and inhumane Japanese turned living Chinese babies into baby specimens.

The baby's limbs were actually cut off by the ferocious Japanese locust

The baby's abdomen was unexpectedly torn open by the ferocious Japanese locust

Do you know why Chinese people like to call Japanese people "Japanese locusts"?
How far apart are the genes of Japanese individuals from those of hyenas and wolves?
Do the Japanese have a little bit of humanity?

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Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Logical and Historical analysis of Contemporary Japan and Japanese:

According to Western standards, Japan has a freely elected government. The Prime Minister elected by the Japanese people must represent the will and thoughts of the Japanese people in the 21st century. Since the Prime Minister elected by the Japanese people has a great fondness for the evil Unit 731, a biological warfare army that once slaughtered countless lives, and even drive its symbolic Unit 731 - related aircraft, doesn't it reflect that most of the Japanese people in modern society are an evil, malicious nation with a penchant for killing people using bacteria and viruses? The social system of a country is determined and chosen by the people, political leaders, and their political parties in that country. Doesn't this mean that Japan's social system today is an evil one? If you don't think so, don't you think that Western democratic elections are very hypocritical? If you are not a hypocritical or evil person, and you believe that you are a person with a sense of justice and conscience, don't you want to change the bad Western political systems? Or are you going to become a slave to the so - called Western democratic selection systems? Wouldn't you then be in a slave society or a semi - slave society? Doesn't this imply that Karl Marx made many mistakes in his classification of human social systems in the past? Can you still claim that your country's liberal democratic system is superior?

Fig. 43. Many babies whose eyes and various organs have been removed by the Japanese

Too many babies had their eyes and various organs gouged out. This happened after the US military landed in Qingdao in 1946. In the basement of Qingdao Cultural Palace (formerly the Japanese Army Club), the U.S. military discovered two large barrels containing infant remains.

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

[Can we forget the atrocities committed by the Japanese invaders? Can we dare forget them? #NeverForgetBloodTearsNeverForgetNationalHumiliation #JapaneseMilitaryAtrocities #WeMustBeStrong #RememberHistory. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ6R2hHY/>]

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."

日本士兵将这位年轻女子绑在椅子上，以供其反复施暴。(新华社供)

南京妇女不仅遭到强奸，还遭到毁尸和其他折磨。(当代中国出版社供)

Fig. 44. Nanjing Massacre

[<https://v.douyin.com/iJMEL72m/>]

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil

Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig. 45. Infant specimens soaked in formalin solution by the cruel Japanese invader 731 unit.

The cruel Japanese invader Unit 731 conducted experiments with live humans.

[This Japanese person said, "The most unforgettable thing for me is the baby specimens, which were truly shocking. There were also skinning experiments conducted without anesthesia, which were also part of the experiments, and this is true. #RememberHistoryNeverForgetNationalHumiliation #731 #History". <https://v.douyin.com/iJMKeSjo/>]

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig. 46. One of the tortures of the Japanese: One of the torture of Japanese Unit 731, the drying experiment of living people
[<https://v.douyin.com/iJN1UJTj/>]

Do you know how the accurate conclusion that living humans contain 78% water was reached?

Do you know how many different methods the only person in the world who bows continuously every day, appears polite on the outside but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely brutal, and extremely anti-human, a Japanese person, has used for drying experiments on living humans?

Do you know how many different methods the only person in the world who bows continuously every day, appears polite on the outside but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely brutal, and extremely anti-human, a Japanese person, has observed and recorded the struggles of living humans in drying experiments?

Fig. 47. The Rape of Nanking----Iris Chang

This girl can be considered lucky compared to many other girls who were bound naked to chairs, beds, or poles, serving as tools for Japanese soldiers to satisfy their bestial desires. Many of these girls did not survive such brutal abuse.

There have been accounts from Chinese witnesses describing the horrific death of an 11-year-old girl who was continuously raped for two days straight. "Her legs were covered in blood, swollen, and torn, a sight that was so repulsive that one could not bear to look at it."

During this mass rape, Japanese soldiers also frequently killed children and infants because they were considered a hindrance. According to witnesses, many children and babies were suffocated to death while their mothers were raped, as soldiers would stuff cloth into their mouths to silence them, or they were stabbed to death. Americans and Europeans who witnessed the Nanjing Massacre have recorded numerous similar incidents, including one account that states, "Around 5 o'clock on February 3rd, **three Japanese soldiers arrived at Shangshu Lane (near Dazhong Bridge) and forced a woman to throw her baby away before raping her. They then laughed maniacally and left.**"

Countless men were killed while trying to protect their loved ones from being raped. When Japanese soldiers dragged a woman out of a grass hut, her husband tried to intervene, only to have Japanese soldiers "pierce his nose with wire and tie the other end of the wire to a tree, like tying up an ox." They then repeatedly stabbed him with bayonets, ignoring his mother's desperate pleas and anguished cries as she crawled to the ground. The soldiers ordered his mother to go back inside the house, threatening to kill her if she refused. The man died instantly due to his severe injuries.

In Nanjing, Japanese soldiers displayed extreme inhumanity and sexual perversion. Just as many Japanese soldiers invented various killing competitions to alleviate the boredom of repeated massacres, some soldiers grew tired of their excessive indulgences and created sadistic rape and torture games.

Perhaps one of the most inhumane forms of amusement for Japanese soldiers was piercing women's vagina.

<https://v.douyin.com/iedULBm4/>

Fig. 48. Group photo of some demons in Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese 731 Unit [Japanese Unit 731 captured 500 female students. Why let them go after eating Shaobing (Baked Cake in Griddle)? The real purpose is very malicious. July 3, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/GMJ6EIH00543L37L.html>]

Table S3. Evil Japanese Unit 731 conducted infectious disease experiments with Allied prisoners of war, and Diary of British prisoner of war Robert Petty

Japanese Unit 731 stationed in Allied Prisoner of War Camp
The Japanese Unit 731 was a special force established during World War II by imperial decree for conducting bacteriological experiments and warfare. It is well known that during the trial at the Far East International Military Tribunal after the war, evidence documents No. 3113 and No. 3114, presented by the British inspection team, revealed a glimpse of the history between the Japanese Unit 731

<p>and the Allied prisoners of war camp in Shenyang. The U.S. National Archives also hold related records on this matter.</p>
<p>According to the records, on February 1, 1943, General Mezu, the commander of the Japanese Kwantung Army, issued a special operational order called "Commander-in-chief Guan's order C No. 98." This order required the Japanese Unit 731 to swiftly dispatch 20 personnel, including 5 officers, 5 non-commissioned officers, and 10 soldiers, along with equipment, to the Allied prisoners of war camp in Shenyang to "conduct bacteriological tests on patients with chronic dysentery."</p>
<p>After receiving the order from the Kwantung Army, the Unit 731 formed a "work group" for the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp. This group arrived at the camp on February 14 of the same year and immediately set up a "workplace" inside the camp.</p>
<p>According to related historical materials, after the Unit 731 "work group" reported to the camp superintendent of the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp upon their arrival, they began their tense "work" on the 15th. The "work group" set up a simple workstation on the playground of the Temporary Camp in Nanda Camp, Fushun, and started conducting "physical examinations" on over 1,000 Allied prisoners of war one by one. During their time in the camp, the "work group" regularly drew blood from the prisoners of war and frequently administered injections of the so-called "vaccine." For a considerable period of time, the Unit 731 "work group" carried out a significant amount of "work" in the Shenyang Allied prisoners of war camp.</p>
<p>The head of the cholera section of Unit 731, Masao Hozumi, was one of the members sent to the "working group" in the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang. After the war, during the trial of some members of Unit 731 conducted in Khabarovsk, Soviet Union, the trial record of Juuzou Tsukaesa provided further understanding of the "work" of the "working group" of Unit 731 in the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang.</p>
<p>Prosecutor: "Can you tell us whether Unit 731 conducted investigations on the resistance of Americans to infectious diseases?"</p>
<p>Juuzou Tsukaesa: "I remember this happened in early 1943. At that time, I was recuperating in the Shenyang Military Hospital. A scientific worker named Soh Kozue from the unit came to see me. He talked to me about his work and said that he lived in Shenyang to study the resistance of Anglo-Saxon prisoners of war to infectious diseases. Kozue was specifically sent by Unit 731 to the Allied prisoner of war camp to investigate their resistance to infectious diseases."</p>
<p>Prosecutor: "Did you carry out tests on American prisoners of war for this purpose?"</p>
<p>Juuzou Tsukaesa: "Yes, that's correct."</p>
<p>During the trial, the Soviet prosecution noted that the experimental project conducted by Masao Hozumi in 1943 was titled "Blood Characteristics of American Soldiers and Their Immunity to Infectious Diseases."</p>
<p>Japanese Unit 731 stationed in Allied Prisoner of War Camp</p>
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<p>Diary of British prisoner of war Robert Petty</p>
<p>Robert Petty, a British lieutenant colonel in the army, was captured on the battlefield</p>

<p>in Singapore and was subsequently imprisoned in an Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang until the surrender of Japan in 1945. His prisoner number was 24. During his captivity, Petty secretly recorded daily events in the camp using a unique code that only he knew, while evading the Japanese guards. Although a part of the diary was discovered and confiscated due to thorough inspections by the Japanese, most of it survived intact. In 1985, he agreed to be interviewed by ITV, where he stated, "In my diary, I truthfully recorded the reasons provided by the Japanese for the vaccinations, injections, and preventive measures they performed on us. At that time, we had no way to determine whether they were genuine or not." Petty subsequently provided the entire diary to the production team, and it was made public.</p>
<p>In the "Petty Diary," there are detailed records of the activities performed by Unit 731 in the prisoner of war camp:</p>
<p>Year: 1943</p>
<p>February 14: Smallpox vaccination was administered.</p>
<p>February 15: Two Americans died in the hospital, and the Japanese who arrived at the camp performed autopsies on the bodies.</p>
<p>February 20: All prisoners were tested for the presence of germs causing diarrhea and dysentery.</p>
<p>February 23: A funeral was held for 142 individuals. In 105 days, 186 Americans died.</p>
<p>February 24: The medical investigation concluded that the cause of death was ordinary diarrhea and not fatal. It was clear that this group of medical personnel claimed to provide medical treatment to prisoners while not actually taking any effective measures to cure their illnesses.</p>
<p>March 8: In 123 days, 194 deaths occurred.</p>
<p>April 19: The Japanese conducted another medical investigation.</p>
<p>June 4th: The Japanese carried out the third medical investigation. However, during these visits, it seemed that the medical team was not enthusiastic about actually treating prisoners' illnesses. They merely administered some "preventive vaccines" and asked many strange questions, such as the ethnic backgrounds of the prisoners. The peculiar behavior of these doctors aroused suspicions among the prisoners, as it appeared that they were not there to provide medical treatment.</p>
<p>June 5: 0.5cc dysentery vaccine was administered.</p>
<p>June 8: The number of people with diarrhea continued to increase.</p>
<p>June 13: 1.0cc dysentery vaccine was administered.</p>
<p>August 6: The number of deaths now reached 206.</p>
<p>August 29: Vaccination against dysentery and 1.0cc typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine was administered.</p>
<p>September 12: Blood tests were conducted on each prisoner.</p>
<p>September 19: Approximately 40cc of blood was drawn from each prisoner for erythrocyte sedimentation rate tests.</p>
<p>October 9: X-ray examinations were performed on all prisoners to check for tuberculosis bacteria.</p>

October 10: 0.5cc cholera vaccine was administered.
October 17: 1.0cc cholera vaccine was administered.
November 21: The death toll has exceeded 230.
Year: 1944
On February 6, vaccinated all prisoners of war.
On February 20, injected 0.5 cc of typhoid and paratyphoid combination vaccine.
On February 27, injected typhoid and paratyphoid combination vaccine.
On May 21, injected 0.5cc of dysentery vaccine.
On May 28, injected 1.0cc of dysentery vaccine.
On August 20, all prisoners of war were injected with 1.0cc of typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine.
Year: 1945
On January 28, vaccinated all prisoners of war.
On February 27, vaccinated all prisoners of war with 0.5cc of typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine.
On March 6, vaccinated all prisoners of war with 1.0cc of typhoid and paratyphoid vaccine.
In this part of Piti's diary, on the one hand, we can see that between February 14th, 1943 when Unit 731 entered the prisoner of war camp and March 6th, 1945, the prisoners of war were injected with various vaccines at least 15 times in the span of two years. The frequency of injections far exceeded the normal vaccination cycle rate.
After the war, Arthur Christie, a former British prisoner of war (number 1210), testified as follows: "The group of people (referring to Unit 731 "work team") started a series of injections as soon as they arrived. Monthly body measurements also started from that time. After that, injections were given 16 times within 12 months. They seriously told us that these injections were for typhoid, paratyphoid, malaria vaccines, etc. But it is perplexing that preventive vaccination for vaccines is once every 7 years for the British army and once every 5 years for the American army. Are the injections we received really vaccines?"
Blood samples were also taken every month. They forced me to separate the blood into red blood cells and plasma using a centrifuge. Each month, 50cc of blood samples were taken from each individual, totaling 50,000cc for 1,000 people. What was all this blood being used for?
Former U.S. prisoner of war (designated as Number 190), Robert Brown, recalled: "Shortly after arriving in Fengtian, a group of Japanese doctors came to the POW camp to administer vaccines and assign numbers to us. However, many people died soon after, and at that time, a Japanese doctor named Ogi saved me. Many years later, Dr. Ogi told me that he was a member of the 731 Bacteriological Warfare Unit.
Harm done by Unit 731 to Allied prisoners of war
After the war, the United States government's post-war investigation team conducted a detailed investigation into what happened at the Allied prisoner of war camp in Shenyang. They compiled a document called "The Experiences of Allied

Prisoners in Manchuria," which was declassified in 2003 and is now stored in the U.S. National Archives. The document contains records of Unit 731's activities in the prisoner of war camp:

People with symptoms of intermittent fever must be reported. Their body temperature and blood must be checked, and they must be given a card recording their daily visits to the pharmacy to collect quinine. The dosage of quinine is as follows: 15 pills per day for the first 3 days, 9 pills per day for the next 10 days, and 3 pills per day for the following 10 days. This constitutes one course of treatment. Generally, after two to three weeks, patients would experience the symptoms of intermittent fever again and have to repeat treatment. Compared to U.S. treatment for this type of malaria, the dosage of quinine was absurdly low. The American treatment plan called for taking 30 to 50 pills per day. The Japanese used similar methods to treat other diseases as well. It can be seen that the "treatment" of prisoners of war may not have aimed to cure them completely, but rather to repeatedly observe their resistance to infectious diseases.

After the war, the U.S. House of Representatives held two hearings of the Committee on Veterans Affairs in 1982 and 1986. During the 1986 hearing, James Frank, a former prisoner of war (Number 843), recalled: in the spring of 1943, two Japanese officers were assigned to work with the visiting medical team, and he was one of them. The Japanese asked him to move bodies from one small house to another, and then they would be placed on autopsy tables. He witnessed the organs of these soldiers being removed, placed in special containers labeled with each prisoner's number, and detailed records being made. The specimens were taken away from the prisoner of war camp in trucks. Soon after, some prisoners were selected for testing. Japanese medical personnel asked detailed questions about the racial backgrounds of American prisoners of war, whether they were Scottish, French, British, or from other countries.

Jack Roberts, a former British prisoner of war (Number 1183), recalled: one morning in early 1943, he was in poor physical condition but didn't dare to go to the "hospital" because no one who went in ever came back. He went to the small house where bodies were stored, and there were about 340 bodies piled up there. The feet of the bodies were tagged with numbers. The Japanese asked him to carry two or three bodies to the Japanese "doctors" who lived there. They wore gas masks and always hid their faces. He and another person were ordered to lift the bodies and place them on the dissecting table. Then, the Japanese would open the abdomens of the bodies, reaching deep inside to remove organs like the stomach, gallbladder, and small intestine. They also took out things resembling liver samples and lungs. Then, they would cut open the heads and remove part of the brain.

Bruce Blythman, a former Australian prisoner of war (Number 25), worked as a doctor in the prisoner of war camp hospital. He hid a diary under a patient's bed (the Japanese never approached prisoners suffering from tuberculosis) and recorded three instances of the "Medical Unit of Unit 731" entering the prisoner of war camp to "work." During the first visit, the "Medical Unit of Unit 731" performed autopsies on deceased prisoners and collected samples with labels. However, during

the three visits to the prisoner of war camp, they only conducted various checks, blood tests, and did not provide any valuable opinions regarding the conditions in the camp or the high death rate.

At a conference in 1986, former American prisoner of war (number 768) Greg Rodriguez testified that for over 40 years after the war, he had to visit the Veterans Administration hospital multiple times each year due to inexplicable symptoms such as fever, pain, and fatigue. One time, his temperature reached a staggering 106 degrees Fahrenheit (approximately 41 degrees Celsius). It wasn't until 10 years ago when a doctor finally diagnosed him with typhoid fever, because his blood had a significant amount of typhoid bacilli.

Greg Rodriguez's son, Langrey, was once president of the American Prisoners of War Association. In September 2003, he visited the Shenyang Allied Prisoner of War Camp where his father had been held captive. In an interview with local media, he revealed that his father had been injected with vaccines while in captivity, and his body temperature remained higher than normal in the following days. Similarly, U.S. prisoners of war experienced unexplained fever, trembling, night sweats, snake-like skin shedding, and numbness, all due to the infiltration of Unit 731 into the prisoner of war camp, where bacteria were injected into prisoners' bodies under the guise of preventive vaccinations.

On September 19, 2003, Langrey presented the Chinese media with an English certificate from the U.S. government entitled "Proof that the Prison Camp Injected Plague into American Prisoners of war." He exposed, "The evidence of vaccine injections is right here."

Thomas George Riggs, a former U.S. prisoner of war with identification number 968, recalled his experience. One night, he had a high fever and experienced alternating chills and heat. A Japanese doctor approached him and asked him to lie down on his bed, placing a mirror under his nose. Later on, a feather was inserted into his nostril. Riggs thought the Japanese were checking his breathing. However, since then, his high fever persisted, and he was plagued by illness. One minute he felt fine, and the next minute he suddenly fell ill. Initially, it lasted several months, then several years, or even longer. Riggs underwent numerous tests and examinations at the hospital, but doctors could not determine the cause of his illness. As a father of six children, he unknowingly transmitted the pathogen on to his children, affecting their physical health. From infancy, two of his daughters developed thyroid disease, and one of his sons suffered from arthritis.

Through the accounts of surviving prisoners of war, we gain a visceral understanding of the "work" of Unit 731 in the prisoner of war camps. On the surface, the purpose of Unit 731's "medical team" in the camps was to investigate the causes of prisoners' deaths and improve their health conditions. However, actual "medical work" did not prioritize prisoners' health or provide them with treatment. Treating illnesses was not important, even insignificant. The Allied prisoners of war had experienced the cruelty of war, transportation, and harsh living conditions in the Fushun POW camp, so falling ill was inevitable. However, apart from severely ill prisoners who died, most prisoners should have recovered, especially if given appropriate treatment. But it

was precisely the "medical" treatment by Unit 731 that had lifelong effects on the prisoners' bodies.

After enduring the tests of war, death marches, and torturous transportation, over a thousand prisoners of war from countries like England and America who were held captive in the "Fushun Prisoner of War Detention Center" began to suffer from a large number of illnesses and deaths.

If the Japanese army really wanted to treat a large number of sick Allied prisoners of war and restore their health, they could easily have done so in Shenyang. There was the "Manchurian Medical University", which belonged to the local area and was ranked among the top hospitals in Japan and its occupied territories at that time. There was also the "Fengtian Army Hospital," which was under military jurisdiction and where Ishii Shiro underwent treatment.

In short, the Japanese army, under its rule, had the capability to provide treatment and there was no need to send Unit 731 to POW camps. Furthermore, Unit 731 was a special unit engaged in bacteriological warfare and did not have a medical nature. Moreover, given the tense situation in the early 1943 stage of the Second World War, Unit 731 was more focused on research and preparation for bacteriological warfare. If the sole purpose was to treat prisoners of war, why would the Japanese army easily deploy such a unit for something that was considered insignificant to them? It is even more puzzling that the Kwantung Army chose to send Unit 731 to POW camps as a way of issuing combat orders.

Investigation of Unit 731 after World War II

After Japan surrendered in August 1945, the United States Strategic Intelligence Agency formulated a mission codenamed "Operation Firebird" with the aim of liberating American prisoners of war held captive in Northeast China. Documents on this mission explicitly stated that members of the agency were to fly immediately to Harbin to rescue American and other Allied prisoners of war once they received notification of victory in the war. It is worth noting that there were no Allied prisoner of war camps in Harbin at the time, with the closest one being Shenyang. This suggests that the American government and military authorities at the time considered the possibility of Unit 731 conducting bacteriological experiments on Allied prisoners of war. American intelligence agencies were aware of the Japanese conducting bacteriological experiments near Harbin, so they firmly believed that there must be prisoners of war there. It seems that their mission to rescue prisoners of war near Harbin was not due to a lack of knowledge of the location of Allied prisoner of war camps, but rather their firm belief that some prisoners of war had already been taken to Harbin to serve as experimental subjects for the bacteriological unit.

In 1946, after the war, various American media outlets such as the "Stars and Stripes Pacific Edition" and "The New York Times" reported on the Ishii Unit's use of Allied prisoners of war for bacteriological experiments.

In August 1947, a U.S. government archival document indicated: "There is a possibility that a independent Soviet investigation team has discovered evidence near Fengtian suggesting that the Japanese used American prisoners of war for live

bacteriological experiments, resulting in the loss of many American soldiers' lives. Moreover, these pieces of evidence are likely to have been utilized by the Soviet Union in the legal trial of Japanese prisoners of war."

In March 1956, a memorandum from the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) stated: "Mr. James Kelleher of the Department of Defense Special Action Office confirmed this further after the US military occupied Japan. He determined that the Japanese used American prisoners of war as subjects for bacteriological experiments in Manchuria between 1943 and 1944, making them undoubtedly victims... The related information is considered highly sensitive and strictly controlled."

After the publication of Shōichi Sonobe's "The Devil's Gluttony" in 1980, the issue of experiments conducted on Allied prisoners of war gained unprecedented attention. He stated, "The majority of the victims were Chinese, Koreans, and Russians, but information from various sources indicates that the victims also included British, Dutch, Australian, New Zealand, and American individuals."

(References: Declassified files from the US National Archives, such as "Experiences of Fengtian POWs," "Fengtian POW Report (February Report) - Work Report of the Temporary Epidemic Prevention and Control Group," and "List of Captured Personnel (Showa 20th Year - Surveillance Intelligence Series)"; "Trial Materials for Former Japanese Army Personnel Charged with Preparing and Using Bacteriological Weapons," Moscow Foreign Document Publishing House, 1950; (Japanese) Fuyuko Saito's "Biological Warfare Unit 731," Grassroots Publishing, 2002; (American) Daniel Barenblatt's "A Plague upon Humanity," Harper Collins Publishers, 2003.)

[Translated from the following literature. <http://dangshi.people.com.cn/n1/2020/0813/c85037-31820562.html>]

Fig. 49. One of the tortures of the Japanese

This young girl resisted gang rape by **Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese** invaders and was dissected and cut off pieces of flesh from her thighs, using a knife to carry a barbecue and eat.

[In the living experiment of Japanese Unit 731, a sex slave was unscrewed and his breasts were cut off..... <https://v.douyin.com/iXu4h6e/>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe

punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 50. One of the tortures of the evil Japanese:

In the horrendous Nanjing Massacre, a Chinese woman was brutally decapitated, and the blood splattered from her saber. The mother opened her mouth wide and her face deformed. Although she died with great fear, she still held the child tightly in her hands.

This is a real photograph of the Nanjing Massacre Memorial Hall. An innocent civilian woman holding her baby in her arms was beheaded by evil Japanese soldiers, and blood splattered from her neck in the air. Even today, the Emperor, Prime Minister, and other Japanese officials, as well as ordinary citizens, still pay tribute to the war criminals who committed these killings every year. **Isn't the Japanese nation an extremely barbaric, extremely cruel, extremely despicable, extremely anti-human, and extremely savage nation? As the supreme strategist and commander of a war, isn't the evil Japanese Emperor a war criminal who has been overlooked and not properly punished or sent to the gallows?**

The actions of the **Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese invaders,** devoid of humanity and inhumane, have no reason or qualification to forgive the Japanese for our ancestors. [<https://v.douyin.com/iyT57f9/>]

Is the Japanese not a species that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

Is the Japanese nation not a nation that appears quite polite on the outside, but extremely evil on the inside, extremely despicable, extremely barbaric, and extremely uncivilized?

Are Japanese an evil species of people on this planet?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."

110	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Immigration to other countries is a latent means and tool for evil countries without conscience and empathy or countries with criminal records to commit crimes, invade, plunder wealth and annex the territory of other countries. It is an important factor leading to an increase in crime rates. It is the basis for evil countries to carry out long-term evil plans under the slogan of freedom and human rights. Farmers in China's three northeastern provinces were once deeply harmed and plundered by Japanese immigrants.</p> <p>The number of immigrants from the evil countries involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this article in any other country is prohibited from exceeding 0.01% of the number of deaths in Nanjing during the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese invaders. Those who have immigrated must be repatriated to the criminal country.</p>
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	Questioning the United Nations and the international community
1	Why has Japan long pretended to be a victim of the atomic bomb explosion?
2	Why do the Japanese people like to pretend for a long time to be victims of the atomic bomb explosion?
3	Why do Japanese politicians like to pretend for a long time to be victims of the atomic bomb explosion, even though they know very well in their hearts that the areas where the atomic bomb actually exploded are uninhabitable?
4	Why is the Japanese media so good at long - term fraud?
5	Why are the highly educated politicians in the international community so mindless and thoughtless that they are actually deceived by such childish tricks?
6	Why are the highly educated politicians in the international community so mindless and thoughtless that they are actually deceived by such illogical tricks?
7	Why does not the United Nations prohibit Japan, the world's most evil war criminal and criminal country, from lowering the marriage and childbearing age to 13 after the war? Isn't this accumulating potential conflict and war population for this evil country? Are United Nations officials not protecting the human rights of the victims, but protecting criminals and accumulating capital for the next crime for criminals? Politicians at the United Nations and in some countries should experience the Japanese army's torture of Chinese and American female soldiers and generals for three years, and be forced to eat

	feces for three years like American generals. If not, what qualifications do you have to be a civil servant of a country or an international organization?
8	The Japanese army killed at least 51.8 – 89.6 (100.80) million Chinese and raped or gang-raped at least 31.45 – 54.4 (61.2) million Chinese women. At least 200,000 Chinese women, pregnant women and young girls were forced to be sex slavery for the Japanese army. If we start counting from the massacre of more than 20,000 people in four days and three nights in Port Arthur, the first territory occupied by Japan in China in 1894, with only 36 survivors, China's population loss reached 280 million. So far, no compensation has been paid to the victims. If for every 50,000 people slaughtered, the childbearing age is increased by one year starting from the normal age of 20. For the slaughter of over 50 million people, childbearing of the descendants of this evil country should be prohibited. The United Nations should at least lay down rules. The marriage and childbearing age of the people of this evil country should be raised to at least 45 years for 5180-10,080 years. Violators are prohibited from enjoying any medical insurance and social insurance.

Fig. 50-1. Putting Japanese Emperor Hirohito on a par with Hitler. Under Japanese protests, the Ukrainian authorities apologized to Japan and were forced to delete the relevant photos. 2022-04-25. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7090362838417444127>

The evil Japanese actually demanded an apology from Ukraine. Is there still morality and conscience in today's world?

During the period of Japanese aggression against China, direct statistics from only 11 provinces show that the Japanese invasion caused at least 41.99-52.48 million

deaths. The number of injured has not yet been counted (China currently has 34 provinces). You should know that when Japan invaded China, the **Japanese aggressors raped and gang-raped at least 31.45-54.40 (61.20) million Chinese women, and forced at least 200,000 Chinese women into sexual slavery. They killed at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people.** Since the Japanese invasion of China in 1874 and Japan's surrender in 1945, data show that **China's population has lost about 280 million people.** Japan looted at least **42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth US\$5,289-7,933.5 billion, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth US\$50,000 billion, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth \$ 132.55-280.5 billion, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth \$114.4 billion, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth \$420 billion.**

The Japanese have never compensated the Chinese people for the losses and harms suffered in the war. Leading countries and influential lawyers around the world should jointly form a group and sue the Japanese government together with the Chinese people to demand war reparations. They will surely receive generous returns from the compensation.

日本媒体评论，**她将参选当作自己人生的转折点，就是想要抓住走向政坛的最后机会。**

东条由布子在接受记者采访的时候，毫不避讳地说：“**我们家父辈一直主张东条家的人一定要低调行事，但是我是一个不甘寂寞的人，我就是要为祖父鸣冤叫屈。**”

东条由布子原本只是自己蹦跶，没有多少人特别注意她，但是在日本前首相小泉纯一郎首次参拜靖国神社之后，东条由布子一下子成了日本电视台采访的红人，她开始有机会出现在电视镜头之中。

她是极端的右翼分子，不仅仅否认历史，还会造谣歪曲历史，为了洗白东条英机，什

Fig. 50-2. Yasuko Tojo, granddaughter of Japanese Class A war criminal Hideki Tojo, once **claimed that Japan launched a defensive war during World War II** and **believed it was unfair to label her grandfather as a Class A war criminal.** She also urged the Japanese prime minister to ignore the opposition of China and South Korea and continue to pay respects at the Yasukuni Shrine. She traveled around Japan, **promoting a re-evaluation of Hideki Tojo and vigorously supporting his heroic status.** She also **disagreed with the legitimacy of the rulings of the International Military Tribunal for the Far East and advocated for the rebuilding respect for the spirits at Yasukuni Shrine,** opposing the separation of Class A war criminals from the shrine. In May 2007, she announced her candidacy as an independent candidate for the Japanese Senate election but was unsuccessful in July 2007. She passed away in 2013.

2013年2月13日

日本甲级战犯东条英机的孙女、保守派评论家东条由布子去世

2013年2月13日，日本甲级战犯东条英机的孙女，东条英隆之女，保守派评论家，东条由布子去世，终年73岁。

东条由布子(とうじょう ゆうこ)，生于韩国首尔，本名岩浪淑枝，日本甲级战犯东条英机的孙女，东条英隆之女。日本政治人物，作家、特定非营利活动法人环境保全机构理事长。同时她还是日本强硬的保守派代表人物之一，战犯后代中最为极端的一个。她极力美化侵略战争和甲级战犯给亚洲人民带来的深重灾难和滔天罪行，歪曲及否认南京大屠杀等诸多历史事实，发表了众多扭曲历史、维护日本军国主义等备受质疑的言论。

日本政治人物，1939年生于韩国首尔，本名岩浪淑枝，二战时期日本首相东条英机长子东条英隆的女儿，曾任NPO法人保护环境机构理事长。日本国内强硬的保守派代表人物之一。早先就职于第一生命保险相互会社，后进入明治学院大学学习，因结婚中途退学(期间获得过圣心女子大学的心理学学士学位)。在成为4个孩子的母亲之后、由布子于国土馆大学教育系进修2年，毕业。

东条由布子曾宣称日本在二战时期发动的是自卫战争，并认为祖父被划为甲级战犯是不公平的事;还呼吁

Fig. 50-3. Yasuko Tojo, granddaughter of Japanese Class A war criminal Hideki Tojo, once claimed that Japan launched a defensive war during World War II and believed it was unfair to label her grandfather as a Class A war criminal. She also urged the Japanese prime minister to ignore the opposition of China and South Korea and continue to pay respects at the Yasukuni Shrine. She traveled around Japan, promoting a re-evaluation of Hideki Tojo and vigorously supporting his heroic status. She also disagreed with the legitimacy of the rulings of the International Military Tribunal for the Far East and advocated for the rebuilding respect for the spirits at Yasukuni Shrine, opposing the separation of Class A war criminals from the shrine. In May 2007, she announced her candidacy as an independent candidate for the Japanese Senate election but was unsuccessful in July 2007. She passed away in 2013.

February 13, 2013. <https://www.chazidian.com/d/2-13/12425/>

Fig. 50-5. Yasuko Tojo, granddaughter of Japanese Class A war criminal Hideki Tojo, once **claimed that Japan launched a defensive war during World War II** and **believed it was unfair to label her grandfather as a Class A war criminal**. She also urged the Japanese prime minister to ignore the opposition of China and South Korea and continue to pay respects at the Yasukuni Shrine. She traveled around Japan, **promoting a re-evaluation of Hideki Tojo and vigorously supporting his heroic status**. She also **disagreed with the legitimacy of the rulings of the International Military Tribunal for the Far East and advocated for the rebuilding respect for the spirits at Yasukuni Shrine**, opposing the separation of Class A war criminals from the shrine. In May 2007, she announced her candidacy as an independent candidate for the Japanese Senate election but was unsuccessful in July 2007. She passed away in 2013.

Yasuko Tojo has publicly denied the existence of aggressive wars and comfort women. She acknowledged the existence of comfort women but denied that the Japanese military forced women into sexual slavery. She completely denied that Japan initiated an aggressive war in the last World War, and even claimed that the so-called Greater East Asia War was a just war, with the only problem being Japan's defeat. She also stated that the Nanjing Massacre was a big lie without any evidence, and that the photos of the massacre were fabricated by historians. **She argued that the Japanese army did not kill 300,000 people in Nanjing**, as there were only 200,000 residents in the city when the Japanese army entered. Regarding the aggressive war launched by Japan, Yasuko Tojo claimed that the Greater East Asia War was completely justified, and the only mistake was Japan's defeat. If her grandfather had to bear responsibility, it would be for defeat rather than initiating the war. Yasuko Tojo intended to participate

in politics to prevent the removal of the enshrined spirits of Class A war criminals from Yasukuni Shrine.

In 1992, Yasuko Tojo wrote a book called "The Truth of the Greater East Asia War," in which she distorted history and glorified Hideki Tojo. **She claimed that the blame for Hideki Tojo's launching of the Pacific War lay entirely with the United States because Japan's economy was threatened by the U.S. oil embargo at the time.**

<https://www.chazidian.com/d/2-13/12425/>

Fig. 51. **A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American John Magee** Footage of American priest John Magee testifying about the Nanjing Massacre at the International Military Tribunal in 1946.

[Video of Reverend John Magee testifying about the Nanjing Massacre in 1946. <https://v.douyin.com/iJDdCy8T/>]

Chris Majee captured real and dynamic images (film) of the Nanjing Massacre, which can be searched on the internet.

南京大屠杀中，一个德国人
冒死救下25万中国人。
请记住他的名字:约翰.拉贝

Fig. 52. Group photo of some members of the Nanjing Safety Zone International Committee and the Nanjing Committee of the International Red Cross

A small suggestion:

Due to the atrocities committed by the Japanese army during the Nanjing Massacre, which set more than 100 records in human history for killings, rapes, and robberies, perhaps Hollywood directors could approach the subject from a different perspective and carefully portray the brave, fearless, kind, and righteous characters of the unprecedented 29 Oskar Schindlers of Nanjing. This could potentially result in a globally sensational film, not only showcasing everyone's acting talents but also achieving an extremely high attendance rate in China at least.

Some of the 29 Oscar Schindlers in the Nanjing Massacre

Fig. 53. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great American, Dr. George Fitch, Director General of the Security Zone and Director of the Young Christian Association of the United States.

Dr. George Fitch, an American, was born in Suzhou, China in 1883. In order to commemorate his birthplace, he gave himself a Chinese name - Fei Wusheng. His father was a missionary and his mother was also a devout Christian. Growing up in China, Fitch developed a deep affection for the country. In 1900, he returned to the United States to study and obtained a doctoral degree. In 1909, he went back to Shanghai and served as a staff member of the YMCA.

In mid-November 1937, Fitch returned to Nanjing. Faced with such a dire situation, he made the brave decision to stay in Nanjing and help protect the remaining residents. Along with several other prominent foreigners who also stayed in Nanjing, he established the International Committee for the Nanjing Safety Zone, with Fitch as Executive Secretary. During the brutal massacre carried out by Japanese troops in Nanjing, Fitch and his colleagues, using their American identity, wholeheartedly assisted and protected the refugees. They also documented the numerous atrocities committed by the Japanese in Nanjing, and these written records and visual evidence became irrefutable evidence exposing the Japanese military's crimes in Nanjing after the war.

Fitch's diary, from December 10, 1937 to January 1938, recorded the changes and horrors in Nanjing before and after the massacre. In Fitch's mind, Nanjing was a "beautiful city that we were proud of, still having law and order." However, after the Japanese army entered Nanjing, it became a "deserted, full of killings, looting, and mostly burned city."

Before the Japanese army entered Nanjing, Fitch and staff of the safety zone were

actively preparing for the construction of the zone. Fitch's diary of December 1 recorded their thoughts before the Japanese army entered the city, "We didn't feel any serious danger, thinking that the Japanese army seemed to want to avoid air raids and shelling in the refugee zone, and compared to the hell caused by the Japanese invasion, Nanjing was a heaven of order and safety." However, they never expected that a few days later Nanjing would turn into a human hell filled with killings and fear.

The atrocities perpetrated by the Japanese army in Nanjing are too numerous to be fully document. **Since their entry into the city, they have engaged in indiscriminate looting, extorting money from refugees, and robbing them of any belongings they could find, "not even sparing the last bit of bedding."** Refugee livelihood necessities, such as carts and livestock, were confiscated. They also looted stores, with Fitch witnessing "thugs setting fire to shops, while others loaded captured items onto trucks." Fitch recalls a day on January 18, where one man was shot in the arm by Japanese soldiers because he didn't have money to give them, and another was injured by soldiers for not having the strength to carry a heavy object, among many similar examples. **In order to eliminate evidence of their looting, Japanese soldiers often set fire to stores and residences after looting,** leading to multiple arson incidents in Nanjing city every day, sometimes even whole streets burning. Fitch wrote in a letter to a friend, "Nanjing has been systematically looted and burned, now reduced to an empty shell. **Most shops and Chinese houses were burned down, after the victors took whatever they wanted from them."**

Japanese brutally killed Chinese people without reason. They could capture anyone they deemed suspicious anywhere, and those with calloused hands were mistaken for Chinese soldiers and taken away to be killed. Power plant workers were mistaken for state-owned enterprise employees and were arrested and executed. Some people were cruelly killed for trying to prevent or resist the Japanese army's rape. Fitch's diary also recorded numerous horrifying scenes of piles of corpses in Nanjing City. **On December 15th, he wrote, "We were indeed driving through layers of corpses that were two to three feet thick and ninety feet long.** The scene is indescribable, and I will never forget this journey." "The stench in the city is overwhelming, and there are stray dogs feasting on corpses everywhere." **On December 22, Fey recorded, "There were 50 bodies in a muddy swamp, all ordinary people with their hands bound behind their backs. One person had his head completely chopped off. Were they practicing assassinations?"** Such brutal scenes were countless in Nanjing at that time. Source: "Nanjing Massacre and Western International Friends"

[Translated from: George Fitch: He witnessed Nanjing City being turned into a hell on earth by the invading Japanese army. January 23, 2019. https://www.sohu.com/a/290943550_241223]

Fig. 54. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great Danish hero B.A.Sindperg, Schindler of Nanjing

[Today is the National Memorial Day for the Nanjing Massacre. We would like to express our gratitude to the Western international friends who provided protection for the people of Nanjing during that time. They were not the so-called living Buddhas, but simply flesh and blood individuals. Truth and great love know no boundaries of nationality or ethnicity. On December 13th, when the city of Nanjing was engulfed in flames and the land was broken, they chose not to leave. The world will forever remember the humane actions of our Western friends. Always remember. 2022-12-13.

<https://v.douyin.com/iJE9PaJw/>

106 days of protection, facing the evil Japanese holding knives and guns

During the Nanjing Massacre, documentary videos and photos of Japanese atrocities and inhumanity captured by Sindperg are easily searchable on the internet.

Fig. 55. 106 days of protection against evil Japanese wielding knives and guns

In June 1938 Sindberg travelled to the headquarters of the League of Nations in Geneva, Switzerland, with his father. His father said, "Son, the purpose of your trip is to undertake an important mission for the Chinese government."

At that time, the Chinese government sent a labor delegation headed by Zhu Xuefeng to attend the 24th International Labour Conference. They invited Sindberg to stay in Geneva for three days to watch footage of the Japanese atrocities in Nanjing that he had brought.

On June 3rd, before playing the related footage, Sindberg strongly demanded that all children and women leave the viewing area because the film was filled with brutal and bloody killings. Sindberg spent several hours explaining the film's background.

During the screening, countless people in the audience were continuously in tears, and many scenes were unforgettable. After the screening, to express gratitude to Sindberg, Zhu Xuefeng inscribed on his passport, "Mr. Sindberg, Friend of China, Inscribed by Zhu Xuefeng with respect." Sindberg, as a citizen of a neutral country and a witness, exposed the crimes of the Japanese army's invasion of China to the international community. Through a carefully designed "deception," he and Kitty protected the lives of 20,000 Chinese people.

2023-03-17.

https://www.360kuai.com/pc/9881405e35157026c?cota=3&kuai_so=1&sign=360_57c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1

Fig. 56. A brave and fearless American general named Claire Lee Chennault

In April 1937, Lieutenant Claire Lee Chennault retired from military service feeling frustrated. At that time, his good friend Hubert Rock sent him a letter from China, asking if he would be willing to come to China for a job. Chen happily accepted the offer. During this period, dark clouds of war loomed as Japan attempted to occupy China. Chen had always wanted to implement his "winning through air power" theory, but his theory was not accepted by mainstream U.S. military theory, which focused on the dominance of bomber forces.

On December 7, 1941, General Chennault led the 1st and 2nd squadrons of the "American Volunteer Group" to move to Kunming. Just 12 days after the Japanese attack on Pearl Harbor, which took place on December 20, Chen Nade finally got the opportunity to showcase his skills. On that day, 10 Japanese bombers attacked, and Chen quickly sent 30 fighter planes into the sky, shooting down 6 enemy planes and damaging 3, without any casualties on his side.

That day, the mayor of Kunming led hundreds of citizens to congratulate "the great benefactors of the Chinese people" by beating drums and gongs. Red cloth strips, used

for prayers, were tied around the necks of these squadron members by the Chinese people. In the evening, a celebration was held in honor of the American Volunteer Group in Kunming.

The next day, almost all Chinese newspapers reported the battle in front-page headlines, referring to the U.S. Volunteer Group's planes as "flying tigers." From then on, this custom-made laurel wreath of "Chinese invention" was presented to the American Volunteer Group led by General Chennault.

According to the statistics of the Chinese Air Force Command on February 16, 1945, under General Chennault's command, a total of 33,450 Japanese soldiers were killed, 494 aircraft were destroyed, and 640,900 tons of ships were sunk.

[The War of Resistance Against Japanese Aggression General Chennault, wife Chen Xiangmei, and their daughter of the US Flying Tigers. 2021-11-21.

<https://v.douyin.com/iJKCRMSP/>, [December 12, 2015.

<https://www.toutiao.com/article/1043056970/>]

<https://www.toutiao.com/article/1043056970/>

Fig. 57. The body of Nanjing citizen who was tragically charred by Japanese (Evil locust) military kerosene during the Nanjing Massacre [Nanjing Massacre <https://v.douyin.com/iV9a58C/>]

Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig. 55. A brave, fearless, kind-hearted, and great German named John Rabe, Schindler of Nanjing

Chairman of the International Committee for Safe Zones and Representative of Siemens AG in Germany.

John Rabe arrived in Beijing at the age of 26. In 1911, he was hired by Siemens' Beijing branch and served as Siemens' representative in Beijing, Tianjin, and Nanjing.

At the end of 1937, during the Nanjing Massacre by the Japanese (Evil locust) army, John Rabe established a safety zone in Nanjing and provided shelter for more than 200,000 people in this zone, even housing more than 600 protected Chinese civilians in his own residence and small garden.

In this shocking and terrifying disaster in human history, he saved the lives of 250,000 Chinese compatriots.

In 1938, Rabe returned to Germany and carefully organized his diary and related materials.

The "Rabe Diary" he wrote is recognized as the most extensive and well-preserved historical document on the Nanjing Massacre discovered in recent years and has become powerful evidence of atrocities committed by the Japanese army.

Fig. 56. What a great American, Minnie Vautrin! A person who should not be forgotten! Schindler of Nanjing

During the Nanjing Massacre, she was the director of Jinling Girls' School. The U.S. government requested her to leave, but she insisted on staying. She protected more than 10,000 refugees from slaughter, and in order to save thousands of Chinese girls from humiliation, she was repeatedly threatened and beaten by the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese (Evil locust) army. Nanjing citizens call her "Living Bodhisattva," and her tombstone reads "Jinling Eternal Life." Her name is Minnie Vautrin, a person who should not be forgotten.

[<https://v.douyin.com/ip8Ehau/>]

An extremely conscientious, courageous and great American Ms. Minnie Vautrin

Business opportunities:

If the Nobel Foundation, global peace - loving investors, and Hollywood cooperate with Hollywood and Chinese film companies to invest in and produce a film about 29 unprecedentedly brave, fearless, kind - hearted and just characters like Oskar Schindler in Nanjing who saved 250,000 Chinese people, it is expected that sales in China alone will exceed about 7 billion yuan (about \$ 1 billion). The author believes that this will make a very significant contribution to world peace and sustainable development. There is no need for war. Peace can create good profit - making opportunities, but we just need to be more open - minded. However, the screenwriter, director, performer, lighting engineer, and costume designer must be the right people.

Fig. 57. Chinese child limb specimens soaked in formalin solution by the cruel Japanese invader Unit 731. The cruel Japanese military unit 731 conducted live dissection experiments on Chinese children.

[Japanese 731 Research Institute, dissecting Chinese children alive and soaking them in bottles # 731 # Japanese atrocities. <https://v.douyin.com/iJMwUo6j/>]

Fig. 58. Infant specimens soaked in formalin solution by the cruel Japanese invader 731 unit. The baby's internal organs were dug out.

The cruel Japanese military unit 731 conducted live dissection experiments on Chinese children.

[Japanese 731 Research Institute, dissecting Chinese children alive and soaking them in bottles # 731 # Japanese atrocities. <https://v.douyin.com/iJMwUo6j/>]

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig. 59. Senior Japanese girls also organized stretcher teams to participate in simulated war games. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Fig. 60. Japanese children are still using homemade airplane models to simulate aerial combat in war games. [Japanese children who have received military education since childhood take color photos of conquering overseas as their dream. March 9, 2022; <https://cj.sina.com.cn/articles/view/7402499933/1b9392f5d00101fge9>]

Fig. 61. [#Remembering History # Remembering National Shame # The Alarm Bell Continues to Sound for Our Generation's Self Strengthening # Iris Chang's Unforgettable History. 2023-08-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iJM7LntR/>]

Fig. 62. [#Remembering History # Remembering National Shame # The Alarm Bell Continues to Sound for Our Generation's Self Strengthening # Iris Chang's Unforgettable History. 2023-08-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iJM7LntR/>]

Fig. 63. Japanese war criminal Taiji Ohno directly or indirectly killed 654 Chinese, raped 14 women, and personally tortured the heroic Ms. Zhao Yiman. This is the confession of Taiji Ohno, a Japanese from Kochi Prefecture. In 1935, he invaded northeastern China as a member of the Foreign Affairs Division and the Police Department of the Puppet Manchukuo Black Dragon River Police Department. During the ten years of the invasion, he commanded the Japanese police and gendarmerie to carry out widespread killings and torture of the Chinese people, as well as innocent civilians and anti-Japanese people. This demon had a disgusting habit of consuming the brain tissue of the Chinese people.

[2023-08-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iLURJec4/B@t.rE EUy:/> 12/11]

There are significant flaws in Marx's classification of human social systems. As can be seen from the above - mentioned situation, the heinous deeds committed by evil Japan show that it is difficult to classify some evil social systems using Marx's classification method.

Fig. 64. **Nanjing Massacre:** The evil Japanese army cut off the heads of Chinese people and took photos to commemorate them. **There are both males and females in these heads.** [#Remembering History # Remembering National Shame # The Alarm Bell Continues to Sound for Our Generation's Self Strengthening # Iris Chang's Unforgettable History. 2023-08-04.<https://v.douyin.com/iJM7LntR/>]

From the heinous and immoral deeds done by the evil Japan, Marx's classification method of human systems has significant flaws and it is difficult to classify various evil social systems.

Fig. 65. During the Nanjing Massacre, a dog trained by the invading Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese (Evil locust) army gnawed on the body of a Chinese civilian. [Don't forget that painful history <https://v.douyin.com/iXRvVbq/>] Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

What kind of evil social system does Japan have? It is a nation that is good at using immigration to infiltrate China on a large scale and cannot be assimilated, a nation that launches aggressive wars, massacres civilians on a large scale, and carries out mass rapes and gang rapes whenever it finds an opportunity.

From the heinous and immoral deeds done by the evil Japan, Marx's classification method of human systems has significant flaws and it is difficult to classify various evil social systems.

Fig. 65-1. This is a picture of a third country persons arrested by the Japanese invaders in China, taken by a reporter accompanying the Japanese army. In order to avoid international disputes, it is naturally not allowed to be exposed.

[During the Japanese invasion of China, photos were "not allowed" to be exposed: each one was unforgivable evidence of a crime. December 13, 2021; http://news.sohu.com/a/507810370_120099902]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 65-2. The profound culture of robbery and plunder among primary school teachers in Japan

Elementary school teachers in Japan instill students with an enthusiastic mindset of pillaging. In their essays, students write about gaining everything if they were to occupy Singapore. At the end of the essays, **the Evil Staphylococcus aureus---Japanese teachers annotate with a red pen, saying, "Indeed, that is true."** [CCTV revealed Japanese militarism brainwashing education, and the truth was revealed in the composition of third grade pupils.

Published on: March 21, 2017; Source: CCTV News; http://news.youth.cn/jsxw/201703/t20170321_9331058.htm

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Li Suzhen, executive Deputy Chairman of the Japan-China Oral History and Cultural Studies Association, said that during the crazy Showa era in Japan, such essays were generally required for elementary school students, and sometimes even assigned as essay topics, with teachers checking and reviewing them. It was through this essay examination system that militaristic educational ideology was forcefully instilled in children, paving the way for them to be sent to the battlefield for aggression and crimes without any hindrance.

The children greatly admired the aggressive and robber-like behavior of the military, and instead of correcting them, the teachers further fueled and encouraged them. It is not difficult to see that during this period, all Japanese society, schools, and families were engaged in pre-war brainwashing education directed towards young Japanese children. However, during the crazy Showa era, an era supported by the Imperial Education Decree, brainwashing could escape, including the teachers themselves.

[CCTV revealed Japanese militarism brainwashing education, and the truth was revealed in the composition of third grade pupils.

Published on: March 21, 2017; Source: CCTV News;
http://news.youth.cn/jsxw/201703/t20170321_9331058_1.htm]

Fig. 66. Video: The above picture is an ice sculpture of Harbin, which is peaceful and beautiful today. [Ice Sculpture # Ice and Snow World # Beauty to the Extreme # Fairyland on Earth is as Beautiful as a Picture. 2024-01-03. <https://v.douyin.com/iLahMpLj/V@l.pD06/21wFU:/>]

Fig. 67. Video: The above picture shows an ice sculpture in Harbin that showcases creativity, as well as the culture, peace, vitality, and joy of Harbin today. [Harbin Ice and Snow World. 2024-01-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iLmdYbx4/h@B.TyQKj:/12/09>]

Evil and greedy Japanese established the notorious **Unit 731** in Harbin, where **they developed and deployed viral, bacterial, and biochemical weapons that resulted in the merciless slaughter of tens of millions of people**, causing immense catastrophes for humanity.

When the evil Japanese invaders invaded China and carried out colonization in the three northeastern provinces of China, they killed civilians with the Unit 731 biological warfare troops. After China defeated the evil Japanese colonizers, Harbin had a big scene during the 2023 Ice and Snow Festival, which is the result of changes in social systems.

Fig. 68. Video:The above picture shows an ice sculpture in Harbin that showcases creativity, as well as the culture, peace, vitality, and joy of Harbin today. [2024-01-10. <https://v.douyin.com/iLaytGBH/Ymd:/v@s.rR12/06>]. Evil and greedy Japanese individuals established the notorious **Unit 731** in Harbin, where they developed and deployed viral, bacterial, and biochemical weapons that resulted in the merciless slaughter of tens of millions of people, causing immense catastrophes for humanity.

When the evil Japanese invaders invaded China and carried out colonization in the three northeastern provinces of China, they killed civilians with the Unit 731 biological warfare troops. After China defeated the evil Japanese colonizers, Harbin had a big scene during the 2023 Ice and Snow Festival, which is the result of changes in social systems.

Fig. 69. Video: The above picture is an ice sculpture of Harbin, which is peaceful and beautiful today. [The scene of Harbin's ice-carved potato princess and white fox embracing each other vividly demonstrates the unique cultural charm of the city, which is astonishing. 2024-01-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iLa5TVmW/> y@g.oD gbn:/02/05]

Evil and greedy Japanese individuals established the notorious Unit 731 in Harbin, where they developed and deployed viral, bacterial, and biochemical weapons that resulted in the merciless slaughter of tens of millions of people, causing immense catastrophes for humanity.

Fig. 70. Video: The above picture is an ice sculpture in Harbin that showcases creativity, as well as the culture, peace, vitality, joy, and beauty of Harbin today.

[#More than a thousand ice and snow landscapes in Harbin Ice and Snow World are extremely rare worldwide, with over 40,000 people making reservations within three hours of opening, ranking among the top scenic spots in the country.2023-12-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iLaxP8Kd/LJI:/r@R.kC> 11/17]

When the evil Japanese invaders invaded China and carried out colonization in the three northeastern provinces of China, they killed civilians with the Unit 731

biological warfare troops. After China defeated the evil Japanese colonizers, Harbin had a big scene during the 2023 Ice and Snow Festival, which is the result of changes in social systems.

Fig. 71. "Intestine Pulling" torture of the Japanese invaders (Evil locust). The savage and evil Japanese soldiers first use bayonets to open the person's anus, dig out the large intestine, and then make the person run forward while holding onto the large intestine, causing it to be stretched longer and longer. In the end, even the internal organs are torn out together, causing the person to suffer excruciating pain, resulting in death. [At that time in Nanjing, the human nature of the Japanese army had become extinct to an unbeatable extent. <https://v.douyin.com/iC1qe8y/>]

If you want to improve the cognitive and computational abilities of your son or daughter who is still in high school, help them understand the complexity of society, enhance their risk prevention capabilities, why not let them calculate how many different types of torture were used by the evil Japanese or the evil Japanese Army's Unit 731 during the Nanjing Massacre in China? Some sources claim there were at

least 170 types, while others say there were over 500 types. Can they figure them out?

Fig. 72. **Survivor in Sex Slaves**

Jan Luff, a **Dutch victim** forced to become an evil Japanese "sex slave" system.

A Dutch woman who has been raped and gang raped by evil and barbaric Japanese (Evil locust) for a long time. [Keep going! Ms. Jan Luff, a victim of the Dutch Japanese "sex slavery" system, passed away. She used her personal experience to expose the evil Japanese atrocities to the world and fought tirelessly. <https://v.douyin.com/iqbkm4/>]

Where is the International Court of Justice in The Hague?

Where are the judges presiding over justice at the International Court of Justice in The Hague?

Law and justice often lag far behind atrocities to begin with. How long have the judges of the International Court of Justice (ICJ) in The Hague been asleep?

For decades, the United States has claimed to be the world's highest leader. When faced with disasters caused by cult forces, the highest leaders and judges of the United States who uphold justice, freedom, and human rights have been sleeping?

For decades, the United States has believed that it is the "most capable of leading the world" and yet, when faced with humanitarian disasters caused by an army composed of cult elements, where are the high-level leaders of the United States when the citizens of its weaker allies fail to receive compensation equivalent to that awarded by the US court's ruling?

Fig. 72-1. The **American general** (The most leading country in the world) who was captured by the Japanese army lived by **eating excrement every day**, and immediately committed suicide after being released. 2018-12-17. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/E383ATQ90514NI3B.html>

Warvigilance:

Table S4. 50 Guinness world records set by U.S. generals forced to eat feces by evil Japanese?

1	The first American general who was often forced to eat feces
2	The first major general of the U.S. Army who was often forced to eat feces

3	The first U.S. general who is often forced to eat feces, or else he will be punished
4	The first major general of the U.S. military who is often forced to eat feces, otherwise he will be punished.
5	The first American general who was often forced by evil Japanese to eat feces
6	The first major general of the U.S. Army who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces
7	The first American general who was forced to eat feces by Japanese people for three years.
8	The first major general of the U.S. Army who was forced to eat feces by Japanese people for three years.
9	In World War II, the first American general who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces
10	In World War II, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces.
11	In World War II, the first American general who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese, otherwise he would be punished.
12	In World War II, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese, otherwise he would be punished.
13	During World War II, the first U.S. military general was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
14	During World War II, the first major general of the U.S. military was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
15	In modern history, the first American general who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces
16	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced to eat feces by evil Japanese forces
17	In modern history, the first American general who was often forced by evil Japanese to eat feces, otherwise he would be punished.
18	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced by evil Japanese to eat feces, otherwise he would be punished.
19	In modern history, the first U.S. military general was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
20	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military was forced by the Japanese to eat feces for three years.
21	In modern history, the first U.S. military general, who was frequently forced by the Japanese to eat feces, and unable to bear the tremendous torture having been rescued, committed suicide by swallowing a gun.
22	In modern history, the first major general of the U.S. military, who was frequently forced by the Japanese to eat feces, and unable to bear the tremendous torture having been rescued, committed suicide by swallowing a gun.
23	Since the founding of the United States, the first American general who was

	often forced by the Japanese to eat feces.
24	Since the establishment of the U.S. military, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced by the Japanese to eat feces.
25	Since the founding of the United States, he was the first American general who was often forced by the Japanese to eat feces, otherwise he would be punished.
26	Since the establishment of the U.S. military, the first major general of the U.S. military who was often forced by the Japanese to eat feces, otherwise he would be punished.
27	The first American general since the establishment of the United States who was frequently forced by Japanese to eat excrement for three years.
28	The first major general of the U.S. military since the establishment of the United States who was frequently forced by Japanese to eat excrement for three years.
29	Since the founding of the United States, the first U.S. military general, who was frequently forced by the Japanese to eat feces, and unable to bear the tremendous torture having been rescued, committed suicide by swallowing a gun.
30	Since the establishment of the U.S. military, the first major general of the U.S. military, who was frequently forced by the Japanese to eat feces, and unable to bear the tremendous torture having been rescued, committed suicide by swallowing a gun.
31	The first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces by the Japanese during World War II
32	The first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces by the Japanese, weighing only 44.5 kilograms
33	During World War II, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces by the Japanese, otherwise facing punishment
34	In modern history, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces by the Japanese
35	In modern history, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces by the Japanese, weighing only 44.5 kilograms
36	The first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces, had his ears injured, and consequently became deaf
37	During World War II, the first U.S. Army General who was often forced to eat feces, had his ears injured, and consequently became deaf
38	During World War II, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces, weighing only 44.5 kilograms
39	In modern history, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces, had his ears injured, and consequently became deaf
40	Since the founding of the United States, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces, had his ears injured, and consequently became deaf
41	Since the establishment of the U.S. Army, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces, had his ears injured, and consequently

	became deaf
42	Since the founding of the United States, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces, weighing only 44.5 kilograms
43	Since the establishment of the U.S. Army, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces
44	Since the founding of the United States, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces
45	Since the establishment of the U.S. Army, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was often forced to eat feces
46	The first U.S. Army lieutenant general, who was frequently forced to eat feces and immediately kneel and bow to Japanese soldiers upon encountering them, as not doing so would result in severe punishment.
47	In modern history, the first U.S. Army lieutenant general, who was frequently forced to eat feces and immediately kneel and bow to Japanese soldiers upon encountering them, as not doing so would result in severe punishment.
48	During World War II, the first U.S. Army lieutenant general, who was frequently forced to eat feces and immediately kneel and bow to Japanese soldiers upon encountering them, as not doing so would result in severe punishment.
49	Since the founding of the United States, the first lieutenant general of the U.S. Army who was frequently forced to eat feces and immediately kneel and bow to Japanese soldiers upon encountering them, as not doing so would result in severe punishment.
50	Since the establishment of the U.S. military, the first U.S. Army Lieutenant General who was frequently forced to eat feces and immediately kneel and bow to Japanese soldiers upon encountering them, as not doing so would result in severe punishment.

残忍至极 禽兽不如

1937年的南京，一群日本畜生将一个中国村民打入麻袋中，然后用绳索将其捆绑在树上。最终，这名手无寸铁的村民在日本新兵的刺刀之下惨遭杀害。

Fig. 72-2. "Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.") Atrocity to the Extreme: More Savage than Beasts

In 1937 Nanjing, a group of extremely malicious and evil Japanese locusts stuffed a Chinese villager into a sack and tied him to a tree with ropes. Ultimately, this unarmed villager met a gruesome death at the bayonets of Japanese recruits.

2023-05-08. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7230602035429674274>

Warvigilance:

During Japan's war of aggression against China, Japanese immigrants were used by Japan to create incidents and conflicts in some large Chinese cities, which greatly encouraged the Japanese army to launch large - scale wars. The international community must be vigilant, because there are always strikingly similar scenes in history, and this is the strategic and tactical means that Japan is best at. Otherwise, the tragic past of over 100 million Chinese people in the last century will be the future of others.

Fig. 72-3. Japan's **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.") in North China, from 1938 to 1940, Japanese troops carried out more than 100 large-scale raids in North China, with a cumulative troop strength of more than 500,000. At the beginning of the implementation of the "Three Alls Policy" alone, **more than 50,000 people died** under the butcher's knife of the Japanese army, and countless houses were damaged. [The old photo reproduces the evil **Three Alls Policy** of the Japanese invaders: burning, killing, looting, and inhumane! March 29, 2019; https://www.sohu.com/a/304702339_99985762]

Fig. 72-4. The British Embassy was bombed by Japanese pirates, and the British Embassy was injured by them. [https://www.163.com/dy/article/H7TEN1SR0528TEDR.html], ["Picture Record of Japanese Savagery"; In July 1938, the Third Division of the Political Department of the Military Committee of the National Government edited and published it.]

Fig. 72-5. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.") Above: The situation where the Zhabei area in Shanghai was set on fire by Japanese pirates; Below: Almost all villages and towns in Pudong, Shanghai were burned down by Japanese pirates[In 1938, " Picture Record of Japanese Savagery ", do not forget national humiliation and the alarm bell rings. (Part 1) <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HBLHR0KQ0543B6OX.html>]

Fig. 73. "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**") The invading Japanese army hung chickens snatched from people's homes around their necks, showing a guilty smile. These are all true portraits of the devils at that time, robbing everything they could. Not to mention chickens, they didn't even let go of eggs, and if they couldn't take them away, they wouldn't leave these things behind. A shameless nation, it is disgusting to the heart.

[The old photo reproduces the evil **Three Alls Policy** of the Japanese invaders: burning, killing, looting, and inhumane! March 29, 2019; https://www.sohu.com/a/304702339_99985762]

The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and

slaughter?

Fig. 74. "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**") During the war against Japanese (**Evil locust**) aggression, there was an infuriating old photograph. In the photo, the evil Japanese invaders (**Evil locust**) had plundered a villager's pig. Faced with such "achievement", every one of these Japanese aggressors, with faces resembling humans but hearts resembling beasts, displayed a smile of delight when facing the camera of a Japanese journalist. A shameless nation, it is disgusting to the heart.

Japanese locusts even plundered sows from poor Chinese farmers who could bear piglets, cutting off their livelihood. They are truly locust like wild species. No one knows how many sows Japanese locusts robbed Chinese farmers during World War II.

[The evil Japanese devil (**Evil locust**) snatched a pig from a Chinese commoner's house during the sweep, and the entire team was very happy when facing the camera. August 9, 2022; <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HEC4H6B90553FOGM.html>]

The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and slaughter?

The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and slaughter?

Fig. 75. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**") Real old photos of evil Japanese devils (Evil locust) plundering property in rural China during World War II
The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and slaughter?

The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and slaughter?

[Photos taken by a Japanese war correspondent. Japanese soldiers entering the village to steal pigs, the disturbing reality is captured in these images. Softening the Demon-Detecting Mirror. April 1st, 2019; <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1629615103108532457&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Warvigilance:

During Japan's war of aggression against China, Japanese immigrants were used by Japan to create incidents and conflicts in some large Chinese cities, which greatly encouraged the Japanese army to launch large - scale wars. The international community must be vigilant, because there are always strikingly similar scenes in history, and this is the strategic and tactical means that Japan is best at. Otherwise, the tragic past of over 100 million Chinese people in the last century will be the future of others.

Fig. 76. "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**") Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

Several invading Japanese soldiers are carrying a Buddha statue, and it is unknown how many similar Chinese cultural relics were looted by the invading Japanese army back then. [Photo of the Japanese invaders committing crimes in China, with ordinary people being searched by Japanese soldiers. Figure 5 shows the Japanese plundering Chinese cultural relics. May 23, 2019; https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s?_biz=MzU5Mjc0NTE0MQ==&mid=2247485106&idx=6&sn=873d27602ac883fd306b8047f1d427e6&chksm=fe1a4168c]

Fig. 77. "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")The picture shows the Japanese army, after looting pigs and other wealth raised by the Chinese people, returning to the camp.

[The Japanese army has huge wealth and wealth! The army has no meat to eat,

they go to the village to grab pigs, and the navy comes standard with Western food and coffee. April 5, 2023;

<https://www.163.com/dy/article/I1J129UM05562E9Q.html>]

Fig. 78. "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.") [The leg bones of Chinese children used by Japanese invaders to make pipes # Forgot National Shame # Remember the alarm bells of history.2022-07-25. <https://v.douyin.com/iNmHPdQC/08/27 Z@Z.MJ jca:/>]

Why is Japan so despicable, evil, cruel, and vicious? Genes?

The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and

slaughter?

Fig. 79. "**Three Alls Policy**" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

The evil Japanese devil showed off and robbed the water tanks of the Chinese people.

Japan is an island country with limited resources, so it launched the "war-sustaining war" plan and engaged in looting activities in China. The "**Golden Lilies**" plan in Japan mainly involves the following aspects:

First: kidnapping local wealthy merchants and mafia leaders, forcefully pressuring them to hand over their wealth, looting bank vaults, and robbing money from ordinary people's homes.

Second: dispatching a large number of Japanese scholars to collect ancient books from libraries and museums across China.

Third: One more thing that the Japanese army issued a high-level order to plunder was the raw materials used to produce guns and ammunition, namely scrap copper and iron.

[Why did the Japanese army invading China plunder not only chickens, ducks, pigs, and dogs, but also the water jars of the common people? May 29, 2017;

https://www.sohu.com/a/144332791_717027]

Fig. 80. Japanese military ticket or military currency issued by Japan
Nature - Pretending Politeness - Fierce, Barbarian, Robbery, Theft, Anti-Human, and War

The Japanese nation – Isn't it a nation that likes to steal, plunder, gang rape, and slaughter?

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

This military currency can be traced back to the period of the Russo-Japanese War in 1904. It was a form of currency issued by the military as salary for soldiers in the army and navy. Unlike the gold standard Japanese yen at the time, Japanese military notes could not be exchanged for gold or regular yen. Essentially, they were worthless pieces of paper with no credit guarantee or backing in gold or silver. In essence, they were promissory notes that relied on the military force of the Japanese army to

forcefully seize resources from occupied areas, making the local population support and sustain the invading forces.

[Anti-Japanese War Finance 4. The Japanese army plundered wealth by issuing a large number of military tickets and became wealthy individuals in the occupied areas.

Chen Tianxing; February 16, 2021;
<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1691813073396850649&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 81. The Japanese nation - a nation that loves to steal, plunder, gang rape, and slaughter----"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")**

The picture shows evil and despicable Japanese troops plundering Chinese historical and cultural materials. In 1938, the wicked Japanese "academic expedition team" looted the materials of the Institute of History and Philology at the Chinese National Central Research Academy under the protection of the Japanese military.

[Japan has plundered nearly a trillion yuan of resources from China. Figure 4 shows the whereabouts unknown, and Figure 7 shows the best of the treasures.
<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1612951046624638118&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Japanese person, can you prove that you are not an appearance of seeming politeness but harboring extreme evil, extreme meanness, extreme barbarism, liking theft, liking plunder, and being an extremely anti-human Japanese person? If you are not, please make a public statement and urge the Japanese people, Japanese business conglomerates, the Japanese government, and the Japanese Emperor to return stolen Chinese cultural relics, books, and wealth to China.

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 82. The Japanese nation - a nation that enjoys theft and plunder
"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

The picture shows the Japanese army plundering Chinese cultural relics and taking them back to Japan. During the War of Resistance against Japan, the Japanese "Ootani Expedition Team" relentlessly looted cultural relics and ancient sites in the northwest region of China. It is no exact number to determine how many cultural relics were stolen during the three expeditions. In the final expedition alone, they stole 86 boxes of cultural relics, weighing a total of 6,731 kilograms.

[Japan has plundered nearly a trillion yuan of resources from China. Figure 4 shows the whereabouts unknown, and Figure 7 shows the best of the treasures.
<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1612951046624638118&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Japanese person, can you prove that you are not an appearance of seeming politeness but harboring extreme evil, extreme meanness, extreme barbarism, liking theft, liking plunder, and being an extremely anti-human Japanese person? If you are not, please make a public statement and urge the Japanese people, Japanese business conglomerates, the Japanese government, and the Japanese Emperor to return stolen Chinese cultural relics, books, and wealth to China.

Fig. 83. A nation that enjoys theft and plunder
"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

The evil, greedy and despicable Japanese invaders and locusts stole at least 42,000 tons of gold from China. The Japanese army not only caused the devastating Nanjing Massacre, but also extensively searched for gold, jewelry, antiques, and more after occupying Nanjing. In just over 40 days, they seized 6,000 tons of gold.

If you are a non-violent person, would you be willing to try, just to see if you or your family can bear one or two of the hundreds of cruel tortures used by the evil and inhumane Japanese against the Chinese people? Would you reconsider your perception of Japan after that? Can you test your true abilities? Can you test how many days or a week you can tolerate?

The international community have allowed evil Japan to escape punishment after massacring 50 million Chinese people and plundering immense wealth. They have neither legally executed all murderers, nor severely punished all criminals in Japan, nor forced Japan to return and compensate for all stolen assets and losses. Is this the kind of inferior and primitive law that a civilized world needs?

If a well-known lawyer or judicial organization considers such laws to be reasonable, does it mean that it is also reasonable for anyone or any organization or country to kill your lawyer, your entire family, or annihilate your nation and seize all your property?

Are you brave enough to openly tell everyone in the world that you have 1,000 kg of gold stored in your living room, and that none of you fear being raped, gang-raped, or even killed and robbed without holding criminals accountable for their actions?

Fig. 84. The Japanese nation - a nation that enjoys theft and plunder
"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

The evil, greedy and despicable Japanese locusts plundered at least 49,000 tons of bronze, 200 million tons of rare earths, and 150 million tons of kaolin from China. [In those years, the Japanese pirates plundered 21000 tons of wealth from our country: gold. About 1 billion tons of coal. February 10, 2023. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HT8GV22H05560WEK.html>]

Fig. 85. The Japanese nation - a nation that enjoys theft and plunder
"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

The evil, greedy and despicable Japanese invaders and locusts plundered various historical relics of China and filled their museums. Jewelry and jade articles are countless in ancient books. [In those years, the Japanese pirates plundered 21000 tons of wealth from our country: gold. About 1 billion tons of coal. February 10, 2023 <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HT8GV22H05560WEK.html>]

Fig. 85-1. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.") In 1942, the Japanese invaded China and in Xuzhou, Jiangsu Province, the evil Japanese army took innocent civilians to the suburbs of the city and killed them, using them as living targets.2024-10-18. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7427126591550917907>

Fig. 85-2. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.") Image above: Wuxiang City and Taierzhuang were burned down by evil and barbaric Japanese invaders; Below: Tanzi Bay in Shanghai was burned down by evil and barbaric Japanese invaders[In 1938, " Picture Record of Japanese Savagery ", do not forget national humiliation and the alarm bell rings. (Part 1) <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HBLHR0KQ0543B6OX.html>]

Warvigilance: Fig. 85-3. **On the 80th anniversary of the Japanese attack on Pearl Harbor, about 100 Japanese lawmakers paid public respects at Yasukuni Shrine, which enshrines several hundred World War II war criminals.** Is this group of

influential Japanese politicians secretly working toward the elimination of the U.S. Pacific Fleet, the conquest of Asia, and the world in the decades and even centuries to come? [On the 80th anniversary of Japan's surprise attack on Pearl Harbor in the United States, approximately 100 Japanese lawmakers visited the Yasukuni Shrine. <https://v.douyin.com/iJkRj1Qr/>]

There is a common Chinese saying: It's easy to change rivers and mountains but hard to change a person's nature. Can a dog stop eating shit? (中国有两句俗语：江山易改本性难移。狗改不吃屎?)

Fig. 85-4. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

Evil, barbaric, greedy, despicable, shameless, and anti-human Japanese plundered wealth from the homes of Chinese civilians and forced them to transport it.

[During World War II, how did the Japanese invaders plunder wealth in China? When everything was gone, they grabbed people and demanded ransom. March 27, 2017. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/CGHHQKOS0523BG3T.html>]

Fig. 85-5. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**")

The evil Japanese people not only killed and burned the Chinese land, but their main

task was also to loot wealth. Below is a set of data, just from a small county in the Resistance War against Japan.

Official media: "Bin Hai Daily."

Robbery is one of the means by which the Japanese aggression army damages the interests of the Chinese people. Wherever they go, they loot property, food, fodder, poultry, and livestock. The Japanese puppet army occupied areas where the people were impoverished and their belongings exhausted. Most of the population suffered from freezing and hunger.

In 1943, when the Japanese army couldn't find any wealth to rob in Dongkan Wei in Fudong County, they extended their claws to the outside of Dongkan Wei. On June 27th, under the pretext of searching for the New Fourth Army, they looted Mengshe and Xikan in the western suburbs of Dongkan, robbing house by house. The next day, they also looted Sanli Kao and Langmaodun in the southern suburbs, seizing more than 40 dou of food, more than 20 cattle, countless clothing, and poultry. In the Yutan incident in September, they took away over 10,000 jin of food, more than 120 dan of bean oil, over 230 pieces of coarse cloth, and 13 cattle.

Dongkan is a relatively large market town in Yanfu District, known as "Golden Dongkan". By the end of 1943, due to the occupation and extensive looting by the Japanese puppet army, shops closed down, pedestrians were scarce, the market was deserted, and people were barely able to survive. Civilians struggling on the brink of starvation could only sustain themselves with moldy bean cakes and tofu residue. That year, more than 20 people froze and starved to death. The exact number of the Japanese puppet army's forced looting of wealth in the Fudong area cannot be calculated, but the number of looted livestock alone reached 14,471.

The Japanese puppet army frequently arrested civilians in the Fudong area and forcibly demanded ransom, using extortion as a means. Near Datouzhuang in Kanbei, 9 households had their young and able-bodied members taken away, and a total of over 320,000 yuan (old currency) was extorted from them.

On July 13, 1943, more than 200 Japanese puppet soldiers swept through the outskirts of Dongkan, including Mengshe, Langmaodun, Hongtao, and Xikan. Over 100 people were captured in Hongtao alone, and each person had to **pay 1,500 kg of grain or 100 silver dollars to be released**. On September 30, during a sweep of Pandang and Shouchaowa, the Japanese puppet army captured over 300 people, all of whom were detained in Dongkan. After being subjected to various tortures, each household had to pay hundreds of silver dollars or dozens of dou of wheat to buy back their freedom. Most households were left devastated and penniless.

The Japanese puppet army, stationed in the eastern part of Fudong County, imposed numerous excessive and varied taxes and levies, mercilessly exploiting the people. **They would collect donations every three days and announce a new tax every five days, with the number of taxes reaching up to dozens.** These taxes were distributed to households by village chiefs, with a deadline for payment. **If unable to pay, people would be forcibly taken away and their belongings seized.** The summer conscription in 1943 was especially harsh on the common people. At that time, Fudong was divided into five small towns and 50 villages, and the basic form of social organization was the

"baojia" system (10 households made up a "jia", 10 "jia" formed a "bao", and more than 10 "bao" constituted a township). Each "bao" had to provide a certain number of conscripts, **each of whom had to pay 800 silver yuan as conscription fee.** Town and village leaders would also add additional charges, profiting from this. Under the direction of the town and village leaders, conscripts would often try to escape, but even after escaping, they would still be pursued and forced to pay the conscription fee. As a result, the common people were burdened with endless conscription and unpayable taxes. **[During World War II, how did the Japanese invaders plunder wealth in China? When everything was gone, they grabbed people and demanded ransom.** March 27, 2017. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/CGHHQKOS0523BG3T.html>]

There are two common Chinese sayings: It's easy to change rivers and mountains but hard to change a person's or a nation's nature. Can a dog stop eating shit?

Fig. 85-6. **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, kill all, **loot all.**") The evil, barbaric, greedy, despicable, shameless, and anti-human Japanese army created "counterfeit currency", causing a devastating blow to China's financial order and social wealth.

According to Japanese statistics, during World War II, Japan's military expenditure reached 755.9 billion yen (approximately 170 trillion yen in today's value, equivalent to CNY 10 trillion yuan). Most of this expenditure was funded by excessive issuance of currency in China, without using Japan's national treasury, in order to sustain their so-called "war economy." In other words, China was forced to **pay CNY 10 trillion yuan in military expenses for Japan, not to mention the gold and various national treasures looted by Japan.**

In order to further drain China's wealth completely, the Japanese secretly established factories to counterfeit the currency issued by the Nationalist government,

known as "Fabi". The counterfeited "Fabi" was so convincing that it was difficult to distinguish it from the real currency.

Japan produced a huge amount of counterfeit currency notes during the war, making it the world's largest producer of counterfeit currency. It is worth noting that the total circulation of the Nationalist government's currency in 1937 was **only 1.48 billion yuan in China**, highlighting the seriousness of Japan's plunder of China's wealth.

[How did Japan plunder China's wealth? February 26, 2018. https://www.sohu.com/a/224186891_100011719]

If a high-level student majoring in film or television were to make a small movie during World War II where the Japanese army created huge amounts of counterfeit currency to defraud the wealth of the Chinese people, they might receive more than 100 million likes and a large number of fans.

Fig. 85-7. "Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.") The picture above shows the Japanese soldiers who marched in Anqing City and grabbed the birds raised by the common people.

The above images and texts are selected from Volume 21 of the "Illustrated Records of Japan's Invasion of China" titled "Economic Aggression and Resource Robbery", edited by Qi Chunfeng and Yan Haijin, and published by Shandong Pictorial Press in May 2015. [The "Ghost" Entering the City: A Group of Japanese Army "Looting" Photos Taken by Journalists Accompanying the Japanese Army.2016-11-13;

<https://www.toutiao.com/article/6352341161038512386/>

The shamelessness of the Japanese army has reached an extremely strange point where it is even inferior to garbage. Every time the Japanese army arrives in a city, they will carry out large-scale organized looting of the entire city. Most of the equipment and supplies in shopping malls, factories, and units are washed away, and these machinery, equipment, and factory supplies are taken, sealed, and transported back to Japan.

Fig. 85-8. The Emperor of Catching Chickens Evil locust
The Great King of Catching Chickens.

According to historical records, during a raid in 1941, the Japanese army looted more than 50,000 chickens in North China alone, resulting in all chickens in villages dozens of miles around being captured by the Japanese army, and the crowing of chickens (cock) could not be heard in the morning.

Nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war?

[Do the Japanese like to catch chickens? Is it portrayed in movies, or do they genuinely enjoy catching chickens in their daily lives? August 24, 2021;

<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1708959082200103454&wfr=spider&for=pc>

"Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.")

Fig. 85-9. The victims of the Zhejiang Jiangxi bacterial massacre walked half a step slower than normal people [Xinhua News Agency focuses on the victims of the bacterial warfare in Lishui: **These elderly people are almost unable to wear socks throughout their lives** (Source: Xinhua News Agency). 2021-11-15. <https://v.douyin.com/iJuVbPDJ/>]

Fig. 85-10. The deployment map of the Japanese army's bacteriological warfare clearly shows that cities such as Ningbo, Jinhua, and Quzhou in Zhejiang province are the targets.

ZheGan Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

ZheGan Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

ZheGan Biological Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre, at Least killed 650,000

Fig. 85-11. Yunnan Biological Warfare Massacre, **at Least killed 200,000**

The actual number of deaths in the Yunnan bacterial slaughter is highly likely to be between **400,000 and 500,000**.

The Biological Warfare Massacre in Yunnan Province

The largest biological warfare massacre in the history of western China

The largest and longest-running biological warfare massacre in Western China's history caused by the evil Japanese army

The ceramic bacterial bomb invented by Japanese Unit 731 was dropped by Unit 731 in Yunnan. After it was dropped and hit the ground, the ceramic shell ruptured, and bacteria emanated from inside.

Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

Fig. 85-12. The Barbaric Evidence of Japan's Inhumanity - The Largest-scale Cholera Warfare Tragedy in History, At Least 500,000 Deaths.

Lu Xi Bacterial Warfare Massacre

Cholera Massacre in Northwest Shandong

Cholera Massacre in Western Shandong

Biological Massacre in Western Shandong

The largest cholera massacre in history

The Largest-scale Cholera Warfare Tragedy in History

Biological warfare Massacre in Western Shandong

The First Tragedy in Shandong -- Biological warfare in Northwest Shandong

[Biological warfare in western Shandong. The war launched by the Japanese invasion of China in 1943. The Japanese invaders launched the Biological warfare in western Shandong in 1943. Causing 1500 kilometers of land to become "unmanned areas".

https://baike.baidu.com/item/%E9%B2%81%E8%A5%BF%E7%BB%86%E8%8F%8C%E6%88%98/5628191?fr=ge_al]

[The largest bacterial warfare launched by the Japanese army resulted in 500,000 deaths in Shandong and 24 counties becoming unmanned areas. August 18, 2023

<https://www.toutiao.com/article/7268252965113463333/>

Fig. 85-13. **The Lushun Massacre**

On November 21, 1894, the brutal, savage, and inhumane Japanese carried out a massive four-day, three-night massacre in Lushun. **More than 20,000 people throughout the city perished in this devastating and heart-wrenching massacre. After the Lushun Massacre, only 36 Chinese people were left in the city.** The evil Japanese military spared their lives so that they could bury their bodies. They were marked with the words "Do Not Kill This Person" on their hats, which allowed them to survive.

[Regarding this massacre, there is the following description: "After the Japanese army entered **Lushun**, their beastly nature was unleashed as they carried out a horrific massacre. They killed people in sight, some with their heads chopped off, others with their ears cut off; children were nailed to the wall, some with their eyes gouged out or their ears cut off; some women were violated and then disemboweled. The massacre lasted four days, and **Lushun** was immersed in a sea of blood; piles of dead bodies reached several feet high." This deep-seated hatred will never be forgotten. Never harbor any illusions, remember that falling behind means being beaten and enslaved by others. Only when a country is strong can its people live and work in peace. #Remember history, let the alarm bell ring for a long time #Positive energy. <https://v.douyin.com/iJ2TTw8F/>]

Fig. 85-14. These two Japanese invaders (**staphylococcus aureus**) were known for their killing of a hundred people during the Nanjing Massacre, including Noda Yi and Minming Xiang. The one on the left is Yoichi Noda, who was only 25 years old at the time and came from Kagoshima Prefecture, Japan. The one on the right is Minami Xiang, who was only 26 years old at the time and came from Yamaguchi Prefecture, Japan. **Japanese aggressor Noda killed 232 people in the Nanjing Massacre** **When the 16th Division entered Nanjing, its commander, Togo Shingon Miyamiya, issued a top-secret "burn after reading" order to the division's commander, Chusho Nakajima, which stated that once the Japanese troops entered the city, they were to "eliminate" all Chinese military personnel who laid down their weapons.**

Nakajima and his 16th Division indeed lived up to the expectations of their superior. After entering Nanjing, they implemented a policy of killing a thousand rather than letting one go, with the armed Chinese soldiers who surrendered being rounded up and "disposed of," and some innocent Nanjing civilians being arbitrarily arrested and killed.

Initially, Japanese troops would bury the bodies of the Chinese soldiers and civilians they killed in trenches, but as the number of victims became too many, they began directly executing Chinese people they believed to be soldiers by the city moat.

The surrendered Chinese defenders and innocent civilians who were captured would be taken to the moat in groups of 500 to 1000, shot or stabbed to death with bayonets, and their bodies thrown directly into the moat.

The 16th Division extensively used Chinese people to help new soldiers "build up

courage." According to a journalist from the Tokyo Daily News who was with the troops entering the city at the time, he witnessed the 16th Division bringing hundreds of Chinese people (both prisoners of war and ordinary civilians) to the 25-meter-high city wall, having them line up, and having the new Japanese recruits practice stabbing them. The Chinese people who were stabbed to death or injured by Japanese soldiers would be thrown off the city wall, and the sight was too horrifying to bear.

If the massacres carried out by the 16th Division were said to be in line with superior orders, then the following massacres were purely for sadistic pleasure.

Noda Takeshi and Mukai Toshimitu, who participated in the infamous "contest to kill a hundred people", were both from the 16th Division. They made a bet on who could kill 100 Chinese people when Japanese troops entered Nanjing, with the prize being a bottle of wine. **On the day Japanese troops entered the city, Noda killed 105 people, and Mukai killed 106 people. The two of them laughed heartily, leaning on their bloodstained swords, having achieved their goal. They then set a new target of 150 people.**

The above is the well-known content of this bloody killing competition, but what people don't know is that Noda and Mukai actually put their ideas into action, especially Noda. **Once he entered Nanjing, he immediately went on a killing spree, and his number of victims quickly surpassed the planned 150, reaching 232 people.**

Noda and Mukai, who took pleasure in killing, were portrayed as heroes by the Japanese media. Noda, who used his katana to kill over 200 unarmed innocent civilians, was even called a **"sword knight"** by the Japanese media. Noda and Mukai were extremely **"proud"** of their massacre of innocent Nanjing civilians, and **they even agreed to raise the goal to "kill a thousand people" directly.**

[In the 16th Division, which killed the most people in Nanjing, the division leader was fond of cannibalism and was later trapped on an isolated island, starving to the point of cannibalism. July 28, 2022. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/HDCEB7UL0553EMEY.html>], [Two Japanese aggressors who killed Chinese people, their brutal crimes, should be made known to more people. June 1st, 2023. https://history.sohu.com/a/681235984_121030345]

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities.

Fig. 85-15. [Two Japanese aggressors who killed Chinese people, their brutal crimes, should be made known to more people. June 1st, 2023. https://history.sohu.com/a/681235984_121030345]

Fig. 85-16. A Japanese aggressor named "Ma Jian Zhong Ba Cang" **killed 107** Chinese people in Nanjing alone and engraved the murder record on his own military knife, but escaped trial # Remember History

2023-02-27. <https://v.douyin.com/iLUr8xdJ/reB:/d@A.TL10/29>

Anti-Japanese War veterans seized a Japanese military knife, and the Japanese wanted to redeem 30 million yuan, but were refused by the veterans because the knife was engraved with 9 words: "107 people killed in the Battle of Nanjing!" 2023-01-17. <https://v.douyin.com/iLUrRLNv/R@K.WM09/21vFh:/>

Japanese military sword engraved with "107 people killed in the Battle of Nanjing"

The owner of this military sword, Maruken Hachizou, set foot on Chinese soil in August 1937, and his first battle took place in North China. At that time, he was a member of the 23rd regiment of the 6th Division, and encountered fierce resistance from Chinese forces led by General Huo Li Huang. This battle caused heavy casualties for the Japanese army, and Maruken Hachizou was also wounded in the fighting.

After Maruken Hachizou recovered from his wounds, he returned to the battlefield and participated in the Battle of Nanjing. After the fall of Nanjing, the Japanese army embarked on a six-week-long massacre of Chinese soldiers and civilians, displaying extreme cruelty and madness.

Unlike Tanaka Shunichi, Mukai Toshiaki, and Noda Takeshi, Maruken Hachizou did not openly boast to the media about his involvement in the massacre, which is why very few people know about him.

In early 1938, Maruken Hachizou was transferred from the 6th Division. On January 15, 1944, he assumed the position of commander of the 72nd Battalion, Independent Infantry Regiment, 1st Independent Mixed Brigade of the Japanese Army, with the rank of lieutenant.

In September 1945, the 1st Independent Mixed Brigade of the Japanese Army surrendered in Dingxian County, Hebei, and then remained in place to await the handover to the Chinese army. In January 1946, they disarmed and were sent to a camp in Tianjin. In May 1946, Maruken Hachizou returned to Kagoshima, Japan. He has since remained at-large, evading trial.

The total number of killings was 831 — Japanese war criminal Keiji Arai

Japanese war criminal Keiji Arai confessed, "From April 1937 to September 3, 1945, I participated in the heinous crimes committed by the Japanese military against the Chinese people. **The statistics are as follows: the total number of killings is 831.** The breakdown of victims includes: 420 male civilians, 14 female civilians, 98 militia members, 252 Eighth Route Army soldiers, 38 anti-Japanese military personnel, and 9 captured soldiers." The methods of murder included shooting, stabbing, beheading, burning alive, beating to death, starving to death, and starving to death in prison.

"The total number of people injured is 519." Methods included gunshot wounds, slash wounds, injuries from stepping on landmines, and stab wounds. "The total number of Chinese women raped is 34."

"The total number of civilians arrested is 112. In addition, the number of captured soldiers on the battlefield is 368. The treatment of these individuals after being sent to the rear is unknown. Additionally, 215 civilians were arrested, interrogated through torture and physical abuse. Furthermore, there were 1171 civilians who were captured

and forced into labour, such as clearing landmines, leading the way, serving as porters, and working without compensation on the construction of military roads and fortifications."

"I used poison gas (12 red canisters) against the Eighth Route Army on the battlefield, one at a time."

[Japanese war criminal Keiji Sangle commanded his troops in China to shoot and kill all villagers, and gang raped women. July 14th, 2014. <http://military.people.com.cn/n/2014/0714/c1011-25275370.html>]

日军占领苏州入城式

第九师团曾在苏州大肆进行烧杀抢掠，可谓是无恶不作且罄竹难书，日军在苏州犯下的累累罪行，当以第九师团的暴行最为凶残，而日军对苏州的屠戮，一点也不亚于南京，只是南京的规模太大并广为人知而已。

请看一个日本老兵晚年的采访回忆：“我所在的部队是日军第九师团富士井部队，在多日的狂轰滥炸之后，我们首先攻陷了中国南方古城苏州。我们踏着一地的血污和尸体占领了苏州，一路能烧就烧，能毁就毁，能杀就杀。作为一个新兵，我竟然用枪打死了4个中国人，用刺刀挑死一个还没咽气的布店老板和一个推板车卖水果的男人。我们得到的命令就是杀、杀、杀，见到一个中国人就杀一个。”

Fig. 85-17. The 9th Division once engaged in brutal arson, killing, and looting in Suzhou, leaving no evil undone. The numerous crimes committed by the Japanese army in Suzhou were most heinous through the acts of the 9th Division. The massacre of Suzhou by the Japanese army was no less horrifying than that of Nanjing, although Nanjing's scale was larger and more widely known. In an interview with an elderly Japanese veteran in his later years, he recalled, "I was part of the Fujiwara Unit of the Japanese 9th Division. After days of relentless bombing, we first captured the ancient southern Chinese city of Suzhou. We occupied Suzhou, stepping on bloodstains and bodies, burning anything we could, destroying anything we could, and killing anyone we could. **As a new recruit, I even shot and killed four Chinese people using my gun, stabbed to death a cloth shop owner who was still gasping for breath, and a fruit vendor pushing a cart. Our orders were to kill, kill, kill. If we saw a Chinese person,**

we killed them."

[Fuji Inoue Yoshi: Captain of the 35th Infantry Regiment of the Ninth Division, who massacred civilians crazily in Suzhou and Nanjing. March 3, 2022. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1726277545136501847&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

“我们抓来了200多个没有跑掉的妇女，有的很年轻，也有不太年轻的和几个老年人，他们都被关在一座庙里。我们不许她们穿衣裤，任凭我们随意奸淫。最后这些妇女都被机枪扫射杀害，倒在虎丘旁。我和几个人奉命去检查有没有漏网没被打死的，并被要求一个也不能活。当我用刺刀刺向每一个还在蠕动的白色肉体时，我感到自己就像在厨房切菜，已经不觉得倒在地上流着血的女人是人了。对那时的我来说，她们是一种东西，任何东西，比如需要被切碎的白萝卜。原来人的内心都潜藏着最野蛮的魔鬼，战争必定会把它召唤出来。我在侵华战争期间，亲手杀死了28个中国人，包括男人和女人，奸污了17个中国女人。”而这仅是一个新兵所为，可以想象日军官兵是何等的残暴。

Fig. 85-18. The number of Chinese people slaughtered and raped by a Japanese new recruit.

"We captured over 200 women who hadn't managed to escape. Some were young, some not so young, and a few elderly. They were all kept locked up in a temple. We didn't let them wear clothes and raped them freely. In the end, these women were all shot and killed by machine guns, falling beside Huqiu Mountain. I, along with a few others, was assigned to inspect and ensure that no one survived. We were told that not a single one should live. As I stabbed each wriggling white body with my bayonet, I felt like I was chopping vegetables in the kitchen. I no longer saw bleeding women lying on the ground as humans. To me, they were just objects, anything, like white radishes that needed to be sliced. It turns out that the most savage demons lie dormant in everyone's heart, and war is bound to summon them. **During the China-Japanese War, I personally killed 28 Chinese people, including men and women, and raped 17 Chinese women.**" **And this was only the act of a new recruit, one can only imagine how cruel the Japanese soldiers were.**

[Fuji Inoue Yoshi: Captain of the 35th Infantry Regiment of the Ninth Division, who massacred civilians crazily in Suzhou and Nanjing. March 3, 2022. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1726277545136501847&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

Fig. 85-19. The evil Japanese army cut the Chinese alive.
[<https://v.douyin.com/iJUweGs6/>]

Fig. 85-20. An unscrupulous nation, with only a little chance, may retaliate or even kill the benefactor. **Continuously portraying snakes and farmers' snakes**

On February 3, 1946, which happened to be the second day of the Lunar New Year, the people of Tonghua were joyfully celebrating the first Spring Festival under the leadership of the Chinese People's Government after the victory of the Anti-Japanese War.

Unfortunately, the Chinese people were too kind-hearted and treated a large number of Japanese soldiers and doctors and nurses who had participated in the war well. They surprisingly did not subject them to strict criminal investigations and even provided them with job opportunities. As a result, **at one fateful moment that night, 150 Chinese soldiers were brutally murdered by Japanese female nurses using surgical knives and scissors in hospital beds.**

[Why can some ethnic groups never be forgiven? Remembering History # Forgetting National Shame <https://v.douyin.com/iJUGqCJu/>]

Do you have the ability to recognize that these Japanese nurses with smooth faces could be extremely cruel criminal killers? If you don't have the ability, why are you so kind to criminals? Isn't that an injury to the victims? Where are your values? Where is your belief? Aren't you also a murderer and a criminal?

日本的八纮一字镇魂塔
至今还镇压着来自中国的238块石头
八纮一字统治天下 镇压中国抗战不得翻身
狼子野心 其心可诛

Fig. 85-21. The Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字) (unite the whole world under one sovereign by force of arms) (Also known as"Tower of Suppressing Souls")

The Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字) (Also known as"Tower of Suppressing Souls"), built in Japan in 1940, proves their ambitions. After Japan's surrender, the U.S. military forced Japan to demolish various evil buildings. The Japanese people changed the name of the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一字), which had the inscription of the Unified Universe (八纮一字) (meaning: unite the whole world under one sovereign by force of arms; or "all the world under one roof"), to the "Gentle Tower"and dismantled the Statue of the Ala mitam, deceiving the American forces. However, in 1962, the Ala mitama statue was rebuilt, and Japan changed the name of the tower back to " Unified Universe " again. This name means that the whole world is under the rule of Japan. From the China-Japanese War to World War II, " Unified Universe " served as the national motto of the Great Japanese Empire. This was a national strategy established by the Japanese emperor more than a thousand years ago. The term is closely associated with State Shinto, militarism, and extreme nationalism. The explanation in the World Encyclopedia states, "Based on a sense of ethnic superiority, it belittles and annexes other ethnic groups. Japan attempted to use this tower to suppress all countries worldwide from a feng shui (geomancy or

geomantic omen) perspective." It is ironic that the 1964 Tokyo Olympics torch relay started at this location in Miyazaki City. Perhaps on that day, Japan provided enough evil and powerful spring spirit to launch another aggressive war.

The tower has an extremely dark feng shui structure layout.

[<https://v.douyin.com/iJUnhMc9/>],

[the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一宇塔)..<https://baike.so.com/doc/522909-553588.html>]

This evil tower ("**Tower of Suppressing Souls**") has a very peculiar design, with its foundation built on top of spirit stones looted or stolen from various countries around the world. **These spiritual stones were used to suppress the fortunes of other nations**, as Japan sought to completely dominate Asia and eventually rule the world. **Publicly known instances of looting and stealing spirit stones include those from China, Korea, Singapore, the United States, Canada, Germany, Peru, the Philippines, and Russia.** **Despite Germany being a friendly country and ally of Japan at the time, Japan still sought to suppress Germany's fortunes.** The United States encountered many crises after World War II, which may be related to Japan using this tower to suppress the fortunes of the United States.

Table S5. 110-World First Records for the Evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls"

1	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls "[the Unified Universe Tower(八纮一宇塔)] to suppress the souls of other countries.
2	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of other countries.
3	During World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and evil techniques to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the souls of other countries.
4	During World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and evil techniques to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the destiny of other countries.
5	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress China's soul .
6	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress China's national luck.
7	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the American soul .
8	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of the United States .
9	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of Canada .
10	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Canada's national luck .
11	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the German soul .
12	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls "to

	suppress Germany's national luck.
13	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of Singapore.
14	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Singapore's national luck.
15	In World War II, the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the Russian soul.
16	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Russia's national luck.
17	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of South Korea.
18	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of South Korea.
19	In World War II, it was the first country to build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of North Korea.
20	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of North Korea.
21	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of Peru.
22	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress Peru's national luck.
23	In World War II, it was the first country to build a " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the soul of the Philippines.
24	In World War II, it was the first country to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress the national luck of the Philippines.
25	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized the theft and plunder of spiritual stones from China to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Chinese spirit.
26	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized the theft and plunder of spiritual stones from China to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of China.
27	In World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls ", suppressing the destiny of China, with the intention of preventing the Chinese people from ever rising again. China has always demanded that Japan dismantle the tower, but Japan has refused to do so.
28	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the Yellow Crane Tower in Wuhan, China, to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
29	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the peak of Mount Tai in China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
30	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from

	the Ming Palace of the Ming Dynasty in China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
31	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen bricks from the Great Wall of China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
32	During World War II, the first evil nation that used stolen spirit stones from the Zhongshan Mausoleum in China to build the Soul Suppressing Tower and oppress the Chinese soul emerged.
33	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from the United States through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the American spirit.
34	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from the United States through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of America.
35	In World War II, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls ", suppressing the destiny of the U.S., with the intention of preventing the American people from ever rising again.
36	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Canada through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Canadian spirit.
37	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Canada through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Canada.
38	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Germany through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the German spirit.
39	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Germany through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Germany.
40	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Singapore through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Singaporean spirit.
41	During World War II, the first evil country that obtained spiritual stones from Singapore through special means to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Singapore.
42	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from Russia to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Russian spirit.
43	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from Russia to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Russia.
44	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from South Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to

	oppress the South Korean spirit.
45	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from South Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of South Korea.
46	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the North Korean spirit.
47	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of North Korea.
48	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Peruvian spirit.
49	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of Peru.
50	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the Philippines.
51	During World War II, the first evil country that utilized theft and plunder of spiritual stones from North Korea to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of the Philippines.
52	During World War II, the first evil country to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the spirits of other nations and issue ten-yuan commemorative currency in honor of the tower was Japan.
53	During World War II, the first evil country to construct a soul-suppressing tower to oppress the destiny of other nations and issue ten-yuan commemorative currency in honor of the tower was Japan.
54	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the souls of other countries.
55	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of other countries.
56	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress China's soul.
57	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress China's national fortunes.
58	In modern history, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark arts to build " Tower of Suppressing Souls " to suppress destiny of other countries.
59	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the American soul.
60	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of the United States.
61	In modern history, Japan was the first country to use mysterious and dark

	arts to build the " Tower of Suppressing Souls ", suppressing the destiny of the United States.
62	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Canadian soul.
63	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Canada's national fortunes.
64	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the German soul.
65	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the German national fortunes.
66	In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of Singapore.
67	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Singapore's national fortunes.
68	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Russian soul.
69	In modern history, the first country built "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Russian national fortunes.
70	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of South Korea.
71	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the national fortunes of South Korea.
72	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of North Korea.
73	In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Korean national fortunes.
74	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of Peru.
75	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Peru's national fortunes.
76	In modern history, it was the first country to build the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the soul of the Philippines.
77	In modern history, it was the first country to build "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress the Philippine national fortunes.
78	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Chinese spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Chinese soul.
79	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Chinese spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress China's national fortunes.
80	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain American spirit stones in a special way and construct the "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the soul of the United States

	The United States is constantly encountering treasury bond crisis and economic crisis. Is the national fortunes suppressed by the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls"?
81	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain American spirit stones in a special way and construct the "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress American national fortunes.
82	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Canadian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the soul of Canada.
83	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Canadian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" to suppress Canada's national fortunes.
84	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain German spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the German soul.
85	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain German spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Germany's national fortunes.
86	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Singapore's spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Singapore's soul.
87	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Singapore's spirit stones through special means and construct the "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Singapore's national fortunes.
88	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Russian spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Russian souls.
89	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Russian spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Russia's national fortunes.
90	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Korean souls.
91	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress Korean national fortunes.
92	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress the soul of North Korea
93	In modern history, the first evil country to steal and plunder Korean spirit stones and build a soul tower in an attempt to suppress North Korea's national fortunes.
94	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Peruvian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress

	Peruvian souls
95	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Peruvian spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls", attempting to suppress Peruvian national fortunes
96	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Philippine spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress the soul of the Philippines
97	In modern history, the first evil country to obtain Philippine spirit stones in a special way and build a "Tower of Suppressing Souls" in an attempt to suppress the Philippine national fortunes.
98	In modern history, the first country to build a Soul Suppression Tower in an attempt to suppress the souls of other countries was evil Japan, and the Japanese bank also issued a ten-yen currency to commemorate the Tower.
99	In modern history, the first country to build a Soul Suppression Tower in an attempt to suppress the fortunes of other nations was evil Japan, and the Japanese bank also issued a ten-yen currency to commemorate the Tower.
100	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of China.
101	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of the United States.
102	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Canada's destiny.
103	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Germany's destiny.
104	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Australia's destiny.
105	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Singapore's destiny.
106	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of Russia.
107	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress Korea's destiny.
108	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of Peru.
109	In modern history, the first evil country that built a world unity centred on Japan and attempted to suppress the destiny of the Philippines.
110	In modern history, the first country to erect a soul-suppressing tower that aimed to conquer the world and suppress the destiny of other nations, deceived the global public by calling it the Tower of Peace, and transformed it into the starting point for the Olympic torchbearer symbolizing peace. However, shortly after the Olympic Games ended, the country reverted the tower's name back to its evil original name.
	Judging from Japan's behavior before and after World War II and its handling of "Tower of Suppressing Souls" [the Unified Universe Tower(八纎

一 字 塔]], what kind of social system does Japan have?

If the Japanese really wanted world peace, they would have destroyed the evil tower long ago. On the contrary, every year countless Japanese come here to worship Japanese war criminals and secretly make wishes to conquer Asia and the world.

灭绝人性！日寇在成安县残杀五千中国老百姓，用尸体填沟铺低洼路方便车辆通行

Fig. 85-22. After the Lugou Bridge Incident in 1937, the Japanese invaders launched a massive attack on the North China Plain. On October 24th, the Japanese army broke through Cheng'an City in Hebei and brutally **slaughtered more than 5,300 innocent compatriots**, creating the shocking "Cheng'an Massacre" that shocked both China and foreign countries. In the evening of October 24th, after the Japanese army entered Cheng'an City, they set up machine guns on the west city wall and fired at the crowd along the east-west street, causing most of the innocent civilians to fall in a pool of blood. The methods of the Japanese aggressors in massacring people were devoid of humanity. **After killing the ordinary people, they used their bodies to fill up the low-lying sections of the road, and then covered it with a layer of soil to facilitate vehicle passage!** #Resistance War #Never Forget National Humiliation #Never Forget History Self-Strengthening #Remember History. 2023-07-19 <https://v.douyin.com/iJryxGng/> **"Three Alls Policy"** ("Burn all, **kill all**, loot all.")

Fig. 85-23. "Three Alls Policy" ("Burn all, kill all, loot all.") The Physical Body of Zen Master Yuanji

There have been miraculous cases of incorruptible bodies among Chinese Buddhists since ancient times. Zen master Yuanji, a monk from the Tang Dynasty, passed away at the age of 91 in Hengshan, Hunan. His physical body did not decay, so a temple was specially built to enshrine and worship him. For thousands of years, this temple was bustling with pilgrims until the end of the Qing Dynasty and the beginning of the Republic of China.

In the 1930s, Japanese spy Watanabe Shirō fell seriously ill and decided to steal the physical body of Zen master Yuanji to study it, hoping to cure his own illness. Taking advantage of the chaos, he poisoned a young monk in the temple and smuggled the physical body of Zen master Yuanji to Japan. The physical body of Zen master Yuanji is currently kept in the Jōchi-ji Temple in Yokohama's Higashi-Kanagawa ward, and it is treasured as a national treasure of Japan. To this day, it has not been returned to China. His actions can only be described as despicable and shameless.

[<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1728920535124373989&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

According to incomplete statistics, during the Anti-Japanese War, the evil Japanese plundered an astonishing amount of resources from China. At least 42,000 tons of gold, at least 10 million pieces of cultural relics, at least 500 tons of natural diamonds, at least 20 million gemstones, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls, at least 25,000 tons of silver, at least 250 million silver dollars, at least 1,000 tons of platinum, at least 1.22 billion tons of grain, at least 1.06 billion tons of coal, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood, at least 200 million tons of rare earths, at least 150 million tons of kaolin, and at least 49,000 tons of bronze.

So far, Japan has not compensated China, but now it is manufacturing more and more warships similar to aircraft carriers. What is Japan preparing for in the future?

What is the value of 500 tons of natural diamonds in US dollars? Anyone can calculate it. Japan was a seemingly defeated country in World War II, isn't it a truly

victorious country?

Fig. 85-23-1. The evil Japanese people use the Nanjing Guanyin statue to redeem Japanese war criminals, and decipher the world's most sinister Feng Shui organization. This Guanyin statue is constructed using **ten jars of soil soaked with the blood of Chinese civilians.**

Warvigilance:

If Japan were truly a peace loving nation, would it be so bloody and shameless?

If the Japanese were truly a peace-loving nation, would a peace-loving nation still be so bloody and shameless in the 21st century after World War II?

In the early morning of 23 December, Hideki Tojo and six other war criminals were executed. At 7 a.m., their bodies were transported to Kuboyama crematorium, where Yoshimi Tobita, under U.S. military supervision, cremated the seven bodies and placed the ashes in seven separate urns. However, Tobita secretly manipulated the process and did not put all of the ashes in the urns. He even attempted to privately offer incense and prayers for the seven individuals, but the U.S. military discovered this and confiscated all the incense.

Unaware of Tobita's actions, the U.S. military packed the seven urns and took them away. The remaining small portion of the ashes were abandoned in a cement pit

at the crematorium, which was used to dispose of unclaimed ashes. After the U.S. troops left, Tobita immediately informed Sanmoto Masami. On the night of the 25th, Sanmoto Masami, Yoshimi Tobita, and Ichikawa Iyo, wearing black cloaks, secretly infiltrated the crematorium. Guided by Tobita, they arrived at the cement pit and used bamboo poles tied to jars to retrieve some of the ashes and fragments of bones from the pile of ash at the bottom.

The stolen ashes were initially stored at Kuboyama Kogyo-ji Temple, and in May of the following year, they were finally sent to Xingya Kannon Temple in Izu-Yama, Atami City, for safekeeping. The origin of this Xingya Kannon Temple is also extraordinary. The term "Xingya" was widely used by various Japanese militaristic and colonial institutions from the Meiji Restoration until Japan's defeat in World War II. For example, in 1938, the Japanese Kono Cabinet established the "Xingya Institute," which was specifically responsible for managing daily affairs and looting of resources in the occupied Chinese territories during the war against China. Therefore, the name Xingya Kannon Temple alone indicates that it is not an ordinary Buddhist temple. What infuriates the Chinese even more is that this temple was funded and built by Matsui Iwane, one of the seven executed war criminals and mastermind behind the Nanjing Massacre, in 1940 as a memorial for the deceased Japanese soldiers and officers in the war against China.

The stolen ashes were initially stored at Kubo Mountain Kōzenji Temple, and were only sent to the Xingya Guanyin Temple in Izu Yama, Atami City in May of the second year. The origin of this Xingya Guanyin Temple is also extraordinary. The characters "Xingya" were widely used by various Japanese militaristic and colonial institutions after the Meiji Restoration until Japan's defeat in the war. For example, in 1938, Japan's Kono Cabinet established the "Xingya Academy," a specialized institution for managing daily affairs and looting of resources on Chinese territories occupied during the China-Japanese War. Therefore, from the name of Xingya Guanyin Temple, it can be seen that this is not an ordinary Buddhist temple. What angers the Chinese even more is that it was funded and built by Matsui Iwane, one of the seven executed war criminals and the main culprit of the Nanjing Massacre, in order to worship the Japanese soldiers who died in the war of aggression against China.

The statue of Guanyin in the temple was specially made from 10 jars of blood-soaked soil taken from Nanjing Dachang Town by Matsui Iwane's men. After the temple was completed on February 24, 1940, Matsui Iwane even built a hermitage nearby and climbed the mountain every morning to worship Guanyin.

Although the ashes of these seven war criminals were sent to Xingya Guanyin Temple, due to the recent end of World War II, the Japanese people still did not dare to openly engage in worship activities, nor did they dare to publicly display the ashes. The then abbot, Itami Shinobishiki, decided to temporarily hide the ashes and "wait for the right moment."

In 1959, the so-called "Monument of the Seven Patriots" written by then Japanese Prime Minister Yoshida Shigeru was completed at Xingya Guanyin Temple. The temple believed that the "time was ripe" and publicly announced the news of the

seven war criminals' ashes being located there and buried them under the monument. In 1960, another so-called "Martyrs' Tomb of the Seven Patriots" was built in Motosu, Hatono District, Aichi Prefecture, and some of the ashes were taken from Xingya Guanyin Temple and buried in the tomb. Therefore, the ashes of the seven war criminals were buried in two different places.

The initial intention of the United States was to scatter the ashes of these seven individuals into the Pacific Ocean in order to prevent their graves from becoming a "sacred place" for the revival of Japanese militarism. However, under a series of actions by the Japanese, this goal has clearly not been achieved.

After several decades of additions, the current Xingya Guanyin Temple houses the ashes of 7 Class A war criminals and 901 Class B and C war criminals, all of whom were executed after being tried by various post-war military courts. There are also a total of 160 Class A, B, and C war criminals who died in prison for various reasons and were not executed by military courts. In total, there are 1,068 individuals. It can be said that this place is a gathering place for war criminals, often referred to as the "Little Yasukuni Shrine."

In addition to places where Class A war criminals are enshrined, such as Xingya Guanyin Academy, there are also some shrines in Japan dedicated to specific Japanese war criminals and militarists. The infamous ones among them are the Naimu Shrine and the Eryu Shrine.

[<https://v.douyin.com/iJPnNp71/>],[How malicious is Matsui Shigen? After the Nanjing Massacre, 10 jars of blood and soil were excavated to create a statue of Guanyin, May 5th, 2022. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/H6JOH9K90543AHBP.html>],[Be vigilant! In Japan, there are shrines that treat war criminals as ancestral offerings, as well as these

August 25th, 2021 https://www.sohu.com/a/485497414_162522]

Fig. 85-23-2. In July 2014, Prime Minister Abe of Japan paid homage to Wewak, Papua New Guinea, the death place of the commander of the Japanese Combined

Fleet, Isoroku Yamamoto, who attacked Pearl Harbor, destroyed the main force of the U.S. Pacific Fleet, and ensured the safety of the flanks of the Japanese attack on Southeast Asia. Prime Minister Abe and his wife bowed their heads and offered flowers. Prime Minister Abe of Japan and his wife bowed their heads and offered flowers.

Japan's Prime Minister Abe said, "It is because of the 120,000 Japanese soldiers who came to this place and died in battle for their motherland that Japan has peace and prosperity today. Today, I recall this fact again and pray for the deceased with respect and gratitude."

Warvigilance:

If Japan were truly a peace loving nation, would it be so bloody and shameless?

If the Japanese were truly a peace-loving nation, would a peace-loving nation still be so bloody and shameless in the 21st century after World War II?

[Abe visits war criminal Isoroku Yamamoto and bows his head to pay homage to flowers (picture). July 14, 2014; <http://news.sohu.com/20140714/n402187739.shtml>]

Questioning the United Nations and the international community	
1	Why has Japan long pretended to be a victim of the atomic bomb explosion?
2	Why do the Japanese people like to pretend for a long time to be victims of the atomic bomb explosion?
3	Why do Japanese politicians like to pretend for a long time to be victims of the atomic bomb explosion, even though they know very well in their hearts that the areas where the atomic bomb actually exploded are uninhabitable?
4	Why is the Japanese media so good at long - term fraud?
5	Why are the highly educated politicians in the international community so mindless and thoughtless that they are actually deceived by such childish tricks?
6	Why are the highly educated politicians in the international community so mindless and thoughtless that they are actually deceived by such illogical tricks?
7	Why does not the United Nations prohibit Japan, the world's most evil war criminal and criminal country, from lowering the marriage and childbearing age to 13 after the war? Isn't this accumulating potential conflict and war population for this evil country? Are United Nations officials not protecting the human rights of the victims, but protecting criminals and accumulating capital for the next crime for criminals? Politicians at the United Nations and in some countries should experience the Japanese army's torture of Chinese and American female soldiers and generals for three years, and be forced to eat feces for three years like American generals. If not, what qualifications do you have to be a civil servant of a country or an international organization?
8	The Japanese army killed at least 51.8 – 89.6 (100.80) million Chinese and raped or gang-raped at least 31.45 – 54.4 (61.2) million Chinese women. At least 200,000 Chinese women, pregnant women and young girls were forced to be sex slavery for the Japanese army. So far, no compensation has been paid to the victims. If for every 50,000 people slaughtered, the childbearing age is increased by one year starting from the normal age of 20. For the slaughter of over 50

million people, childbearing of the descendants of this evil country should be prohibited. The United Nations should at least lay down rules. **The marriage and childbearing age of the people of this evil country should be raised to at least 45 years for 5180-10,080 years.**

Fig. 85-23-3. Another World Record of Evil Japanese Locusts Massacring Humans. **Eating a feast of more than ten living people's hearts at once** Digging the **hearts of more than ten living Chinese people to cook at once** **The infamous "Cannibal Devil"** during World War II! The repugnant and despicable Japanese locust in the photo is named **"Kondo Shingoro,"** a high-ranking officer and bloodthirsty butcher. He has committed numerous gruesome crimes in China. The most anger-inducing and inhumane act was his disturbing preference for cooking and consuming the hearts of live people. In 1944, he was appointed as the commander of

the 19th Brigade of the Independent Mixed Brigade of the Japanese Aggression Army in China. Kondo Shingoro's troops carried out massacres and mass burials in areas such as Huizhou and Jieyang in Guangdong. In Huizhou alone, his subordinates **killed and buried more than 5,000 people**. Even more horrifying, in Jieyang, the devil Kondo Shingoro ordered his men to randomly capture over a dozen Chinese civilians (some as young as a few years old), and their hearts were ripped out while they were still alive, cooked, and consumed.

The atrocities committed by the demon Kondo Shingoro are truly abhorrent. However, evil-doers always meet their fate, and after the Japanese military's defeat, Kondo Shingoro was captured by the Nationalist forces. He was executed by firing squad on October 31, 1947, in Guangzhou.

Fig. 85-23-4. **Extremely Cruel! The Japanese aggressors laughed heartily after skinning the victims.**

[The cruel experiment of the Japanese Unit 731, flaking the skin alive, heinous # remember history; <https://v.douyin.com/iq8qf3F/>]

Peeling the skin off a live girl, a group of Japanese locusts laugh uncontrollably with

their mouths unable to close. Isn't the Japanese nation a shameless, evil, brutal, and uncivilized nation?

Can you quickly or slowly recognize from the appearance or facial features of these Japanese people that they are murderers and non-human nature tomorrow?

Can you quickly or slowly identify these Japanese from their appearance or facial features as war criminals and non-human nature?

When you put on suits and ties for them, can you recognize from their appearance or facial features that they are tomorrow murderers and evil non-human nature?

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 85-23-5. Babies with a painful expression after being skinned alive and soaked in formalin.

Japanese nature - pretending to be polite - the most despicable, cruel, barbaric, robbery, theft, anti-human, and war

Heinous Crimes - **Penalty of Japanese Unit 731**: Live skinning of baby and children: Japanese soldiers skinned babies alive in China, testing how long they could survive without skin. The babies' faces were contorted in pain. Babies and children were made into specimens. In the jars, there are infant specimens skinned by the Japanese army, displaying various expressions of agony. [The Japanese army skinned alive Chinese infants to test how long a baby without skin can survive. The babies twisted their faces in pain. <https://v.douyin.com/iq2TWGQ/>]

Will there be lasting peace in the world without a thorough reckoning and severe punishment for these abominable crimes?

Fig. 85-23-6. **Tanaka Memorial of Japan's desire to dominate the world**

The overall strategic plan for Japan's conquest of the world - Tanaka Memorial

Japan's proposed "New Continent policy" towards China was documented in a file. From June 27 to July 7, 1927, Japanese Prime Minister Tanaka Giichi convened the Oriental Conference in Tokyo, attended by officials from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Army, the Ministry of Navy, the General Staff, the Military Command,

the Kwantung Army, and the resident diplomats in China. The conference adopted the "Outline of China Policy." On July 25, Tanaka wrote to Minister of the Imperial Household, Yoshinori Ichiki, to request the Emperor's approval for the "Empire's proactive fundamental policy towards Manchuria and Mongolia." He stated, "My rights and interests in Manchuria and Mongolia are enormous. Therefore, every cabinet in history has followed the teachings of Emperor Meiji, expanding its scale and implementing the New Continent policy." He believed that the current Chinese authorities in the three eastern provinces were becoming aware, and the Nine-Power Treaty restricted "my special rights and interests in Manchuria and Mongolia." He emphasized that "if we do not make every effort to break through, our country's existence will not be solid, and our national power will not develop." He further stressed, "The Russo-Japanese War was essentially a war against China that we supported. In the future, if we want to control China, **we must first eliminate American influence as a prerequisite.** It is similar in significance to the Russo-Japanese War. However, **if we want to conquer China, we must first conquer Manchuria and Mongolia. If we want to conquer the world, we must first conquer China. If China is completely conquered by our country, other nations such as Central Asia, India, and Southeast Asia, which are different from us, will fear and respect us, and surrender to us."**

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&share_version=270200&ts=1697477305&from_ssr=1&utm_source=copy&utm_campaign=client_share&utm_medium=android&app=aweme 11/17 aNj:/ U@l.pd

<https://baike.so.com/doc/5933237-6146167.html>

110	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Immigration to other countries is a latent means and tool for evil countries without conscience and empathy or countries with criminal records to commit crimes, invade, plunder wealth and annex the territory of other countries. It is an important factor leading to an increase in crime rates. It is the basis for evil countries to carry out long-term evil plans under</p>
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	<p>the slogan of freedom and human rights. Farmers in China's three northeastern provinces were once deeply harmed and plundered by Japanese immigrants.</p> <p>The number of immigrants from the evil countries involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this article in any other country is prohibited from exceeding 0.01% of the number of deaths in Nanjing during the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese invaders. Those who have immigrated must be repatriated to the criminal country.</p>
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	Questioning the United Nations and the international community
1	Why has Japan long pretended to be a victim of the atomic bomb explosion?
2	Why do the Japanese people like to pretend for a long time to be victims of the atomic bomb explosion?
3	Why do Japanese politicians like to pretend for a long time to be victims of the atomic bomb explosion, even though they know very well in their hearts that the areas where the atomic bomb actually exploded are uninhabitable?
4	Why is the Japanese media so good at long - term fraud?
5	Why are the highly educated politicians in the international community so mindless and thoughtless that they are actually deceived by such childish tricks?
6	Why are the highly educated politicians in the international community so mindless and thoughtless that they are actually deceived by such illogical tricks?
7	Why does not the United Nations prohibit Japan, the world's most evil war criminal and criminal country, from lowering the marriage and childbearing age to 13 after the war? Isn't this accumulating potential conflict and war population for this evil country? Are United Nations officials not protecting the human rights of the victims, but protecting criminals and accumulating capital for the next crime for criminals? Politicians at the United Nations and in some countries should experience the Japanese army's torture of Chinese and American female soldiers and generals for three years, and be forced to eat feces for three years like American generals. If not, what qualifications do you have to be a civil servant of a country or an international organization?
8	The Japanese army killed at least 51.8 – 89.6 (100.80) million Chinese and raped or gang-raped at least 31.45 – 54.4 (61.2) million Chinese women. At least 200,000 Chinese women, pregnant women and young girls were forced to be sex slavery for the Japanese army. So far, no compensation has been paid to the victims. If for every 50,000 people slaughtered, the childbearing age is increased by one year starting from the normal age of 20. For the slaughter of over 50 million people, childbearing of the descendants of this evil country should be prohibited. The United Nations should at least lay down rules. The marriage and childbearing age of the people of this evil country should be raised to at least 45 years.

Fig 85-23-7. [Emperor Hirohito of Japan sent gold and beautiful women to MacArthur in order not to commit suicide by caesarean section, and the transaction was shameless. Historical Encyclopedia.May 11th, 2017.
<https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1567021878409567>(in Chinese)]

Fig 85-23-8. This is a Chinese cultural relic that was looted and placed at the National Museum in Tokyo. [How much wealth does Japan plunder from China?2023-01-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iNACmYcP/> dAT:/ 04/06 [r@R.Kw](https://v.douyin.com/iNACmYcP/)]

The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all.

Fig 85-23-9. This photo was taken in the city of Nanjing in 1937, showing a group of barbaric, greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese soldiers boasting about the valuables they had looted from the more than four hundred people they had just killed. They look smug and triumphant, as if they had just done something to be proud of. They have the audacity to treat the city of Nanjing as if it were their own home, with such shameless boldness. After taking the lives of more than four hundred people, they can still leave casually as if nothing had happened; four hundred lives seem so insignificant to them. [2022-08-25. <https://v.douyin.com/iNACC18H/07/09/iC:/A@g.bA>]

The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all.

Most of the wealth possessed by the evil Japanese country and its citizens was plundered from China.

Fig 85-23-10. The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all. [The photo shows the scene of barbaric, greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese invaders snatching pigs from Chinese villagers. 2023-12-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAXBJaP/>]

Most of the wealth possessed by the evil Japanese country and its citizens was plundered from China.

Fig 85-23-11. The **"three all" policy** of the Japanese invasion of China: **burning all, killing all, and looting all.** [The Japanese invaders harm the people, **snatch their chickens, and walk with high spirits.** # Stories from old photos # Remembering history and not forgetting national shame. 2022-03-23. <https://v.douyin.com/iNACxF3q/VYM:/R@X.zT> 12/07]

Most of the wealth possessed by the evil Japanese country and its citizens was plundered from China.

这是一张记录抗战时期的照片，照片中的这名日本侵略者赤裸上身，属于日军第六师团，他怀中抱着的是在“扫荡”行动中掠夺的“战利品”。在侵华战争期间，日军推行了极端残酷的“三光政策”，包括“杀戮、抢劫、焚烧”。这是日本军国主义在侵华战争中实施的一种野蛮政策。

具体来说，日军在占领区进行了大规模的屠杀和强奸，抢夺了大量的粮食、财物和资源。他们不仅对中国军民犯下了无数罪行，还对被占领区的政治、经济和社会文化进行了全面控制和掠夺。在这张照片中，他们的笑容背后，是中国无数人遭受痛苦和

Fig 85-23-12. The "three all" policy of the Japanese invasion of China: burning all, killing all, and looting all. [The photo shows the scene of barbaric, greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese invaders snatching food from Chinese villagers. 2023-10-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAXrH5y/> 01/28 CUL:/ H@V.yG]

The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur.

Fig 85-23-13. In May 1939, two traitors and a large number of Japanese invaders went to the countryside to grab grain. Three innocent girls over the age of ten were also abducted by the evil, despicable, and shameless Japanese people. The girls remained childish and trembling with fear and helplessness. 2024-02-01. <https://v.douyin.com/iNAX8w6L/04/22> Tyt:/ G@v.SI

If the United States were occupied by Japan, how many traitors would lead the evil, despicable and shameless Japanese to capture young girls?

Fig 85-23-14. **Real camera videos** [Millions of Japanese prisoners of war returned to Japan and were welcomed like heroes. 2023-09-15. <https://v.douyin.com/iNkSw4Fa/07/23E@h.BTUyt:/>]

The Japanese have never had a heart of repentance for massacring the Chinese people and plundering huge amounts of wealth.

The biggest mistake in today's world is not overestimating the law and judges?

Greedy, despicable, and evil Japanese plundered vast amounts of gold, silver, jewels, diamonds, artifacts, and rare books, and slaughtered at least 51.80 to 86.90 (100.80) million Chinese people. Isn't Japan the real victor? The wealth was long transported back to Japan, and the people also returned safely. Aren't they very happy in their hearts?

How could Japan be considered a defeated nation? Japan did nothing more than sign a single A4-sized document of surrender, which excited the utopian nerves of kind-hearted people around the world. The biggest war criminal even openly bribed the occupying commander, General MacArthur, with beauty, and was not only spared the death penalty, but was astonishingly not sentenced at all. Where are human rights?

Where is empathy? Where is freedom? Where is democracy?

Fig 85-23-15. [On December 12, 1942, as dawn approached, Japanese military leader Raiya led his troops to surround Wangjia Mountain Village in Zhaitang Town, Mentougou District, Beijing. Tragically, the village's elderly, women, and children were trapped in the encirclement. After the invaders entered the village, they set up machine guns around the perimeter. Raiya ordered the village to be set ablaze. Sadly, **42 women and children perished in the inferno, some of the women being pregnant.** #Resistance Against Japan #Japanese Atrocities #Never Forget National Humiliation #Remember History. 2024-02-07. <https://v.douyin.com/iNrxqBnY/04/08 Uyt:/R@K.jp> **Evil Japan must be re-named SRM-Japan or SR-Japan**

Evil Japan must be re-named SRM-Japan or SR-Japan

Fig 85-23-16. [Unit 100 was a top-down restructured bacteriological unit under the command of the Japanese Army Ministry and General Staff Headquarters. This unit conducted live human experiments, field toxicity tests, and field exercises, with the entire ecosystem as its intended target. Like Unit 731, Unit 100 conducted live human experiments on Chinese individuals, committing unforgivable atrocities. Remember the true nature of these demons. #Japanese Army Bacteriological Unit100 #Never Forget National Humiliation Remember History. 2023-12-18. [https://v.douyin.com/iN6wyc6U/E@u.fb07/12Gvs:/](https://v.douyin.com/iN6wyc6U/E@u.fb07/12Gvs/)]

日军欠衡阳的血债

1944年8月8日衡阳城陷落，这个原本有**50万**人口的城市，因战争死亡了**29480人**，伤残了**25430人**，被日军毒气弹致死的有**30000余人**。照片是被日军屠杀遇难者者的头盖骨，一共有**5000余人**，看了令人看着又震撼又心痛！

Fig. 85-23-17. The Japanese army owes a blood debt to Hengyang.

On August 8, 1944, Hengyang city fell. This city, which originally had a population of 500,000, **suffered 29,480 deaths** and 25,430 wounded due to the war. More than 30,000 people were killed by the Japanese army's poison gas shells. **The photo shows the skulls of more than 5,000 victims slaughtered by the Japanese army.**

[2023-08-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iL5ResFe/d@a.ATWzG:/08/27>]

Fig. 85-23-18. During the invasion of Foshan by the Japanese invaders, Japanese soldiers were transporting tea and other materials looted from Foshan.

The Anti-Japanese War resulted in the loss of 850,000 people in Foshan.

Foshan is not only a famous historic city with developed industry and bustling commerce, but also boasts beautiful scenic spots and historical sites in Shunde, Gaoming, Nanhai, and Sanshui. The cuisine in the Foshan area ranks among the top in Guangdong.

On October 21, 1938, Guangzhou fell. In order to ensure the smooth operation of major cities and important transportation routes and plunder war resources, the Japanese army continued to infiltrate and occupy the surrounding areas of Guangzhou. Shunde, Nanhai (at that time Foshan was a town in Nanhai), and Sanshui subsequently fell, and the Japanese invaders unleashed their slaughter and brutal destruction on the land of Foshan in a savage and inhumane manner.

"Just in Chen Village, Xinwei, and Bijiang areas, nearly 100 people were beaten or stabbed to death. The blood of the dead and stabbed people dyed the fish ponds and roads red," said Chen Sheng, a 95-year-old revolutionary. Even before the fall of Foshan in 1938, the Japanese army bombed Nanhai, Shunde, Sanshui, and Gaoming, causing numerous casualties. **What was even more horrific was that the Japanese army used airplanes to drop poison using bacteria and gas, targeting local civilians and military personnel.**

During the period of resistance in Foshan, direct casualties amounted to 20,526, including 15,458 deaths, 2,548 injuries, and 250 missing. Indirect casualties reached 103,001, including 14,226 captured or arrested, 85,842 displaced persons or refugees, and 2,933 labourers. Other casualties are difficult to estimate. The Japanese army also established Japanese language schools in occupied areas, forcing local people to attend and instilling in them a subservience mentality. **In the occupied areas, Nanhai County had a total of 32 Japanese language schools, while Sanshui County had 2. In Shunde, the Japanese army established Japanese language schools** in places such as

Dalang, Rongqi, Guizhou, and Chen Village, making Japanese the main subject with the requirement that failing the Japanese language exam would prevent students from advancing to the next level.

[Sadly, the history of Foshan losing 850,000 people cannot be forgotten. 2016-09-18. https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s?__biz=Mjm5OTgwOTQ2NQ==&mid=2650584369&idx=1&sn=eb25ecb77b986b812da0229cbcedce4ad&chksm=bf3dcde7884a44f1cb78d81a86ac45cd38333873ea44fc5091848b56844819eb9c83a101ca98&scene=27]

Fig. 85-23-19. **Survivor of the bacterial warfare in Zhegan Bacterial Massacre** Lawyer Ms. Wang Xuan quit her job with an annual salary of CNY 500,000 to force Japan to acknowledge and apologize for their use of bacteriological warfare, exhausting all her savings over 25 years and taking Japan to court 29 times. It forced Japan to acknowledge and apologize, and to include this history in textbooks.

[She is a woman who makes the Japanese itch with hatred. In order to make Japan apologize, she spent all her savings over 25 years and sued Japan 29 times, finally

forcing Japan to recognize the use of biological warfare and include it in textbooks. Salute to the heroine Wang Xuan. <https://v.douyin.com/iJaHUuQ9/>

Fig. 85-23-20.

Lawyer Ms. Wang Xuan quit her job with an annual salary of CNY 500,000 to force Japan to acknowledge and apologize for their use of bacteriological warfare, exhausting all her savings over 25 years and taking Japan to court 29 times. It forced Japan to acknowledge and apologize, and to include this history in textbooks.

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Isn't the current international legal system hindering justice and protecting crime? Don't these ugly regulations need to be amended immediately?

Table S6. Questioning the makers of the judicial system and politicians:	
1	Is Japan really a peace-loving country?
2	Are the Japanese really honest?
3	Are the Japanese really kind?
4	Do the Japanese really have a conscience?

5	Is Japan really a country that wants peace?
6	<p>Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the death of about 650,000 Chinese people.</p> <p>If Japan and the Japanese are really such, it is an obvious fact that the Japanese invaders carried out biochemical warfare of bacteria and viruses to massacre the Chinese people.</p> <p>On August 27, 2002, after 27 court hearings, the Tokyo District Court of Japan announced that lawyer Wang Xuan and the plaintiffs of the bacterial warfare of the Japanese invaders in China lost the lawsuit. From the first session of the Court in 1998 to 2006, it has been eight years. After eight years of litigation and more than 40 court sessions, some media commented on Wang Xuan in this way: Another eight-year war of resistance. The eight-year war of resistance that took place 60 years ago won victory, while the eight-year war of resistance in 2006 still sees no end. On July 19, 2006, lawyer Wang Xuan and members of the bacterial warfare plaintiff group once again heard the result of losing the lawsuit in the courtroom of the Tokyo District Court of Japan.</p> <p>Why did the Japanese government admit that it had carried out bacterial biochemical warfare in China only after being sued 29 times from the 20th to the 21st century, and that these people were victims of biochemical warfare? However, the evil Japanese government refused to pay any compensation to the victims.</p>
7	Who made ugly and evil laws and rules that require victims to sue a group of criminals in the criminal country?
8	Who made ugly and evil laws and rules that require victims to sue the criminal country in the criminal country?
9	Who made ugly and evil laws and rules that require victims to sue the criminal country in the criminal country? Can victims get fair and just results?
10	Is the maker of such ugly and evil laws and rules a pig? A stupid pig? If the maker is a stupid pig, what qualifications do he has to make laws and rules? If he takes bribes to make such ugly and evil laws and rules, and the evil Japanese invaders killed at least 51.80–89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people, why can't the evil criminals be exterminated? The reason why Chinese civilization has endured for a long time is that criminals are severely punished by special means in special circumstances.
11	If the maker of such ugly and evil rules appeared in ancient China, it is estimated that his nine clans would be exterminated and all personal and family property would be confiscated.
12	If the judicial officials responsible for matters related to cracking down on criminals at the United Nations are unable to restrain heinous crimes, should they not be removed from their positions?
13	Zhejiang-Jiangxi Bacterial Warfare Massacre perpetrated by world's most

seemingly polite but extremely evil, extremely despicable, extremely savage, fond of stealing and looting, and extremely anti-human Japanese resulted in the **death of about 650,000 Chinese people**.

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Why did the Japanese government admit that it had carried out bacterial biochemical warfare in China only after being sued 29 times from the 20th to the 21st century, and that these people were victims of biochemical warfare? However, the evil Japanese government refused to pay any compensation to the victims.

You can believe that dogs don't defecate, but you must never believe that Japan is kind, and you must never believe that Japan wants world peace.

Table S7. International consensus and United Nations conventions that must be established	
1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any criminal state or nation of war criminals that has committed crimes involving mass fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, trafficking in human beings, harvesting of live organs, massacres including biowarfare, as covered by the Consensus, will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next 10,000 years. Moreover, if such a war criminal</p>

	<p>State, having committed any of the aforementioned crimes against the public of another nation since 1900, has not so far provided full compensation for the losses of the victims and killed all criminals, it will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next ten thousand years.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Immigration to other countries is a latent means and tool for evil countries without conscience and empathy or countries with criminal records to commit crimes, invade, plunder wealth and annex the territory of other countries. It is an important factor leading to an increase in crime rates. It is the basis for evil countries to carry out long-term evil plans under the slogan of freedom and human rights. Farmers in China's three northeastern provinces were once deeply harmed and plundered by Japanese immigrants.</p> <p>The number of immigrants from the evil countries involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this article in any other country is prohibited from exceeding 0.01% of the number of deaths in Nanjing during the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese invaders. Those who have immigrated must be repatriated to the criminal country.</p>
3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of 10 million people and plundering over 100 billion US dollars worth of wealth (calculated at the value of all goods or cultural artifacts in 2023 US dollars), will be prohibited from</p>

	<p>establishing any military schools, academies, or universities for the next 5000 years unless the evil country fully compensates the victimized countries and victims or their relatives and returns the plundered wealth. All military schools, academies, colleges, or universities operated by an evil country must be shut down within one year. In addition, any person from an evil country or their descendants will be prohibited from studying military subjects in any third country.</p> <p>Exceptions are made for nations that have already made full reparations, such as Germany after the Second World War, which is the sole exception to this rule.</p>
4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of 10 million people and plundering over 100 billion US dollars worth of wealth (calculated at the value of all goods or cultural artifacts in 2023 US dollars), will be prohibited to have any military or self-defense forces for the next 5000 years, and only police officers who maintain social order will be allowed. The army of the victimized country can be stationed or enter anywhere in the criminal country or war criminal country at any time. All expenses shall be borne by the criminal country or war criminal country.</p> <p>Exceptions are made for nations that have already made full reparations, such as Germany after the Second World War, which is the sole exception to this rule.</p>
5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries or their descendants or their overseas descendants, causing the deaths of 200,000 people, will be prohibited from establishing any military schools, academies, or universities for the next</p>

	<p>200,000 years unless the evil country fully compensates the victimized countries and victims or their relatives and returns the plundered wealth. All military schools, academies, colleges, or universities operated by an evil country must be shut down within one year. In addition, any person from an evil country or their descendants will be prohibited from studying military subjects in any third country.</p>
6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries or their descendants or their overseas descendants, causing the deaths of 200,000 people, will be prohibited to have any military or self-defense forces for the next 200,000 years, and only police officers who maintain social order will be allowed. The army of the victimized country can be stationed or enter anywhere in the criminal country or war criminal country at any time. All expenses shall be borne by the criminal country or war criminal country.</p>
7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If the officials responsible for peace at the United Nations were just a group of thoughtless and incompetent officials who can only receive salaries, that was a waste of taxpayers' wealth and they must be dismissed and punished immediately.</p>
8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a</p>

	<p>permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If the officials responsible for peace at the United Nations were just a group of thoughtless and incompetent officials who can only receive salaries, that was a waste of taxpayers' wealth and they must be dismissed and punished immediately.</p> <p>For the victims covered by this article, as long as the State which committed the crime and/or the State which committed the war crime does not make full reparation to the victims and the victimized country, the victimized country can refuse to pay its dues to the United Nations.</p> <p>The United Nations must impose fines on criminal countries and war criminal countries such as Japan, Myanmar, Vietnam, and Indonesia according to the number of victims and property losses to offset China's dues to the United Nations.</p>
9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>In order to maintain world peace, it is necessary to establish a United Nations convention prohibiting any country from transferring weapons production lines and weapons technology to other nations.</p>
10	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>It is necessary to prohibit war criminal countries or criminal countries that have committed large-scale crimes since 1950 from providing any weapons to other countries or transferring any weapons manufacturing technology to other countries.</p>
11	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world</p>

	<p>civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For all the criminal countries and war criminal countries that have committed the large-scale crimes referred to in this article, as long as they have not fully compensated the victims and the victimized countries, when the United Nations holds a meeting, a special group of seats for criminal countries must be set up, and only representatives of those evil countries should be confined to those seats.</p>
12	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>States that have committed large-scale crimes as described in this article since 2000 must be prohibited from immigrating to any country.</p>
13	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>All criminal countries and war criminal States that have committed the crimes referred to in this article on a large scale since 1900 shall be prohibited from providing loans to any State, institution, bank or individual to criminal States, war criminal States, their companies or individuals as long as they have not made full reparation to the victims.</p>
14	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, for any country that has carried out large-scale telecom fraud,</p>

large-scale kidnapping, mass looting of property, large-scale massacre, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, forcing women into sexual slavery, germ warfare, biological warfare, and chemical warfare and has destroyed criminal evidence; including evil countries that failed to fully and voluntarily admit and announce all crimes in court within five years after the end of World War II; evil countries where war criminals or criminals of the criminal country fail to voluntarily admit their crimes, but instead force the victims to present evidence to make these criminals admit their crimes, and where victims or victim countries have not been fully compensated, any commitments and documents made by any country or citizen to the criminal country and war criminal country in the past are all abolished. The criminal country and war criminal country must bear all compensation for war losses, even if it takes 10,000 years to compensate. Any country that fails to severely punish all criminals and families who have benefited from crimes and fails to fully compensate victims and victim countries must be disintegrated and reorganized. The reorganized criminal country must also bear all compensation responsibilities and obligations.

At the same time, the following acts are prohibited:

Within the next 5,000 years, it is strictly prohibited for any country, institution or individual to provide any form of loan to such criminal countries.

Within the next 5,000 years, States or institutions or individuals are strictly prohibited from supplying and selling any weapons to such criminal countries.

Within the next 5,000 years, it is strictly forbidden for any country to accept immigrants from such criminal countries or war criminal countries.

Within the next 5,000 years, it is forbidden for the immigrant population of this criminal country in other countries to exceed 0.01% of the number of Chinese deaths in the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese invaders. If the number of immigrants who have already occurred exceeds this limit, repatriation must be completed within six months.

Within the next 5,000 years, citizens of this criminal country or their descendants must be at least 30 years of age or older for legal marriage and childbearing. For countries with serious crimes, penalties must continue to be increased, and the legal age for marriage and childbearing must be further raised. For those who violate the regulations, any medical insurance or social security must not be provided.

Within the next 5,000 years, it is strictly prohibited for any country or institution or individual to help such criminal countries in any form of infrastructure services, technology transfer or the construction of any plant.

Within the next 5,000 years, it is strictly prohibited for any country or institution or individual to help such criminal countries in any form of railway or high-speed rail construction service.

Within the next 5,000 years, it is strictly prohibited for any country or institution or individual to help such criminal countries in any form of power station construction service.

	<p>The personal and family property of all persons in that criminal country or war criminal country must be permanently and fully disclosed.</p> <p>Criminals all have a mouth and can speak for themselves. Such criminals are far better at creating lies than kind normal people. It is prohibited for any lawyer to defend such criminals or criminal countries. Any lawyer who provides defence services for such criminals or criminal countries is regarded as committing the same type of crime. For example, those who defend criminals of massacres are regarded as committing massacre crimes. Their crimes are knowing the law and breaking it, and the punishment is aggravated.</p> <p>For anyone who violates the agreement, all personal and family property will be confiscated, and they will be sentenced to at least five years in prison. And within ten days after the crime, all personal and family property of their nine generations of relatives will be unconditionally and permanently announced. All violators will be included on the credit blacklist. They will be banned from taking high-speed rail and airplanes for the next 100 years. Before leaving any city, they must report to the police agency. For the next 300 years, all immediate relatives of all violators will be prohibited from holding any employment in government agencies and entering financial institutions, military institutions and security institutions.</p> <p>Exceptions are made for nations that have already made full reparations, such as Germany after the Second World War, which is the sole exception to this rule.</p>
15	<p>As long as the museum fails to indicate that it belongs to false cultural relics, the following penalties must be imposed on the museum for displaying false historical cultural relics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. As long as the museum does not indicate that it belongs to false cultural relics, all viewers who have visited the museum can claim compensation at three times the ticket price. 2. For any museum with free admission tickets, compensate visitors twice the travel expenses of ordinary visitors to the museum. 3. Remove the position of the person responsible for appraising cultural relics in the museum. If the appraiser makes incorrect appraisals more than five times in formal work, the appraiser is permanently prohibited from appraising cultural relics for any museum. 4. Any museum that displays fake artifacts that falsify major historical events but does not clearly tell the public that once the number reaches three, the museum's top leader will be removed from his position. From the date of the occurrence and confirmation of the event, the relevant responsible persons are prohibited from enjoying medical insurance services for three years.
16	<p>Anyone who falsifies historical relics and causes the academic circles of history to revise history textbooks and university history books shall be sentenced to death, all personal and family property shall be confiscated, the families of the criminals shall be exiled to remote and cold areas, and the descendants of the criminals shall permanently bear joint and several liability</p>

	<p>for compensation.</p> <p>Most of the cultural relics unearthed in Egypt and Europe are forged by evil people who create false histories.</p>
17	<p>Anyone who manufactures cultural relics with fictional history shall be sentenced to ten years' imprisonment, all personal and family property shall be confiscated, and the families of the offenders shall be exiled to remote and cold areas, and the descendants of the criminals shall permanently bear joint and several liability for compensation.</p> <p>Most of the cultural relics unearthed in Egypt and Europe are forged by evil people who create false histories.</p>
18	<p>For any fictional history created through forged cultural relics or books, as long as one million people provide evidence and report it, any media must stop spreading this fictional history and must tell the public that this period of history is fictional reasoning. Otherwise, the editor in charge of the media field will be removed from his or her position, the media will be prohibited from operating for one month, all illegal income will be confiscated, and a fine of three times the income brought by media dissemination will be imposed. The person directly responsible, the largest shareholder, the actual controller and the legal person of the media will be sentenced to two years' imprisonment.</p> <p>Most of the cultural relics unearthed in Egypt and Europe are forged by evil people who create false histories.</p>
19	<p>For any fictional history created through forged cultural relics or books, as long as one million people provide evidence and report it, any publishing house must stop publishing or spreading this fictional history and must tell the public that this period of history is fictional reasoning. Otherwise, the person in charge of the publishing house and the editor in charge of the media field will be removed from their positions. The publishing house will be prohibited from operating for one month, all illegal income will be confiscated, and a fine of three times the amount based on the number and amount of publications will be imposed. The person directly responsible, the largest shareholder, the actual controller and the legal person of the publishing house will be sentenced to two years' imprisonment.</p> <p>Most of the cultural relics unearthed in Egypt and Europe are forged by evil people who create false histories.</p>
20	<p>For any fictional history created through forged cultural relics or books, as long as one million people provide evidence and report it, any teacher in any school must stop teaching this fictional history. Moreover, they must inform all the students they have taught that this period of history is fictional and forged. Otherwise, the teacher who teaches this subject will be removed from his or her position, banned from teaching, and prohibited from enjoying any medical insurance in the subsequent three years.</p> <p>Most of the cultural relics unearthed in Egypt and Europe are forged by evil people who create false histories. However, many people who tell these histories clearly know that these cultural relics cannot be real, but they tell false</p>

	histories as if they were real. Hasn't the conscience, morality and ethics of today's world regressed by 6,000 years?
21	<p>Is Japan a peace-loving country? Are the Japanese really peace-loving? Are the Japanese not extremely evil? Hasn't Japan been deceiving the Nobel Peace Prize Committee for a long time?</p> <p>In April 2023, Japanese Foreign Minister Yoshimasa Hayashi publicly denied the Nanjing Massacre, only admitting that there were civilian casualties caused by battles. Yoshimasa Hayashi said that there is no document within the Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs to prove that Japan carried out the massacre of civilians in Nanjing.</p> <p>At present, Japan has begun to deny the heinous crimes committed during the Second World War! This is denying the conclusion of the Tokyo Trials and trying to overthrow the international order after the Second World War. Militarism is resurgent!</p> <p>In fact, the Japanese invaders massacred at least 500,000–650,000 people. Some evidence left in the documents destroyed by the Japanese army is that in the two months before and after the Nanjing Massacre, the population fell by 785,000 people.</p> <p>The Japanese are extremely evil in their hearts but are good at disguising themselves as polite on the outside. They carried out the Nanjing Massacre using various forms of torture. At least 100,000 or more women were raped and gang-raped, yet they still do not admit their crimes.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Government officials of that criminal country denied the crimes they had committed, and the victims or victim countries have not received any compensation. This has formed an actual crime. Any commitments and documents made by any country or citizen to criminal countries and war criminal countries like Japan in the past are all abolished. This criminal country and war criminal country must bear all compensation for war losses, even if it takes 100,000 years to compensate. Any country, such as Japan, that fails to severely punish all criminals and families that have benefited from crimes and fails to fully compensate victims and victim countries must be disintegrated and reorganized, and forced to compensate the families of victims and victim countries with land. The restructured criminal country must also bear all liability and obligations for compensation.</p>

22	The international community and the United Nations should form the following conventions on the control of war criminal countries and criminal countries as mentioned above, and amend the constitutions of various countries.
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Fig. 85-23-20-1.

日本否认南京大屠杀！日本对华实施认知作战，正攻破我们心灵防线

Japan denies the Nanjing Massacre! Japan is implementing cognitive warfare against China and is breaking through our psychological defenses. 2023-04-18. <https://www.163.com/dy/article/I2L2KA320536HVG.N.html>

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In fact, the Japanese invaders massacred at least 500,000–650,000 people. Some evidence left in the documents destroyed by the Japanese army is that in the two months before and after the Nanjing Massacre, the population fell by 785,000 people.

Is Japan a peace-loving country?

Are the Japanese really peace-loving?

Are the Japanese not extremely evil?

Hasn't Japan been deceiving the Nobel Peace Prize Committee for a long time?

Fig. 85-23-20-2.

日本否认南京大屠杀！日本对华实施认知作战，正攻破我们心灵防线

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Evil Japan =evil Japanese = EastAsianPoisoner = East AsianDrugDealer

The total revenue from opium trafficking in China by the Japanese aggressors after their invasion amounted to at least **353,682,875 US dollars** (calculated in terms of the value of the US dollar at that time).

The Japanese invaders established a complete industry chain of planting, producing, and trafficking opium in Northeast China. After the Russo-Japanese War, the Russian forces were expelled from the Liaodong Peninsula in China by Japan. Subsequently, the Japanese invaders established the "Kwantung Governor-General's Office" in Qingdao region of China in 1905 and established a colonial government called the "Kwantung State." Based on this "Kwantung State", the Japanese invaders established a complete industrial chain of planting, producing, and trafficking opium in Northeast China, poisoning the Chinese people and extracting huge profits from drug trafficking.

Table 2. Fifteen questions for the Japanese people triggered by the Japanese people and the Japanese government falsely claiming to be victims of the Hiroshima atomic bombing and stealing the Nobel Peace Prize.

	Fifteen questions to question Japan
1	If one wants a dog to change its nature of eating feces, why doesn't Japan compensate all the losses to the Chinese victims?
2	Why doesn't Japan prohibit the descendants of any World War II war criminals and criminals from participating in any political and government work for the next one hundred thousand years?
3	Why, after World War II, didn't it limit the potential war - making population, but instead lowered the marriage and childbearing age to 13 years old?
4	Why does Japan continue to expand its military strength?
5	Why does Japan, knowing full well that the psychological warfare of atomic bomb explosions could not have been carried out by the US military alone, still pretend to tell the world that Japan is a victim of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki?
6	Why do countless Japanese people, knowing full well that the radiation from the atomic bomb explosions is huge and that the radioactive elements in the epicenter have a very long half - life and that humans cannot live there even after 100 years, still pretend to tell the world that Japan is a victim of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki?
7	Why does Japan, knowing full well that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were psychological warfare carried out by both Japan and the United States and that the U.S. military did not actually drop atomic bombs on Japan, still have many so - called survivors of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki?
8	Why has Japan for a long time fabricated a large number of false testimonies of so - called survivors of the atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki?
9	Why has Japan long - term used a large number of false testimonies of so -

	called survivors of the atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki to deceive the international community and the Nobel Peace Prize Committee?
10	Why do Japanese government officials, knowing that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were fake, deceive the global public for a long time?
11	Why do professors in Japan's university academic circles, knowing that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are fake, deceive the global public for a long time?
12	Why do the people in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan, know that the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are fake, deceive the global public for a long time? Only when all Japanese people participate in the fraud can the psychological warfare of the atomic bombings deceive the global public
13	Why have the so - called survivors of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki in Japan long deceived the world peace organizations and stolen the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize?
14	<p>Why, having plundered huge amounts of wealth from China, does Japan still use the so - called survivors of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki to deceive world peace organizations in the 21st century and successfully steal the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize? Why do the Japanese even want to steal this amount of money?</p> <p>There are two common Chinese sayings: It's easy to change rivers and mountains but hard to change a person's or a nation's nature. Can a dog stop eating shit? (中国有两句俗语：江山易改本性难移。狗改不吃屎?)</p>
15	<p>Dogs don't defecate in their own dens. Wild boars don't defecate in their own dens either.</p> <p>Why does Japan keep discharging nuclear - contaminated water into the sea, where human beings live?</p> <p>Since Japan has discharged nuclear - contaminated water into the sea, large - scale accumulations of dead fish, stretching for several kilometers, have appeared on some Japanese seashores.</p>

	Table S8. Question those "saints" and law makers who ignore the pain of victims.
1	If you are a non-violent person, would you be willing to try, just to see if you or your family can bear one or two of the hundreds of cruel tortures used by the evil and inhumane Japanese against the Chinese people? Would you reconsider your perception of Japan after that? Can you test your true abilities? Can you test how many days or a week you can tolerate?
2	If you are a "saint" or unconsciously imagine yourself as a "saint", ignoring the pain of the victims, and you want to formulate policies for the benefit of the criminals, what reason do you have to formulate or randomly advocate policies for pardoning criminals without experiencing the tragic and painful experiences of the victims?
3	If you are truly a "saint", you must make yourself and all your family members experience the same tragic and painful experiences as the victims, and for the

	<p>same length of time. Otherwise, you are nothing but crap in front of justice. Suppose the victim has been robbed of \$10 million or \$100 million worth of property and the criminal has squandered it. Will the victim demand that you give all the assets of you and those of your family to the victim?</p> <p>If you can't, could you be a "saint"? You must or should be an evil accomplice of criminals, specifically trying to mislead the government into formulating wrong policies and disrupting social order.</p>
4	<p>How many officials and military officers do you know have been bribed by the evil Japanese with looted Chinese gold and jewelry?</p> <p>Who knows how many babies the evil and despicable anti-human Japanese killed in China, and how many baby carriages they have stolen?</p>
5	<p>Japan, on the surface, was a defeated country in World War II. However, it had actually emerged as a victor through extensive looting and massacres, amassing a vast amount of wealth. It never compensated China for the colossal losses it inflicted upon them.</p>

1	Have evil Japanese people been severely punished by the law?
2	Have evil Japanese people compensated for the massive wealth they looted from China?
3	How many countries in the world today uphold justice?
4	Do you still believe that the law must be fair?
5	Do you still believe that the law can definitely punish criminals severely?
6	Invading a country, killing innocent civilians, raping and gang raping women and pregnant women, and not executing the criminals. Does the law severely punish the criminals? Is this law just? If you think it is just, then what if the criminals kill all the members of your family, rape your wife and daughter, and the law made by your country doesn't severely punish the criminals either?
7	Don't you think the justice of the law lags far behind atrocities?
8	Don't you think it's necessary to quickly and thoroughly reform the current legal system?
9	Don't you think victims must participate in legislation?
10	Don't you think victims must lead legislation?
11	If you think that heinous criminals can be forgiven, please let your entire family experience three types of torture in Japan for two months?
12	If you think that heinous criminals can be forgiven, please let your entire family experience being raped and gang-raped by Japanese people, followed by being stabbed in the vagina or anus with a bayonet?
13	Isn't murder a crime that should be pursued over the long term?
14	Aren't rape and gang rape crimes that should be pursued over the long term?
15	Doesn't the United States pursue murder as a long-term crime?
16	Doesn't the United States pursue rape and gang rape as long-term crimes?

17	<p>From the point of view of the logic of American law, doesn't the United States pursue killers and rapists / gang rapists permanently? Isn't it illegal for killers and rapists / gang rapists to transfer the wealth they plundered to the next generation or their war - criminal - affiliated countries, rather than being legal? If you think it is legal and still enjoy the property plundered from the victims after killing and raping, then you are also a killer, a rapist / gang - rapist, and a robber, and any just person can execute these evil criminals.</p>
18	<p>Evil Japanese invaders looted at least 42,000 tons of gold, 500 tons of natural diamonds, 1,000 tons of platinum, 250 million silver dollars, 10 million cultural artifacts, 20 million gemstones, 1.23 billion tons of food, 1.06 billion tons of coal, 700 million cubic meters of natural gas, and 200 million tons of rare earth minerals from China. After 70 years, has all of this become legitimate Japanese assets?</p> <p>Do you know the value of these materials in US dollars?</p> <p>The Japanese aggressors destroyed at least 300 million houses and ancient buildings, do you know their value?</p> <p>Evil Japanese military massacred at least 51.8-89.6 (100.80) million Chinese people and raped at least 31.45-54.4 (61.20) million Chinese women, based on 14 years alone, the total number of rapes and gang rapes against Chinese women is estimated to be at least 6.13 billion times, while Japan itself suffered only around 3 million casualties.</p> <p>Do you think Japan was the defeated or victorious country in World War II?</p> <p>If this is considered legal, please store \$10 million in cash and 1,000 kilograms of gold in your own home, and then announce to the world that anyone who plundered it and kept it for 70 years is considered legal. How about that?</p>
19	<p>If you were a judge, and you did not support severe punishment for murderers or compensating all losses caused by murder, including property damage, would you be willing to publicly declare all of your assets online? Would you be willing to experience yourself or your entire family being killed by someone else? If you are not willing, then where is your sense of justice? Why have you chosen to pursue this profession? Are criminals providing you with comfortable living conditions in exchange for their funds?</p> <p>Why do you use antiseptics or antiviral medications when you experience bacterial infections or severe viral infections? Why don't you allow the bacteria or viruses that like your body to grow even better? By killing these living organisms and suppressing these non-living entities, aren't you committing a crime or seriously going against God's will?</p> <p>Shouldn't you go to hell for that?</p> <p>If you are a Christian, a Catholic, or a follower of Judaism,</p> <p>If you are a politician,</p> <p>If you are a media practitioner,</p> <p>If you are a company leader,</p> <p>If you are a father, if you are a mother, if you are a son,</p> <p>Would you be willing to let your parents be infected with living bacteria and</p>

	viruses and let them continue to grow? Don't you want to kill the bacteria and viruses that cause severe infections in your body? If you and your family were such people, you wouldn't need health insurance, never have to go to the hospital, and never need to take any medication, even in the case of severe infections, fractures, or cerebral or myocardial infarctions.
20	Do you still believe that the 21 st century is a civilized era for humanity?
21	Will the symbol of human civilization still be the possession of words, castles, and bronze vessels?
22	If you view civilization this way, don't you think you are very narrow and shallow?
23	Will the symbol of humanity entering the era of civilization still be the possession of the Internet, AI, cell phone, castles, and intelligent rice cookers?
24	Will the symbol of human civilization still be the possession of iPhone15, F16 fighter jets, castles, and intelligent washing machines?
25	What kind of mechanisms and social system do you think should be established for crime prevention and punishment of criminals?

Warvigilance:

Table S5. Re-evaluate Japan's social system from the fact that Japanese prime ministers have long been worshipping war criminals at Yasukuni Shrine.

<p>Prime Minister who visited Yasukuni Shrine from 1945 to 2001</p> <p>Japan is the world's largest war criminal state, responsible for killing at least 50 million people. However, to this day, Japan still enshrine 2.325 million war criminals and criminals from World War II and the Pacific War at Yasukuni Shrine, which accounts for 94% of the total number of dead spirits.</p> <p>During World War II, Yasukuni Shrine served as the departure site for the Kamikaze Special Attack Corps, which launched attacks against American aircraft carriers. Even now, there are often Japanese WWII veterans, including former child soldiers and members of Taiwan's indigenous Kaohsiung Volunteer Corps, who hold various memorial activities there, identifying themselves as former soldiers of the Imperial Japanese Army. They dress in WWII-era Japanese military uniforms, march in formation, and chant slogans of militarism. Therefore, Yasukuni Shrine is also considered one of the spiritual sanctuaries of Japanese militarists.</p> <p>Additionally, Yasukuni Shrine has many monuments. On one of the reliefs on a corner of a monument, although it is blurry, if observed very carefully, it depicts the China-Japanese War of 1894-1895, and another depicts the Japanese military's attack on Shanghai during the Second China-Japanese War, attacking Chinese troops at that time. These are commemorative objects that existed before the end of World War II, and were not established after the war.</p> <p>However, because their content praises how the Imperial Japanese Army fought "heroically," they are considered unconstitutional for government leaders to officially visit Yasukuni Shrine according to the principle of separation of religion and politics in the Japanese constitution. However, conservative forces</p>
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have long been determined to break through this barrier.

In October 1951, Prime Minister Yoshida Shigeru, along with Cabinet members and leaders of both houses of parliament, officially visited Yasukuni Shrine. Since then, almost every Prime Minister has visited Yasukuni Shrine, although very few have done so openly as Prime Minister on August 15 (the day of Japan's defeat in the war).

From 1945 to 2021, part of the Prime Ministers who visited Yasukuni Shrine were as follows:

On August 15, 1975, Prime Minister Takeo Miki visited Yasukuni Shrine for the first time in a "personal capacity."

On August 15, 1978, Prime Minister Fukuda Takeo visited Yasukuni Shrine as the Prime Minister of the Cabinet.

In 1982, Japanese Prime Minister Takeo Fukuda went to Yasukuni Shrine to offer sacrifices and pay respects in the name of "Prime Minister of the Cabinet."

On August 15, 1985, Prime Minister Nakasone Yasuhiro officially visited Yasukuni Shrine in his official capacity.

On July 29, 1996, former Prime Minister Ryutaro Hashimoto visited Yasukuni Shrine on his own birthday.

On August 13, 2001, current Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine as the Prime Minister.

Japanese Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine on April 21, 2002.

Japanese Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine on January 14, 2003.

Japanese Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine on January 1, 2004.

Japanese Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine on October 17, 2005..

Japanese Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi visited Yasukuni Shrine on August 15, 2006.

On December 26, 2013, Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe visited Yasukuni Shrine.

On December 26, 2014, on the occasion of the first anniversary of taking office, Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe brazenly visited Yasukuni Shrine, where Class-A war criminals of World War II are enshrined.

Since October 17, 2020, Yasukuni Shrine has held the so-called autumn grand festival. Japanese Prime Minister Yoshihide Suga offered sacrifices at Yasukuni Shrine on the 17th.

Former Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe visited Yasukuni Shrine on the morning of October 19,

2020. On August 15, 2021, former Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe visited Yasukuni Shrine on the morning of the 15th.

<http://news.sohu.com/51/59/news200555951.shtml>

http://www.xinhuanet.com/world/2016-08/17/c_129236709.htm

http://www.chinadaily.com.cn/hqzx/2013-12/27/content_17200778.htm

There are two common Chinese sayings: It's easy to change rivers and mountains but hard to change a person's or a nation's nature. Can a dog stop eating shit? (中国有两句俗语：江山易改本性难移。狗改不吃屎?)

34.9. A reclassification of past, present and future social systems from historical and philosophical perspectives.

Karl Marx identified and planned six social systems. However, Marx's classification of social systems is too simple and abstract. The social systems of different countries in past history and reality are far from Marx's simple classification, which leads to difficulties in identification and cognition.

In addition, in some so-called socialist countries, the ruling party disguises itself as a communist party with the lofty ideal of achieving human equality. But it greedily seeks assistance from other countries and in turn massacres the descendants of the aiding country or ethnic minorities or people of that country or other countries, or carries out piratical plundering of the wealth of the people of other countries or their descendants. Some countries disguise themselves as democratic countries and slaughter or plunder the wealth of the people of other countries or their descendants at certain times. Some countries like to commit fraud. They use national government institutions and the military to protect criminals for a long time to carry out large-scale fraud or gang rape, or to protect the live harvesting of human organs for a long time, or to protect the massacre of ethnic minorities for a long time and carry out piratical plundering of wealth. Furthermore, the social systems of some countries will change dynamically. A country may have two or more systems at the same time. The social system in some countries may be in decline and retrogression. Therefore, it is very necessary to reclassify social systems according to their characteristics.

At least human social systems can be classified into multiple social systems according to various characteristics, moral levels, and whether they are piratical plundering countries, so that the systems of these countries can be quickly identified. Specific examples are as follows: **The reclassification of human social systems like an encyclopaedia.**

Table 3. Reclassification of past, present, and future social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives

Classification of human social systems	Country
Primitive society	
Slave society	
Semi-slave society	
Feudal society	
Semi-feudal society	
Semi-feudal and semi-colonial society	
Capitalist Society	
Semi-feudal and semi-capitalist society	

Socialist society: In a socialist society, land and assets are implemented under state public ownership or collective ownership, and distributed according to work.	Early Soviet Union
A society of piracy under warlord centralization.	
A semi-piratical society under the centralization of political parties and the military.	
Semi-pirate society with centralized power of political parties.	Vietnam
Semi-pirate society with centralized power of multiple parties.	
Semi-pirate society with decentralized power of multiple parties.	
Semi-pirate society with centralized power and electoral system of multiple parties.	
Semi-pirate society with decentralized power and electoral system of multiple parties.	
Semi-pirate society with centralized power and electoral system of the military.	
Semi-pirate society with centralized power of warlords.	
Semi-pirate society with centralized power of warlords and electoral system of multiple parties.	
Semi-pirate society with centralized power of the military and electoral system of multiple parties.	
A semi-piratical society with multi-party elections where the military centralizes power and warlords decentralize power.	Myanmar
A semi-slave and semi-piratical society with multi-party elections where the military centralizes power and warlords decentralize power.	Myanmar
Semi-pirate society with electoral system of multiple parties.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties and families.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties, families and plutocrats.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties, families, plutocrats, and religious groups.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties, families, plutocrats and the military.	Japan
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties, families, plutocrats, the military, and religious groups.	India
A fraudulent society controlled by multiple political parties, families, plutocrats, military and religious groups through elections.	India
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties, emperors, families and plutocrats.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by multiple parties, emperors, families, plutocrats and the military.	
Semi-pirate society controlled by upper-class people, the military,	

families and plutocrats.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by upper-class people, the military, families and plutocrats.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by upper-class people, the military, and families.	
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by upper-class people, the military, religion, and families.	Indonesia
Electoral semi-pirate society controlled by upper-class people and the military.	
A partly feudal society with a chiefdom federal system controlled by families.	
A semi-feudal society with a chiefdom federal system.	
A feudal society in which politics and religion are integrated and controlled by families.	
A feudal monarchy society under the combination of politics and religion controlled by families.	
A semi-feudal society where politics and religion are integrated and controlled by families and monarchs.	
A feudal society under the combination of politics and religion controlled by families and religious groups.	
A semi-feudal society with the integration of politics and religion controlled by families and religious groups.	
Centralization of power by the emperor, prefecture-county system, semi-slavery society.	
Centralization of power by the emperor, prefecture-county system, partial slavery society.	Qing dynasty
Decentralization of power by the emperor, prefecture-county system, semi-slavery society.	
Decentralization of power by the emperor, prefecture-county system, partial slavery society	
Society controlled by families, plutocrats, emperor, and religious groups.	
A multi-party electoral society without the equal-field system.	
A multi-party electoral society controlled by the military and without the equal-field system.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties and families.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, families, and plutocrats.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, families, and the military.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, families, tribes, and the military.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, families, plutocrats,	

and religious groups.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, families, plutocrats, emperor, and religious groups.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, families, plutocrats and the military.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, emperors, families and plutocrats.	
Electoral society controlled by multiple parties, emperors, families, plutocrats and the military.	
A multi-party electoral society controlled by families, plutocrats, the military, religious groups, and featuring elements of capitalism, socialism, communism , and piracy.	Israel
A society with imperial decentralization and morality above all.	
A society with imperial decentralization and morality above all.	
A society with imperial centralization, decentralized power in prefectures and counties, and morality above all.	
A society where the emperor centralizes power, has a county and prefecture system, and an equal-field system, and where morality is paramount.	
A society with imperial centralization where evil forces can be severely punished.	
Party centralized new equal-field system empathetic society.	
Party decentralized new equal-field system empathetic society.	
A multi-party electoral society with the equal-field system.	
Consultative society of the new equal-field system with centralized power of political party.	
The new equal-field system version: A society of empathy with the new equal-field system version 3.0 or above optimized and improved from the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty, or a society with socialism with Chinese characteristics (Current: new equal-field system version 4.0). For short, it is called the society of the new equal-field system version 4.0,4.5,5.0,6.0,7.0,8.0,9.0, X. etc. When X approaches infinity or a certain number, at this time, in a society with highly abundant material supply and a very equalized material distribution, and where people's moral characters are all very noble, it may be called a communist society.	China
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist controlled by political parties and the military.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist with morality as the supreme principle and controlled by political parties and the military.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, with empathy as the paramount principle and controlled by political	

parties and the military.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, controlled by political parties and the military, with empathy as the supreme principle and a strong negative feedback mechanism.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, with empathy as the paramount principle and controlled by political parties.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, with empathy as the paramount principle and controlled by multiple political parties and the military.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, controlled by multiple political parties and the military, with empathy as the supreme principle and a strong negative feedback mechanism.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, controlled by multiple political parties and the military.	
A society partly capitalist, partly socialist and partly communist, controlled by multiple political parties.	
A society with morality above all under the political party system.	
A society with morality above all under the multi-party system.	
A society with democracy and morality above all under the political party system.	
A society with democracy and morality above all under the multi-party system.	
A society with a political party system that advocates morality and severely punishes evil.	
A society with a multi-party system that advocates morality and severely punishes evil.	
A society with political parties, democracy, advocating morality and severely punishing evil.	
A society with multiple parties, democracy, advocating morality and severely punishing evil.	
A society based on morality and empathy without political parties or emperors.	
<p>Civilized society: Definition of civilization: Respect life and severely punish criminals. Let the weak not be fearful, the strong not be arrogant, power not be haughty. Let the incompetent voluntarily step aside. Let the immoral occupy fewer public offices. Let the mediocre make fewer decisions. Let the virtuous and capable not waste their talents. Let the wicked be afraid to do evil. Let the kind people be safe. Make society fairer and more just. Make society full of vitality and let people have inner peace. Let there be education in childhood, learning in adolescence, medical care when sick, support and</p>	India Indonesia Philippines Vietnam (Some countries that must be restructured)

<p>guarantee when unemployed, support for the elderly. Basic family housing does not need to be taxed. Everyone respects each other. Let the operation of the government be based on a negative feedback mechanism.</p> <p>The world should re-establish global political and judicial systems according to the new definition of civilization and rebuild some countries that have lost empathy and morality, so as to re-build a new situation of national and global governance.</p> <p>In the right - hand frame are the societies and countries that need to consider restructuring.</p>	
<p>Communist society</p> <p>A social system in which land and assets are implemented under state public ownership or collective ownership, and individual and family consumption expenditures are distributed according to needs. This can be implemented regionally or in partial areas.</p>	

Definition of a semi-pirate country or a semi-feudal or semi-slave country:

Whenever there is an opportunity, the army or people of these countries will carry out large-scale looting of the legal land of other countries or others, large-scale looting of the wealth of other countries or others (gold, silver, diamonds, platinum, cultural relics, jewels, chickens, ducks, cattle, sheep, pigs, horses), large-scale looting of the resources of other countries or others (automobile production lines, steel mills, rare earths, iron ore, pig iron, steel, bronze, copper mines, kaolin, zinc mines, salt, coal, grain, rubber, tungsten mines, caustic soda, soda ash, etc.), large-scale rape, gang rape, and forcing women of other countries to be sex slaves (To cover up its ugly crimes, this country names sex slaves as comfort women). Occupying the territory of other countries in violation of history. During the war, encourage women in their own countries to become military prostitutes (To cover up its ugliness, this country names military prostitutes as comfort women). After the defeat, encourage women in their own countries to become prostitutes to serve the soldiers of other countries (To cover up its ugliness, this country names prostitutes as comfort women). Massively counterfeiting the currency of the victimized country. Planting opium on a large scale in the victimized country. Transport opium on a large scale to the victimized country. Encourage people to plant opium on a large scale. Force ethnic minority areas of other countries to form countries in violation of history. Force ethnic minority areas of other countries to form countries in violation of agreements. Force ethnic minorities to be inferior ethnic groups (there is an obvious difference between ID cards and the main ethnic group), deprive ethnic minorities of their rights and interests, bomb ethnic minority gathering places, wage long-term wars with ethnic minority areas, use compulsory or semi-compulsory means to destroy the culture and customs of ethnic minority areas, invade other countries and destroy houses, bury people alive, remove human organs alive, commit crimes such as massacres, torture, kidnapping, and massacres. If one to three of these crimes are committed, or the army and government of that country act as umbrellas for the above-mentioned criminal acts and do not

severely punish the criminals, punish a small number of criminals with very low crimes, do not fully compensate the losses of victims, and have not yet fully compensated the losses of victims and the affected country.

Table 4. Reclassification of past, present, and future social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives (Continued Table 3). The reclassification of human social systems like an encyclopaedia.

Reclassification of Human social systems	Country
Partially slave society of fraud combination.	Myanmar
Partially feudal society of fraud combination.	
Partially capitalist society of fraud combination.	
Fraud-combined society with false democracy and no empathy.	
Fraud-combined war-type society.	
Society with a social system of underworld model.	
Society with a semi-underworld model.	
Society with a partial underworld model.	Myanmar
Society with a partial underworld model under multi-party system.	
Multi-party, externally plundering, false democratic society.	
Multi-party, externally plundering society.	
Multi-party election society controlled by elites with no conscience, implementing war and threats externally.	
Party-type institutional society controlled by elites that implements war and threats externally.	
A society of ethnic discrimination that combines different ethnic groups through fraud and suppresses through war and policies.	Myanmar
A loose society of ethnic discrimination that combines different indigenous ethnic groups through fraud and suppresses through war and policies.	Myanmar
Capitalist society of interest combination.	
Capitalist society of interest combination with no empathy.	
Society of interest combination with no empathy and no conscience.	
Capitalist society of interest combination with no empathy and no conscience.	
A society of racial discrimination that obtains territory by defrauding other ethnic groups and then forms a country through military suppression combinations.	Myanmar
A society of racial discrimination that forms a country by fraudulently forcing combinations of other ethnic groups and suppressing policies.	Myanmar
A society with military repression that fraudulently obtains the territory of other indigenous ethnic groups and then forms a country through violent combinations.	
A society of racial discrimination that forms a country by fraudulently forcing combinations of different indigenous ethnic groups.	

A society of racial discrimination that forms a country by forcing combinations of different indigenous ethnic groups.	
A society of racial discrimination with multi - party elections that forms a country by forcing combinations of different indigenous ethnic groups.	
A society of racial discrimination with violent suppression after annexing the territories of other indigenous ethnic groups.	India
A multi - party society with violent repression after annexing the territories of other indigenous ethnic groups.	
A society of racial discrimination and habitual lying with multi - party elections and violent combinations after annexing other countries.	India
A society that likes to annex the territories of other countries, has multi - party elections, lacks empathy, and is racially discriminatory.	
A society that likes to annex the territories of other indigenous peoples, forces combinations, has multi - party elections, is good at fraud, and is racially discriminatory.	India
A society that is accustomed to annexing the territories of other countries by force, has multi - party elections, lacks empathy, and is racially discriminatory.	India
<p>The devilish society that is fond of taking over the bodies of all the people in a country through immigration and occupying its territory.</p> <p>A large number of Indians are demonstrating and shouting in Canada: "We Indians are the masters of Canada, and the whites are the invaders. Whites, go back to Europe! We call on India to send troops to stations in Canada." If the world does not try to quickly control the population growth of India and the Indian diaspora overseas, in the future, Indians will become the population that initiates the most wars in the world. If the countries around the world still do not prohibit any weapon technologies and advanced industrial technologies from being imported into India, then the achievements in manufacturing and the growth of India's military strength will all become the capital for India to launch large-scale wars in the future, and large-scale wars among humans will inevitably occur.</p> <p>The indigenous peoples of North America are descendants of the Chinese people. They have lived in North America for at least 4,000 years. Many cultural relics unearthed in North America and the customs of the indigenous peoples of North America can prove this. When China was powerful in ancient times, it did not take the initiative to invade other countries. When Zheng He made voyages to the Western Seas, what he brought was civilization. Nowadays, the so-called missionaries in the West have fabricated the so-called Indian civilization, ancient Egyptian civilization, ancient Greek civilization, ancient Babylonian civilization, ancient Roman civilization and Mesopotamian civilization that did not exist in the past at all, which</p>	India

<p>has messed up the ideological systems of the whole world. The only civilization on earth is Chinese civilization. Humans didn't evolve from apes at all, and Darwin's theory is completely wrong.</p>	
<p>A devil society will come to possess someone else's body.</p>	<p>India</p>
<p>A society that attempts to seize the entire territory of Canada.</p> <p>A large number of Indians are demonstrating and shouting in Canada: "We Indians are the masters of Canada, and the whites are the invaders. Whites, go back to Europe! We call on India to send troops to stations in Canada."</p> <p>Recently, about 2 million Indians have immigrated to Canada in a single year. In a large community alone, a demonstration parade consisting of over 80,000 Indians was formed, which is roughly equivalent to the strength of eight divisions. As long as they were equipped with weapons and equipment, Indians could immediately form forces equivalent to at least 30 divisions in Canada.</p> <p>After occupying Canada, the warm regions of the United States and South America will be the second and third targets for large-scale immigration infiltration and occupation by greedy, evil and fraudulent Indians.</p> <p>At least 40 million Americans have been affected by fraudulent calls made by Indians through telecommunications fraud.</p> <p>A country that possesses nuclear weapons, lacks moral principles and is fond of carrying out large-scale telecommunications fraud is the greatest disaster for humanity and the country that is most likely to launch nuclear weapons attacks. It is necessary to control the population of these evil countries and prohibit any advanced technologies from flowing into them.</p>	<p>India</p>
<p>In 1962, when India's military strength was still weak, the Indian government and Indian Prime Minister Nehru dispatched troops to forcibly occupy Chinese territory. Before starting a war against China, they put forward the following five tough demands for peace negotiations, almost seizing half of China's territory. According to their terms, if through peaceful negotiations, China had to cede half of its territory to India, otherwise India would wage war against China.</p> <p>Is India a society composed of normal human beings?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tibet belongs to India. 2. Parts of Xinjiang belong to India. 3. India stations troops in Chengdu. 4. China is not allowed to set up defenses and station troops in Shaanxi. 5. India continue to pose a threat to Beijing. <p>Could an arrogant, greedy, likes large-scale fraud, belligerent country that has been established for less than a hundred years give birth to an ancient civilization????? What is civilization????? Is the</p>	<p>India</p>

<p>definition of civilization simply determined by the three elements set by Westerners????? Unless you suffer from dementia and have been brainwashed by fake missionaries (Their true identities are thieves of ancient Chinese science, technology and culture. They fabricated a large number of famous figures in Europe and Egypt who had neither parents, nor tombstones, nor descendants. A large number of fake cultural relics unearthed in Egypt and Europe are used to deceive the public and distort history. Perhaps for these fake cultural relics that are collected, even 5 euros for each one would be too expensive.) in Europe who fabricated civilizations.</p> <p>In the future, once India's military strength increases, it will become the center of global war and one of the greediest and most evil forces in the world. If India is not dismantled and forced to give up the land it has occupied from other countries, a future nuclear war might be triggered by the Indians.</p> <p>Whenever Indians enter any company, usually a group of them will come in, form cliques and disrupt the whole company.</p>	
<p>An evil and extremely bad religious society that has been able to carry out large-scale telecommunication fraud activities against the people of the permanent members of the United Nations Security Council for four consecutive years, with an average annual fraud amount of at least \$5 billion. However, it cannot be excluded that a very small number of people in it are good people.</p>	India
<p>An evil and extremely bad religious society that has been able to carry out large-scale telecommunication fraud activities against the people of the permanent members of the United Nations Security Council and another country for four consecutive years, with an average annual fraud amount of at least \$ 6 billion. However, it cannot be excluded that a very small number of people in it are good people.</p> <p>Doesn't the Western theoretical community believe that there is a severe overpopulation on Earth?</p> <p>Is it necessary for a large number of criminals in this evil society to exist in humanity?</p>	India
<p>A society with a super-large criminal religious organization or religious group</p> <p>Definition of a super-large criminal religious organization or religious group: It places religion or religious beliefs above the morality, ethics, conscience, and empathy that normal, kind-hearted people possess. It takes advantage of the so-called religious beliefs and the freedom of religious belief, uses religious doctrines to numb individuals, gathers individuals who share the same so-called specific religious belief, raises the so-called anti-racism slogan, commits large-scale</p>	India

<p>crimes (such as large-scale telecommunication fraud, or large-scale rape and gang rape crimes, large-scale kidnapping of women, students and children to be used as sex slaves, large-scale torture of the kidnapped, large-scale live organ harvesting from the kidnapped, large-scale massacre of victims, or build telecommunication fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zone for a large number of criminals, or not abiding by agreements, constantly launching civil wars and annexing the territories of indigenous peoples who hoped for normal rights, or constantly waging civil wars, oppressing and wiping out ethnic minorities who are trying to obtain normal rights), or accumulates a population advantage through the large-scale immigration or long-term immigration of these individuals, drives away the original inhabitants, seizes part of the territory of other countries, attempts to seize the entire territory of other countries, or annex another country with military force, or seize the territory that historically belonged to other countries, or it has already annexed another country by military force since the establishment of the United Nations, or takes advantage of the so-called democratic election rules and the so-called democratic voting advantage brought by a large population to seize the political power or the right to speak of other countries, and forcibly changes the culture or customs of the original inhabitants. Such religious organizations or religious groups are evil.</p>	
<p>A society with a super-large criminal country-type underworld society Definition of a super-large criminal country-type underworld society: A society that commits large-scale crimes, such as large-scale telecommunication fraud, large-scale rape and gang rape crimes, large-scale kidnapping of women, students and children to be used as sex slaves, large-scale torture of the kidnapped, large-scale live organ harvesting from the kidnapped, large-scale massacre of victims, or build telecommunication fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zone for a large number of criminals, or annex another country with military force, or not abiding by agreements, constantly launching civil wars and annexing the territories of indigenous peoples who hoped for normal rights, or constantly waging civil wars, oppressing and wiping out ethnic minorities who are trying to obtain normal rights, or seize the territory that historically belonged to other countries, or the heinous crimes of forcing sex slaves to give birth to babies, setting up human milk factories, and creating sources of newly born human organs such as corneas and skin, or accumulates a population advantage through the large-scale immigration or long-term immigration of these individuals, drives away the original inhabitants, seizes part of the territory of other countries, attempts to seize the</p>	<p>India Indonesia Japan Myanmar Vietnam</p>

entire territory of other countries, or annex another country with military force, or seize the territory that historically belonged to other countries, but in the name of a country or ethnic group, has seemingly legal military and police institutions, can legally purchase weapons from other countries, and can be protected by the rules of the United Nations! It also legally uses various weapons to attack people's armed organizations that fight criminal gangs that are committing large-scale crimes.	
A society that is bound to wage aggressive wars, carry out massacres, start civil wars, commit rapes and gang rapes, plunder the wealth of civilians or annex the territory of other countries as long as its economy and military strength grow.	India Indonesia, Japan, Myanmar the Philippines Vietnam
A society that needs to be deterred by force and dares not carry out large-scale massacres, rapes and gang rapes, or plunder the wealth of civilians anymore.	Indonesia, Japan, Myanmar the Philippines Vietnam
A society with a system that puts profit first and condones drug proliferation.	Myanmar
A society with a system that puts profit first and condones drug proliferation and human trafficking.	Myanmar
A society that puts profit first and condones drug proliferation, kidnapping, and harvesting of live organisms.	
A society that puts profit first and condones drug proliferation, kidnapping, and rape or gang rape.	Myanmar
A society that puts profit first and condones drug proliferation and gambling.	Myanmar
A society that puts profit first and condones and encourages gambling.	
A society that puts profit first and condones and encourages getting something for nothing.	
A society that puts profit first and has drug proliferation, kidnapping, rape or gang - rape, and live - organ harvesting.	Myanmar
A society that puts profit first, builds a large number of fraud - related parks, conducts large - scale fraud, kidnapping, rape or gang rape, live - organ harvesting, and has the government and military secretly protecting crimes.	Myanmar
A society that puts profit first, builds a large number of beautiful fraud - related parks, conducts large - scale fraud, and has the government and military secretly protecting crimes.	Myanmar
A society that has long kidnapped women, raped and gang-raped	Myanmar

them, and used them as cows after they become pregnant and give birth.	
A society with false democracy and lacking empathy.	India
A multi - party electoral society with no conscience and no empathy for the outside world.	
A society with no conscience, no empathy towards the outside and without being bound by the same laws.	
A discriminatory society with no conscience, no empathy and not following the same legal system.	
A religion - based society with no conscience, no empathy for the outside world, and not following the same legal system.	India
A society that has developed specific judicial systems and habitually uses lawyers to earn high incomes by reducing the sentences of criminals or acquitting the guilty innocent.	
A society that, after carrying out mass killings, mass rapes and gang rapes, and plundering huge amounts of wealth, lurks or remains silent while waiting for an opportunity to commit crimes again.	Indonesia, Vietnam
A society that, after implementing large - scale immigration, uses massacres or drugs to plunder huge amounts of wealth and then remains silent while waiting for an opportunity to start a war.	Japan
A society that, through large - scale immigration, plundering or seizing the lands of other countries by trickery, carrying out large - scale massacres, using drugs to disable indigenous people, and plundering huge amounts of wealth, then remains silent while waiting for an opportunity to start a war.	Japan
A society that likes to carry out mass killings, mass rapes and gang rapes, plunder huge amounts of wealth, and then lurk or remain silent while waiting for an opportunity to start a war.	Japan
A society that formulates legal systems, resulting in the default of cooperative exporters and plundering huge amounts of wealth by insidious seemingly legal means.	India
A society that likes to use religion to create contradictions, conflicts and confrontations.	
A society that likes to create super lies on a global scale and deceives the global public for a long time, including fabricating being bombed by atomic bombs that, in fact, never happened.	Japan
A predatory society that likes to violate common historical knowledge, occupies the territory of other countries with its army, and then claims it as its own territory without any sense of shame.	India Indonesia, Japan, the Philippines Vietnam
Caste discrimination society	India
A society disguised as a joint-stock company of a country.	
A consortium society disguised as a country.	South

	Korea
A society that takes it as an honor to defraud Americans of their wealth.	India
A society that takes it as an honor to defraud Americans of their wealth to the fullest extent through telecommunications fraud.	India
A society that has defrauded more than 50 million Americans of their wealth.	India
A greedy society that takes it as an honor to annex a long-existing innocent country and its wealth to the greatest extent by force.	India
A society that parents have always taught their descendants that 'people have a mouth for two reasons, one is to eat, and the other is to lie'.	India
A greedy, dishonest, heartless, and evil society. In the society, the richest person owes more than ten billion CNY to the Bank of China and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank but does not repay it. They can spend hundreds of millions CNY to buy luxury yachts and private jets, yet they say they have no money to repay. However, the people of this country regard those who can fraudulently obtain huge loans from the international community as idols.	India
In a society where a person, after becoming the captain of an ocean-going ship, deliberately nitpicks and habitually takes at least a 20% or more kickback from suppliers.	India
An evil society that wants to annex Nepal at any time.	India
In an evil society, a female student was raped by thugs. Surprisingly, the teacher said that the girl was also at fault in the rape incident. This is a society with a bizarre way of thinking.	India
A strange society. In this society, Indian girls say that in a rape incident, girls should also be blamed. Girls must have done something wrong to be raped.	India
An Indian student said: When a girl smiles at a boy, the boy feels seduced. This is the reason for rape to occur.	India
A society where a female student being raped because of smiling is regarded as normal.	India
A society without morality and conscience where a female student being raped because of smiling is regarded as normal.	India
A society that likes to rape and gang rape women.	India
An evil society that invades and annexes Pakistani territory.	India
An evil society that has occupied 95,000 square kilometers of Pakistani territory.	India
An evil society that has occupied 93,000 square kilometers of Nepalese territory.	India
An evil society that has occupied 125,000 square kilometers of Chinese territory.	India

A society with a false Thanksgiving.	
A society that randomly and fanatically supports LGBT and LGBTQ. ★	The USA
A society that legislates to encourage the robbery of wealth is extremely abnormal and unjust. Such a society would be plunged into chaos and moral decay.	
<p>A society where legislation encourages the act of robbing wealth within 950 US dollars to be considered innocent.</p> <p>However, some political parties in some countries regard legislation that encourages the robbery of wealth as normal behaviour. Therefore, for any political party and government that enacts such legislation, any act of robbing all members and supporters of that party, especially the property of the top leaders of that party, should logically be legal. All members and supporters of that party should actively hand over the wealth specified by that law to robbers when encountering such robberies. Resisting robbers is instead a crime. The great philosopher, strategist, military strategist, thinker, logician and poet Chairman Mao Zedong said, "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the future trend in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership." This political party has laid a solid legal foundation for the legal robbery of the future of its members and supporters' families. It has made a significant contribution to alleviating the lack of social food. It is an extremely far-sighted political party. The leaders of this political party should tell potential robbers what good things in their homes can be legally robbed. Even after being robbed, all members of their families are forced to go hungry for a day or two.</p>	The USA
The strange society around the world today: Female middle - school students in a country were raped by refugees in a refugee settlement. After being brainwashed by the social system, instead of demanding severe punishment for the criminal refugees, the reason these middle school girls remain silent about being sexually assaulted by refugees is astonishingly that they don't want to ruin the reputation of the refugees. Even more strangely, judicial institutions do not severely punish criminals either.	India
A society where almost everyone is a spy.	Japan
A society that likes to wage aggressive wars. In this country, women like to be sex slaves or comfort women and use their bodies to encourage evil invaders.	Japan
A society that A Nobel Prize-winning academic claimed that his country had infiltrated China in all aspects.	Japan
A society in which the entire nation pretends to be a victim country of atomic bomb explosions and obtains the Nobel Peace Prize	Japan

through perjury and deception.	
A society that took photo showed that the green leaves of two trees in the central area after an atomic bombing still existed and were surprisingly not burned down. Under the irradiation of the high temperature above 6,000 °C in the central area of the atomic bomb explosion, the leaves and branches of the two trees in the pictures were still intact, and this society was cheating the whole world.	Japan
A society with the following system: It is completely impossible for people to live in the central area of an atomic bomb explosion even after a thousand years. Otherwise, all people would inevitably suffer from radiation diseases and die. However, the media in this society spread rumors that within two to three weeks, the radioactive substances in the so-called central area of the atomic bomb explosion in that coastal city were blown away by the sea wind, so the city soon became suitable for people to live in, and now its population exceeds one million.	Japan
A society with the following system: The explosion of an atomic bomb in a city is an extremely serious matter. The severely damaged and heavily polluted area is at least 400 square kilometres. The half-lives of some radioactive substances released by the atomic bomb explosion exceed 10,000 years. It is impossible for people to live in an area of at least 400 square kilometers in this city within 1,000 years. However, both the media and the government in this society falsely claim that it is inhabitable. As a result, the population of this so-called city that was severely contaminated by the atomic bomb explosion now exceeds one million.	Japan
A society where the whole nation and its people has been continuously lying to the global public for almost 80 years about one thing, that is, claiming to be a victim country of the so-called atomic bomb explosion.	Japan
A society that buys land in Brazil with an area more than three times its own territory and attempts to change its country.	Japan
In a society where the son of a country's prime minister gathers members of his political party for a gathering and clamors to destroy the United States with 500 hydrogen bombs.	Japan
A society in which a large number of government lawmakers and the prime minister habitually pay tribute to Japanese war criminals on the day Japan attacked Pearl Harbor.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that forced at least 200,000 Chinese women and children to be sex slavery but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that massacred 51.8 million to100.80 million Chinese people but refused	Japan

to compensate the victims.	
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that raped and gang-raped 31.45 million to 61.20 million Chinese infants, women and pregnant women during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth \$420 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth \$114.4 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 42,000 – 63,000 tons of gold worth \$5,289 – 7,933.5 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about \$3,535.71 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth \$20,000-300,000 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 1,000 tons of platinum worth about \$32.258-37.868 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 20 million tons of cotton worth about 53.3 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 180 million tons of iron ore worth about \$18-23.4 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 10 million pieces cultural relics worth about \$100,000 billion from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A risky and evil society without empathy and conscience that looted at least 100 million tons of steel worth about \$ 311.55 from China during World War II but refused to compensate the victims.	Japan
A society in which in the 21st century, Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe still publicly pilots an aircraft number 731 commemorating the evil Japanese Unit 731 biological warfare unit that carried out large-scale massacres through germ warfare.	Japan

<p>A vicious society that is accustomed to taking children from invaded countries as a source of meat.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>A wicked society that is accustomed to taking children from invaded countries as blood donors.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>A wicked society: A country that has just suffered a devastating earthquake with extremely heavy losses. Although its neighboring countries are oppressed by it, out of benevolence, it still calls on the people of the whole country to donate huge sums of money and materials to rescue the people of the disaster-stricken country. But unexpectedly, this country carried out massacres on more than 700 innocent civilians of the country that donated material and wealth. Afterwards, there is no apology and no compensation. This significantly reflects that the social system of the country attacked by the strong earthquake is a social system without conscience, gratitude, and extremely evil intrinsic nature. According to the philosophical concept of the unity of man and nature, the will of heaven is to warn such a society implementing an evil social system through a strong earthquake.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纮一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fates of Germany. Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace? 在日本的传说中，日本统治者神武天皇曾下达“八纮一宇”诏书，上书：征服世间的四面八方，置诸于一个屋顶之下。The meaning of the above Chinese text translated into English is: In Japanese legends, Emperor Jimmu, the ruler of Japan, once issued an imperial edict of "the Unified Universe or 八纮一宇", which read: "Conquer all directions of the world and place them under one roof." At that time, Germany was an ally of Japan, but Japan even wanted to conquer and annex Germany. Japan is now an ally of the United States. Japan has misled the United States into wasting at least \$7.2 trillion in the field of nuclear weapons, seriously disrupting the U.S. economy, and constantly creating a tense situation in the world. After World War II, military investment in the United States should have decreased. However, under the promotion by its so-called ally Japan, it has instead increased by \$22 trillion in 60 years, successfully leading the U.S. economy into a trap. Sadly, basically all Americans still don't know the truth of the matter. Thus, it is better to believe that a dog will not defecate than to believe Japan's false claim of wanting world peace.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil "Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纮一宇塔)" to suppress the souls and national fates of the United States.</p>	<p>Japan</p>

Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of Canada . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of Russia . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of Peru . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of Singapore . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of South Korea . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of North Korea . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan is A society still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of North the Philippines . Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
To this day, Japan still uses the evil " Tower of Suppressing Souls (the Unified Universe Tower or 八纎一宇塔) " to suppress the souls and national fates of China, etc.	Japan
A society with multi - party elections, a penchant for plundering, and racial discrimination. Is Japan a social system that hopes for world peace?	Japan
A society used to cut off the flesh of prisoners of war and eat it as sashimi or raw meat slices. A society that once nearly captured President George H.W. Bush and then cut the flesh off his body and ate it as raw meat slices.	Japan
A society accustomed to eating the brain matter of civilians in invaded countries.	Japan
A society accustomed to eating the brains of children in invaded countries.	Japan
A society accustomed to eating the genitals of male civilians in	Japan

invaded countries.	
A society accustomed to eating the livers of civilians in invaded countries.	Japan
A society accustomed to eating the breasts of women in invaded countries.	Japan
A society accustomed to eating the uteruses of women and young girls in invaded countries.	Japan
A society that is accustomed to using bayonets to cut open the bellies of pregnant women in invaded countries and pick out fetuses with bayonets .	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone with a crew cut or student hairstyle would be slaughtered if found. Have you or your son ever had a crew cut or student hairstyle? Japan is the country that committed genocide and is the worst, most despicable and most evil. If Japan ranks second, there should be no country in the world that can rank first.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, any women with short haircuts would be slaughtered if found. Has your wife or daughter ever had a short haircut? Japan is the country that committed genocide and is the worst, most despicable and most evil. If Japan ranks second, there should be no country in the world that can rank first.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone wearing gray clothing would be slaughtered if found. Have you ever worn gray clothes?	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone who are afraid upon seeing them, would be slaughtered if found.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone who open the door slightly late during inspections, would be slaughtered if found.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone with self-defense firearms would be slaughtered if found.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone wearing commemorative coins of the founding of the country would be slaughtered if found.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone in possession of central banknotes would be slaughtered if found.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone with military supplies at home would be slaughtered if found.	Japan
A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone wearing leather shoes would be slaughtered if found. Have you and your family members worn leather shoes?	Japan

<p>Japan is the country that committed genocide and is the worst, most despicable and most evil. If Japan ranks second, there should be no country in the world that can rank first.</p>	
<p>A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone carrying a camera would be slaughtered if found.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone with gold teeth would be slaughtered if found.</p> <p>In China, the Japanese would slaughter all those who had gold teeth. This shows the ferocity of Japan in plundering the wealth of the Chinese people and the amount of gold looted. At that time, the amount of gold held by the Chinese people privately far exceeded that held by the government.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>A society that brutally invaded China. In this society, anyone with student-style appearances would be slaughtered if found.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>A society with multi - party elections, predilection for plundering, racial discrimination, and being good at staying silent while waiting for an opportunity to launch plundering again.</p>	
<p>A society that uses the government to set preferential conditions to encourage foreign businessmen to invest and build factories in its development zones, uses means to cause investors to lose money rapidly, and plunders huge amounts of wealth from many investors.</p>	<p>India</p>
<p>A society that likes to launch aggressive wars and, during wars, produces large quantities of counterfeit banknotes or useless military vouchers to plunder the people of invaded countries on a large scale.</p>	<p>Japan</p>
<p>A society that uses the government to set preferential conditions to encourage foreign businessmen to invest and build factories. After making profits, it uses legal systems to make cooperative investors violate laws, or forcibly prevent profits from being transferred to the countries where the investors are located, or forcibly acquire the equity of the cooperative partners, or forcibly demand to obtain the controlling stake in the company, plundering huge amounts of wealth and technical secrets from numerous investors by insidious means.</p>	<p>India</p>
<p>A society that clearly knows that the islands in the South China Sea all belong to China but illegally occupies a large number of Chinese islands.</p> <p>In 2024, the writings of British legal experts prove that the islands in the South China Sea belong to China.</p> <p>"The History and Sovereignty of the South China Sea Islands" was written by British international law scholar Anthony Carty. Carty has spent more than ten years consulting a large number of national archives of France, the United Kingdom and the United States on the ownership of the South China Sea islands since the end of the 19th century. Based on history and jurisprudence, he clarified the</p>	<p>Indonesia, the Philippines Vietnam</p>

<p>sovereignty of the South China Sea Islands and also provided important historical materials and international law evidence for research on the sovereignty of the South China Sea Islands.</p>	
<p>An evil society that attempts to conquer other countries by war, dominate Asia alone, and unify the world together with the former Soviet Union.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>An evil society that attempts to annex Laos and has waged wars.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>An evil society that attempts to annex Cambodia and has waged wars.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>An evil society that attempts to annex Thailand and has waged wars.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>An evil society that attempts to annex China and has waged wars.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>An evil society. Vietnamese leaders instructed soldiers to bury landmines at the door of Su Zhongliang, a Chinese benefactor who had long rescued Vietnamese leaders and soldiers, resulting in his family members being disabled by stepping on landmines.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that has long received free accommodation and food provided by kindhearted Chinese villagers when they are in distress. After the survivors succeed, they not only instruct their underlings to forcibly seize the houses and land of their benefactors, but also attempt to bury landmines at the door of their benefactors' homes and kill their benefactors.</p> <p>When Vietnam was colonized by France, Ho Chi Minh and other founding fathers of North Vietnam had nowhere to hide after being driven away by the French army. Out of kindness, the villagers of Pingmeng Village on the China-Vietnam border not only took them in, but also gave them food. After Vietnam was unified, Vietnamese soldiers took photos left by Ho Chi Minh and other founding fathers of North Vietnam while living in Pingmeng Village area as "evidence." Pointing to some background in the photos, they said that Pingmeng Village is Vietnamese because most of the founding fathers of North Vietnam lived here for many years and demanded that China "return" the houses and land of Pingmeng Village to Vietnam.</p> <p>Vietnam, an evil country that can never be trusted, a nation that can never be trusted, a nation that robs your houses and land and wealth in the end after you help them. In the end, they will even kill you and your family with landmines and guns.</p> <p>Having pity on a greedy, evil, fierce and warlike country and its people is the greatest blow to world peace and the greatest blow to human civilization.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>In the war years when food was scarce, the kind and honest villagers on the Chinese border would rather dig and eat very unpalatable wild vegetables by themselves and give rice to the Vietnamese leaders and soldiers who took refuge in their village. The Vietnamese leaders promised that after Vietnam was unified, they would definitely invite these villagers to be honored guests. However, after Vietnam was</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>

<p>unified, these Vietnamese leaders sent troops to lay landmines at the door of the benefactor who had rescued them, trying to kill the benefactor. Superstructure constructs the social system.</p> <p>What kind of society with a social system constructed by such ferocious people is this? Can one invest or build factories in this society? Once a crisis occurs, you may lose everything.</p> <p>Can you imagine that when you give the only food in your family to the leaders of Vietnam and their soldiers to eat, you and your family members go to the mountains to dig very unpalatable wild vegetables to fill your hunger? A year later, they established a unified Vietnam. Then, they send soldiers to secretly lay landmines on your doorstep, preparing to blow up everyone in your family. If you are still alive, are you angry?</p> <p>Only in a society constructed by Chinese civilization can people give rice to refugees for a long time and eat wild vegetables by themselves when food is most scarce. Investing and building factories in China is guaranteed by a system with empathy.</p> <p>Having pity on a greedy, evil, fierce and warlike country and its people is the greatest blow to world peace and the greatest blow to human civilization.</p>	
<p>An evil society that attempts to annex Asia and has waged wars.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that has long continuously requested China provide about CNY 40 trillion yuan worth of materials in the form of free aid. After the country was unified, it massacred 1.5 million Chinese people and their descendants. It is an evil society.</p> <p>A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a long time. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.</p> <p>Having pity on a greedy, evil, fierce and warlike country and its people is the greatest blow to world peace and the greatest blow to human civilization.</p>	
<p>A society that has long continuously requested China provide about CNY 40 trillion yuan worth of materials in the form of free aid. After the country is unified, it drove 2 million Chinese people and their descendants into the sea. It is an evil society.</p> <p>A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>

<p>longtime. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.</p>	
<p>A society that has long continuously requested China provide about CNY 40 trillion yuan worth of materials in the form of free aid. After the country is unified, it extorts 12 tons of gold from 2 million Chinese people and their descendants. Otherwise, it will kill them or put them in concentration camps. It is an evil society.</p> <p>A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a long time. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society without gratitude, empathy, morality or conscience, and a high-risk society.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that uses the Communist Party, which has lofty ideals of humanity, as the name of its ruling party to deceive the public and the international community, but likes to massacre civilians on a large scale and plunder their gold and wealth.</p> <p>Only in a society constructed by Chinese civilization can people give rice to refugees for a long time and eat wild vegetables by themselves when food is most scarce. Investing and building factories in China is guaranteed by a system with empathy.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that uses the pursuit of an equal socialist system society with lofty ideals of human beings as the name of the national system, but likes to massacre civilians on a large scale and plunder victims' gold.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that has long continuously requested China provide about 40 trillion yuan worth of materials in the form of free aid. After the country was unified, it suddenly started a war against Laos and wanted to annex Laos. It is an evil society.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that has long continuously requested China provide about CNY 40 trillion yuan worth of materials in the form of free aid. After the country was unified, it suddenly started a war against Thailand and wanted to annex Thailand. It is an evil society.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that has long continuously requested China provide about 40 trillion yuan worth of materials in the form of free aid. After the country is unified, it suddenly starts a war against China and wants to annex China. It is an evil society.</p> <p>A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>

<p>longtime. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.</p>	
<p>An evil society that tried to cooperate with the former Soviet Union to annex the United States, divide American territory, and wrote this plan into national government document.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>A society that acknowledges the existence of genetics in organisms but is reluctant to admit that a specific race or ethnic group with specific biological attributes is very bad and has a strong criminal tendency, which is a society with divided thinking.</p> <p>When this specific group of people commits crimes or brings disasters to kind-hearted people or those with a sense of pity who have been brainwashed by the media or politicians, the politicians who hold the views that lead to the harm of the above-mentioned kind-hearted people or those with a sense of pity, the voters who support this politician, the political party to which the politician belongs, all the members of the political party, the voters who support the political party, the media, the person in charge of the media, the editors of the media, the owners of the media, the actual controllers of the media, and the legal representatives of the media do not bear legal responsibilities and full compensation responsibilities with all their personal and family property.</p> <p>Politicians, the political parties to which they belong, or the persons responsible for the media and the actual controllers of the media must bear all compensation responsibilities with all personal and family property, and their descendants have an unlimited obligation to compensate! Otherwise, politicians will be able to deceive people just by talking without having to produce anything useful for society, and the media will become a tool for politicians to spread rumors. They will not have to admit legal responsibilities and compensation responsibilities. Is this a society that respects democracy and human rights?</p> <p>Obviously, this is a society of false democracy and false human rights.</p> <p>This is a society where criminal groups or potential criminal groups utilize the voting rights of people with mouths. The number of people receiving higher education in Western society is far more than that in 1900, more than ten times that in the past. Why do they choose to believe in such false democracy and human rights? Who brainwashed them? Shouldn't all the politicians, the media and their actual controllers who brainwash the people and their descendants bear all legal responsibilities and compensation responsibilities? Especially for the victims and their families thus caused, shouldn't they? The relevant responsible persons of such politicians and the</p>	

<p>media must be prohibited from using any defense lawyers to defend themselves, because they are very clear about what bad things they have done and why they have misled the people. Their IQs are already high. Do they still need lawyers with more professional IQs to absolve them of their crimes? They have ears and mouths and must defend themselves.</p>	
<p>One of the ways to significantly reduce crime and optimize human society:</p> <p>Massively eliminate the criminals who commit heinous crimes on a large scale, reduce the number of heinous criminals and voters, significantly raise the marriage and childbearing ages of the people in the countries where large-scale crimes are committed, and strictly control the immigration from these countries to other countries. Only in this way can we reduce the possibility of them triggering wars by using immigration.</p> <p>Prohibit any country, company or individual from conducting any transactions related to weapons, weapons manufacturing technologies, production lines and raw materials for weapons manufacturing with criminal countries or any company or individual in those criminal countries. Prohibit any transactions related to weapon-related manufacturing technologies. Disintegrate and reorganize the evil criminal countries that commit large-scale crimes, and eliminate the evil religions that protect large-scale crimes. Only by doing so can we change their deeply evil social systems at their core.</p> <p>Western countries have been emphasizing that the earth is overpopulated. Then why don't they eliminate the anti-human criminals who continuously commit large-scale crimes and put them on public trial and execute them all?</p> <p>Why don't they quickly strike at and disintegrate those countries where politicians don't consider large-scale crimes as something to be ashamed of, but rather take pride in them? Why is conducting trade with these countries that commit large-scale crimes regarded as an achievement in governance instead of being seen as politically and ethically incorrect or a huge mistake?</p> <p>The most crucial first step:</p> <p>Immediately prohibit any country, any company or any individual from selling or transferring any research and development, manufacturing technology, or production lines related to weapons globally. Any country that does not agree to implement the provisions of this ban shall be listed as an anti-peace country, and all countries shall be prohibited from conducting trade with it. Meanwhile, any country and company can detain and</p>	

confiscate any property of the country's citizens that violates the ban.

This is one of the methodologies for purifying the earth, reducing conflicts and wars, and rescuing the victimized people. It is the inevitable path for the world economy to move towards a healthy and correct direction and for global governance to move towards a healthy path.

The international community must reach the following consensus:

For any trade contract between a company of any country and the criminal country, the criminal country must use its national and government assets, as well as any assets of its citizens, as collateral. If any citizen of the criminal country illegally embezzles the assets of a company from another country, the criminal country must make compensation. The penalty amount shall be five times the value of the subject matter in the contract. If the criminal country fails to make compensation, the aggrieved company may seize any state-owned or private assets of its citizens in any country around the world at any time and entrust them for auction.

★ Analysis and Reflection on the LGBT and LGBTQ Phenomena

The emergence of LGBT- and LGBTQ - related behaviors is, in essence, a complex issue involving psychological and physiological aspects. From a medical perspective, normal human reproduction and sexual development have their inherent physiological laws, and phenomena that deviate from traditional sexual orientation and gender identity often imply physiological or psychological abnormalities. For example, some studies suggest that it may be related to physiological factors such as hormonal imbalances and differences in brain structure. It may also stem from psychological factors such as childhood trauma and incorrect cognitive guidance. It may also be related to the consumption of meat from animals fed hormones and other chemicals. Widely used herbicides around the world also seriously interfere with the secretion of reproductive hormones, causing many adverse consequences. These abnormal manifestations can be regarded as a disease state.

In the West, the prevalence of LGBT and LGBTQ has gone beyond the scope of normal phenomena and has formed a politically influential class. This is the result of medical and political errors, as well as their dereliction of duty and failure. For example, the California bill in the United States stipulates that parents have no right to know about or interfere with their children's gender orientation, which seriously damages the normal parent - child relationship and family communication patterns. Parents are one of the most important guides in a child's growth. When parents are deprived of the right to guide their children's gender cognition, it will lead to a breakdown of trust within the family. Children may blindly accept external concepts of gender change without the support of a family support system.

The medical field should uphold the scientific spirit and conduct in - depth research and reasonable intervention on this phenomenon. However, it has abandoned its proper position under the pressure of so - called "political correctness", which is a serious dereliction of duty. Western politicians, for the sake of short - term political interests, such as obtaining votes from specific groups, vigorously support and promote these concepts, completely ignoring their damage to social structures and value systems. This is a stupid act. The flood of this phenomenon also highlights the failure of governance in Western countries. Social systems have failed to effectively resist the impact of violating traditional ethics and moral concepts, exposing huge loopholes.

Even more seriously, capital is fueling this. Capital uses means such as the media and cultural industries to continuously spread and beautify LGBT-and LGBTQ- related content, deliberately disrupting social order and misleading the public, especially those who may themselves be in psychological or physiological confusion, causing them to fall further into wrong perceptions, and then profiting from such people in the long term. Therefore, strict laws and regulations must be established to severely punish those politicians who encourage such improper behaviors, in order to maintain social stability, ethics, and healthy development. Only in this way can society be guided to return to rationality and protect the public, especially teenagers, from harm.

Sydney Burwell, a former dean of Harvard Medical School, once pointed out, "Students are often confused when I tell them that half of what they learn in medical school may be considered wrong in ten years. What's worse, no teacher knows which half is wrong." It can be seen that contemporary Western medical theories cannot predict the correctness of the theories and knowledge taught by medical school professors. In many cases, the entire medical theoretical system lacks forward - looking thinking and foresight. However, the experts who control the World Health Organization have made completely erroneous judgments and conclusions about the disease nature of LGBT and LGBTQ issues, even believing that they are not diseases. This is very bad! Decision - makers completely lack the level of normal medical philosophy and foresight, and those who make such bad decisions are simply not suitable for leadership positions at WHO.

On May 31, 1945, in his concluding remarks at the Seventh National Congress of the Communist Party of China, Chairman Mao pointed out that "there is no leadership without foresight," and that "foresight is seeing the trend ahead." He elaborated on the methods and importance of foresight and overcoming blind action. Chairman Mao stated: "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend ahead. Without foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot. Stalin said: without foresight, it is not called leadership; to lead, there must be foresight."

Politicians who lack foresight on LGBT and LGBTQ issues should not hold leadership positions in regions, countries, or international organizations.

If you have doubts about the judgments based on medical philosophy in this article and attempt to attack the viewpoints herein, first of all, you should consider whether you have a medical level comparable to that of the author of this article, at

least in dealing with difficult medical issues. If you do not have the author's medical record, have you considered that your promotion of the LGBT and LGBTQ movements is seriously misleading these people, and if you are proven wrong in the future, will you bear all legal responsibility and compensation? If you do not have such capabilities, please restrain your arrogance and folly. When the author of this article has a viral cold, it usually cures itself in one or two days without the need for leave, while modern Western medical methods generally require 4 - 7 days of treatment, and some patients still need to take sick leave and rest in bed. In February 2020, the author of this article found that it is very difficult for COVID-19 vaccines to prevent novel coronavirus infection. Not only will the manufacturing and vaccination of COVID-19 vaccines waste huge amounts of funds, but vaccination will also bring unexpected abnormal events and adverse reactions. Although no company had successfully developed a COVID-19 vaccine at that time, facts three years later show that COVID-19 vaccines do not have the preventive effect of a normal vaccine, but instead bring many abnormal vaccination events and serious adverse reactions. During the three - year pandemic, the author of this article neither received a COVID - 19 vaccination nor infected with the novel coronavirus, despite frequent contact with severely infected COVID-19 patients. The author can also reverse and relieve the symptoms of severely ill patients within 1 - 4 hours, without the use of ventilators or hormones at all. Patients' appetites can increase in about 1 - 4 hours, and then they will gradually recover. LGBT and LGBTQ are a combination of mental and physical diseases. For those who claim to be male within a few hours and then claim to be female a few hours later, those who constantly change their gender and keep intruding into private places of the opposite sex, the police should intervene to deal with it.

By the way, let me mention a correct methodology for a British MP to discuss issues in parliament. On November 25, 2015, Chancellor of the Exchequer Osborne submitted the government's spending review for the next five years to Parliament. After Osborne's statement, John McDonnell, the shadow chancellor of the Labour Party, took out a copy of "Quotations from Chairman Mao" from his coat pocket. He said, "Let me quote from Chairman Mao." There was an uproar in the meeting. Speaker Bercow shouted to stop the noise: "Quiet! I want to hear what the book says." McDonnell opened the "Quotations from Chairman Mao" in his hand and read, "We must learn how to do economic work from all who know how, no matter who they are. We must regard them as our teachers, learning from them earnestly and modestly. We must not pretend to know when we do not know."

Table 4-1. The redefinition of the United Nations???	
1	The United Nations is not really a very bad organization or institution?? It has continuously protected countries that commit large-scale crimes. Since its establishment, large-scale criminals and wars have kept emerging. What's even more outrageous is that it legalized crimes committed by countries, leaving victimized countries unable to carry out comprehensive strikes! It is an institution that protects the crimes of religious groups under the pretext of protecting extremely large-scale religious beliefs. Aren't these so-called

	countries that commit evil large-scale crimes actually super-large criminal gangs? Should they still exist?
2	It is an organization or institution that has long maintained the organizational structure of countries that commit large-scale crimes to be stable and legal and their military forces to exist legally.
3	It is an organization or institution that has difficulty in restraining crimes but is able to protect countries that commit large-scale crimes and fully safeguard the organizational structures and military forces of such countries.
4	It is an organization or institution that can legally protect the leaders of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes and an institution that can prevent the armies of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes from being immediately attacked and eliminated by victimized countries.
5	It is an organization or institution that can prevent the criminals of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes from being immediately attacked and eliminated by victimized countries.
6	It is an organization or institution that can protect criminal groups that commit large-scale crimes from being immediately attacked and eliminated by victimized countries.
7	An organization or institution where a victimized country has been defrauded by criminal groups with the nature of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes, yet the victimized country still has to pay membership fees, even though these criminals have caused the citizens of the permanent members of the United Nations to lose an average of \$5 billion annually for four consecutive years and the victims are unable to recover their losses.
8	<p>The criminal countries that commit large-scale telecommunications fraud crimes have repeatedly attempted to become permanent members of the UN Security Council, and the United Nations has even held meetings to discuss and vote on this issue many times. Should such evil things still be discussed and voted on in meetings?</p> <p>Isn't this era an obviously absurd world constructed by countries that commit large-scale telecom fraud crimes?</p> <p>You may have encountered the most shameless ethnic groups and races, but have you ever seen one that is even more extremely shameless than this?</p> <p>India, which has defrauded the United States and Canada of at least \$5 billion annually on average for four consecutive years, has constantly proposed to become a permanent membership in the UN Security Council. Hasn't the United Nations become an organization that includes members of the underworld? Isn't it strange that India is so shameless? Could an ancient civilization have been born in such a region? Does this make sense? Isn't it fabricated by false missionaries? Does morality, ethics, conscience and empathy still exist in today's world? Ancient India was in the region of present-day Pakistan. India should change its country name and stop using it to deceive the global public.</p> <p>However, the United Nations has actually tried to hold meetings to discuss granting the status of permanent membership to countries that commit large-</p>

scale crimes. **Why not revoke the right to propose, vote and elect of such criminal countries that commit large-scale crimes based on their crimes.** For every \$1 million defrauded from victims of large-scale fraud crimes, the criminal country's right to propose, vote and make decisions in any international organization shall be revoked for **one year**; for **every \$100 million defrauded from citizens of other countries**, the above rights shall be revoked **for 100 years**; **if the cumulative amount of fraud against citizens of other countries reaches \$10 billion, the above rights shall be revoked for 10,000 years.**

How could President Joe Biden of the world's leading power shake hands with Narendra Modi, the head of a super-large underworld gang that is constantly committing large-scale fraud crimes against the United States? Aren't you afraid of soiling the hands of a leader of a major power? When it comes to large-scale crimes, India has absolutely no moral bottom line. U.S. security agencies and the media should work together to conduct statistics to see when the number of Americans harassed by Indian telecom fraud will increase from the current 50 million to 100 million in the future.

Fig. 85-23-19. **India's existence is a nightmare for neighboring countries.**

India annexed Sikkim, controlled Bhutan, and sent troops to Sri Lanka and the Maldives. India occupied 125,000 square kilometers of Chinese territory. It occupied 95,000 square kilometers of Pakistani territory and two large islands. It also occupied 93,000 square kilometers of Nepalese territory.

Is an evil country that likes to occupy and annex the territory of other countries a country with normal religious beliefs or one that believes in cults? If they do not believe in evil religions, how can these evil believers like to occupy and annex the territory of other countries and constantly start wars? You'd rather believe that dogs don't defecate than believe that Indians don't have bad hearts and bad brains.

2024-07-20. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7393606885838146852>

If they do not believe in evil religions, how can these evil believers like to occupy and annex the territory of other countries and constantly start wars????

Shouldn't this evil religion be abolished immediately???

What kind of social system is this society? Is it the so-called democratic system?

The best way for Europe and the United States to obtain fair and accessible markets is to dismantle an evil India that likes to launch aggressive wars, commit large-scale fraud, and openly annex neighboring Sikkim, and reorganize into multiple countries.

Fig. 85-23-19. Episode 3 | In 1975, Indian troops occupied the Kingdom of Sikkim, placed the King of Sikkim under house arrest, and annexed it as a state of India. Sikkim is the only sovereign country in the world to be annexed after the Second World War. 2024-06-12. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7379528866169130267>

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Shouldn't this evil religion be abolished immediately???

Perhaps only evil nations and evil people do not place human beings' possession of

conscience, noble morality and empathy at the top of being a person, but instead place so-called religious beliefs first, intending to lead the ignorant crowd onto a distorted path. Isn't an evil religious belief a deceptive trick? Catholicism, Judaism and Christianity were founded only after the 15th century, which can be proved by mathematical methods. Can you test the mathematical level of your friends around you?

What kind of social system is this society? Is it the so-called democratic system?

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Indians will be the biggest demons of future large-scale wars for humanity.

If there are no restrictions on India's population, Indian immigration, India's weapons development and trade, India's heavy industry, space technology, nuclear technology and railway technology, there will be very little hope for human peace.

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Indian laws support Indians in cheating on goods, and Indians do not have to bear legal responsibilities. When doing business with India, it is necessary to ask Indians to pay the full payment in advance before the goods are shipped or before the goods are prepared. Otherwise, there will be traps in the future.

{ Attention to Indian customers, why are there so many bad debts for Indian customers?

Why do Indian customers blatantly cheat on goods? # Freight Forwarder # Foreign Trade # International Logistics # International Trade # India. 2022-11-18. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7167245659341458721> }

Fig. 85-23-19. The history of Sikkim's founding and its annexation by India. 2024-09-15. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7414704958085270818>

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原创 印度是如何混成专骗美国人的诈骗强国？

2024-08-21 11:26 发布于：天津市

说起印度这个国家，想必许多人都不待见。的确，印度有着森严的种姓制度、巨大的贫富差距、数量庞大的人口、脏乱差的环境……其中不得不提到印度的诈骗行业，已经发展得相当发达，每年诈骗的金额高达几百亿美元。

让人意想不到的，印度人诈骗最多的对象，竟然是美国人。那么印度是如何成为专骗美国人的诈骗强国呢？

一、印度诈骗行业崛起原因

一直以来美国都以“世界霸主”的身份自居，但就是这样一个经济军事都不知比印度强大多少倍的国家，竟然成为被印度诈骗分子诈骗的主要对象。整个印度针对美国进行电话诈骗的人数，达到数百万之多。

Fig. 85-23-20. [印度是如何混成专骗美国人的诈骗强国？

How did India become a fraud - strong country that specializes in defrauding Americans???? 2024-08-21. http://news.sohu.com/a/802437149_121645968]

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Indians will be the biggest demons of future large-scale wars for humanity

If there are no restrictions on India's population, Indian immigration, India's weapons development and trade, India's heavy industry, space technology, nuclear technology and railway technology, there will be very little hope for human peace.

The best way for Europe and the United States to obtain fair and accessible markets is to dismantle an evil India that likes to launch aggressive wars, commit large-scale fraud, and openly annex neighboring Sikkim, and reorganize into multiple countries.

Indian laws support Indians in cheating on goods, and Indians do not have to bear legal responsibilities. When doing business with India, it is necessary to ask Indians to pay the full payment in advance before the goods are shipped or before the goods are prepared. Otherwise, there will be traps in the future.

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Fig. 85-23-21. Indian scam call centers looted over \$20 billion from US citizens over this past few years and how is affecting the transportation industry.

[21 MARCH, 2024. <https://garcias-autotransportandlogistics.com/indian-scam-call-centers-looted-over-20-billion-from-us-citizens-over-this-past-few-years-and-how-is-affecting-the-transportation-industry/>]

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Fig. 85-23-22. **Video:** Indian man shouts' **Let the Indian army march into Canada!**
'2024-11-08. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7434830246207147316>

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Fig. 85-23-23. Indian immigrants in Canada shouted: We are the masters of Canada, demanding that white Canadians return to Europe # International News # Hot Topics

Racial Talent # India. 2024-11-18.ttps://www.douyin.com/video/7438421581631704370

Fig. 85-23-24. Video: Indians gathered in Canadian communities and shouted: "We are the masters of Canada." Who would have thought of such a move! Who on earth is the master of Canada? #NeverExpectedThat #India #Canada.

Netizen: Accepting one Indian is equivalent to opening a compressed file. Now Canada is almost losing everything as if being stolen from under its nose. 2024-11-18. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7438540577953680703>

Fig. 85-23-25. **Eighty thousand Indians in Toronto have once again flooded the streets! They gathered together, set fires, and reveled until late at night!** #Canada #India. 2024-10-17. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7426574170533743882>

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Fig. 85-23-26. **Video:** Canada wants to "get rid of Indians". Let's see how the Indian guys respond arrogantly! **The Indian replied arrogantly: "Fool! India is already empty. It's too late. We've all come to Canada. We're going to work as telemarketers. We'll call you at one o'clock in the morning, even if you're not on the list. We'll cheat your grandparents. We'll turn your plain bedsheets into floral ones. We'll also go dancing in the city square center soon. Soon you'll be gone. And I'm not even an Indian, you fool."**2024-09-06.

<https://www.douyin.com/video/7411454987835903282>

Fig. 85-23-27. Video: Another Chinese merchant was defrauded of over 30,000 US dollars by an Indian.

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fraud, and openly annex neighboring Sikkim, and reorganize into multiple countries.

Fig. 85-24. **Real videos** On November 25, 2015, Chancellor of the Exchequer Osborne submitted the government's spending review for the next five years to Parliament. After Osborne's statement, John McDonnell, the shadow chancellor of the Labour Party, took out a copy of "Quotations from Chairman Mao" from his coat pocket. 2024-10-25. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7429658438432476425>

Table 5. Reclassification of past, present, and future social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives (Continued Table 4). The reclassification of human social systems like an encyclopaedia.

Reclassification of Human social systems	Country
A social system that cultivates extremely evil, morally - bottomless,	India

empathy - lacking, and inhumane people, and is likely to hide its ugly human nature at present. People in this society may appear normal, polite, democratic, or kind, and are good at using the sympathy of others to accumulate resources for the implementation of evil plans. When the time comes, the state institutions or people cultivated by this society will inevitably carry out any of the following large - scale crimes:	Indonesia, Japan, the Philippines Myanmar Vietnam
1. Invading other countries;	
2. Annexing normal countries regardless of the opposition of the majority of the people of other countries;	India Japan
3. Seizing the land of the original inhabitants of other ethnic groups;	India Myanmar
4. Carrying out large - scale massacres;	Indonesia Japan Myanmar Vietnam
5. Raping women and young girls on a large scale;	Indonesia Japan Myanmar Vietnam
6. Plundering the wealth of the people or their descendants of other countries on a large scale;	Indonesia Japan Myanmar Vietnam
7. Implementing a system of serious racial discrimination within their own territory;	India Myanmar
8. Carrying out large - scale human trafficking;	Myanmar
9. Carrying out large - scale kidnappings and live - organ harvesting;	Myanmar
10. Defrauding the wealth of the people of other countries through large - scale telecommunications fraud;	
11. Allowing evil people to open a large number of telecommunications fraud parks within their territory to carry out any criminal activities such as kidnapping, fraud, rape, gang - rape, human trafficking, live - organ harvesting, massacre, and live - burial;	Myanmar
12. Using the government and the military to secretly protect large - scale crimes;	
13. Making large - scale use of immigrants to create conflicts or crises or annex other countries;	Japan
14. Attempting to occupy several countries;	Japan Vietnam
15. Attempting to occupy a continent;	
16. Attempting to occupy and rule the world;	Japan Vietnam
17. A society that commits crimes such as massacring innocent people	Indonesia

of other countries or their overseas citizens and plundering their wealth, but fails to fully compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases and impose punitive damages, and does not confiscate all the personal and family property of the criminals.	Japan Myanmar Vietnam
18. A society that commits crimes such as massacring innocent people of other countries or their overseas citizens and plundering their wealth, but fails to execute all murderers, impose severe criminal penalties on other criminals, and confiscate all the personal and family properties of the criminals.	Indonesia Japan Myanmar Vietnam
19. A society that commits crimes such as mass - raping women and young girls of other countries or their overseas citizens and plundering their wealth, but fails to execute most of the main criminals, severely punish other criminals, and confiscate all the properties of the criminals.	Indonesia Japan Myanmar Vietnam
20. A society that commits crimes such as mass - raping women and young girls of other countries or their overseas citizens and plundering their wealth, but fails to fully compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases.	
21. A society that commits crimes such as massacring innocent people of other countries or their overseas citizens, but fails to fully compensate the victims according to the standards of American legal cases and imposes punitive damages.	
22. A society that commits crimes such as mass live - organ - harvesting from abductees, but fails to execute all the criminals after a public trial, fails to fully compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases, and impose punitive damages.	Myanmar
23. A society that commits large - scale human trafficking, but fails to fully compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases and imposes punitive damages.	Myanmar
24. A society that commits crimes such as mass abductions and torture, but fails to combat and execute the criminals, compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases, and impose punitive damages.	Myanmar
25. A society that commits crimes such as mass or long - term abductions and live burials, but fails to combat and execute the criminals, compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases, and impose punitive damages.	Myanmar
26. A society that commits crimes such as mass - raping women and young girls of other countries, causing them to become tools for childbearing or producing human - milk - based cosmetics or making their infants organ - transplantation donors, but fails to compensate victims according to the standards of American legal cases and execute all the criminals.	
27. A society that commits large - scale gambling - cultivation or -	Myanmar

implementation crimes, but fails to compensate victims according to the standards of U.S. legal cases and imposes punitive damages.	
28. A society that cultivates a large number of politicians who distort right and wrong, like to lie, and regard the massacre of civilians as a trifle.	Myanmar
29. A society that cultivates politicians who like to wage civil wars for a long time.	
30. A society of politicians who protect large - scale telecommunication fraud criminals on a large scale and obtain huge profits.	
31. A society of politicians who protect large - scale civilians slaughter criminals on a large scale and do not execute murderers.	
32. A society that protects large - scale murderers on a large scale and has an evil system where not only the criminals themselves are allowed to defend themselves, but also evil murderers are provided with defense lawyers.	
33. A society that protects large - scale rapists and gang - rapists of women and young girls of other countries or their overseas citizens on a large scale and has an evil system where not only the criminals themselves are allowed to defend themselves, but also the evil rapists and gang - rapists are provided with defense lawyers.	
34. A society with long - term and large - scale serious judicial injustice.	
35. A society in which, within five years, orders or commands lead the country's army or thugs to slaughter more than 500,000 innocent civilians, and all the criminals cannot be executed, and the relatives of the victims or the victimized country cannot receive full compensation.	
36. A society in which, in various ways, the country's army or thugs rape or gang rape more than 100,000 women within five years, and all criminals cannot be executed, and victims or their relatives cannot receive full compensation.	
37. A society that cultivates a large number of politicians, enabling them to enjoy the sense of holding executive power during their tenure, the feeling of traveling within or outside the country, and the feeling of talking with leaders or the powerful and wealthy of other countries, but does not formulate rules to force bad, incompetent or low - ability politicians to bear the serious consequences of wrong governing nation. They are not sentenced for major economic losses, let alone the death penalty, and at the same time, their personal or family property is not confiscated in full. The bad consequences are borne by the country or the people of the country, while the politicians enjoy the benefits.	
38. A society that promotes itself to the world as a society of democracy, freedom, and human rights, but the elected politicians serve the minority ruling party and voters, rather than the interests of the whole country. Moreover, it does not formulate rules to force bad,	

<p>incompetent or incompetent politicians, the ruling party, and supporters among voters to bear the serious consequences of bad governing nation. They are not sentenced for major economic losses, let alone the death penalty, and at the same time, the personal or family assets of these politicians and members of the ruling party who support them are not confiscated in full. The bad consequences are borne by the country or all the people of the country, while the politicians and the ruling party enjoy the benefits.</p>	
<p>39. A society that creates super lies, claiming to be a victim country and victims of atomic bombing, deceiving the United Nations and the Nobel Peace Prize Committee for a long time, and deceiving kind - hearted people or foundations of other countries to donate money to its victims and affected areas.</p>	<p>JAPAN</p>
<p>40. A society in which a large number of religious people rape women for a long time.</p>	
<p>40. A society that seems to serve the global population but is very bad needs to be described in the following words. The people of China have risked their lives many times to rescue the main leaders of a political party of another country and their colleagues. They would rather go without food themselves and share it with the leaders and their colleagues of that political party who were in distress. However, after that political party becomes the ruling party of the country, it instructed its army, police or killers to use landmines and weapons to kill those who once saved them.</p>	
<p>41. A society that seems to serve the global population but is very bad needs to be described in the following words. In a just war, the people of China have risked their lives many times to rescue the main leaders of a political party of another country and their colleagues. They would rather go without food themselves and give food to the leaders and their colleagues of that political party who were in distress. The political party and its leaders requested large - scale free aid from China again and again, enabling them to receive free aid for a long time. However, after that political party became the ruling party of the country, it instructed its army, police, or killers to use landmines and weapons to kill those who once saved them, just like a venomous snake society.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>42. A society that requests large - scale free aid from other countries again and over again. After receiving free aid many times, or once the aid - providing country reduces aid or is unable to provide free aid, it begins to expel the people or overseas citizens of the aid - providing country on a large scale, or immediately complains about or abuses the aid - providing country, or massacres the people or overseas citizens of the aid - providing country.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>
<p>43. A society that seems to serve the global population but is very bad</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>

<p>needs to be described in the following words. The ruling party and its leaders of a seemingly friendly and conscientious country repeatedly requested large - scale free aid from China. From 1950 to 1977, the total amount of free aid exceeded \$20 billion. After receiving free aid many times, once China reduced or was unable to provide free aid, they not only massacred the Chinese people, overseas Chinese and their descendants on a large scale. Each person who was expelled had to pay 12 taels of gold, otherwise they would be killed, thrown into concentration camps or driven into the vast sea. It is a hypocritical and malicious society like the underworld. This evil country also assembled troops to attempt to invade China, trying to annex China, and also attempting to annex multiple Southeast Asian countries. It also formulated national policies, trying to cooperate with a superpower to defeat the United States together, divide the United States jointly, and dominate the world.</p>	
<p>44. A greedy and evil society that relies on the national boundaries of several countries randomly drawn on the map by people of a third country located in the third country, attempts to take advantage of mistakes, tries to use these randomly drawn national boundaries as a legal basis, illegally occupies the territory of neighboring countries, attempts to plunder them for itself, and has been trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council to gain world leadership.</p>	India
<p>45. A society with an evil system that illegally occupies the land of other countries, practices racial discrimination and a racial hierarchy, assassinates the leaders of ethnic minorities who are forcibly incorporated into its territory, and has been constantly trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council to obtain global leadership.</p>	India
<p>46. A society with an evil system that illegally annexes the land of other countries, practices racial discrimination and a racial hierarchy, wages wars against and assassinates ethnic minorities who are forcibly incorporated into its territory, and has been constantly trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council to obtain global leadership.</p>	India
<p>47. A society with an evil system in which at least 10 - 20 million American people have been defrauded through telecommunications fraud, with the cumulative fraud amount exceeding \$20 billion, yet this criminal country has been constantly trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council to obtain global leadership.</p>	India
<p>48. A society with an evil system that illegally occupies the land of other countries, practices a racial hierarchy, and whose people have defrauded at least 10 - 20 million Americans through</p>	

<p>telecommunications fraud with the cumulative fraud amounting to more than \$20 billion. Moreover, the country likes to use its so - called institutional and demographic advantages to attract foreign investment in manufacturing. When companies make profits, it creates various reasons to forcibly seize their equity at low prices or confiscate their earnings, and it has been constantly trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council to gain global leadership.</p>	
<p>49. A society that seems to serve the global population but is very bad needs to be described in the following words. It obtains information from other countries through a large number of immigrants or expatriates in those countries, uses immigrants to create excuses for conflicts, launches aggressive wars, massacres a large number of military and civilians of other countries, rapes and gang rape women, pregnant women, female primary and secondary school students and young girls on a large scale, occupies cities of other countries, and destroys ancient buildings of other countries. And the entire population of this criminal country cheers, celebrates, and parades for the success of the massacre crimes and aggression of its army, reflecting that the entire population of the country supports the aggression of its government and army in various ways. This is a typical case of the whole - nation crime. After the war, this criminal country lowers the legal age of marriage to 13 years old to create a population for future wars and to have a large - scale reserve of criminal population advantage for future crimes. For example, Japan.</p>	Japan
<p>50. A society that seems to serve the global population but is very bad needs to be described in the following words. In the war of aggression against China, it massacred 51.8 - 89.6 (1,008) million Chinese people. This criminal country did not hold public trials and did not conscientiously execute all murderers, allowing all criminals to return to their own country. The Chinese people, the victims, and their families have never stated that they do not demand compensation from the criminal state. They have repeatedly demanded compensation for all the losses, but so far no compensation has been paid to all the victims and their families. Almost no compensation has been made for the losses of any civilian killed, let alone full compensation according to the standards of American legal cases. However, the country has been trying to become a permanent member of the UN Security Council to gain world leadership. Can the world allow a country with an evil system to lead the world development?</p>	Japan
<p>51. A society that seems to serve the global population but is very bad needs to be described in the following words. In the war of aggression against China, at least 30 million women, pregnant women, female</p>	Japan

<p>primary and secondary school students, and young girls were raped and gang - raped, and at least 200,000 women were forced to become sex slaves. A large number of women were killed. This criminal country did not hold public trials and did not conscientiously execute all murderers and rapists, allowing all criminals to return to their own country. To date, the losses of all the dead and the families of the victims have not been compensated. Almost no compensation has been made for the losses of any civilian raped, gang-raped, or killed, let alone full compensation according to the standards of American legal cases. The Chinese people, the victims, and their families have never stated that they do not demand compensation from the criminal state. On the contrary, they have repeatedly sought compensation for all losses. After the war, this criminal state lowered the legal age of marriage and childbearing to below 14 years old to create a population for future wars and to have a large - scale reserve of criminal population advantage for future crimes. It is an evil society that has been trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council to gain world leadership.</p>	
<p>52. Japan obtains spiritual stones from multiple countries through improper means and builds evil towers for suppressing souls in the country. It attempts to use evil sorcery to suppress the national fortunes of several countries such as the United States, Germany, Canada, Peru, Singapore, North Korea, and China, etc., and to suppress the souls of these countries, and it is also trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council. Isn't this a very bad social system?</p>	Japan
<p>53. A society that habitually uses a large number of immigrants or land - reclamation groups to forcibly acquire or plunder farmers' land in China at low prices, create crises and conflicts, and launch aggressive wars in an attempt to plunder China's territory and wealth.</p>	Japan
<p>54. A society that has established Yasukuni Shrine or churches, etc. to worship the military personnel and criminals of a war criminal country that once waged aggressive wars and massacred 20 million civilians. However, it is also trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council.</p>	Japan
<p>55. A society that has established Yasukuni Shrine or churches, etc. to worship the military personnel and criminals of a war - criminal country that once waged aggressive wars and massacred at least 51.80 - 89.60 (1008.0) million people. However, it is also trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council.</p>	Japan
<p>56. A society that has established Yasukuni Shrine or churches, etc. to worship the military personnel and criminals of a war - criminal country that once waged aggressive wars and raped or gang - raped 10 million women, pregnant women, female primary and secondary school</p>	Japan

<p>students, and young girls. However, it is also trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council.</p>	
<p>57. A society that has established Yasukuni Shrine or churches, etc. to worship the military personnel and criminals of a war - criminal country that once launched aggressive wars and raped or gang - raped 31.45 - 54.40 (61.20) million women, pregnant women, female primary and secondary school students, and young girls. However, it is also trying to become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council.</p>	Japan
<p>58. On October 20, 2023, local officials appointed by the Myanmar government organized relevant armed personnel. When attempting to transfer a large number of telecom fraudsters, they buried four Chinese undercover police officers alive who had identified themselves as being involved in combating telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, and rape crimes. What kind of social system does Myanmar have?</p>	Myanmar
<p>59. A social system that safeguards evil judicial interests: A social system that supports lawyers to reduce the sentences of criminals who deserve severe punishment, turning guilty criminals into innocent ones through a flood of words and evil evidential logic. The global public must call for the formulation of international covenants and United Nations conventions, and the revision of the constitutions of all countries to abolish such evil, dirty social system.</p>	
<p>60. A social system created by ignorant, incompetent and incompetent politicians that is extremely infuriating: The strange societies of various countries around the world today: Female middle - school students in a country were raped by refugees in a refugee settlement. After being brainwashed by the social system, instead of demanding severe punishment for the criminal refugees, the reason these middle school girls remain silent about being sexually assaulted by refugees is astonishingly that they don't want to ruin the reputation of the refugees. Even more strangely, judicial institutions do not severely punish criminals either.</p>	
<p>61. Dogs don't defecate in their own dens. Wild boars don't defecate in their own dens either. However, the Japanese actually dump a large amount of nuclear contaminated water that can cause disease and be fatal into the ocean, which is the living place for all human beings. The harm of nuclear contaminated water to the human body and the earth is extremely serious, with nuclear wastewater posing a greater threat to the human body. It contains 64 kinds of radioactive materials, including tritium, carbon-14, iodine-129, strontium-90, and cobalt-60. The most harmful to human beings and marine organisms are carbon-14 and iodine-129, with a half-life of over 5000 years for carbon-14 and an even longer half-life for iodine-129. Carbon-14 can</p>	Japan

<p>accumulate in the bodies of marine organisms, such as fish, with an abundance or concentration possibly 50 times that of tritium.</p> <p>What kind of social system does the nation have?</p>	
<p>62. A society where the Burmese government cooperates closely with local governments appointed and authorized by the Burmese government to carry out large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, murder, and drug trafficking. After a long - term colonization by the British, what kind of social system is this? Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.</p> <p>The Chinese government-wanted criminal mastermind from northern Myanmar is offering a significant cash reward to the Burmese government army in an attempt to unite against the Kokang Alliance, who are actively fighting against telecom fraud criminals.</p> <p>[The wanted Burmese crime leader, Bai Suocheng, who is also the head of one of the four major families in Kokang, and his second son, Bai Yingcang, appeared on the streets of Old Town. His words shocked Myanmar. According to reliable sources from Myanmar, Bai Yingcang inspected all the firepower bases in Old Town under the protection of armed militiamen in the morning. He made a speech, stating that he would fight alongside his father, Bai Suocheng, and Old Town, vowing not to surrender or escape. If necessary, he would personally lead a death squad to kill the commander-in-chief of the Alliance, Peng Deren. Today, Bai Suocheng, the head of one of the four major families in Kokang, distributed CNY 10 million in cash at the villa in Old Town, rewarding all the government troops and Kokang militia. During the cash distribution, Bai Suocheng announced a decision to offer a bounty in future wars. He declared that if the Kokang Alliance soldiers were completely defeated, there would be a cash reward of CNY 100,000 for killing any Alliance officer above the company level. Killing the deputy commander-in-chief of the Alliance will be rewarded with 200,000 CNY, and killing commander-in-chief, Peng Dejun, will earn a reward of 5 million CNY, in addition to 10 kilograms of gold, totaling approximately 11 million CNY. Bai Suocheng stated that all rewards would be given in cash on the spot. In addition, a decree was issued, stipulating that anyone who flees or surrenders will be killed on the spot. Bai Suocheng firmly stated that he would not run away or surrender, putting his life and fortune on the line in the life-or-death battle in Old Town. December 7, 2023. https://v.douyin.com/i8Fwvh3G/]</p>	<p>Myanmar</p>
<p>63. What kind of social system in Myanmar is this? Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.</p> <p>A real - life video of an interview with a lucky escapee from Myanmar: In the telecom fraud park, people are shot in the head and</p>	<p>Myanmar</p>

<p>killed by AK-47 every week. After being killed, they are dragged outside. Although the blood on the ground is cleaned every day, the victims never see the blood at the door being clean. When having meals in the cafeteria, it can be seen that many people's hands and feet are electrocuted by electric batons. The flesh is beaten and burned with electric batons, looking like coke, and there is no intact flesh left on their hands and feet. Every week, victims are whipped with rattan whips. One can see the flesh after a whip, and after about 50 whips, the bones are exposed.</p> <p>[August 24, Changsha, Hunan. A Burmese man who escaped revealed that there are daily deaths in the fraud zone in northern Burma. "The blood at the entrance is cleaned every day, but it has never been clean." #What is the root of the chaos in northern Burma? 2023-08-24. https://www.douyin.com/video/7270852192498666771]</p>	
<p>64. What kind of social system in Myanmar is this? Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.</p> <p>Burma trapped persons recount their escape experience: "My flesh was beaten to a pulp. It was either being beaten to death or having my organs sold." A Fujianese lad's harrowing experience in Burma for three months.</p> <p>The victim witnessed two people being beaten to death.</p> <p>If the victims cannot be rescued, they will either be beaten to death or have their organs sold.</p> <p>[2023-07-08. https://www.douyin.com/video/7253439090228596026]</p>	
<p>Once the claims of the following victims are realized, will it not be conducive to world peace and able to prevent and reduce future wars, massacres, and rapes? Isn't this also a huge business opportunity?</p>	
<p>The intelligence work of the Japanese invaders was extremely meticulous. In an era of extremely underdeveloped communications, long before the all-out war of aggression against China, they sent spies pretending to be tourists to spy on precious mineral deposits in a remote mountainous area of Leiyang that most Leiyang people didn't even know about, preparing for purposeful aggression and plunder. Just as when they invaded Nanjing, then the capital of China, and carried out the Nanjing Massacre, soldiers carried pliers with them to extract gold from the teeth of the killed Nanjing citizens.</p> <p>During the Japanese invasion of Leiyang, they carried out a large number of massacres, rapes and gang rapes, plundered various materials and money, burned houses, ancient buildings, shops, factories and boats, and blew up bridges. At least 104,680 people died in Leiyang, 80,280 were seriously injured, 58,868 were slightly injured,</p>	

and countless women were humiliated. Wherever the Japanese army went, the people's property was looted. According to statistics, total property losses amounted to 285.58 billion silver dollars, and direct economic losses amounted to 242.33 billion silver dollars. The people of Leiyang have never stated that they do not demand compensation from the evil Japanese government. Have the Japanese and the Japanese government admitted their guilt? Do the Japanese really have a conscience? **The Japanese never offered compensation on their own initiative. Instead, they pretend that Japan was the victim of the atomic bombings, using countless false evidence to deceive the global public, the United Nations, and the Nobel Peace Prize Committee.**

Total property losses were 285.58 billion silver dollars, and direct economic losses were 242.33 billion silver dollars. The Japanese government has not compensated the people for their losses at all. Having slaughtered at least 104,680 people in Leiyang and not compensating for the losses at all, can such an evil country become a permanent member of the United Nations within 104,680 years? If Japan can become a permanent member of the United Nations Security Council, the author of this article can take to be General Secretary of the United Nations now.

The global public can discuss this. Japan, which is constantly developing new military equipment and highly hiding its intention to launch wars in the future, and whose **prime minister publicly declared in September 2024 that US military power is declining and Japan wants to station troops in the United States. What kind of system does Japan have today?**

Lawyers around the world can unite to sue the Japanese government and force it to compensate the people in the victimized areas with 40 - 50% of the average annual investment return rate of Warren Buffett from 1965 to 2018 for the looted wealth. Part of the compensation for the dead may be received on behalf of the local government and used as a public welfare fund. Lawyers with a sense of justice around the world and relevant peacekeeping groups can thus enjoy half of the proceeds brought by just judicial action and severely punish the war - criminal country.

The following are two folk ballads circulated among the people during the Japanese invasion of Leiyang, Hunan, reflecting the ferocity and true features of the Japanese. When people encounter crises, their true characteristics are revealed, and the same is true for society and its social system. Readers can try to find someone who knows Chinese to translate:

“民国三十三，日本进湖南；先占城，后围湾。抓了男人来挑担，抓个女人就强奸。”“日本鬼子最可恶，普通百姓爱折磨；日里天天丢炸弹，夜里就把

<p>夫子捉。”流传在耒阳城乡的两首民歌揭露了日寇无恶不作的罪行。 At that time, German officers in China were extremely resentful of the atrocities of the Japanese invaders. Some German officers evaded being forcibly returned to Germany and helped the Chinese army fight against the evil Japanese, and some German officers sacrificed their lives for China's war of resistance against Japan.</p>	
<p>Refuting the evil logic of the Japanese people If you think that murderers who kill civilians and plunder property do not need to be severely punished or compensated, then wouldn't anyone be able to kill you, your wife and children, and your parents, and plunder the property of your entire family? According to your so - called clever logic, isn't this an excellent way to create wealth? If the Japanese believe that killing civilians and plundering their wealth were the business of the previous generation and have nothing to do with them, even though they enjoy the social welfare created by the looted wealth. Then, according to Japanese logic, wouldn't it be the case that anyone could kill the Japanese, loot their wealth, and pass that wealth on to their next generation, making it legal? If following such absurd logic fabricated by the Japanese, the global public could kill the Japanese, rob Japanese banks and any property, and it would be legal as long as their descendants held it.</p>	

▲ The definition of National Democracy or Country's Democracy:

The purpose of any activity of any ruling party in a country must be to serve the whole people. Democratic electoral activities and governance that are not responsible for all the people of the country, but only for the election and governance of one or more political parties, cannot be regarded as true democracy. Local or regional democracy cannot be equated with national democracy. In today's world, politicians are used to describing local democratic election activities, or governance activities of members of a single political party, or governance monopolized by two or three parties in combination, or governance activities of the government in which only the high - funded contributors in presidential or prime - ministerial elections can participate as democracy, but none of these are true democracy.

Table 6. Explanations of Several Countries with Special Social Systems

Indian, Indonesia, Japan, Myanmar, Vietnam	
1	<p>In recent years, Indian telecom fraudsters have swindled at least \$20 billion in property from Americans every year. [Ref. Fooling Americans: Indian telecom fraudsters swindle Americans out of \$20 billion of property every year. October 18, 2021. https://www.sohu.com/a/495793670_121119257] India is a typical pirate country that likes to annex the territory of other countries. If there is still justice in this world, an evil country must not be allowed to become a permanent member of the United Nations. Any person</p>

	<p>or country that proposes or agrees to make that country a permanent member of the United Nations is an evil, immoral, and unempathetic person or country.</p> <p>In 1642, the Sikkim dynasty was established. Since then, it has been frequently invaded by Nepal. In 1700, Nepalese troops fully invaded Sikkim and captured Radhazi, the then capital of Sikkim. This new dynasty faced the crisis of national subjugation. Nepalese troops marched north all the way and advanced towards Tibet. The Qing government of China sent troops twice to drive out all Nepalese troops and also relieved the danger of national subjugation of Sikkim. In 1950, Sikkim became a protected state of India. Naturally, the Sikkimese government was very reluctant and had constant conflicts with the Indian side.</p> <p>In February 1975, the evil Indian troops dispatched to disband the palace guards of King Sikkim, imprisoned King Sikkim, and manipulated the resolution of Sikkim to make it a state of India. During this period, Sikkim's "National Party" had many times negotiated with China for help. A total of 149 cables requesting "political mediation" and "armed intervention" were sent to Chinese diplomatic institutions, business groups, and civil groups in various South Asian countries and at the United Nations. This frequency can be said to be unique in the history of world diplomacy. At that time, however, the international situation was complex. For various reasons, the Chinese side rejected the Sikkim side's request. In the face of a critical moment in domestic and foreign affairs, the Sikkim National Party even hung the Chinese five-star red flag on the building of its own party headquarters and simultaneously sent letters to countries around the world, unilaterally announcing that all Sikkim's foreign affairs had been entrusted to China.</p> <p>Indian scammers have fleeced gullible Americans of a whopping \$10 billion in 2022.</p> <p>Indian scam call centers looted over \$20 billion from US citizens over this past few years and how is affecting the transportation industry.</p> <p>By the end of the year, Indian scam call centers will loot about \$12 billion from senior citizens and other non-tech-savvy people in the US alone. FBI's data shows that this is a 47 per cent increase from last year.</p> <p>India forcibly occupied a large amount of China's territory as its own simply by relying on a line drawn on the map by a Briton in his home country of Britain. He even tried to start a war to occupy Tibet. This is typical pirate behavior. If the pirate logic of the Indians holds true, then Pakistan can also find a Briton to draw a line in the center of New Delhi and allocate half of all Indian land on the side adjacent to Pakistan to Pakistan. Then Pakistan can send troops to occupy this land, which is also in line with India's pirate logic.</p>
2	<p>In 1965, there was a massacre of ethnic Chinese in Indonesia. Five hundred thousand ethnic Chinese were brutally killed. The highest estimate is that even three million ethnic Chinese, overseas Chinese and leftists in Indonesia died at that time. All their wealth was plundered by Indonesians.</p>

	<p>In the 1998 anti-Chinese riots in Indonesia, in that incident, 100,000 ethnic Chinese women were sexually assaulted in the streets, and 500,000 ethnic Chinese died under the butcher's knife. All their wealth was plundered by Indonesians.</p> <p>At the end of World War II, official U.S. maps clearly showed that basically all the islands in the South China Sea were islands owned by the hardworking ancestors of China. In ancient times, China had advanced navigation technology. Fishermen often fished and took shelter near the islands in the South China Sea. As early as when Zheng He voyaged to the Western Seas, these islands belonged to China. In the 1960s and 1990s, countries around the South China Sea, regardless of basic facts, illegally occupied many islands belonging to China when China's naval power was weak. Vietnam, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Malaysia are several of the main greedy plundering countries.</p>
3	<p>There has never been a country in the world that has invaded another country and massacred at least 40 million or more people and raped more than 20 million women. Japan has become the most evil butcher in the world. During the period of Japanese aggression against China, direct statistics from only 11 provinces show that the Japanese invasion caused at least 41.99-52.48 million deaths. The number of injured has not yet been counted (China currently has 34 provinces). You should know that when Japan invaded China, the Japanese aggressors raped and gang-raped at least 31.45-54.40 (61.20) million Chinese women, and forced at least 200,000 Chinese women into sexual slavery. They killed at least 51.80-89.60 (100.80) million Chinese people. Since the Japanese invasion of China in 1874 and Japan's surrender in 1945, data show that China's population has lost about 280 million people. All Toyota Motor's production equipment, assets, workers, and every screw comes from the evil Japanese looting of Minsheng Motors in Shenyang, China.</p> <p>Japan looted at least 42,000-63,000 tons of gold worth US\$5,289-7,933.5 billion, at least 250 million silver coins, looted at least 20 million cultural relics worth US\$50,000 billion, 500,000 kg of natural diamonds worth \$ 132.55-280.5 billion, 20 million gemstones such as white jade, sapphire, ruby, and agate worth about \$5,000 billion, at least 10 million strings of natural pearls worth at least about \$800 billion, at least 200 million tons of rare earth minerals worth \$20,000-300,000 billion, at least 49,000 tons of bronze worth about \$3,535.71 billion. at least 1.06 billion tons of coal worth \$114.4 billion, at least 700 million cubic meters of wood worth \$420 billion, at least 1,233 million tons of food worth about \$700 billion, at least 1,000 tons of platinum worth about \$32.258-37.868 billion, at least 20 million tons of cotton worth about 53.3 billion, at least 180 million tons of iron ore worth about \$18-23.4 billion, as well as 480 million pigs, sheep, chickens, and ducks, and 20 million head of cattle, horses, and donkeys. Additionally, 300 million houses were destroyed.</p> <p>From 1957 to 2022, Buffett's average compound annual return on investment was 20.44%. Please calculate using 50% of Buffett's average annual</p>

	rate of return on investment, what was the average annual rate of return on investment over 85 years (1928-1945-2024) for the evil Japanese invaders who plundered wealth from China?
4	<p>In the 1940s, after the disintegration of British colonial India, under the deception of the ethnic equality slogan of Aung San, a big liar, who said "if the Burmese get one dollar, you will also get one dollar", the ethnic regions in northern Myanmar that originally belonged to China agreed on a ten-year period and allowed each ethnic group to choose to stay or leave after ten years. Finally, in a small town called "Panglong" in northern Myanmar in 1947, many ethnic leaders in northern Myanmar were successfully gathered and the "Panglong Conference" for the founding of the modern Union of Myanmar was held. On January 4, 1948, it announced its withdrawal from the British Commonwealth and the formal establishment of the Union of Myanmar. This is the origin of the Panglong Agreement.</p> <p>However, after the establishment of the Union of Myanmar, the Burmese army, disguised as the federal army, suppressed various ethnic groups and tried to annex the territorial sovereignty of ethnic minorities. Not only did it not fulfill the promise of Aung San, a big liar, that "if the Burmese get one dollar, you will also get one dollar," but instead discriminated against these ethnic minorities. Millions of ethnic minorities cannot obtain identity cards normally and must bribe Burmese officials with at least several hundred to several thousand dollars to handle it. In order to prevent ethnic minorities in northern Myanmar from leaving the Union of Myanmar in accordance with the Panglong Agreement, the Burmese Government has used its military superiority to wage war against ethnic minorities in northern Myanmar for 70 years, causing countless deaths. The Burmese people are one of the most evil ethnic group in the world.</p> <p>Myanmar is now one of the most notorious regions for this crime, with criminal groups brazenly engaging in kidnapping, human trafficking, and openly harvesting human organs. The Myanmar government and military openly protect these criminal organizations and co-govern the northern region with them, jointly launching armed attacks against anti-telecom fraud militias. Despite China's vigorous crackdown on such crimes, under the protection of the Myanmar government, it cannot penetrate Myanmar to combat criminals more effectively, due to the so-called UN conventions. Myanmar's characteristic crime of establishing telecom fraud rings has never ceased. These criminal groups first force victims to commit fraud, and if it does not yield profit, they resort to torture and organ harvesting. Women who end up in Myanmar are often forced into sexual slavery, impregnated, their breast milk extracted, and newborns used as organ donors. Once the value of a sex slave is exhausted in a fraudulent ring, they are usually resold, or their organs are harvested, after which they are buried alive or slaughtered. China is well aware that large numbers of women and civilians are being kidnapped in Myanmar, subjected to daily torture, rape, or facing organ harvesting, slaughter, or burial alive. They</p>

	<p>also know that the Myanmar government and military serve as protectors of criminals, earning trillions of CNY in illegal profits, yet they cannot send troops to rescue and thoroughly dismantle Myanmar as a criminal state and some criminal organizations. Today's United Nations is like a retirement institution that only consumes salaries, utterly worthless, and only protects criminal states and organizations like Myanmar.</p>
5	<p>During the most difficult times in Vietnam and China, China has provided Vietnam with the greatest unconditional assistance. The Chinese people are not even able to have enough food or decent clothing. Despite this, they provided \$20.9 billion of US dollars in free aid to the Vietnamese people. However, as soon as Vietnam gained independence, it began massacring 1.5 million Chinese, raping countless women, and extorting 12 taels of gold per person, threatening to kill those who refused. If this were ancient times, evil Vietnam would have been wiped out long ago.</p> <p>The evil Vietnamese Communist Party and its government have never compensated 2 million victims or their families.</p> <p>From a moral and emotional perspective, the Communist Party of Vietnam is an evil cult organization disguised under the guise of communist party. It is an evil ruling party that likes to carry out large-scale massacres of the descendants of those who have helped Vietnam. Otherwise, it would be impossible for Vietnam to expel 2 million Chinese people from Vietnam after China provided Vietnam with \$20.9 billion worth of materials for free. Each of the expelled people was extorted for 12 taels of gold. Otherwise, they would be killed. The Vietnamese government even drove countless Chinese people into the sea, resulting in a large number of Chinese drowning. In total, 1.5 million people died. The family of Mark Zuckerberg's wife, Facebook's U.S. CEO, was among those expelled from Vietnam at the time. Fortunately, her family survived. The UN must form a convention and include it in the constitutions of various countries to prohibit Vietnam's ruling party from using the name Communist Party. Otherwise, any country or company is prohibited from trading with it. For those who violate the rules, any country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>For an evil country that massacred 1.5 million innocent civilians or their innocent descendants of other countries, the United Nations must formulate a convention at the same time and include it in the constitutions of various countries. Any evil country that massacres 1.5 million innocent civilians or their innocent descendants of other countries is prohibited from using words such as socialism, democracy, freedom, progress or republic in its national name for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>Communists have lofty spirits and virtues higher than ordinary people. Only by possessing such personality strength can communists be worthy of their titles and win the praise of the people. As early as in the Yan'an period,</p>

Chairman	<p>Mao Zedong clearly pointed out that Communist Party members should be "a noble person, a pure person, a moral person, a person who is free from vulgar tastes, and a person beneficial to the people." The cultivation of communists' noble moral character fundamentally depends on self-awareness and self-discipline.</p> <p>The Communist Party is an organization with noble personality. Its purpose is to serve people. Any ruling party that connives with the army or thugs wantonly slaughtering civilians, plundering civilian property and raping women is an evil criminal party and mafia. It is absolutely not allowed to call itself the Communist Party and damage the reputation of the Communist Party.</p> <p>If these evil people organize and disguise themselves as the Communist Party to carry out large-scale slaughter of civilians, plunder wealth and rape women, people with a sense of justice or countries with a sense of justice around the world must rise up to eliminate, despise and abandon these criminal organizations or their countries. Any country or company that funds such an evil and criminal political party should be condemned.</p> <p>At the end of World War II, official U.S. maps clearly showed that basically all the islands in the South China Sea were islands owned by the hardworking ancestors of China. In ancient times, China had advanced navigation technology. Fishermen often fished and took shelter near the islands in the South China Sea. As early as when Zheng He voyaged to the Western Seas, these islands belonged to China. In the 1950s and 1990s, countries around the South China Sea, regardless of basic facts, illegally occupied many islands belonging to China when China's naval power was weak. Vietnam, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Malaysia are several of the main greedy plundering countries.</p>
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Table7. The event of assets being taken away for various reasons after investing in India. Losses below \$100 million are basically not listed^{11-21,23-29}

No.	List of various bad losses experienced by different companies List of Disguised Fraud History
1	<p>In 2004, the investment attraction policy of India saw business opportunities for POSCO of South Korea. They decided to make a large-scale layout in India and invest 12 billion dollars to build an Ultimate Factories with a capacity of 12 million tons. South Korea's Puhang believes that India has abundant iron ore resources, coupled with extremely low labor costs and weak domestic infrastructure, they can definitely make a lot of money investing here. But it wasn't until they actually invested the money that they realized it wasn't the same thing. In the process of building the factory, the Indian environmental protection department demanded environmental protection fees of up to 15.2 billion rupees, and the land acquisition process cost several billion rupees, forcing them to provide a large number of job positions to benefit local</p>

	<p>residents. India said that they will not be allowed to start factory construction until all these issues are resolved. It took POSCO 5 years and countless funds to forcefully handle all problems properly. After Posco had already invested tens of billions of rupees, India cancelled their factory building permit on the grounds that the 5-year period stipulated in the investment promotion agreement had expired. POSCO has already invested such a huge amount of funds that such a big deal cannot be settled on like this. Otherwise, wouldn't these 5 years become a pure gift package for India? Therefore, POSCO can only struggle with the re approval process by paying tens of billions of rupees again. POSCO, South Korea, spent 11 years preparing for the construction of the factory, until the Indian government officially approved the plan to build the factory in 2015. But at this point, an unofficial organization in India jumped out and said that Posco had caused damage to the Indian people and had to pay huge compensation before starting work. Despite Pohang's continuous efforts to gain rights, it was ultimately forced to withdraw from India in 2016. Over the past 12 years, South Korea's POSCO has invested a lot of money in this, but ultimately did not receive any output.</p>
2	<p>In 2007, Vodafone acquired CPG Investment Company for US \$11.12 billion. The company holds 67% of the shares of India Hutchison, so it gained control over India Hutchison. However, the Indian tax authorities believe that the income from equity transfer should also pay taxes to India, and Vodafone is suspected of tax evasion. Finally, the Indian government issued a \$2 billion ticket to Vodafone.</p> <p>The Indian Parliament has amended relevant laws, breaking the principle that the law cannot be traced back. It has specially customized a rule for Vodafone on the tax collection of overseas company equity transactions, and stipulated that the rule can be traced back 50 years, which has aroused widespread concern in society.</p> <p>Subsequently, the Indian finance department filed a lawsuit again with the Supreme Court against the newly introduced regulations. According to the new bill, the company is considered a tax evasion company and is subject to a 50 year retroactive clause. Based on this judgment, the Supreme Court of India required the company to pay a fine of 5 billion dollars and late fee (including the unpaid late fee of 3 billion dollars). The Indian finance department has accelerated the pace of fines and has issued a total of \$13.5 billion in fines against 17 European and American multinational companies. All European and American multinational companies in India are now in great trouble, which has led to many doubts from the Indian tax authorities. This incident may establish legal precedents and even allow Indian tax authorities to modify regulations and declare the company guilty at any time. Taking this as an example, the tax department can impose arbitrary fines on any company, which is not only a huge burden on the company, but also a huge suffocation of the company, which is worrying.</p> <p>Western countries have coined a new term for this, calling it "tax terrorism".</p>

3	In 2008, India fined Microsoft 7 billion rupees for not paying enough taxes
4	In 2013, India heavily fined IBM \$860 million for monopolistic operations and unfair competition.
5	In 2013, India fined German BMW \$100 million for violating import laws.
6	In 2013, Nokia directly closed its Indian factory due to a \$360 million tax refund.
7	In 2014, Samsung in South Korea was fined \$200 million in taxes.
8	In August 2014, 14 automakers were fined a total of \$650 million for violating fair competition, with Suzuki receiving the highest penalty, reaching \$80 million. In addition, the top few with higher fines are Toyota, Honda, Nissan, and General Motors.
9	In March 2015, Cairn Energy was fined \$1 billion for tax evasion, but Cairn Energy refused to pay. In September, Cairn Energy's \$1 billion worth of shares were confiscated.
10	In 2020, after 11 years of high taxes in India, the Harley motorcycle suffered and it withdrew from India.
11	In 2021, Ford Motor, which had accumulated a loss of \$2 billion in India, also closed some of its manufacturing operations. When Ford established its factory in India, it was under pressure from various local departments, resulting in an investment loss of over \$1 billion over the past 8 years, and ultimately decided to withdraw from the Indian market. However, India prohibits Ford from transferring factory equipment to people from other countries, and all buyers Ford has found themselves have been rejected by India. India prohibited Ford from transferring factory equipment to investors in other countries, resulting in Ford having to sell its \$1 billion modern chemical plant to an Indian company for \$90 million in order to leave. This resulted in a huge loss of \$2 billion for Ford.
12	In 2021, Wal Mart will be fined US \$1.35 billion by India for violating the foreign investment law. Wal Mart can't stand it and will withdraw from the Indian market in 2022.
13	In 2022, India fined another \$212 million for Samsung's tax evasion.
14	In 2022, the Honor Mobile Team withdrew from India
15	In 2022, India fined Amazon \$172 million for violating relevant financial regulations.
16	In July 2022, the Indian government claimed that OPPO mistakenly used tariff exemptions when importing mobile phone parts, requiring it to recover taxes of 3.7 billion CNY; on the grounds of suspected violation of the Money Laundering Prevention Act, 119 bank accounts of Vivo in India were frozen, and they were required to provide CNY 800 million as unfrozen guarantees.
17	On August 3, 2022, the Indian Taxation Intelligence Agency (DRI) issued a notice accusing vivo of tax evasion of 22.17 billion rupees (approximately 1.89 billion CNY). Vivo just said to invest 3 billion CNY
18	In 2022, Google fined \$275 million twice within a week for violating India's antitrust laws.

19	<p>According to foreign media reports, the Indian Law Enforcement Bureau issued a formal notice on the 9th to Xiaomi's subsidiaries, some executives, and relevant banks in India, accusing them of illegally transferring funds overseas and suspected of violating India's Foreign Exchange Management Law. This accusation means that Xiaomi's 4.8 billion yuan frozen by India last year is likely to be formally confiscated, which is also the largest amount of funds confiscated since the establishment of the Indian government.</p> <p>In 2014, Indian Prime Minister Modi proposed the national strategy of "Make in India". Unlike 'Made in India', the new strategy encourages foreign companies to invest and produce in India, rather than simply exporting domestic products. With this east wind, Xiaomi officially entered India. After 10 years of development, Xiaomi has built 7 factories in India, created over 20000 job opportunities, and had a market share of up to 30% at one point. It seems to be developing smoothly, but it will be a resounding blow in 2022. Xiaomi India Company was first accused of tax evasion by the Indian Ministry of Finance in January, with a fine of 558 million yuan. In April, the Indian law enforcement agency directly froze Xiaomi's funds of 4.8 billion yuan, citing that Xiaomi had illegally remitted funds to foreign entities under the name of "royalties" since 2015.</p> <p>At the beginning, Xiaomi was optimistic about the situation and believed that "all operations strictly comply with local laws and regulations, and paying royalties is a legitimate commercial arrangement that will work closely with government departments and clarify any misunderstandings". At the same time, Xiaomi filed a lawsuit with the Indian High Court. But in April of this year, an Indian court rejected Xiaomi's appeal, and recently the Indian Law Enforcement Agency officially issued a notice of charges.</p> <p>At its peak in India, Xiaomi's annual profit was also less than 500 million yuan. If this 4.8 billion yuan fine is finally implemented, it would be equivalent to Xiaomi working in India for 10 years in vain.</p> <p>Although Xiaomi has lodged an appeal at present, in June, the Indian Karnataka High Court finally ruled that the confiscation of about 4.8 billion yuan from Xiaomi India Company rejected Xiaomi's appeal, which means that Xiaomi can hardly get the money back.</p> <p>On June 13th, shortly after the official charges against Xiaomi were filed, the Indian government demanded that the CEO, CFO, COO, and other executives of Chinese smartphone manufacturers "must be Indian nationals", and that local enterprises participate in the production process and local distributors participate in the export process.</p>
20	<p>After "confiscating" RMB 4.8 billion of Xiaomi, India tried to take full control of Chinese enterprises and once again extended its black hand to SAIC Motor, a Chinese car company.</p> <p>Recently, the Hindustan Times reported that India Jindal Southwest Group (JSW for short) is trying to acquire part of the equity of Mingjue Automobile India Co., Ltd., a wholly-owned subsidiary of SAIC Motor in India.</p>

	<p>According to the progress, JSW Group will hold a 45% -48% stake in SAIC MG India, with dealers and Indian employees holding a 5% -8% stake. In this way, India will hold over 51% of the shares.</p> <p>After such an operation, SAIC Motor will become a minority shareholder and lose control of its Indian subsidiary, and Mingjue India will become a company controlled by Indians.</p> <p>After 6 years of development and investing so much money, while the development momentum is still good, the MG India Company was taken away by India, which is regrettable.</p> <p>For many years, India has been a huge magnet and graveyard for foreign investment, with many foreign investors coming in one after another but ultimately failing.</p> <p>According to foreign media, India has begun to review the accounts of more than 500 Chinese enterprises in India, including almost all Chinese companies in almost all, such as Huawei, Ali, Baidu, Tencent, etc.</p>
21	<p>In 2023, Weichuang, an Apple foundry that had been hit, smashed, and looted by Indian workers, announced its full withdrawal from the Indian market. Apple's OEM factory was sold for \$500 million, and Weichuang has never made a profit in India, claiming to have not made a penny in 15 years.</p>
22	<p>Shanghai Electric was defrauded of CNY 8.8 billion by India and claimed CNY 2.1 billion.</p> <p>Shanghai Electric is the largest manufacturer of electrical equipment in China. Large thermal power plants, hydropower stations, nuclear power plants and photovoltaic power plants all use power generation devices made by Shanghai Electric. In overseas markets, SAIC Electric has successively entered dozens of countries around the world, including Mongolia, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Egypt, Serbia, Croatia, etc.</p> <p>What Shanghai Electric did not expect was that it would fall into the hands of India and be cheated by India for CNY 8.8 billion at one time. Even if you don't pay, the Indian company that defrauded Shanghai Electric also went against the wind and sued Shanghai Electric in the reverse direction, claiming CNY 2.1 billion.</p>

The content of table 5 has been made public below:

Liu, L. (2023). A New Metrological Theory for Assessing and Grading the Value of International Settlements and Reserve Currencies. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138301>

Table 8. Reclassification of past, present, and future social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives (Continued Table 4). The reclassification of human social systems like an encyclopaedia.

Reclassification of Human social systems	Country
A society or country that fabricates illness and forcibly sends normal	

people to mental hospital.	
An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that likes to commit large-scale heinous crimes and does not compensate all the losses of the victims and severely punish criminals, or a criminal country or evil criminal society that protects those who commit large-scale heinous crimes, does not compensate all the losses of the victims and severely punishes the criminals.	
An evil criminal society or An evil criminal country has long been fond of deliberately fabricating lies about companies in other countries' tax arrears or tax evasion, seizing most of the property of these companies, or robbing them of control or equity.	
An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that will carry out large-scale heinous crimes when the opportunity arises.	
An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that likes to carry out or protect heinous crimes such as large-scale telecom fraud.	
An evil criminal country or evil criminal society that likes to carry out large-scale heinous crimes or a country that protects criminals who carry out such crimes.	
An evil criminal society or An evil criminal country that commits large-scale heinous crimes such as rape, gang-rape, burying people alive, massacring, and plundering the property of victims, or protects those who carry out such large-scale crimes. This evil criminal country or evil criminal society has never fully compensated the victims for their losses or severely punished the criminals.	
An evil criminal country or An evil criminal society that commits any of the heinous crimes on a large scale, such as telecom fraud, kidnapping, plunder, torture, rape, gang rape, forced organ harvesting, human trafficking, massacre, or protects those who commit such large-scale heinous crimes.	
An evil criminal country or An evil criminal society that commits heinous crimes such as large-scale fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape or forced organ removal, or protects those who commit such heinous crimes on a large scale.	
A criminal country or An evil criminal society controlled by an evil race that likes to carry out large-scale heinous crimes or protect criminals who commit such crimes.	
A society formed by deceiving the public with religion based on fictional history and thus gathering a large number of believers.	
Establish an evil fictional religion by fabricating history, deceive the public, make them gather to form a large number of believers, and thereby establish a society of a specific so-called ethnic group.	
By fabricating history, an evil fictitious religion is established to deceive the public and make them gather to form a large number of believers, thus establishing a specific so-called ethnic society.	

By fabricating history, a fictitious religion is established to deceive the public and make them gather to form a large number of believers, thus establishing a specific so-called ethnic society.	
A fictitious religion based on fabricated history, used to deceive the public, gather them to form a large number of believers, and defraud money from these believers, thus establish a society of a specific religious group.	
A society with a cult system that uses fabricated history to establish an evil religion, fools the public, induces them to believe in this religion, tells believers that this religion must be their only faith, and labels those who don't as heretics.	
A society with a cult system fabricates a religion, induces the public to believe in it, tells believers that it is the only belief that can be followed, and labels those who don't believe as pagans.	

34.8.1. **Fraud - A cultural and educational habit cultivated by Indians since childhood**

In countries where parents generally spread the following belief in educating their offspring: **eating and lying are the two essential factors for a person's survival.**

From psychological analysis, this uncivilized behavior, once formed as a habit since childhood, can be incredibly difficult to change as the individual grows older, and fraudulent behavior will become even more proficient. However, if one cooperates with such people, they may fall into a high probability commercial trap. From the perspective of talent development, educational models and structures, the behaviour of this group may not be universally changed within 20-40 years. Chinese culture expects business partners to benefit together, support and achieve mutual success, and cooperate for the long term. In the event of difficulties, we should find ways to overcome them together. Anyone can make mistakes, and Chinese culture emphasizes tolerance for minor mistakes, rather than having bad intentions, lacking basic ethics, and digging holes that harm business partners.

In July 2014, Japanese scholar and former deputy editor of the Japanese magazine "Modern Weekly", Mr. Daisuke Kondô, wrote about his experience dining at an Indian restaurant in Tokyo and having a conversation with an Indian chef, even though the food he served was not outstanding.

Due to the lack of customers, he conversed with the chef and found his views to be particularly interesting. Here is an English translation of their dialogue from the article:

Indian Chef: "Yes, I really can't understand why you Japanese put so much effort into filling your stomachs. I think Japanese and Chinese cuisines are almost identical! The Chinese also like to make their dishes luxurious and gorgeous. Why is that?"

Mr. Daisuke Kondô: I was surprised again. Because in my impression, Japanese and Chinese people are very different. So I asked again, "Are there any other similarities between Japanese and Chinese people?"

Indian Chef: "There's also the aspect of 'not lying'. **My parents have always taught**

me that 'people have a mouth for two reasons, one is to eat, and the other is to lie'.

So in my consciousness, eating and lying are the two essential elements for a person to survive. However, Japanese and Chinese people have been taught from an early age that 'lying is wrong'! The most similar thing between Japanese and Chinese people is that they are 'too serious'. Indians believe that life is just a game, while Japanese and Chinese people dream of becoming rich and successful. Indians start to leisurely contemplate the afterlife in their old age, while Japanese and Chinese people are still thinking about making money before they die. It's no wonder that Japanese and Chinese people often argue."

Mr. Daisuke Kondô: I see. But doesn't India also have a powerful military and nuclear weapons?

Indian Chef: "The Indians you are talking about are only a small part of India's 1.2 billion people, and the vast majority of Indians are playing the game of life - eating curry, taking naps, watching movies, dancing, sleeping - repeating this cycle endlessly, enjoying it. The difference between humans and other animals like elephants is that humans can play and enjoy themselves. But Japanese and Chinese people are so serious that they are almost mechanical. You are really wasting your life."

Mr. Daisuke Kondô: "I never dreamed that I would hear such a unique philosophy of life in an extremely simple Indian restaurant."

(日)近藤大介

一天早上，一位厨师打扮的印度人在我的东京住所附近发宣传单。我友好地接了过来，他用黑黑的手握住了我的手，热情地说：“今天，我的印度咖喱店开业，欢迎您来捧场。”

当天晚上，我便按照宣传单上的指引找到了这家咖喱店。店里只有两张四人桌，和一个能供三人并排而坐的吧台。店里没有客人，只有那位早上在街边发单传的印度人悠闲地站在吧台后面。

我吃了一顿咖喱饭，喝了几口淡得像水一样的印度啤酒。“酒足饭饱”之后，我发现店里依然只有[来自 www.lw5u.com]我这一位客人。我问：“是不是快打烊了？”

“第一天开业，中午只有两位客人，晚上只有您一位。”他没有正面回答

Fig. 85-25. Indians say that they believe the mouth has two uses: one is for eating, and the other is for lying. Someone even wrote an article specifically about it. A conversation between a Japanese and an Indian. [你们真是在浪费人生. You are really wasting your lives.2022-03-31.]

“第一天开业，中午只有两位客人，晚上只有您一位。”他没有正面回答我，而是开始抱怨起来。

“为了庆祝你的咖喱店隆重开业，我再点一瓶啤酒，咱们一起喝吧。”我抱着安慰他的打算说道。

听我这么说，他露出了一口白牙，笑着取来了啤酒坐在我对面。也许是为了纪念自己第一天“老板生活”的结束，他的话逐渐多了起来。

我没去过印度，对印度的文化也没有太多了解。借着这个机会，我问了一个让我百思不得其解的问题：“为什么你们印度人那么喜欢吃咖喱呢？”

“不吃米饭或者饊会饿肚子，但是米饭和饊都没有什么味道，光吃它们很难下咽，而咖喱就是最简单的下饭菜。”他直爽地回答，

Fig. 85-26. Indian: My parents have always taught me that 'people have a mouth for two reasons, one is to eat, and the other is to lie'. [你们真是在浪费人生. You are really wasting your lives.2022-03-31.]

这个意料之外的答案让我有些吃惊，不由地说了一句：“这和日本料理有点不一样啊。”

他再一次露出了满口的白牙：“是啊。我真是无法理解，你们日本人为什么会在填饱肚子这件事上费尽心思呢？我觉得日本人和中国人在做菜方面简直就是一模一样！以前，我在上海的一家印度料理店打工，偶尔去外面吃中国菜，我发现中国人也喜欢把菜做得奢华绚烂。这到底是为什么呢？”

我再次愕然。因为在我的印象中，日本人和中国人有着很大的区别。于是，我追问道：“那在其他的方面，日本人和中国人还有相似的地方吗？”

“在‘不说谎’这个方面也很像。我的父母一直教育我说‘人之所以有一张嘴，一是为了吃饭，二是为了说谎’。所以在我的意识中，吃饭和说谎是一个人能够活下去的两大要素。可是，日本人和中国人竟然从小就被教育说‘说谎

是不对的’。”

Fig. 85-27. A conversation between a Japanese and an Indian. Indian: My parents have always taught me that 'people have a mouth for two reasons, one is to eat, and the other is to lie'. [你们真是在浪费人生. You are really wasting your lives.2022-03-31.]

人能够活下去的两大要素。可是，日本人和中国人竟然从小就被教育说‘说谎是不对的’！”

我完全说不出话了，只能听他继续说下去。

“日本人和中国人最相似的地方就是‘过于认真’。印度人认为人生不过就是一场比赛，而日本人和中国人做梦都想着飞黄腾达、大富大贵。印度人在垂暮之年开始惬意地思考来生，而日本人和中国人在临死之前还在想着赚钱。”

原来如此呢。但是印度不也拥有强大的军队、核武器吗？

“你说的这种印度人只是印度 12 亿人口中的极少一部分，剩下的绝大多数印度人都在游戏人生——吃咖喱、午睡、看电影、跳舞、睡觉——如此反复，乐此不疲。人类不同于大象等动物的地方在于，人类可以玩耍，可以享乐。但是日本人和中国人竟然认真到了近乎死板的地步，你们真是在浪费人生啊！”

Fig. 85-28. A conversation between a Japanese and an Indian. Indian: My parents have always taught me that 'people have a mouth for two reasons, one is to eat, and the other is to lie'. [你们真是在浪费人生. You are really wasting your lives.2022-03-31.]

Table 8-0 Why do Indians love to lie?

	Why do Indians love to lie? Another story
	An Indian told me he was innocent and was taken the next day! Why do Indians love to lie # Indians # India # Culture. https://v.douyin.com/idPPUt2E/10/27n@d.NjseO:/
1	In terms of work, I met an Indian university student, to be exact, a postgraduate student who is 25 years old and studying engineering for a master's degree in Australia. Among many Indians, he is considered quite neat and tidy, wearing shirts and trousers every day, with glasses, and giving off an intellectual appearance. If you don't associate him with the inherent impression of Indians and those Indian images you see online, he can be considered a talented young man.
2	One day, during a casual chat, he told me that he might have caused trouble. The night before, he was strolling on the street and saw an intoxicated Australian girl, stumbling while walking. Kindly, he helped her and escorted her home. However, when he was leaving, the girl might have misunderstood and didn't know whether he would call the police. After hearing his story, I comforted him, saying, "Oh, you did a good deed, it's just a misunderstanding, nothing to worry about." However, I also had a question mark in my mind. Luckily, life didn't disappoint me. The next day, several police officers appeared right before my eyes and took him away, reportedly searching his house as well. This scene seemed to clear all the doubts in my mind. No need to ask anything anymore, no matter what, he didn't make any mistakes in what he told me, he must have

	lied.
3	About a month later, he had to go to court for sentencing and asked me to help him write a character reference letter, but I politely declined. As for the final outcome, I am aware that he received a relatively light sentence, so it probably wasn't a major offense, but he still broke the law. After this incident, he flew back to his hometown in India, and in the blink of an eye, two years passed. Unfortunately, just after he returned, the pandemic hit.
4	As for the situation in India, most people are well aware of it. I'm discussing this today because some netizens asked me to reflect on the issue of Indians lying. However, the details of the specific offense committed by this Indian person are not the focus of my discussion today. The most profound realization I gained from this incident is that Indians indeed have a tendency to lie, and they are quite good at it. This even exists within Indian graduate education and culture. Why is this the case? After interacting with many Indians, I have come to the conclusion that they have been lying since childhood. Lying about small things is not a big deal in their education and cultural upbringing, especially if it is to save face. They justify lying under such circumstances. Once, an Indian person gave me an example of a situation where an Indian man was fired from his job, but when he returned home, he had to lie to his relatives and exaggerate his success and earnings, lest they ridicule him. In his eyes, this lie was justified, and they may even portray it as a white lie. However, let's not forget that this example of lying was shared by an Indian person.
5	In reality, I believe there are many ugly lies. I have observed a pattern that people who love fantasizing tend to exaggerate and are more prone to telling falsehoods. The Indian people are truly a diligent and intelligent nation. There is a saying, you see, it is said that Western philosophy originated from India. The story goes like this: because Indians are lazy and have nothing to do, they like to lie in banana groves, looking at banana leaves, the sky, or the stars, and daydreaming. Thus, philosophy was born. Perhaps this statement is a bit exaggerated, but it is not entirely unfounded. Indians emphasize their spiritual world, they worship impractical ideals and admire expressive individuals. Therefore, when they talk to others, they only talk about their strengths. While they are busy boasting about themselves, they inadvertently tell lies to cover up their imperfections. Those exaggerated claims that they cannot achieve then become new lies, forming a cycle that starts and ends with lies. Just look at their boasts and grand plans for over a decade, how many of them have actually succeeded?

Fig. 85-29. Video : Now you know why India has earned the title that we all recognize today as a country with a high incidence of rape, right?

The logic of this country with a high incidence of rape, India. The thinking logic of Indian students is really an eye-opener. India, which we call a country with a high incidence of rape. In fact, we can see from the education and cognitive thinking of children that today's result is doomed. Let's watch a video. In this video, we will be very surprised. These Indian students are so young, yet their thinking is like this. I find it very unbelievable.

An Indian girl said that in rape incidents, girls should also be blamed. Girls must have done something wrong to be raped. Another Indian girl said that our teacher said that girls are also at fault in rape incidents. Notice that she mentioned what the teacher said, which means that these teachers in schools instill such cognitive thinking in students. **Another Indian male student said that when girls wear jeans, boys will be attracted at a glance. Wearing jeans can even become a reason for being raped.** Then if he comes to China and sees many girls in our country wearing yoga pants on the street, won't they be so surprised that their jaws drop? **An Indian student said: "When a girl smiles at a boy, the boy feels seduced. That's why rape happens.** Then again, not long ago, **an animal protection official in their country raped a goat**, that is, this animal goat. Is it because the goat is not wearing clothes? **Another Indian male student said that both boys and girls were at fault. Girls should not leave their homes unless they have a job. Thus it can be seen that Indians have a globally rare and evil logic that crime is reasonable.** India is a very bad and evil country. The nature of Indians is generally very bad. Perhaps only extremely rare people have a slightly better nature. **The so-called Indian civilization is all forged by Western missionaries.** Most people who write Indian history have no speculative ability. In our view, isn't such

a statement a typical victim-blaming theory? Yesterday, I also read a news article that said when a South Korean male blogger was traveling in India, he randomly stopped a car. Then, after being warmly invited by the driver in the car to get on, he was drugged. It seems that not only girls but also boys need to be very careful when traveling in India. And there is something that just happened. Today, when I was very surprised by Indian education, I saw another Indian news related to Indian teachers. An Indian male teacher molested **a 13-year-old female student**. Now you know why this country has earned the title that we all recognize today as a country with a high incidence of rape, right?

[2024-09-01. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7409696560105262371>]

One of the largest fraud countries in the world that is best at defrauding the wealth of Americans - India

AUTO TRANSPORTATION SERVICES ▾ INTERNATIONAL PORT TO PORT

AUTO TRANSPORTATION

Indian scam call centers looted over \$20 billion from US citizens over this past few years and how is affecting the transportation industry

POSTED ON 21 MARCH, 2024 BY TRANSPORTG

Fig. 85-30. With 85% of scam calls originating in India

The world's largest fraud country

The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.

In criminal countries where large-scale crimes have occurred, the legal age for marriage must be at least 28 or 30 years old for men and at least 28 or 30 years old for women in order for them to get married and have children.

India has given birth to a population that has been taught to cheat from an early age and has the largest number of fraudulent criminal populations in the world. India must control its birth rate.

India must raise the age of marriage and childbirth for its citizens.

Table 8. Farmer of China and the Snake of Vietnam

<p>Farmer of China and the Snake of Vietnam</p> <p>History always repeats itself in astonishingly similar ways. Forgetting history means betrayal, ignorance, and foolishness.</p> <p>The tragic experiences of the Chinese people after they selflessly helped the Vietnamese people and the Communist Party of Vietnam who were in trouble countless times. At that time, the Guangxi people near the China - Vietnam border would rather fill their stomachs with unpalatable wild vegetables themselves and give rice to the Vietnamese.</p> <p>Americans and Europeans can't imagine how well - mannered the Chinese are towards their friends! They can't imagine at all that the badness of the Vietnamese is deep - rooted and almost incurable. It is just that they are currently militarily weak and it is difficult for them to go to war with powerful countries. Like the Japanese, they can deceive the global public and the United Nations for nearly eighty years, constantly claiming that Japan was the victim of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki. They also gather thousands of people to pretend to be victims of the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, forming teams one by one to freely express their claims of being victims. The Nobel Peace Prize Committee has been severely deceived by the evil Japan and wrongly awarded this year's Nobel Peace Prize to these so - called victims. The Japanese prime minister actually pretends not to know that Japan was not bombed by US nuclear bombs and congratulates the nuclear - bomb - victim groups.</p> <p>China is the only origin of civilization in the world, and the other three major civilizations were forged by European missionaries. It is impossible for humans to have evolved from apes. It is impossible for genetic mutations to turn apes into humans. Darwin's theory of evolution is fundamentally wrong. Humans are products from outer space. Just like the COVID-19 virus, it can't come from nature. It is impossible to be produced by bats or other animals. It is caused by leaks from U.S. laboratories. It is very difficult for the COVID-19 vaccine to prevent novel coronavirus infection, and it is very likely to cause unpredictable severe abnormal reactions and other serious adverse reactions after vaccination. I predicted these two points in January 2020. Therefore, the author of this article has not been vaccinated and has not been infected, even though countless people were infected at that time and the author often came into contact with severely ill patients. Research in this area is a complete waste of scientific research funds and human resources and misleads the treatment of patients. If the author of this article were the top leader of the NIH in the United States, it would be impossible to approve funds for researchers with obviously wrong</p>

	<p>research directions. It is meaningless research with predictable results. The author hopes to help people in the United States and around the world quickly control the spread of the virus, however, relevant articles have been rejected by top - tier journals all the time.</p> <p>The world dominated by Americans and Jews is in a mess. Instead of liking to have exchanges with China, the only origin of civilization in the world, which has long - term civilized manners, order, and self - discipline, the United States wants to destroy China, suppress China, and make China regress. Americans really have extraordinary and strange psyches. American politicians should see psychiatrists. However, Western medicine does not provide solutions to completely cure the mental illnesses of American politicians. If the United States really wants to solve this problem, it may come to me, even though 1.2 billion Chinese have higher IQs than mine.</p>
	<p>The following content in this table about the inhumane atrocities committed by the Vietnamese one by one, which brought great pain to the Pingmeng people in Guangxi with a kind and civilized tradition who once helped the Vietnamese, is from the translation of Chinese literature.</p>
1	<p>Pingmeng Area, Napo County, Guangxi was a former base for the revolution led by Chairman Ho Chi Minh. It is known as the "homeland of the Vietnamese revolution" on Chinese soil. Many Chinese elders in this area fought against French colonialism alongside Vietnamese leaders, many suffered injuries and shed blood for Vietnam. Su Zhongliang, a revolutionary veteran who is now in his seventies, once risked his life to hide Chairman Ho Chi Minh in a cave and escaped from the enemy's pursuit. During those difficult years, the local people would rather dig wild vegetables for themselves and save their scarce food to give to their Vietnamese comrades who were leading the revolution there.</p>
2	<p>In 1963, during Vietnam's National Day celebration, the Vietnamese invited Su Zhongliang and the revolutionary veteran Li Yuanyong from Pingmeng Area to a banquet in Hanoi. Chairman Ho Chi Minh and other Vietnamese leaders personally welcomed and sent them off and warmly said, "We will invite you again when our north and south are unified." More than a decade later, Vietnam was unified. Su Zhongliang, Li Yuanyong, and the people of Pingmeng were so happy for the victory of the Vietnamese people! However, there was no response from Vietnam's "invitation," and Su Zhongliang never expected that Vietnamese armed personnel would bury landmines outside his home.</p>
3	<p>Li Yuanyong's daughter-in-law was shot by Vietnamese gunmen while cutting grass within Chinese territory. The most infuriating incident was the encounter of a young villager. When his wife gave birth, he went to his sister's house in Vietnam to share the good news, and was unreasonably arrested by the Vietnamese. They chopped off his limbs and tied him to a tree as a live target to be shot at random until he died...</p>
4	<p>An elderly guerrilla fighter, Zhao Zhinan, who once stood guard and delivered letters to Chairman Ho Chi Minh, angrily told reporters, "For decades, we have regarded Vietnam's anti-colonial and construction work as our own, fulfilling our</p>

	<p>greatest internationalist duty without any regrets towards Vietnam. Today, the Vietnamese authorities have betrayed us and our deep China-Vietnam friendship, disregarding the lives of the Vietnamese people. It's truly treacherous and immoral!"</p>
5	<p>Friendship Pass is a historical witness to the friendship between China and Vietnam. During the difficult years of the Vietnam War, bombs were exploding outside Friendship Pass while an iron flow of vehicles roared beneath it. Day and night, Chinese trains and cars carrying aid to Vietnam filled the pass without interruption. Under Friendship Pass, Chinese border troops warmly received waves of Vietnamese refugees fleeing from American aircraft bombings. To accommodate the transportation of aid supplies to Vietnam, roads were widened and train stations expanded. However, today, due to the deliberate deterioration of bilateral relations by the Hanoi authorities, the sound of trains and the sight of cars have disappeared beneath Friendship Pass, replaced by the sound of gunfire as the Vietnamese side shoots towards China.</p>
6	<p>In Pingxiang City, within the Friendship Pass, Hua Zhengxing is responsible for the transportation of military aid supplies on the Pingxiang railway section. He is an old soldier who had participated in the Battle of Dien Bien Phu in Vietnam. Later, he fought for the friendship between the people of China and Vietnam both inside and outside the Friendship Pass for 28 years. Flipping through the old duty diaries, he said to the reporter, "Comrade journalist, look through these books and see how the Vietnamese authorities are treating us now. I really can't understand it!" He told the reporter that during the ten years of the Vietnam War, nearly 400,000 tons of military supplies were transported from Pingxiang to Vietnam annually, including everything from the soldiers' clothes to their hats, which amounted to 800 million USD. At that time, under simple equipment conditions, our comrades at the transportation station each carried an average of 12 tons of goods per day. Many people often became so exhausted that they fainted in the cargo compartments. However, they still encouraged each other, saying, "We would rather sweat more ourselves than let our Vietnamese brothers shed blood!" But now, the Vietnamese authorities spread rumors, slander our support work, and send armed personnel to injure our people. They have done things that we never could have imagined.</p>
7	<p>Yong Guizhong, whose left leg was blown off by a landmine buried by Vietnam within our territory, spoke out against the brutal crimes of the Vietnamese reactionary authorities at a mass meeting attended by thousands of people in the Friendship Pass area. Yong Guizhong is the son of the former militia hero, Yong Yingting. Yong Yingting made significant contributions to supporting Vietnam in its fight against French invasion and against the United States. He attended our National Militia Representative Conference and was awarded a semi-automatic rifle by the Ministry of Defense. Following in the footsteps of his father, Yong Guizhong became a militia member and dedicated himself to ensuring the safe transportation of aid materials to Vietnam. He patrolled and guarded the roads day and night, with the sole aim of allowing the Vietnamese</p>

	people to enjoy a peaceful and happy life as soon as possible. Who would have expected that today, the Vietnamese authorities would have turned him into a disabled person by blowing him up!
8	On the vast Gulf of Tonkin, there used to be a story of cooperation and solidarity between fishermen from China and Vietnam, working together and fighting side by side. But now, Vietnamese pirates are rampant, causing our fishermen not only to be unable to fish normally but also staining the blue sea with blood. One day, a reporter came to the shore of the Gulf of Tonkin in northern Guangxi and spoke to an old fisherman hiding in the fishing port for shelter. The fisherman said that during the Vietnam War, the Vietnamese side laid underwater mines in their own territorial waters in the Gulf of Tonkin. As a result, tens of thousands of Vietnamese fishermen came to our territorial waters to fish and seek refuge. We warmly received them, helping to repair their broken ships and mend their torn fishing nets. We provided them with rice and firewood when they were short of supplies. We treated them like family and considered them as brothers. Our navy also frequently dispatched warships to escort and protect Vietnamese fishing boats, rescue them in times of danger, and help them clear the waters of mines, opening up the "China-Vietnam Friendship Passage." Several young sailors sacrificed their lives in the process.
9	A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a long time. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.

Table 9. Farmer of China and the Snake of Vietnam

	The 20th century Farmer and the Snake was staged in Vietnam. —2 http://www.1979217.cn/?p=16 https://zhuanlan.zhihu.com/p/265645749 A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a long time. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.
1	Before the China-Vietnamese Self-Defense Counterattack, Zhao Zhinan, an old guerrilla fighter from Pingmeng Village, pointed out incisively and vividly that the Chinese people have never done anything to offend Vietnam in nearly half a century. The reason why the Le Duan Group betrayed its trust and occupied Chinese territory was to destroy the evidence of their ingratitude.
2	As early as 1974, Le Duan began to initiate plans to encroach on Chinese territory. The Pingmeng area was just a part of Le Duan's invasion plan, and the specific execution of the plan to occupy Pingmeng was carried out by the

	Vietnamese 246th Regiment.
3	At first, the Vietnamese 246th Regiment used photos left behind by Ho Chi Minh and other founding fathers of North Vietnam when they lived in the Pingmeng Village area as "evidence." They pointed to some background in the photos and claimed that Pingmeng Village belonged to Vietnam because most of the North Vietnamese founding fathers had lived there for many years. They demanded that China "return" Pingmeng Village to Vietnam.
4	However, in 1956, Vietnamese Prime Minister Pham Van Dong, on behalf of the Ho Chi Minh government, acknowledged the China-Vietnamese Land Border Agreement signed between the French colonial government and the Qing Dynasty government of China. Pingmeng Village is an inherent part of Chinese territory. Pham Van Dong, as a core member of the Le Duan Group, still held the position of Vietnamese Prime Minister during the provocation by the Vietnamese 246th Regiment. China questioned Pham Van Dong, asking what his intentions were. The Vietnamese 246th Regiment failed to escalate the situation.
5	Later, the Vietnamese 246th Regiment only dared to secretly come to the Pingmeng Village area at night to lay landmines, set up barbed wire, or bury bamboo stakes. The Baise Military District organized local militias to patrol day and night and remove obstacles set up by the Vietnamese troops.
6	On August 25, 1978, after the Vietnamese Public Security 12th Regiment, 1st Company, and 4th Company occupied the Chinese territories of Punieling and Puyingding in Tongdeng Town, Liangshan Province, Vietnam, the 246th Regiment of the Vietnamese Army couldn't sit still and directly used mortars and light and heavy machine guns to launch a large-scale invasion of the Pingmeng area in Napo County, Guangxi.
7	On September 29, as members of the Pingmeng Production Brigade were preparing for work, gunfire suddenly erupted. Militia soldiers carrying out border patrol missions discovered that large numbers of Vietnamese infantry were advancing towards the residential settlements in Pingmeng village.
8	The Vietnamese Army came prepared, and the Pingmeng Commune was temporarily unable to resist such a large number of Vietnamese troops, so they had to evacuate the people immediately. During the evacuation process, more than 10 people tragically lost their lives due to gunfire from the Vietnamese Army.
9	This was the largest bloodshed event planned by Vietnamese authorities following the "Punieling Bloodshed Incident". During the invasion of the Pingmeng area, the Vietnamese 246th Regiment deployed the forces of 1,200 soldiers to use force against thousands of unarmed civilians in the Pingmeng area of Napo County, Guangxi. This is an undeniable massacre event.
	The 20th century Farmer and the Snake was staged in Vietnam. —3 https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1730467093454189635&wfr=spider&for=pc https://zhuankan.zhihu.com/p/265645749

1	<p>"The Case of Redemption with Twelve Tael Gold or \$1500 to \$3000"</p> <p>In the second half of 1977, the Li Sun Group, under the pretext of "border purification," prohibited Vietnamese civilians from approaching the border and coastline, effectively controlling the land and sea routes for people to flee Vietnam. They then implemented a commercial operation model, where anyone wanting to leave Vietnam had to surrender twelve tael gold or \$1500 to \$3000. Of this amount, five-sixths of the gold or dollars went to the Vietnamese "treasury," while the remaining one-sixth served as a processing fee. This incident is known as the "Vietnamese Case of Redemption with Twelve Tael Gold."</p> <p>The so-called processing fee, however, only included a small portion for transportation expenses, with the majority being "legitimate" commissions that flowed into the pockets of Vietnamese officials. It was from this time onwards that officials in various Vietnamese departments developed the habit of openly soliciting bribes. Even today, some personnel at Vietnam's immigration checkpoints consider it perfectly normal to demand bribes during passport inspections.</p>
2	<p>The Vietnamese authorities use the pretext of expelling Chinese citizens to forcibly remove a certain number of civilians each month based on quotas set by each province. Among those expelled are not only people of Chinese descent but also some families who have been Vietnamese citizens for up to five generations, or citizens from other countries.</p> <p>For those who are expelled but cannot produce gold or dollars, they are either forcibly sent to "economic zones" to do manual labor or are killed or mysteriously disappear.</p> <p>In June 1978, the Vietnamese authorities directly participated in the operation of smuggling groups and established a department for refugee outflows, headed by Vietnamese Prime Minister Pham Van Dong. This department colluded with criminal organizations in countries and regions such as Hong Kong, the Philippines, and Australia, openly engaging in human trafficking activities.</p>
3	<p>Using refugees as weapons</p> <p>The Vietnamese authorities uses methods of harming the Vietnamese people and creating refugees in order to not only obtain funds to support their ongoing war efforts in a short period of time, but also to sow seeds of instability in the region.</p> <p>Since 1975, the United States, Canada, Australia, France, and various Southeast Asian countries have annually uncovered intelligence operatives infiltrated by Vietnamese authorities among Vietnamese refugees.</p> <p>These Vietnamese spies carry out various tasks, including assassinations, military sabotage, and intelligence gathering, posing a significant threat to the security of host countries.</p> <p>On June 30, 1976, the Thai security department discovered an intelligence operative disguised as a Vietnamese refugee in a refugee camp along the Thai-</p>

	<p>Cambodian border. The suspect, posing as a "refugee," continuously collected military targets within Thailand.</p> <p>On July 14, 1979, the Philippines captured two Vietnamese spies disguised as refugees. These two suspects conducted surveys on an uninhabited island in the Philippines.</p> <p>In August 1979, the Chicago Tribune pointed out that since February 1979, every Vietnamese ship leaving Vietnam had Vietnamese intelligence operatives onboard.</p> <p>Thus, on August 13, 1979, the Indonesian Times bluntly stated that the Lisan Group infiltrates spies among refugees, seriously undermining peace in the region. In the near future, Vietnam will send more spies disguised as refugees to carry out various destructive activities.</p>
4	<p>On June 12, 1979, after conducting in-depth investigations, a journalist from The New York Times discovered that Vietnam had confiscated a large amount of gold from civilians, which was then transported to Ho Chi Minh City in Vietnam for smelting and refining. The gold was subsequently sent to Moscow via military transport planes, where it was used to purchase Soviet weapons or repay debts.</p> <p>During the late 1970s to mid-1980s, it was evident that many gold bars sold by the Soviet Union to European countries bore markings left by the Vietnamese authorities.</p> <p>Thanks to the support of the Soviet Union, whenever Vietnam was accused by other countries of deliberately creating regional turmoil by exporting refugees, Vietnam could always fabricate claims that China posed a threat to Vietnam's security, leading to a large number of Vietnamese civilians "fleeing" the country.</p> <p>In August 1979, as Vietnam's founding leader, Huang Wenxuan, was critically ill, he made the courageous decision to move to China and exposed the true nature of the Li Sun Group's atrocities against Vietnamese civilians and their military expansion. He quickly recruited an "Anti-Li Sun Liberation Force" from the Vietnamese refugees residing in China, to reveal the sinister face of both the Soviet Union and Vietnam.</p> <p>A righteous person does not fear shadows. In order to safeguard its own security and regional peace, China launched a retaliatory self-defense operation against Vietnam on February 17, 1979, followed by a border war that lasted for ten years. Throughout the process of striking the Vietnamese army, the Soviet Union never dared to openly intervene and assist Vietnam.</p> <p>https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1730467093454189635&wfr=spider&for=pc</p>
	<p>The 20th century Farmer and the Snake was staged in Vietnam. —4 https://zhuanlan.zhihu.com/p/410102726</p>
	<p>China's free assistance to Vietnam.</p> <p>The plan and ambition of Vietnam to annex Cambodia, Thailand, Myanmar, Bangladesh, India, Bhutan, Nepal, Pakistan, China, the United States, etc.</p>

1	On November 20, 1979, the Chinese People's Daily announced, "During the Vietnam War, China dispatched a total of over 320,000 support troops, including air defense, engineering, railways, and logistics. The highest number of troops reached over 170,000 in a single year."
2	According to statistics, starting from 1950 when Ho Chi Minh sought help from China until the complete cessation of aid due to the deteriorating relations in 1978, China provided Vietnam with over 20 billion US dollars in assistance, which is equivalent to over 50 trillion yuan in gold value today.
3	Despite spending so much money, China still raised a white-eyed wolf, as Mr. Zhai Qiang described it. The massive material support resulted in Vietnam turning its blade against China, and China did not receive gratitude from the Vietnamese.
4	Vietnam has always been China's little brother throughout history, but at that time, they had such an ambitious plan that they even formulated a detailed plan to swallow China and destroy America. The Vietnamese government not only had the idea but also developed a comprehensive plan: Vietnam declared China as its number one enemy and actively attacked Chinese forces to eliminate all Chinese troops and occupy Chinese territory. Vietnam invaded and occupied "barbaric" countries such as Laos, Cambodia, Thailand, Myanmar, Bangladesh, India, Bhutan, Nepal, and Pakistan. Vietnam planned to invade and occupy the United States and merge all territories worldwide into Vietnamese territory, in collaboration with the Soviet Union, aiming to "unify the world." Although it seems like a joke to us now, this plan would have been a serious blow to us if it had been realized at the time.
5	The second plan, however, was quickly put into practice by the Vietnamese:
6	In December 1976, the decision of the 4th National Congress of the Communist Party of Vietnam clearly defined the policies towards Laos and Cambodia, initiating the unscrupulous implementation of control, overthrow, aggression, and annexation in these two countries.
7	Starting in 1977, Vietnamese authorities continuously engaged in military provocations and invasion operations in the border areas between Vietnam and Cambodia.
8	In September 1977, the Vietnamese army launched the first invasion offensive, penetrating several tens of kilometers into Cambodian territory in some areas.
9	In December 1977, they launched the second offensive, employing 14 divisions to invade the eastern and southwest regions of Cambodia, but were defeated by the Khmer Rouge regime.
10	In the same year, Vietnam forced the Laotian authorities to sign a so-called "friendship and cooperation treaty" and a border agreement. They not only annexed large areas of Laotian territory along the border but also exerted strict political influence on Laos. Under the pretext of "aid" and "cooperation," Vietnam engaged in economic plundering of Laos.
11	In November 1978, Vietnam signed a "friendship and cooperation treaty" with the Soviet Union. With the support of the Soviet Union, Vietnam deployed

	250,000 troops on December 25, 1978, and launched a full-scale invasion of Cambodia. Led by the traitors Hun Sen and Kang Kek Iew, the Vietnamese military occupied Cambodia entirely and propped up the puppet regime of the "People's Republic of Kampuchea."
1 2	It can be said that after Vietnam freed itself from American aggression, it wasted no time. The Vietnamese army, fresh from the baptism of the Vietnam War, was undoubtedly much stronger than the neighboring weak countries. With the support of the Soviet Union and armed with various Soviet-style equipment in all branches of the military, Vietnam had become a dominant power in Southeast Asia.
1 3	Imagine if Vietnam were allowed to continue developing in this way, it would have essentially unified Southeast Asia and established a "Great Vietnam" within a few years.
1 4	Is Vietnam a trustworthy nation? Vietnam is a nation that can make friends? Would a true Communist Party rape women? They executed Chinese overseas who couldn't pay for 12 ounces of gold. Would it kill 1.5 million Chinese overseas? When Vietnam becomes strong, the world is likely to face a massacre, and the Vietnamese will not only plunder your wealth, but also your life.
1 5	A profound lesson: a country that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the foundation of the nation, and citizens of a nation that does not take empathy, conscience and morality as the highest standard for being a person and dealing with affairs, must not be helped casually, and even less can they be helped for a long time. Otherwise, it is to strangle good people, raise lone wolves, trigger wars, destroy peace, and strangle civilization.

Revealing the arrogant plans of the Vietnamese people: defeating China, occupying the United States, and dividing the world equally with the Soviet Union. July 26, 2019. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1640109995299386548&wfr=spider&for=pc>

34.10. It is wrong and childish for Western politicians to use ideology to create national opposition in philosophy and history.

When Marx created the classification method of social systems, he overly emphasized ideology, which objectively caused opposition between countries with different systems.

Marx lacked understanding and research on Chinese history and failed to clarify the socialist system, capitalist system, and communist system. China had **extremely time traveling ideology** of socialist and even communist ideas as early as the dynasty founded by Wang Mang around 5 A.D. In the middle and late Tang Dynasty of China, the characteristics of monopoly capitalism characterized by the liberalist market economy were very obvious. The financial industry in the Tang Dynasty was very developed and radiated to the surrounding countries of the Silk Road, but the characteristics of privatization, private monopoly or market economy system were

very obvious. **It can be said that according to Marx's classification method, the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China were all capitalist systems.**

From the perspective of historical origin, China's current social system originated from the improved version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty. It was formed by the Communist Party of China and its leaders based on China's national conditions and practical development, and has the theoretical and practical basis of philosophy and history. Stalin, the supreme leader of the former Soviet Union, clearly pointed out that China's social system did not conform to the socialist system proposed by Marx. China's current socialist system **(the new Equal-field system)** is an original creation in China and is set up to solve the unavoidable historical cycle law that emerged when the equal-field system was implemented in the early Tang Dynasty. In China, public ownership and collective ownership of farmers are implemented for land, and private sale of land and permanent ownership of land is prohibited.

The Tang Dynasty system was actually composed of the 1.0 version of the equal-field system in the early Tang Dynasty with the early characteristics of socialism. After experiencing institutional changes and loss of control in the middle period, the entire Tang society gradually entered the 2.0 version of the capitalist monopoly system of crazy mergers and acquisitions characterized by the new liberalist market economy. Finally, due to the large gap between the rich and poor in society and the high concentration of social wealth, **the Huang Chao Uprising (黄巢起义) occurred**. The **uprising** army killed eight million bureaucrats and plutocrats, eliminating the plutocrats who affected Chinese society and entering a new cycle of selecting talents through examinations and a new land distribution system. In the West, financial crises and economic crises keep emerging, which is also a repeatedly occurring situation formed by the monopoly of private capital based on liberal political and economic thinking.

Gorbachev once asked the Americans to help design the capitalist system, which resulted in the former Soviet Union's social wealth being concentrated in private hands in a short period of time. In the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China, there were obvious typical characteristics of a capitalist system society. The financial industry was privatized, free transactions were realized, and mergers and monopolies were free. If Russia or the U.S. hopes that China can help design a freer method and system to concentrate social wealth on a few specific individuals or the rich, it is believed that the Chinese have more historical experience than the Americans. The Chinese only found that the free monopoly system in the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in China would only bring disasters, so in the early periods of different dynasties after the Tang Dynasty in China, they tended to a non-liberal monopolistic capitalist system. If politicians, the public, and the media in the United States and around the world think that the improved version of the equal-field system implemented in China is not essentially superior to the liberalist merger and monopoly system in the middle and late periods of the Tang Dynasty in the United States, it should be ignorance of history and the law of historical cycles.

Each country has its unique history, culture, social background and development needs. China's system is not suitable for the United States today. However, if the

current social system of the United States is transferred to China, the result of free monopoly and merger-driven economic development will only trigger the cycle law of social system change in populous China. There will surely be new **uprising** armies in China that will kill a large number of greedy politicians and plutocrats. If the situation escalates, greedy politicians and plutocrats in the United States or other places who are closely connected with China will also be killed. And China will implement a new equal-field system again. Perhaps it is difficult for Westerners to understand why such things will happen.

34.11. The periodic law of the asset marketization system following the 80/20 rule or the democratic free asset market system. =The System of Middle and Late Tang Dynasty in China=The Asset Marketization System in the U.S.

Due to the principles of democracy and freedom, which maximize the allocation of assets for self-realization, the idea, power, and voting rights that determine asset marketization and financial marketization, national assets cannot avoid large-scale marketization or repeated marketization, nor can they avoid large-scale acquisition of core assets by interest groups. As a result, the country's future will inevitably move with the large-scale marketization and acquisition of core assets. When a country's most important means of production or land assets are concentrated in the hands of a few people as the core of financial marketization, the 80/20 rule dictates that this leads to a huge structural change in the asset allocation of the entire society, making it difficult for the country to achieve a balanced use of resources among all social strata, leading to economic or financial crises. Once the world recognizes that the highly marketized asset system following the 80/20 rule is similar to the political, economic, and financial system of China's late Tang Dynasty, and is the cause of economic or financial crises, these countries are unlikely to be easily plundered by their wealth. When internal contradictions within a country cannot be reconciled, it is difficult for the rich to release their wealth to reverse domestic economic or financial crises, which may lead to war. If the country is unable to plunder the wealth of other countries through war or financial means, it may also lead to internal division, with rich regions and impoverished regions separating. However, when a country is about to enter a new era, it is likely to kill off the previous controllers of the interest groups that have affected the country, leading to a redistribution of monopoly assets, and then society will enter a period of foundation building, growth, and prosperity. The pursuit of maximizing private interests in assets will inevitably lead to a new wave of asset marketization and consolidation, ultimately forcing the country to face another crisis. Therefore, countries with a system centred on asset marketization will continue to repeat this cycle, as it is the historical law of countries dominated by fully marketized capital. Unless there is internal change and the adoption of a system such as the equal-field system or socialism to restrain large interest groups, and a rational negative feedback control mechanism for the redistribution of important means of production in the country.

34.12. Kibbutz in Israel: Exploration, challenges and future of an approximate

communist system.

In today's global economic and political landscape, different ideologies and social systems collide and coexist. As a unique social and economic organizational form, Israel's kibbutz, with its system concept similar to communism, has lasted for about 100 years. It is the only income and achievement distribution system in the world that has long realized an open and free communist model, showing completely different concepts and practices from the mainstream capitalist model. Every year, it attracts many tourists and people with socialist or communist ideas to visit, providing the world with a perspective for in-depth thinking about the diversity of social systems.

The first kibbutz in Israel was built in 1910. There are currently 275 kibbutzim of various sizes in the country. The population of each kibbutz ranges from 200 to 3,000 people. Today, the population living in Kibbutzim is about 120,000, accounting for only about 1.2% of the national population. However, the value of agricultural output accounts for about 42% of the country's total, and agricultural exports account for 43% of the country's total. It is Israel's main agricultural production base.

The kibbutz is an ideal collective society. Here there is no status hierarchy, no difference between mental and manual labor, and no private property. Each kibbutz is a micro-society that engages in diversified operations. In the community, there are restaurants, auditoriums, office buildings, and libraries; there are farms, orchards, factories, and livestock farms; there are tourism, sightseeing, stores, and tourist centers; there are nurseries, schools, hospitals, post offices, and nursing homes; there are entertainment, stadiums, and fitness facilities. The kibbutz public cafeteria is not only a place for employees to eat collectively, but also a restaurant for receiving tourists. Three meals a day are buffet style and all are free (not free for tourists).

Despite these problems, the future of kibbutzim is not entirely bleak. On the one hand, kibbutzim can actively carry out reforms and innovations to adapt to the development needs of modern society. In terms of economy, kibbutzim can further explore diversified development paths. Combining their own advantages and market demands, they can develop characteristic industries and service industries. For example, by taking advantage of the natural environment and cultural characteristics of Kibbutzim, develop the tourism industry and attract domestic and foreign tourists. At the same time, kibbutzim can introduce modern enterprise management concepts. On the basis of maintaining collective ownership, appropriately stimulate individual initiative and creativity and improve production efficiency. Kibbutzim, on the other hand, can continue to play its unique role in social values. The spirit of sharing, unity and mutual assistance advocated by kibbutzim still has important significance in today's society. It can become a platform for social experiments and provide new ideas and methods for solving social problems. For example, in dealing with aging, environmental protection, educational innovation and other aspects, kibbutzim can give play to its collective advantages and explore sustainable solutions.

In order to meet the development needs of the times, it may continue to play its unique role in the future and provide people with a more just, harmonious and sustainable social model. It is not only a unique landscape of Israeli society, but also provides valuable experience and inspiration for the development of global society.

In conclusion, Israel's kibbutz, as a system practice similar to communism, has achieved remarkable achievements in the past years, but also faces some unavoidable obstacles and flaws, mainly as follows:

First, Israel's kibbutz has huge limitations. Israel's territory comes from the plunder of Palestine and locks Palestine in a narrow range. In fact, this is the behavior of using Israel's internal collective economic system of win-win cooperation to achieve Israel's external expansion and consolidate the goal of plundering Palestinian territory. This is an extremely selfish act. The success of Israel's kibbutz is built on the pain of the original Palestinian residents. Members of Israel's kibbutz are similar to the pioneer groups dispatched to Northeast China during the Japanese invasion of China. They occupy Chinese people's land by various means, resulting in the difficult life of Northeast farmers whose land has been plundered or snatched by tricks. Even those who create communist life in Israel's kibbutz cannot cross the fence of the name of invaders.

Second, Judaism is modern fiction. There is no Jewish nation constructed by bloodline. Instead, it is constructed by belief. The theories promoted by Judaism are actually very selfish, self-interested, greedy, and cunning. The secular goal of Jews is to do business and gain benefits. The secular god of the Jewish people is money. In front of it, all gods must abdicate. Members of the kibbutz believe in Judaism and it is difficult to substantially get rid of the influence of Judaism. If Jews in Israel want to further expand the development area of kibbutz, they must abolish overly selfish, greedy, and forged Judaism, revise the lie that Jehovah's savior created humans and the world, and make it clear that Judaism is a religious fiction in modern times (**This can be proven by mathematical methods. If you or your friends have a certain foundation in mathematics, you might as well give it a try and see if you or your friends can prove mathematically in a day or three days or a week that Judaism is fiction after the 16th century.**). Only in this way can they be freed from spiritual shackles and put an end to conflicts and wars with the world. Otherwise, kibbutz is the cradle for cultivating war members.

Third, Kibbutz trained many soldiers for the founding of Israel. In the first four Middle East wars of which Israel is most proud, the leaders were all children of kibbutz farms, and many soldiers were kibbutz members. After the appearance of kibbutz farms, many Jews were busy farming on the farms during the busy farming season and training in their spare time. They also handed over surplus agricultural products to the Palmach guerrillas and Haganah (Zionist armed forces). Palmach guerrillas and Haganah members are also scattered in kibbutz farms at ordinary times. If Israel or Jews hope that kibbutz can continue to develop and grow, and to truly achieve social justice, fairness, and fairness by implementing socialist and communist systems, Israel must make major changes. According to the relevant provisions of the United Nations, occupied Palestinian territory should be returned to Palestine, and the two sides should negotiate the assumption of responsibility and compensation for war losses.

34.13. Lessons and experiences in the process of optimizing social systems in China.

There are various reasons for the failure of advanced rural cooperatives,

communal dining halls, and people's communes in China in the 1950s.

First, instead of proceeding step by step through a pilot model, there was an illusion of quickly surpassing the Soviet Union and entering communist society. Rural advanced cooperatives and people's communes were quickly organized, although with good intentions. **Second**, in a situation divorced from reality, nationwide political campaigns such as low-quality mass steel-making, the Great Leap Forward, merging small cooperatives into large ones, and releasing high-yield satellites seriously disrupted agricultural production. In particular, the false and exaggerated style of seriously overreporting grain production led to more grain being requisitioned, and instead farmers went hungry. **Third**, unlike kibbutzim, there was no screening, evaluation, and elimination of voluntary joiners. **Fourth**, the leading cadres of people's communes were not democratically elected by the masses but appointed by higher-level authorities. Even if the masses in the commune knew that the cadres were violating regulations or had low abilities, the masses had no power to remove unqualified leaders by voting on their own, resulting in farmers having no enthusiasm to participate. After criticizing the leaders, they would receive very bad treatment.

Nevertheless, the implementation of rural cooperatives and people's communes in China during a specific historical period had profound historical background and positive significance. At that time, China was facing a very poor situation with a weak agricultural foundation and almost zero industry. The establishment of rural cooperatives and people's communes integrated rural resources to a certain extent, improved the degree of organization of agricultural production, and provided a large amount of funds, raw materials and labor support for the country's industrialization construction. At the same time, during the period of people's communes, large-scale infrastructure construction such as farmland water conservancy construction was also carried out, laying a foundation for later agricultural development. Moreover, in this process, the vast number of farmers demonstrated great dedication and creativity. Through the above-mentioned arduous efforts, a foundation was laid for China to enter the industrial age.

The land of Chinese farmers indeed holds special importance and cannot be freely bought, sold or annexed to prevent farmers from becoming urban poor who lose their means of livelihood after losing their land. Historically, for those in charge of reform measures that led to major failures and regional riots, they often faced extremely severe consequences. They could be killed, and even their entire families, three clans, or nine clans, would be implicated, with all their property confiscated. Those who were not executed might have their relatives exiled to remote areas.

At present, China must enact strict laws and regulations to restrain reforms that may cause major social unrest. Once reforms fail and riots occur, those who actively promote, formulate rules, and resolutely implement them should bear serious consequences. Their personal and family property, as well as the property of relevant stakeholders, should be confiscated, and relatives of offenders should be exiled to cold and remote areas to quell public anger. After all, once land annexation becomes serious, China's current population far exceeds that of the Tang Dynasty, and it is hard to guarantee that a situation like the Huang Chao Rebellion, in which a large number

of plutocrats and officials were massacred, will not recur. Moreover, the number of plutocrats and officials in China today far exceeds that of the Tang Dynasty.

However, in modern society, China should deal with land issues and social reforms in a more scientific, rational and democratic manner. Through measures such as improving laws and regulations, strengthening policy guidance, safeguarding farmers' rights and interests, and promoting coordinated urban - rural development, adverse phenomena such as land annexation can be avoided, while ensuring smooth progress of reforms and social stability and harmony. China cannot simply apply ancient methods of handling, but should combine the characteristics and needs of modern society to explore a development path suitable for China's national conditions.

China has a population of 1.4 billion, with serious regional imbalances. It is a serious crime to devise plots to cause disadvantaged farmers who lack industrial production skills to lose their land and buy houses in cities. In ancient China, people generally could not hold official positions without talent and integrity. Those who hold official positions must bear responsibility and consequences. Consideration should be given to trying such cases in military courts, and after a public trial, the officials who set up such conspiracy plans to plunder farmers' land should be executed and all their property confiscated.

Devising plots to make farmers to freely transfer their land and buy urban apartments is indicative of poor management and regional governance capabilities as well as low moral character. Before such situations occur, relevant personnel should be removed from government positions and never be re - employed.

34.14. Social system from the perspective of the historical equal-field system (均田制).

Table 10. Evaluating the current social system from the perspective of the historical equal-field system (均田制).

1	<p>In the ninth year of Taihe during the Northern Wei Dynasty (485 AD), Emperor Xiao Wen issued a decree to implement the Equal-field System (Juntian System 均田制). The main points are as follows:</p> <p>(1) Men over the age of 15 were granted 40 mu (1 mu= 479.3 - 660m²) of land for cereal cultivation, while women were granted 20 mu. Slaves and maids were allotted land in the same way as ordinary men and women, with land given to their masters. If there were oxen for plowing, an additional 30 mu was granted for each ox, limited to a maximum of four oxen, to accommodate the need for fallowing at the time. The land for cereal cultivation was double granted - in some regions, the amount of land granted was twice the standard allocation, known as "double land" (倍田). The elderly was exempt from taxes, and the land was returned on death. Slaves, maids, and oxen were allocated or returned based on their availability.</p> <p>(2) For those receiving land for the first time, men were given 20 mu of mulberry land (蚕桑地). Within three years of receiving this land, 50 mulberry trees, 5 jujube trees, and 3 elm trees had to be planted; otherwise, the unproductive mulberry land would be reclaimed. Slaves and maids were also</p>
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allocated mulberry land, just like ordinary men and women. Mulberry land could be inherited by descendants as hereditary property. Those who originally lacked mulberry land would receive a sufficient amount according to the regulations, and any shortages would be made up according to the regulations. Any surplus could be considered "double land", thus reducing the amount of double land allocated. The excess portion of mulberry land, if it exceeds the amount of double land, was not permitted to be used as cereal land for reallocation. Mulberry land could be bought and sold, but only the surplus could be sold and only deficiencies could be bought, with transactions not exceeding the limit of 20 mu of mulberry land per man. In regions that did not produce silk and mulberry, adult men were given 10 mu of hemp (**such as 苧麻、黄麻、青麻、亚麻、罗布麻, ramie, yellow hemp, green hemp, flax, apocynum venetum**) land (麻田), and women 5 mu of hemp land. Like fallow land, hemp land had to be restituted as well.

(3) In areas with vast land and sparse populations, people can cultivate the land as they wish, without restrictions. In areas with scarce land and dense populations, if the number of new adults exceeds the allotted farmland, they may relocate to sparsely populated areas to receive land. Those who are reluctant to move can substitute mulberry fields for their cereal fields if the allotted land is insufficient. If it still falls short, they will not be given extra land, and if the shortage persists, the amount of cereal farmland will be reduced among family members. Those willing to move can be fully allocated land according to the system, but they must not evade their duties. In sparsely populated areas, one must not relocate without a valid reason.

(4) Local officials are granted public land for their official tenure. Government officials of various ranks are allocated land according to their positions: about 15 x 3.33 hectares for the Governor, 10 x 3.33 hectares for the Prefect, 8 hectares for administrative assistants and deputy directors, and 6 x 3.33 hectares for county magistrates and deputy governors. Officials can rent out the land and collect rent as part of their salary. However, ownership of the land remains with the government and must be transferred to the successor when leaving office; it cannot be sold.

(5) Every January, a verification of household registrations is carried out, together with the work of returning the received duties.

The specific content of the Equal-field System during the Northern Wei Dynasty (about 485 A.D.) includes:

1. Land ownership: Theoretically, all land belonged to the state, which allocated land to farmers based on the number of people in a household for cultivation. Land allocated to farmers included per capita allocated land (koufen tian), per capita subsistence land (koushi tian), and private land (guitian), mainly distributed according to family size. Per capita allocated land and per capita subsistence land were distributed according to population ratios, while private

	<p>land referred to land that was permanently owned by individuals.</p> <p>2. Land Usage: The land allocated to farmers was meant for temporary use rights and could not be bought or sold, to ensure equal distribution of land. After a certain period, the allocations needed to be readjusted; initially, this reallocation cycle was set to occur roughly every three years.</p> <p>3. Cultivation Obligation: Farms that received the allocated land had the responsibility to cultivate and farm the land and pay the corresponding taxes. Land that was not cultivated could potentially be reclaimed and reallocated.</p> <p>4. Taxation: Farmers were required to pay rent and corvée (labor service) to the state, which followed a practice of levying taxes upfront and then providing relief later, aimed at reducing the tax burden.</p> <p>5. Effects and Issues: Initially, the Equal-field System may have guaranteed a certain degree of stability for the Northern Wei government and improved agricultural production efficiency. However, over time, due to implementation issues such as land encroachment by landlords and power, the system gradually became obsolete in practice.</p> <p>[The equal field system of Northern Wei. January 1, 2024. https://www.kekeshici.com/lishi/gudaizhidu/152783.html]</p>
2	<p>In 528 A.D. (the second year of the Kaihuang period), Emperor Wen of Sui, Yang Jian, issued the Equal-field Order. At the beginning of the Sui Dynasty, Emperor Wen built upon the foundation of the equal-field systems of Northern Qi and Northern Zhou, and continued to implement the equal-field system. That year, Emperor Wen enacted the Equal-field Order, stipulating that each adult male would receive 80 mu (1 mu= 479.3m²) of allotted land for cultivating grains and an additional 20 mu of permanent land. Women were each allocated 40 mu of allotted land, but were not provided with permanent land. Slaves and maidservants received land allocations on the same terms as free citizens. The permanent land did not need to be returned, while the allotted land had to be returned to the state upon the death of the cultivator.</p> <p>[The Order of Equalizing Fields in the Sui Dynasty. https://baike.so.com/doc/2644112-2792005.html]</p>
3	<p>In the Tang Dynasty, adult men aged 18 to 60 were entitled to receive 20 mu of permanent property land (yongye tian) and 80 mu of land allocated per capita (koufen tian) for lease, making a total of 100 mu. Elderly men, the sick, and the disabled were only eligible for 40 mu of koufen land, while widows could receive 30 mu of koufen land. Apart from adult men, including underage boys, if they were heads of households, they were granted 20 mu each of both yongye and koufen land. The descendants could inherit the land. Within three years, 50 mulberry trees per mu, and 10 elm and date trees per mu should be planted. In areas not suitable for the aforementioned species, other fruit trees could be substituted. Eight-tenths of the land was allocated as sharecropping land, koufen tian, which would return to the state upon the holder's death and be granted to another. In sparsely populated broad villages, industrial and commercial practitioners were also allocated land, although half of what farmers received; in</p>

	<p>densely populated narrow villages, industrial and commercial practitioners were not allocated land. [Tang Ji 42 (1) - Tang Dynasty's Renting and Doctrine Regulation and Two Tax Laws. August 29, 2019 http://www.360doc.com/content/19/0829/07/99076_857684126.shtml]</p>
4	<p>The Equal Field System stipulated that the State would allocate land to farming households for cultivation, but ownership of the land belonged to the State; farmers had the right to cultivate and use the land. Both men and women of adult age could receive land according to established standards; this portion of land was known as "allowed land per mouth." Additionally, there was "permanent land" and "private land." Permanent land was land that could be passed down through generations, and its quantity was usually limited. Private land, on the other hand, was land that farmers could freely trade, typically acquired through purchase or donation.</p>
5	<p>The land system mainly implemented during the Northern Wei Dynasty, Sui Dynasty, and the early Tang Dynasty was the "Equal-field System," which was a land distribution system that sat between private ownership and state ownership. While the content of the Equal-field System varied between different dynasties, the core model of the system or underlying philosophical ideas were essentially similar, or one could say, consistent.</p>
6	<p>The content of the socialist land public ownership system in current China mainly includes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) All land is under the socialist public ownership system, that is, ownership by the whole people and collective ownership by the working masses. (2) The land under ownership by the whole people takes the form of state ownership by the socialist country. The state, representing all the working people, possesses the land owned by the whole people and exercises the rights of possession, use, benefit, and disposition. (3) The land under socialist collective ownership by the working masses takes the form of collective ownership by the peasants of rural collective economic organizations. Rural collective economic organizations, village committees, or villager groups represent all peasants to possess land owned collectively by the peasants, and they exercise the rights of operation and management over this collectively owned land. (4) All land within urban districts belongs to the state. (5) In the countryside and suburban areas of cities, land belongs to the peasants' collective (including village collectives and township (town) collectives), except for the land stipulated by law to be owned by the state. (6) A system of paid use for state-owned land is implemented. <p>According to "The People's Republic of China Rural Land Contracting Law": Article 3: The state implements a system of rural land contracting management. Rural land contracting adopts the method of household contracting within rural collective economic organizations. For rural land unsuitable for household contracting, such as barren hills, gullies, ridges, and beaches, other methods such</p>

	<p>as bidding, auctioning, or open negotiation can be used for contracting. [The existing land system in rural China. September 18, 2022. https://wenda.so.com/q/1686794454219391];[2017.12.15.https://wenda.so.com/q/1485000334729662]</p>
7	<p>The Historical Cycle of Chinese Dynasties:</p> <p>In the history of ancient China, the power to govern was not hereditary apart from imperial authority, slowing the natural formation of vested interest groups within society. However, this did not completely prevent the formation of such groups. Due to the inevitability of land—the core asset—undergoing extensive marketization and consolidation in ancient times, the rise and fall of Chinese dynasties followed this trend of land marketization and consolidation. This inevitably led to the destruction of the equal-field system, the allocation of state-owned assets, and the structural imbalance in the distribution of private assets. When the most important means of production or asset—land—became concentrated in the hands of a few, the entire distribution of social assets underwent significant changes, causing the dynasty to collapse due to an inability to maintain balance. However, before the establishment of a new dynasty, the uprising army is bound to massacre in large numbers the officials and landlords of the previous dynasty who own large amounts of property or land, seize their land or other resources, and redistribute land to almost everyone in the country. This allowed the state or nation to enter a period of prosperity again. Eventually, however, the dynasty's conceptual framework would collapse due to the marketization and consolidation of land assets. In general, the history of ancient China is characterized by this repetitive cycle, reflecting the historical cyclical law of past Chinese dynasties.</p>

34.15. The Strategies for Rapidly Resolving the Crime Problems Caused by Myanmar's Social System and the Great Violations of Human Rights by Myanmar's Mafia - like System and Slavery.

34.15.1. Various videos of victims who have been kidnapped to Myanmar.

网易新闻 | 有态度

打开

缅北毫无人性，男子器官被摘掉，一行人潇洒离去！

Fig 86. Northern Myanmar devoid of humanity as a man's organs are forcibly extracted and the perpetrators casually depart the scene.

2023-08-03. <https://www.163.com/v/video/VGA9JNMB7.html>

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

In Myanmar, it seems that the whole nation is involved in crime, and almost everyone is a criminal.

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization.

Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

Fig 87. Video of Burmese militants beating victims.

<https://v.douyin.com/idc3udND/>] The video link was surprisingly blocked by bribed Myanmar telecom fraud groups several months later. It can be seen from this that the fraud groups in Myanmar are so vicious!

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

Fig 88. Video of the victim being tortured and beaten in northern Myanmar.³⁶
How Dangerous is Northern Myanmar # Telecom Fraud Companies # Telecom Fraud Criminals. 2023-09-21. <https://v.douyin.com/id3o5Mox/>
What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

Fig 89. Video: "Look at Myanmar, a large number of piglets are escaping from the Mawadi-KK Park in eastern Myanmar. I advise everyone not to go to Myanmar, as there is no return once you go there!"

2023-04-16. <https://v.douyin.com/idT6XvkQ/>

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you and your relatives return to your country alive?

Fig 90. Video: Some of the telecommunication scam parks in Mawlamyine, Myanmar are starting to relocate. Some have moved to the suburban areas of Bangkok, Thailand, while others have headed to Dubai, Andhra Pradesh, and Malaysia. The second largest park in Mawlamyine, Yulong Bay, and the Jinzitan Park have recently been exposed.⁴⁰ 2023-08-19. <https://v.douyin.com/idTuxsPv/>

Who can imagine that such buildings are not science and technology parks, but telecommunications fraud parks in Myanmar where large - scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, and massacre are carried out? There are many such seemingly nice criminal parks openly existing in Myanmar now. Is this still a country? It is fundamentally a highly profitable den of underworld gangs.

Myanmar: A society that puts profit first, builds a large number of fraud - related parks, conducts large - scale fraud, kidnapping, rape or gang rape, live - organ harvesting, and has the government and military secretly protecting crimes. .

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 91. Video: A few young men who refused to listen ended up getting caught and **brutally beaten to death** while trying to scam and make money in Myanmar. Myanmar is truly a hell on earth, and everyone must never go there. Myanmar is an extremely dangerous place, and one must never go there. This is a firsthand account of a telecommunications fraud, a documentary based on true events.

2023-10-10. <https://v.douyin.com/idTHGVaA/>

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."

Fig 92. Video: Chinese compatriots who were killed in Myanmar were dumped in the wilderness among garbage piles.

2023-10-10. <https://v.douyin.com/idT9NNox/>

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 93. Video: At night, a naked person was hung and tied with both hands
Local people in northern Myanmar accidentally filmed a scene # Golden Triangle
2023-10-15. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7290192569026235700>

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 94. Experiencers recount the true situation in northern Myanmar, where corpses of people can be seen scattered along the roadside, and young girls are bought and sold like livestock.

In northern Myanmar, there are generally two common scams used in telephone fraud. One is to entice you with high salaries, easy entry, and easy money, among other conditions. Once they have gained your complete trust, they will tell you that they are a multinational company in the Internet industry and convince you to come to their headquarters to work, but ultimately take you to Myanmar.

The second approach involves a "roundabout" tactic. They first establish a legitimate company in the country and have you work there for a period of time. Once you have completely let your guard down, they organize a team-building activity and take everyone out.

Of course, those who are more cautious will not go directly to Myanmar but will travel to famous tourist destinations such as Thailand. They will make a stopover in Myanmar and then detain everyone.

The 20-year-old girl, Xiao Li, fell for the first scam. She dropped out of high school and was able to support herself when she was on her own. However, her grandmother fell seriously ill, and she had to allocate a large portion of her monthly salary to her grandmother's medical treatment, barely making ends meet. Influenced by numerous online advertisements, she yearned for a job with high wages and weak technical barriers.

With this mindset, she added an unidentified customer service representative online. She later said, "Ordinary people usually ignore these types of advertisements, but I was desperate for money at the time. I added him with a lucky mentality." Unexpectedly, under the guidance of this "customer service" step by step, Xiao Li gradually believed in him. The person then assigned her a simple task, which allowed Xiao Li to earn a few hundred CNY. This further convinced her that it was not a scam.

Afterward, the "customer service" asked Xiao Li to complete simple tasks every day and rewarded her with CNY 50 yuan each time. After some time, Xiao Li felt that it was too easy to make money this way.

The "customer service" explained that they were a company specializing in telecommunications and the internet sector, and they happened to have a multinational project that welcomed young people like them to participate. Xiao Li initially had some skepticism, but with explanation from the "customer service," she became even more convinced and expressed her willingness to join them. And so, Xiao Li was progressively deceived and ended up in northern Myanmar (Burma). After enduring torment for a period of time, the undercover journalist's report made the scammers in the fraud camp feel uneasy. As a result, they released a group of people on condition of removing the videos. Xiao Li was among them.

It is unknown what happened to Xiao Li in northern Myanmar. When the police asked her about her experiences there, she just shook her head, crying uncontrollably. Perhaps she will spend the rest of her life trying to overcome the shadows brought by that impulsive decision. Xiao Li is considered one of the luckiest to have returned home safely. Most of those who managed to escape were left with lifelong disabilities, especially women. Those with average looks were treated just like men, subjected to beatings and abuse. However, the most unfortunate are women who have been deceived and lured by their exceptional beauty. They face the daily repetition of labor and remain uncertain when and where they will experience rape or gang rape. If they are noticed, there is a possibility of becoming a breeding tool for the locals, and their children will be sent away to become a "pork pig" for organ donors.

Instead of blaming them for being deceived, it is important to consider why such heinous crimes exist in an era of peace and how to identify those insidious smiles hiding behind screens. Since liberation, the average quality of the Chinese people has greatly improved, especially after several crackdowns on criminals. Criminal activities that once ran rampant in regions like northern Myanmar have almost disappeared from this land. Our education from a young age has emphasized the importance of following the law and maintaining social order. Therefore, the impact on people accustomed to a peaceful environment is doubly shocking when they encounter evil blooming in such territories.

Among those who have been rescued, there are young boys who have been blinded and underage girls who already have pregnant bellies. These bloody examples serve as a warning for us to guard our internal order and not to easily fall for words like "high salary" or "easy work." There is a saying that "you reap what you sow," and anyone who tries to make money beyond their capabilities is either already being deceived or on the path to deception.

Lastly, we should pay attention to the psychological well-being of these rescued victims and ensure that they do not suffer a second time from public opinion. Helping them truly "return home" should be the responsibility of society.

[Looking back at the accounts of fraudsters in northern Myanmar: both men and women will be violated, imprisoned, poisoned by snakes, and their human organs will be cut off. 2023-08-18. https://www.sohu.com/a/712831300_120099892]

After British colonization.

What is the social system in Myanmar?? Economists engaged in institutional economics are invited to respond.

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.

Does this world need such evil people who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such evil people who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such evil criminals who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

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Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you and your relatives return to your country alive?

Fig 95. Video. Why are they destroying so many phones? Eliminating criminal evidence# Severely Punish Black and Evil Forces # China Myanmar Border # Strike down Criminals

2023-12-02. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7307945547791355175>

What is the social system in Myanmar??? After British colonization.

Economists engaged in institutional economics are invited to respond.

Does this world need such evil people who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such evil people who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Fig 95. Video. The number of refugees evacuated from Myanmar's old streets has decreased, with discarded mobile phones all along the way. 2023-12-02.

<https://v.douyin.com/iRwMqFBH/>

What is the social system in Myanmar??? After British colonization.

Economists engaged in institutional economics are invited to respond.

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

In Myanmar, it seems that the whole nation is involved in crime, and almost everyone is a criminal.

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Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 96. Video. The business phones of the pig killing plates in the fraud park of Mujie City have to be destroyed every day as evidence # # Stay away from the North Myanmar fraud group## 2023-05-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iRw2EEE8/>
What is the social system in Myanmar? After British colonization.

Fig 96. Video. Southeast Asian telecommunications fraud companies are monitoring the real scale of international telecommunications fraud, which is known as overseas fraud. Night shift personnel # stay away from fraud! 2023-12-08.

<https://v.douyin.com/i8Fs3wM9/>

What is the social system in Myanmar??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics are invited to respond.

Fig 97. [The people of Myanmar were extremely poor humanity, as demonstrated by the case of a girl in the northern region who had escaped from a scamming park but had not escaped abuse from the locals, **local people considered her a car thief and cut off her hair to prevent her from escaping.** 2023-05-23. <https://v.douyin.com/iL9urD4b/v@S.yg> CHI:/ 12/17]

There are many and many videos of Myanmar Telecom fraud groups attacking victims in Tiktok and the Chinese version of douyin's APP.

From the reality of Myanmar society in the above video, if Marx's classification of human social systems is used to classify Myanmar's social system, what will the result be? Will the result be very accurate?

Fig 98. Danyang, Wanka, and Huasheng Telecom Fraud Park in Myanmar
In September 2024, more than 20 Chinese people who had been kidnapped to Myanmar attempted to escape from a telecommunications fraud park in Tangyang, Myanmar, but failed. They were all killed by armed guards with guns. The person who posted the video proposed that all Chinese families whose parents had been kidnapped to Myanmar form a volunteer army, equipped with large knives, break into Wanka, Tangyang, Myanmar, kill all the armed men, and rescue the kidnapped relatives.

The families of the victims appeal to the State to rescue the victimized children who have been deceived and trafficked to Myanmar.

2024-10-20. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7427839634933091595>

The kidnapped Chinese are called "piglets" in Myanmar. Men are forced to engage

in telecommunications fraud, while women are raped and gang - raped almost daily and are also forced to profit for criminal bosses through telecommunications fraud. If they fail to defraud money, they will be beaten and put in water prisons. After squeezing out all their resources, **they will be sold to other fraud companies at a price of CNY 100,000 - 400,000 yuan.** Men are forced to continue to engage in telecommunications fraud, and women are still raped and gang - raped almost every day and continue to be forced to make profits for criminal bosses through telecommunications fraud. If they fail to defraud money, they will be beaten. Such human trafficking may last 5 – 7 times. **If the "piglets" bought by fraud bosses at a price of CNY 100,000 - 400,000 yuan really cannot create profits from telecommunications fraud for them, their organs will be harvested while they are still alive next. After the organs are harvested, they will probably be buried alive.** If organs are harvested on a medical ship on the high seas, the corpses should be thrown into the sea. If the kidnapped women become pregnant after being raped and gang - raped, babies born can become organ donors for criminal groups, and women's breast milk is used as raw materials for cosmetics. When the kidnapped women are truly worthless, all their useful organs will be harvested while they are still alive, and then they will be buried alive or their corpses will be disposed of. The total number of Chinese people who are deceived into going to Myanmar through tourism, work, and commercial cooperation far exceeds 200,000, bringing illegal profits of trillions of yuan every year to fraud groups and relevant officials and soldiers of the Myanmar government.

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.

Myanmar: A society that puts profit first, builds a large number of fraud - related parks, conducts large - scale fraud, kidnapping, rape or gang rape, live - organ harvesting, and has the government and military secretly protecting crimes.

Today, the real terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar. However, evil and inactive politicians and the fatuous UN officials who like to demand membership dues from member states have never launched a 24-hour emergency plan to fight evil criminals in Myanmar. Although these kidnapped children are beaten every day, tortured, and forced to participate in telecommunications fraud, creating trillions of CNY in illegal profits for Myanmar. The ethical and moral conscience of today's world has regressed by at least 3,000 years, and the judicial system has regressed by at least 5,000 years. This is the abominable by - product of European missionaries stealing Chinese science, technology, and culture in large quantities and then forging ancient Egyptian civilization, ancient Greek civilization, ancient Roman civilization, Mesopotamian civilization, ancient Indian civilization as well as political and judicial systems.

Fig 99. In mid - September 2024, in a telecom fraud park in Myanmar, militants slaughtered more than twenty victims, most of whom were minors. They were all killed by armed guards with guns. The location coordinates of this telecom fraud park have been marked.

Dangyang, Wanka, and Huasheng Telecom Fraud Park in Myanmar.

2024-10-20. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7427517274187156799>

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

In Myanmar, it seems that the whole nation is involved in crime, and almost everyone is a criminal.

Fig 100. Video: In northern Myanmar, Chinese people are traded as commodities. The lowest price for selling a Chinese person is 100,000 yuan. Chinese people are sold from one telecom – fraud den to another. The interests of the fraud dens are tied to those of the local people. If someone escapes from a fraud den, all local residents and the armed personnel of the local telecom fraud parks will spare no effort to capture the escapee and send him or her back to the telecom fraud park. Local residents will receive a bounty, and the armed personnel of the local telecom fraud parks will also get a considerable income. Even if you call the police, the Burmese police agencies will notify those telecom fraud dens to come and claim the escaped victims. Those who are caught and brought back will be tortured and shackled until they give up the idea of escaping and continue to defraud others for the heads of the fraud parks.

In Myanmar, it seems that the whole nation is involved in crime, and almost everyone is a criminal.

[Countrymen are sold like commodities in northern Myanmar, stay away from illegal exit, and protect themselves # against telecommunication fraud. 2023-08-09. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7265256042722774307>]

Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you and your relatives return to your country alive?

Fig 101. Video. The Chinese government-wanted criminal mastermind from northern Myanmar is offering a significant cash reward to the Burmese government army in an attempt to unite against the Kokang Alliance, who are actively fighting against telecom fraud criminals.

[The wanted Burmese crime leader, Bai Suocheng, who is also the head of one of the four major families in Kokang, and his second son, Bai Yingcang, appeared on the streets of Old Town. His words shocked Myanmar. According to reliable sources from Myanmar, Bai Yingcang inspected all the firepower bases in Old Town under the protection of armed militiamen in the morning. He made a speech, stating that he would fight alongside his father, Bai Suocheng, and Old Town, vowing not to surrender or escape. If necessary, he would personally lead a death squad to kill the commander-in-chief of the Alliance, Peng Deren. Today, Bai Suocheng, the head of one of the four major families in Kokang, distributed CNY 10 million in cash at the villa in Old Town, rewarding all the government troops and Kokang militia. During the cash distribution, Bai Suocheng announced a decision to offer a bounty in future wars. He declared that if the Kokang Alliance soldiers were completely defeated, there would be a cash reward of CNY 100,000 for killing any Alliance officer above the company level. Killing the deputy commander-in-chief of the Alliance will be rewarded with 200,000 CNY, and killing commander-in-chief, Peng Dejun, will earn a reward of 5 million CNY, in addition to 10 kilograms of gold, totaling approximately 11 million CNY. Bai Suocheng stated that all rewards would be given in cash on the spot. In addition, a decree was issued, stipulating that anyone who flees or surrenders will be killed on the spot. Bai Suocheng firmly stated that he would not run away or surrender, putting his life and fortune on the line in the life-or-death battle in Old Town. December 7, 2023. <https://v.douyin.com/i8Fwvh3G/>]

Fig 102. Video. Three female college students were lured overseas by the promise of high - paying jobs and then transferred to Myanmar. They were beaten, bound, humiliated, raped, and forced to commit fraud. These female college students were forced to become money - making tools for human traffickers. Another two female college students who were kidnapped together were travelling overseas but were abducted on the street. These female college students have no chance of escaping. [Five female college students who were lured to Myanmar by the attraction of high - paying jobs were beaten, bound, humiliated, raped, and forced to engage in fraud.2023-12-09. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7310566335224745253>]

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Does this world need such evil criminals who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 103. Real video of Myanmar telecom fraud criminals beating some victims, with tragic voices! Not going to Myanmar. 2023-07-19.

<https://www.douyin.com/video/7257473347481603343>

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

In Myanmar, it seems that the whole nation is involved in crime, and almost everyone is a criminal.

Fig 105. The 15 major tortures in Myanmar.

2023-09-26. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7283152960048188683>

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you and your relatives return to your country alive?

Fig 130. Real video of Myanmar. Title: "A True Story from Northern Myanmar" Everyone, keep your eyes open and don't be tempted by high salaries. Otherwise, you'll end up dead without a complete body. 2023-05-05. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7229552841965210920>

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

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Myanmar: Society with a social system of underworld model.

Fig 106. Burma trapped persons recount their escape experience: "My flesh was beaten to a pulp. It was either being beaten to death or having my organs sold." A Fujianese lad's harrowing experience in Burma for three months.

The victim witnessed two people being beaten to death.

If the victims cannot be rescued, they will either be beaten to death or have their organs sold.

[2023-07-08. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7253439090228596026>]

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

Fig 107. A real - life video of an interview with a lucky escapee from Myanmar: **In the telecom fraud park, people are shot in the head and killed by AK-47 every week. After being killed, they are dragged outside. Although the blood on the ground is cleaned every day, the victims never see the blood at the door being clean. When having meals in the cafeteria, it can be seen that many people's hands and feet are electrocuted by electric batons. The flesh is beaten and burned with electric batons, looking like coke, and there is no intact flesh left on their hands and feet.** Every week, victims are whipped with rattan whips. One can see the flesh after a whip, and after about 50 whips, the bones are exposed. [August 24, Changsha, Hunan. A Burmese man who escaped revealed that there are

daily deaths in the fraud zone in northern Burma. "The blood at the entrance is cleaned every day, but it has never been clean." #What is the root of the chaos in northern Burma? 2023-08-24. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7270852192498666771>]

Fig 108. A Chinese girl who was invited to travel in Thailand went missing and her body was finally found in Myanmar. Before losing contact, she sent a message saying that there were telecom fraud parks all around. The screenshot shows the location where the body was buried, and the locations of organ harvesting and organ transplantation.

2023-09-03. <https://www.douyin.com/note/7274501387436690722>

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

Myanmar: Society with a social system of underworld model.

Partially slave society of fraud combination.

Fig 109. Throwing corpses into the river # inhumane and inhumane in northern Myanmar. 2023-11-24. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwY3Mhc/C@h.odqRK:/04/12>

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

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Myanmar: Society with a social system of underworld model.

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Does this world need such evil criminals who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 110. Real northern Myanmar. 2022-07-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwD35St/g@O.Kw fBt:/ 10/21>

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

Fig 111. Zhang, a 21-year-old young man, was lured to northern Myanmar by an online acquaintance promising a high-paying job. He didn't want to become a fraudster and, more importantly, didn't want to bring trouble to his family. In front of a crowd of onlookers, he had four of his fingers severed by a "ruthless associate."

[Attention! A narrow escape from death! After risking their lives to escape from northern Myanmar, they recounted their harrowing experiences. Dated August 24, 2022. http://news.sohu.com/a/579536538_162758](http://news.sohu.com/a/579536538_162758)

What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond.

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Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you and your relatives return to your country alive?

Fig 111-1. Never believe in going to Myanmar to find a high-paying job. It is a place where scammers gather. Watching the videos is extremely terrifying. It is a region of nobody's jurisdiction. Once you go there, you may be tortured and don't expect to come back alive. 2023-07-06. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7252555863611821324>

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Does this world need such evil criminals who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 111-2. KK Park in Myawadi, Myanmar. A murder factory that digs out the human organs of Chinese people.2024-09-02.

<https://www.douyin.com/video/7409858835579489563>

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

緬北公海醫療船有多恐怖？

活體取器官售賣全世界

專門嚙中國人“腰子”

公海上面有船隻每天都在等着買人呢

第3/3集

點擊頭像觀看全集

Fig 111-3. How terrifying is the medical ship on the high seas in northern Myanmar? Organs are taken from living people and sold all over the world. Even dying becomes a luxury. The kidneys, hearts, livers, lungs, corneas, skin and all other organs of the victims bring huge profits to criminal groups. All surgeries are performed without anesthesia, and the victims are operated on while awake. **Evil medical ships exist on the high seas every day.** 2023-12-07.

<https://www.douyin.com/video/7309685795412167963>

The following is the text converted from the audio of this video:

The medical ship on the high seas is waiting to buy people every day. Do you know what each person is for? It is to cut your organs while you are alive. Your kidneys, spleen, heart, all organs, including the cornea, are valuable. This is your ultimate fate.

If you board this medical ship in Myanmar, what greets you will be a bloody hell. The medical personnel on the ship will not treat you as a human being at all. To save money, they will perform organ transplants on 'piglets' without any anesthesia measures. Of course, these surgeons are also unprofessional. Perhaps they are even butchers who have switched professions. So there is a high chance that they will accidentally cut off some of your important organs with a scalpel during the operation and then you will die on the spot. In addition, because there is no anesthesia, the victim is awake throughout the entire operation. To prevent the 'piglets' from struggling wildly due to unbearable pain, the people on the ship will tightly block the victim's mouth in advance and tie up the victim's limbs with thick iron chains. Generally, the removed organs are not easy to store. If a buyer is not found within the transplantable period, the organs will be damaged, which is also something they don't want to see. Therefore, operators on the ship will not let the victim to die directly. Instead, they will act when the 'piglets' reach the limit of survival. After the customer places an order, they will directly perform the operation and remove the required parts. As for those 'piglets' who have not received orders for the time being, their days will not be easy either. To save on food expenses, the people on the ship will give them things that even dogs won't eat. Compared to such a harsh environment, the most terrifying thing is that they don't know when they will be taken out, either for blood drawing or organ removal. It can be said that these victims have completely lost their basic dignity as human beings on the medical ship on the high seas. For them, death may also be a kind of relief. Once, a Taiwanese businessman was cheated and taken to Myawaddy, Myanmar. After much effort, he finally contacted his friend. According to the demands of the fraud syndicate, his friend brought 170,000 US dollars to redeem him. But when he was about to take his friend back to his country, the fraud park told him that it was impossible to redeem the person. Because a buyer from Dubai took a fancy to his organs and bought his organs at a price five times higher than the 170,000 US dollars. The person had long been sent to the medical ship. The man was not reconciled and continued to ask. There must be a corpse if the person is dead. But the reply from the fraud syndicate was that after taking out the organs, the body was thrown directly into the sea. This is the fate of most 'piglets' without value in the fraud syndicate, and even the rich are no exception. Let's live a good life and stay away from northern Myanmar.

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Does this world need such evil criminals who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

缅北公海医疗船内部真相

进去的人被开膛破肚掏空身体
残缺的尸体都被扔进海里喂鱼

这是缅北公海医疗船内部的真实录像

全集

Fig 111-4. The scene of the evil Burmese medical ship harvesting human organs from victims on the high seas.2024-09-21.
<https://www.douyin.com/video/7416959967133027603>

Does this world need such evil people who kidnap, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, and slaughter humanity?

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Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

Fig 111-5. A person who experienced fraud in northern Myanmar recalled the "nightmare" experience of being deceived to Laogai in Kokang. They saw someone being beaten until they vomited blood and died. "I did not expect that in the 21st century, life could escape the scope of the law." #Fraud #Real Experience in Northern Myanmar #Beware of Fraud.

2024-11-15. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7437493290347416869>

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Can you, your wife, son, and daughter experience being subjected to torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, or massacre at a telecom fraud park in Myanmar?

Can you and your relatives return to your country alive?

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

Today, the real and extremely vicious terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar.

Myanmar is not only a major failure of the combination of evil and greedy politicians and its system, but has also become a paradise for global crimes and an evil country with the highest output of opium and drugs in the world. The international community must clearly recognize the situation. It must not only disintegrate and reorganize this evil country, but must also put all the politicians who forcibly combined multiple loose ethnic groups into one country on public trial and execute them, and confiscate all their personal and family property. All criminals who commit large-scale crimes such as telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, live burial, and slaughter must be executed.

Western countries have been emphasizing that the earth is overpopulated. Then why don't they eliminate the anti-human criminals who continuously commit large-scale crimes and put them on public trial and execute them all?

Table 10-1. Questioning the international community and the United Nations	
1	With such cruel crimes occurring for a long time, why does the United Nations protect Myanmar from being attacked or destroyed by victimized countries or victims?
2	Should Myanmar's founders not be severely punished and executed?
3	Should the leader of the Myanmar government not be severely punished and executed?
4	Shouldn't the government army of the Myanmar state be severely punished?
5	Since these armies have become the umbrella for fraudsters, shouldn't they all be executed?

6	Shouldn't the countless people in Myanmar who help fraud syndicates be severely punished and executed?
7	Isn't the United Nations the biggest umbrella for criminals in the world today?
8	Isn't the United Nations an evil institution?
9	Should the principal officials of the United Nations not bear legal responsibility?
10	Should not the principal officials of the United Nations be sentenced according to law?
11	Should not the principal officials of the United Nations have their property confiscated to compensate the victims?
12	Isn't Myanmar not the world's largest and most serious terrorist organization of national and regional armed forces?
13	United Nations officials only like to receive salaries from the United Nations. Why don't they come up with a plan to destroy this most evil terrorist country with the most serious crimes in the world? Why don't they make rules to limit the marriage and childbearing ages of the evil people in this most evil terrorist country with the most serious crimes in the world?
14	If United Nations officials do not have managerial skills, you should not hold this position at all. In ancient China, if such serious crimes occurred, the nine clans of criminals would all be completely exterminated. Administrative officials who improperly governed the region or their entire families would also be executed and all property confiscated. In this extremely evil country of Myanmar, human morality, ethics, conscience, and law have been suppressed and regressed for at least 10,000 years.
15	This should be the result of Western missionaries plagiarizing Chinese civilization, falsifying Western civilization, and formulating a judicial system that does not conform to Chinese philosophy and dialectics. It is the result of using false cultural relics to create the non-existent ancient Egyptian civilization, ancient Greek civilization, ancient Roman civilization, ancient Indian civilization and Mesopotamian civilization.
16	What kind of social system in Myanmar is this??? After British colonization. Isn't the fate of these victims even more tragic than that of slaves? <u>Noble legislators and eloquent politicians, can you let your whole family or your clan experience the fate of being organ-harvested on the medical ship on the high seas of Myanmar???</u> Is it normal or shameful to establish diplomatic relations with such an evil country? Does humanity still have a little little little bit of conscience??? Shouldn't this extremely evil and loosely organized country be disintegrated and reorganized??? Economists engaged in institutional economics or political science are invited to respond ???
17	The United States is a country that most people from other countries hope to immigrate. The vast majority of people around the world believe that the

	<p>laws of the United States are claimed to be based on democracy, freedom and the protection of human rights. Under U.S. law, when the residences of U.S. residents are illegally invaded and residents feel threatened, they have the right to use force, including firearms, to defend themselves and shoot the intruders dead under the following U.S. laws.</p> <p>The Castle Doctrine: The "Castle Doctrine" is an important part of self-defense laws for U.S. citizens. Its core idea is that citizens have no obligation to retreat within certain areas such as their own residences and can use violent resistance to safeguard their lives and property. Under this principle, when the residences of residents are illegally invaded and their personal safety is threatened, they have the right to use force, including firearms, to defend themselves.</p> <p>Stand Your Ground Act: Some states implement the "Stand Your Ground Law", which stipulates that a person does not need to fulfill the obligation to retreat to areas where they can legally stay. If he has reason to believe that he has already been or is about to be seriously threatened with injury or death, then he can use any means available to fight back.</p> <p>Since the United States is a country that most people from other countries hope to immigrate to and its laws are claimed to be based on democracy, freedom and the protection of human rights, why not kill all criminals who commit large-scale crimes according to American law?</p> <p>Don't European and American politicians often say that there are already nearly seven billion people on the earth nowadays and that there is overpopulation? Is the death penalty for criminals who commit large-scale heinous crimes higher than the standard for the American people to lawfully kill illegal intruders?</p> <p>Those who do not support executing criminals who commit large-scale crimes, if you don't think you are a person with a false appearance of kindness, you should send yourself, your wives and your children to the telecom fraud parks in northern Myanmar to experience whether you can survive. It's time to test whether legislators have the empathy that legislators must possess.</p>
18	<p>The laws you've created have failed to protect victims. So why should you be the one making the laws?</p> <p>Since the inferior legal system you created did not protect victims and instead allowed criminals to continue to harm new people and turn them into new victims, shouldn't you be severely punished?</p> <p>Shouldn't you be put to death? Are you nobler than the victims? Why can't victims make laws? Aren't the victims equal human beings?</p> <p>Can't victims make laws to sentence these criminals who committed heinous crimes to death? If you insist on such extremely stupid views, you must let the victims use the same means as the criminals to make all members of your family experience the process of being victimized with similar intensity and for a similar length of time, and end up in a similar situation of being victimized. If anyone in your family dies or loses all their property as a result,</p>

wouldn't that be caused by your ignorance?

Since you are ignorant, you should not be involved in law-making at all. You shouldn't be able to work in any government agency or engage in any government affairs.

Would it would be legal to rob the national treasury and banks of your country, plunder all the gold and currency, and pass them on to the next generation for ownership? The next generation of criminals, knowing full well that these properties were obtained through robbery and are illegal gains, continue to hide and consume them. Aren't they criminals?

If not, wouldn't it be legal to send a few people or an army to rob any bank in the United States of its gold, diamonds, jewels and dollars, kill all the security personnel, and then pass the gold, diamonds, jewels and dollars on to the next generation?

Don't you think that's absurd? If you don't think it's absurd, what qualifications do you have to be involved in law-making? Aren't you just a pig's head that can't produce any grain?

Fig 112. Video. The telecom fraudster, at least protecting telecom fraudsters, has defrauded 2 trillion CNY. The head of the Myanmar government, Aung Lae, dispatched at least one brigade of the Myanmar military to protect several telecom fraudsters, organ traffickers, and murderers of Chinese citizens who are wanted by the Chinese government in the Kokang area. They also collaborated with the armed forces of these criminals to launch attacks on the Allied forces who are combating telecom fraud criminals.

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Myanmar is not only a failure of state - building and systems, but also a haven for global crimes and must be restructured.

Does this world need such an evil criminal country that enjoys large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and human slaughter?

All countries that commit large-scale crimes must be dismantled or restructured into multiple countries.

Today, the real terrorists in the world are concentrated in Myanmar. However, evil and inactive politicians and the fatuous UN officials who like to demand membership dues from member states have never launched a 24-hour emergency plan to fight evil criminals in Myanmar. Although these kidnapped children are beaten every day, tortured, and forced to participate in telecommunications fraud, creating trillions of RMB in illegal profits for Myanmar. The ethical and moral conscience of today's world has regressed by 3,000 years, and the judicial system has regressed by 5,000 years. This is the abominable by - product of European missionaries stealing Chinese science, technology, and culture in large quantities and then forging ancient Egyptian civilization, ancient Greek civilization, ancient Roman civilization, Mesopotamian civilization, ancient Indian civilization as well as political and judicial systems.

The greedy, selfish, and evil Burmese politicians and military officers lack the basic ability to govern the country. They only care about controlling a large territory. Through deception, they gathered the short - sighted leaders of the indigenous people of northern Myanmar, which historically belonged to China, and signed the evil Panglong Agreement to form a new country, Myanmar. Later, just ten years after its formation, the Burmese government of the new country violated the previously signed Panglong Agreement and used force to suppress the aboriginal people in northern Myanmar who requested to withdraw from the Union of Myanmar according to the rules of the agreement. After a long - term and continuous war, Myanmar has not only become the most evil devil, like a country in the world that produces the most opium, but has also turned into a human trafficking market where almost all Burmese are eager to participate in the trafficking of kidnapped Chinese people, and they can earn 100,000 - 400,000 yuan per transaction. Northern Myanmar, which used to have simple folk customs, has also become a paradise for fraudsters. The politicians and military personnel who created today's ugly criminal situation in Myanmar have never been severely punished, publicly tried and executed, and their properties have never been confiscated. All criminals enjoy illegal benefits.

When running for office or in power, the politicians who claim to be the most globally - leading, the leaders who claim to be the most globally - leading, and the UN officials who enjoy the rich membership dues every day have never come up with effective solutions to quickly eradicate the tumors, poisoned fruits, poisoned trees, and poisoned weeds all over Myanmar. Every year, countless victims are kidnapped, defrauded of property, tortured, raped, gang - raped, have their organs harvested while alive, and massacred. Isn't this an indication that the social systems of some countries and the global governance system are extremely poor? Systems are developed by officials and politicians. Therefore, effective governance must be carried out on the above - mentioned personnel.

34.15.2. Myanmar's evil politicians and warlords use the Panglong Agreement to make Myanmar create twenty world records worldwide.

Table 11. World records for 20 crimes set by Burmese people, Burmese government and Armed telecom fraud groups in Myanmar

	Twenty world records created by evil – doing Myanmar
1	In the post – World War II world, for the first time in the world, there emerged a country that is the world’s largest telecommunications fraud country.
2	In the post – World War II world, for the first time in the world, there emerged a country that is the world’s largest kidnapping country.
3	In the post – World War II world, for the first time in the world, there emerged a country that is the world’s largest torture.
4	In the post – World War II world, for the first time in the world, there emerged a country with the largest number of telecommunications fraud parks in the world.
5	In the post – World War II world, for the first time in the world, the first country to emerge with the largest number of criminal – style human organ harvesting.
6	It is the country that conducts the largest – scale telecommunications fraud in the world and illegally profits more than CNY 1 trillion.
7	It is the first telecommunications fraud country in the world that has publicly built a large number of seemingly nice telecommunications fraud parks.
8	It is the telecommunications fraud country that is the largest in the world in publicly building a large number of seemingly nice telecommunications fraud parks, where criminals brazenly commit various crimes for a long time, such as kidnapping, rape, forced harvesting of human organs, trafficking in human beings, and massacres, and the victims and the victimized countries are unable to carry out armed strikes against them.
9	The country that is the first in the world to publicly build a large number of seemingly nice telecom fraud parks and illegally profit more than 1 trillion CNY.
10	It is the world’s largest kidnapping country.
11	It is the country that conducts the largest – scale kidnappings in the world and illegally profits over one trillion CNY.
12	It is the world’s largest opium – producing country today.

13	It is one of the world’s largest countries in the illegal human organ harvesting and trafficking
14	The country that ranks first in the world, where most people are involved in human trafficking, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, forcibly harvesting of human organs, massacres, fraud, drug trafficking, opium related, and cooperating with criminal groups for profit.
15	It is one of the worst countries in the world that practices racial discrimination, restricting ethnic minorities from obtaining ID cards, resulting in the largest number of people without ID documents.
16	It is one of the evil countries in the world that uses ID cards to restrict the largest number of ethnic minorities from freely traveling within the country.
17	It is one of the evil countries in the world that uses ID cards to restrict the largest number of ethnic minorities from freely traveling overseas.
18	It is the most evil country in the world that openly uses the national army to protect a large number of telecommunications fraud groups in Myanmar.
19	It is one of the countries that uses the military and air force to protect telecommunications fraud groups.
20	It is the only evil country in the world that deploys Su-30 military aircraft to bomb the “National Security Alliance” engaged in fighting criminal organizations to protect criminal organizations engaged in telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, organ trafficking, and slaughtering Chinese people within its territory.

Table 12. Governance measures for politicians, criminals, and criminal groups in Myanmar

1	The property of all persons in Myanmar must be made public, beginning with all government officials, staff, and military personnel in Myanmar. The property of all individuals, their families, and their six – generation relatives must be made public.
2	The property of all known criminals in Myanmar, those with any possibility of committing crimes, their individuals, families, and six generations of relatives must be made public.
3	The property of all employees of financial institutions and their six – generation relatives must be made public.
4	The personal and family property of all Myanmar people should be made public, regardless of where the property is located, whether it is in a particular place, country or bank.
5	Human trafficking in Myanmar is a crime committed by the entire nation. Myanmar people’s monthly income is usually CNY 1,000-3,000, while trafficking a Chinese person can earn CNY 100,000-400,000, which is a huge sum. Whenever the “piglets” who escape from the telecommunications fraud parks ask for directions, they will be regarded as “gold” by Myanmar citizens, who will call the bandits in the fraud parks to catch them or catch the victims and take them to the telecommunications fraud parks by themselves to get

	rewards. According to ancient Chinese traditional laws, heavy penalties should be used in chaotic times. All those who violate the ban will be sentenced to death. Only in this way can Myanmar possibly not be the world's largest fraud – prone region and the number – one fraud – prone country.
6	All Myanmar officials who have implemented the Panglong Agreement must be punished. Based on the number of deaths, injuries, and property losses caused by the Myanmar government's violation of the Panglong Agreement that led to the war in northern Myanmar, U.S. and European lawyers should preside over judicial trials and demand full compensation from the Myanmar government. Any official who has implemented the Panglong Agreement, if they prevent the aboriginal areas in northern Myanmar that wish to secede from Myanmar from doing so and participate in or plan civil wars, all personal and family property shall be confiscated to compensate the victims. The descendants of all criminal officials are prohibited from holding any jobs in government agencies or the military. The length of the restriction is determined by the number of deaths caused by the Myanmar government in the civil war in northern Myanmar. One death results in a one – year ban, and 10,000 deaths result in a 10,000-year ban.
7	Freeze all overseas assets of the Myanmar people. The number of daily flights from Myanmar to foreign countries should not exceed three. All Myanmar nationals flying abroad must disclose all their personal and family property and its sources two weeks in advance. Banks and financial institutions in any country shall not keep the property of the Burmese people confidential on the grounds of confidentiality, especially for Burmese criminals; otherwise, they will be regarded as criminals. The bank will be fined three times the amount of property stored by Myanmar criminal groups in the bank. At the same time, criminal arrest warrants will be issued for those responsible, legal responsible persons, and major shareholders who prevent the bank from exposing the assets of Myanmar criminals and their families to prevent the arrest of criminals.
8	If the number of victims of a country due to telecommunications fraud carried out within Myanmar exceeds 5,000, the military of the victim country can directly enter Myanmar for military strikes or use any weapons permitted by the United Nations for armed strikes.
9	The Myanmar military is prohibited from attacking the Kokang Alliance Army and the Ta'ang National Liberation Army, which have been fighting telecommunications fraud since the 1027 Operation.
10	Any country is allowed to provide any legal weapons and ammunition to the Kokang Alliance Army and the Ta'ang National Liberation Army, which have been fighting telecommunications fraud, and order them to eliminate telecommunications fraud – related armed gangs and local armed forces within Myanmar within one year. If necessary, the military of any country can assist in combating telecommunications fraud related to militants in Myanmar. If 80% of telecommunications fraud – related elements within Myanmar cannot be

	eliminated within one year, the two local armies will pay for the weapons and ammunition provided by the countries.
11	Criminals who participate in telecommunications fraud, human trafficking, kidnapping, rape, gang – rape, live – organ harvesting, and homicide shall be shot dead on the spot if they resist when the military and armed police carry out large – scale anti – crime operations.
12	Myanmar’s crime is a national – level issue. Myanmar people are prohibited from immigrating to any country. Starting from 2015, whenever a Myanmar citizen immigrates to any country, they must disclose all personal and family properties and the time of acquisition.
13	The disclosure of assets by officials is a sign of societal progress, while the anonymity provided by cryptocurrencies encourages the safe transfer of illegal funds by criminals. A global consensus must be reached to permanently ban the use of cryptocurrencies by all residents of criminal states such as Myanmar, any individuals under suspicion of criminal activity, their family members (including direct relatives), nationals, persons with dual Myanmar nationality, and anyone within Myanmar’s territory. Anyone who has made transfers or payments in excess of \$500 using cryptocurrencies in the past must provide the name and details of the person involved in the transfer.
14	<p>All criminals and their patrons who commit large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and indiscriminate killing, have hoarded enormous amounts of wealth. In criminal states like Myanmar, they not only relentlessly extract the properties of the victims, pushing their families into severe debt, but also unceasingly force victims to scam others to amass wealth for them. They continuously rape and gang-rape their victims, akin to subjugating sex slaves. They coerce kidnapped females into pregnancy and childbirth and extract the victims’ breast milk for the wealthy in Myanmar to consume, and produce luxury skincare products. They turn the newborns of these victims into sources for illegal organ harvesting. Concurrently, they are also making more and more victims into living organ donors. After organ extraction, they bury the victims alive or slaughter them.</p> <p>Therefore, any resident or national of the criminal country Myanmar, and any suspected criminal and their family members (including direct family members) must publicly and permanently disclose any property they hold in any country. Anyone who has resided in Myanmar for over a month, or who holds dual citizenship with Myanmar (excluding staff of embassies of other countries in Myanmar), must permanently publicly disclose all their personal and family assets to everyone globally. Every bank around the globe must publicize all assets and detailed listings and accounts of Burmese people, their family members, and those holding Myanmar nationality or dual nationality with Myanmar, including a detailed record of asset growth or decrease over the past 30 years, to help curb fraud and the transfer of fraudulent funds. All account details must be publicly available on the internet for anyone to review. Any</p>

	<p>assets suspected to be illegal by law enforcement officials from the United Nations, the United States, China, or the affected countries must be clarified within 48 hours. In addition, everyone in other countries where similar large-scale cases have occurred and their families, regardless of whether their spouses are Burmese, must publicly disclose all their property and bank assets.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, “The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
15	<p>Any criminal or suspect who has committed a crime in conjunction with a resident of the criminal state of Myanmar must permanently disclose all personal and family property in any country (including direct family members). Every bank worldwide must publicize all assets, detailed listings, and accounts held by the offender or suspect, along with a record of the increase or decrease in assets over the past 30 years. All details must be displayed on the internet and accessible for anyone to view.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, “The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
16	<p>Since the beginning of the last century, the number of law students worldwide has increased several times. However, there has been a significant increase in serious crimes against humanity such as kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking or organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres. Judicial institutions have never modified laws to enforce efficient and rapid crackdowns on these crimes. The current judicial system is far less effective than China’s ancient system and does not provide adequate protection for citizens’ personal safety. Instead, lawyers receive the highest income level, and judicial institutions have completely failed to fulfill their obligations and responsibilities to suppress and reduce crime. They have also not demonstrated the capacity to curb and reduce crime. Consequently, all judicial personnel responsible for formulating the above-mentioned legal provisions should no longer be allowed to formulate any legislative ideologys. Legal rights and procedures for defending criminals and criminal nations involved in these large-scale crimes should be abolished. Any lawyer should not be allowed to defend these criminal States and criminals, and their defense should be regarded as committing serious and equivalent crimes against humanity. Any secondary attacks by the victim against the above-mentioned criminals should not be considered as excessive defence, but should instead be commended.</p>
17	<p>It is prohibited for all countries to conduct arms transactions with the Myanmar government, the Myanmar government’s military, and armed organizations in Myanmar that protect telecommunications fraud. It is also prohibited to sell any military technology, paramilitary technology, or paramilitary equipment to the above – mentioned units in Myanmar. Those who violate this rule will be fined three times the transaction amount. Any country may freeze all the</p>

	property of State – owned or national companies of the violating country within its territory and prohibit all trade with the violating country.
18	All murderers, kidnappers, human organ harvesting criminals, rapists, gang rapists, human traffickers, and those who bury people alive in Myanmar will be publicly tried by the Kokang Alliance Army and the Ta’ang National Liberation Army, and then sentenced to death. Their entire property will be confiscated, and their family members will be exiled to remote areas and barred from returning to their original places of residence.

34.15.3. Disposition of relevant United Nations officials and failed interveners from other countries

Not a single United Nations official or secretary – general has ever made a written admission that, under their leadership, the post – World War II world has given birth to a country that is the world’s largest in telecommunications fraud, the first country to carry out telecommunications fraud and illegally profit over one trillion RMB, the largest telecommunications – fraud – country openly building a large number of fancy telecommunications – fraud parks, the world’s largest kidnapping – country, the first country to carry out kidnappings and illegally profit over one trillion RMB, and the world’s largest opium – producing country, and that the victims and victim – countries are unable to carry out armed strikes to eliminate all the criminals. What kind of shitty international order is this? What kind of shithole international order has the United Nations established in the approximately 80 years since its founding? These top – level politicians have never shown any sense of shame or guilt. If you have no capacity for global governance, why engage in politics? With such a low – level of global governance by the United Nations, at least 1.2 billion people in China could be UN secretaries – general or supreme leaders of any of the most leadership – claiming countries. If the leaders of the countries claiming to have the most global leadership are of such a level, without any punitive constraints, and are still able to travel frequently at public expense by plane, be entertained by officials of other countries, and enjoy a lot of vanity, about 1.2 billion people in China only need two months of training to be the supreme leaders of such globally – most – leadership – claiming countries. Although the author of this article has a lower-than – average intelligence level, inferior to the 1.2 billion Chinese people, after about three months of training, he could also be the supreme leader of such globally – most – leadership – claiming countries.

The current malicious and vicious situation in Myanmar is the result of the failure of the world’s greedy, selfish, evil, incompetent, and arrogant politicians in governing their countries or the global community. These people are of low ability, turning a blind eye and a deaf ear to the tragedies of the people trapped in the malicious land of Myanmar, yet continuously enjoying the prestige and vanity of holding office, without any punitive constraints for their governance failures. Therefore, criminal punishment must be imposed on the politicians who currently hold leadership positions in global governance, politicians from the countries that claim to have the most leadership in the world, and politicians who claim to be the most global leaders. According to the

punishments for such derelict officials in ancient China, the specific disposal methods are as follows.

Table 13. Methods of disposal for the UN, relevant UN officials and interveners from other countries.

1	Senior United Nations officials and the highest – ranking UN officials who coordinate and manage countries around the globe shall be dismissed from office, investigated, and punished with 30 strokes of the cane.
2	Politicians around the world who claim to have the most leadership should be removed from office, investigated, and punished with 30 strokes of the cane.
3	Politicians from countries around the world who claim to have the most leadership should be dismissed from office, investigated, and punished with 30 strokes of the cane. If the above – mentioned personnel re – offend, they will be punished with the above – mentioned criminal penalties again, and all members of their families will be sent to telecommunications fraud parks in Myanmar to experience the tragic experiences that the victims in the telecommunications fraud parks once endured. After one year, if they are still alive, have not had their organs harvested while alive, and can still be found in telecommunications fraud parks in Myanmar, and telecommunications fraud criminals are willing to release their family members, they will be allowed to return to their own countries. If Myanmar’s telecommunications fraud centres are unwilling to release their family members, the politician may ask the armed forces of their country to use any weapons not prohibited by the UN to attack Myanmar or telecommunications fraud parks and kill the criminals they deem necessary to kill.
4	After dealing with the officials who failed to govern Myanmar in the first round, UN officials will be reappointed to govern Myanmar. All countries are required to use all means to combat criminal groups and criminals in Myanmar, and combat effectiveness will be inspected once a month. All officials who fail to significantly reduce the rampant telecommunications fraud in Myanmar, fail to largely prevent Myanmar criminals from escaping, politicians, those who obstruct in the name of human rights, all incompetent governors and interveners who have seriously failed in governing Myanmar must be punished by military law every month. They will be whipped with the special criminal law whips of Singapore, and the victims who have been rescued from Myanmar and tortured will execute the flogging, with each person being whipped five times. For ordinary UN officials, male official will be whipped three times a month, and female official two times a month. If a female official believes that she must have the same rights as male officials, she can also be whipped three times a month. Senior and top – level UN officials have unshirkable responsibility for the situation in Myanmar and must be whipped four times and five times a month respectively. All consequences resulting from the above – mentioned punishments shall be borne by the punished.
5	The United Nations had not introduced effective and serious measures to combat the crimes of criminal countries that carried out large - scale telecom

	fraud, and the victim countries had suffered huge economic losses. In such a situation, the United Nations must bear legal and economic loss responsibilities. Half of the economic losses suffered by the victim countries due to the fraud of the criminal countries of the telecommunications fraud shall be regarded as the membership dues paid to the United Nations until the United Nations introduces effective measures to combat the crimes of the criminal countries and makes the criminal countries and criminals fully compensate the losses of the victim countries. Only when the losses of the affected countries and victims were fully compensated would the victim countries begin to pay membership dues to the United Nations. Only in this way can the payment of United Nations membership dues be fair and just, and it is possible for United Nations officials to manage the United Nations well.
6	The above - mentioned rules of conduct are intended to tell all interveners and participants that those without the ability should not participate in or interfere in government affairs, and that those who are not capable should not come to government to receive a salary but do nothing.

The United Nations and the international community must change the concepts, strategies, and methods of crime control and develop a permanent global consensus or convention to combat large - scale crimes such as those in Myanmar, and accordingly amend the constitutions of various countries.

34.15.4. A series of global consensuses or conventions to combat large - scale crimes similar to those in Myanmar

Table 14. A series of global consensuses or conventions to combat large - scale crimes similar to those in Myanmar.

1	The factors that lead to large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, human trafficking, or organ harvesting crimes in a country are human beings, and politicians who are evil, selfish, greedy, despicable, narrow-minded, and have limited perspectives are more likely to create crime factories. From a philosophical and logical perspective, solving global problems requires understanding the main aspects of contradictions, and politicians in criminal countries have an undeniable responsibility for the crimes defined by this consensus.
2	Any person, organization, or government that commits and harbours crimes such as mass fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and looting of wealth constitutes a serious crime against humanity that poses a significant threat to global peace. Strict measures must be taken to prevent and punish such crimes. If the countries that are home to the criminals and provide the venues for the crimes, as well as the countries and organizations that protect the criminals, are not severely punished and do not compensate the victims and affected countries for their losses, any country or criminal may repeat the

	<p>crimes defined by this consensus to plunder wealth, disrupt global peace, and lead humanity's desire for peace into a vicious cycle. Since 1900, all acts of large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rapes, human trafficking, and organ harvesting must be thoroughly addressed and compensated. Only when past crimes were fully investigated, perpetrators and their countries severely punished, the potential for criminal intent suppressed and reformed, and victims and affected countries fairly compensated, could the world gradually become peaceful.</p>
3	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, rape, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Criminals involved in this consensus are not eligible for parole. Anyone who personally participates in three or more cases of kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, or trafficking in human beings shall be sentenced to death. Anyone who participates in live organ removal or massacre shall be sentenced to death.</p>
4	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, rape, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the</p>

	<p>massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>The criminal country must compensate for all losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country, and pay for all medical and living expenses of the victims. The criminal State must also pay punitive compensation for the losses suffered by the victims and the victim State. All fraudulently obtained property must be returned in full to the affected country and victims, and damaged property must be compensated at least double the amount of the loss.</p>
5	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, rape, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Considering that in the process of fraud, criminals not only commit inhumane acts such as torture, organ harvesting, or burying victims alive, but also extort large sums of money, leading to the collapse of victims' families, the compensation standards outlined in this consensus must be implemented according to the compensation standards for 18 death and victim cases in the United States to prevent similar incidents from happening again and to maintain world peace. In the case of large-scale criminal offenses, the minimum compensation for each deceased victim or for each living organ extraction shall be 100 million dollars; for the injured, the minimum compensation shall be 5 million dollars per person. The fines for organ recipients shall be at least \$5 million per organ per person.</p>
6	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, rape, gang rapes, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching</p>

	<p>200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>The criminal nation is required to publicly disclose detailed information about all suspects and masterminds behind all criminals within its borders, including detailed information about their immediate family members and all descendants, within 15 days of the occurrence of this incident. Any individual who defrauds money shall have all their assets confiscated, including their family's assets, in order to fully recover the victims' properties and ensure complete compensation for the losses.</p>
7	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 300 or more within three years, or with 100 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Within the next 100 years, all criminals and their descendants must have traceability whenever they leave any city or region, and must report to the law enforcement agencies of the victim countries. All assets of the immediate family members and all descendants of the offender must be permanently disclosed.</p>
8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term</p>

	<p>world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The criminal nation must compensate the victims' property losses in the victim country. The calculation of the monetary interest rate for property losses must be based on a compensation rate of 40-50% of Warren Buffett's annual compound real return of 20.44% from 1957 to 2022. If punitive damages are to be awarded, the rate of compensation should be higher. Any act of deceiving or coercing gambling is considered illegal plunder of wealth. Any act of deceiving or coercing tipping is considered illegal plunder of wealth.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If a criminal State lacks sufficient funds to fully compensate the victim State or victims in cash, with the agreement of the victim State or victims, part of the compensation from the criminal State can be in the form of land, with the maximum compensation not exceeding 50% of its territory based on land area. However, this land must be legally owned by the country without controversy, and should be used to offset 20-80% of the compensation amount. Land should not be contaminated and compensated land must be continuous. If the criminal State is adjacent to the victim State, then a portion of the adjacent land should be partitioned directly and compensated to the victim State. If the land is not adjacent to the affected country, then it must border another country or be located along the coast. If the land is coastal, then the criminal country must compensate the victimized country with nearby islands and corresponding waters. All rights to land and its corresponding waters belong to the affected State and become part of its territory and waters. The criminal State must evacuate all residents of the compensatory land at the expense of the criminal State. All living facilities must be maintained and not destroyed. If resettlement causes difficulties, up</p>

	<p>to 10% of the female population in the area may be allowed to remain. Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
10	<p>Politicians, military personnel, police, intelligence personnel, or public officials involved in or protecting the implementation of large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, and human trafficking must be sentenced to a minimum of 6 to 60 years of imprisonment or death without parole. Dietary standards in prisons can only be based on the minimum standard of living set by middle-income countries in Africa for survival. The offender must serve their sentence in the victim country, and the prison where the offender serves must be a national prison in the victim country or a prison built and managed by the victims. The criminals can also be forcibly exiled to cold regions or desert areas to perform forced labor. These criminal individuals, their family members, or their descendants are not allowed to engage in the government, military, police, intelligence, judicial, biological, chemical, medical, media, or financial industries, nor can they hold any government positions in the next 5000 years. They are permanently banned from running for any parliament, presidency, or any government office. They are permanently barred from running for or holding leadership positions in any non-governmental organization. Individuals currently employed in the aforementioned fields must resign within 48 hours. All personal properties or assets under the control of these individuals must be fully compensated to the victim country and victims. Such individuals, their descendants and family members must report all currency assets held in bank accounts to the relevant institutions in the victim country and to the United Nations within 48 hours of receiving the account.</p> <p>For the next 100 years, the annual consumption level of their descendants and family members must not exceed the national average level.</p>
11	<p>Since the beginning of the last century, the number of law students worldwide has increased several times. However, there has been a significant increase in serious crimes against humanity such as kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking or organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres. Judicial institutions have never modified laws to enforce efficient and rapid crackdowns on these crimes. The current judicial system is far less effective than China's ancient system and does not provide adequate protection for citizens' personal safety. Instead, lawyers receive the highest income level, and judicial institutions have completely failed to fulfill their obligations and responsibilities to suppress and reduce crime. They have also not demonstrated the capacity to curb and reduce crime. Consequently, all judicial personnel responsible for formulating the above-mentioned legal provisions should no longer be allowed to formulate any legislative ideologies. Legal rights and procedures for defending criminals and criminal nations involved in these large-scale crimes should be abolished. Any lawyer should</p>

	<p>not be allowed to defend these criminal States and criminals, and their defense should be regarded as committing serious and equivalent crimes against humanity. Any secondary attacks by the victim against the above-mentioned criminals should not be considered as excessive defence, but should instead be commended.</p>
12	<p>Given the serious and long-standing mass criminality in Myanmar, the United Nations, as the global organization responsible for global affairs, has completely failed to coordinate swift action to suppress and combat this crime. This failure has allowed Thailand to become a conduit for the trafficking of kidnapped persons from Myanmar. Salaries of officials in the UN Nations justice system and those in charge of Asian affairs must be reduced by at least 30%. The annual fees paid by China to the UN must be reduced by at least 15-30% until all Chinese victims in Myanmar have been fully assisted, all criminals have been severely punished, and all perpetrators and protectors involved in large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and slaughter have been severely punished. Only after all victims have received adequate compensation, as specified in this article, can the previously deducted amounts be restored.</p>
13	<p>All criminals and their patrons who commit large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and indiscriminate killing, have hoarded enormous amounts of wealth. In criminal states like Myanmar, they not only relentlessly extract the properties of the victims, pushing their families into severe debt, but also unceasingly force victims to scam others to amass wealth for them. They continuously rape and gang-rape their victims, akin to subjugating sex slaves. They coerce kidnapped females into pregnancy and childbirth and extract the victims' breast milk for the wealthy in Myanmar to consume, and produce luxury skincare products. They turn the newborns of these victims into sources for illegal organ harvesting. Concurrently, they are also making more and more victims into living organ donors. After organ extraction, they bury the victims alive or slaughter them.</p> <p>Therefore, any resident or national of the criminal country Myanmar, and any suspected criminal and their family members (including direct family members) must publicly and permanently disclose any property they hold in any country. Anyone who has resided in Myanmar for over a month, or who holds dual citizenship with Myanmar (excluding staff of embassies of other countries in Myanmar), must permanently publicly disclose all their personal and family assets to everyone globally. Every bank around the globe must publicize all assets and detailed listings and accounts of Burmese people, their family members, and those holding Myanmar nationality or dual nationality with Myanmar, including a detailed record of asset growth or decrease over the past 30 years, to help curb fraud and the transfer of fraudulent funds. All account details must be publicly available on the internet for anyone to</p>

	<p>review. Any assets suspected to be illegal by law enforcement officials from the United Nations, the United States, China, or the affected countries must be clarified within 48 hours. In addition, everyone in other countries where similar large-scale cases have occurred and their families, regardless of whether their spouses are Burmese, must publicly disclose all their property and bank assets.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
14	<p>The disclosure of assets by officials is a sign of societal progress, while the anonymity provided by cryptocurrencies encourages the safe transfer of illegal funds by criminals. A global consensus must be reached to permanently ban the use of cryptocurrencies by all residents of criminal states such as Myanmar, any individuals under suspicion of criminal activity, their family members (including direct relatives), nationals, persons with dual Myanmar nationality, and anyone within Myanmar's territory. Anyone who has made transfers or payments in excess of \$100 using cryptocurrencies in the past must provide the name and details of the person involved in the transfer.</p>
15	<p>Any criminal or suspect who has committed a crime in conjunction with a resident of the criminal state of Myanmar must permanently disclose all personal and family property in any country (including direct family members). Every bank worldwide must publicize all assets, detailed listings, and accounts held by the offender or suspect, along with a record of the increase or decrease in assets over the past 30 years. All details must be displayed on the internet and accessible for anyone to view.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
16	<p>Reward system: The victim country should first transfer the compensation received from the offender and the offending country to the victims. The compensation received by the victim country will then be proportionally distributed as rewards to global peace warriors who assist in upholding justice, as well as to all other countries and the United Nations that make claims against the offending country. The remaining 50% will be rewarded to the global leading countries that support and lead the claim, for example, if the leading country is the United States, then the reward will be given to the United States. If the criminal country compensates the victims and the affected country in the form of permanent land transfer, 0.7-1% of the annual fiscal income generated by the region over the next 30 years will be awarded as a bonus to the lead claimant, if the United States is the country leading the claim, then the bonus will be awarded to the United States. Other problems in dealing with the crimes of the offending country have also led to the permanent transfer of land to the affected country, and the same provisions</p>

	<p>for rewarding the leading country as mentioned above apply.</p> <p>Only by adequately rewarding countries that lead the fight against malignant criminal nations, can the world sustain peace.</p>
17	<p>In Chinese history, there has never been such a large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and massacre of civilians by criminals within another country's jurisdiction during peacetime. This is a major regression in human ethics and law. Despite a significant increase in the number of government officials worldwide, the number of graduates and doctors in political science, philosophy, management, and law far exceeds that of ancient China. In ancient China, once such large-scale crimes occurred, officials would either be dismissed or executed if they failed to resolve the situation within a specific time frame, allowing more capable officials to govern the country and the world. Today, the United Nations, to some extent, resembles a salaried organization that fails to demonstrate any strong emergency response and coordination capabilities in combating criminals and their host countries. Therefore, it is necessary to establish the necessary punitive measures for officials.</p> <p>Any city, county or region in any country with a population of one million or less, if it experiences 6 cases of missing or abducted children, 6 cases of adult kidnapping, human trafficking, 30 cases of torture, 20 cases of rape or gang rape, 3 cases of organ harvesting within a year, the officials in charge of the city, county or region's security work as well as the officials directly responsible must be dismissed. After dismissal, their official positions must be demoted by at least three levels. For more populous counties, cities, or regions, penalty rules are calculated proportionally based on their population. If the number of victims in any of the categories exceeds three times the aforementioned quantities, county, city, or regional chiefs, security chiefs, and the head of the police department must be dismissed. After dismissal, their official positions must be demoted by at least five levels, and their legal responsibilities must be pursued.</p> <p>Cases that are promptly stopped are not included in punitive statistics.</p>
18	<p>In ancient China, unless there were special considerations, all criminals had to be publicly displayed during their detention and transportation. They had to march in the streets to make the public fully aware of their appearance in order to deter criminals, increase public awareness of precautions, and deter those who were considering committing crimes but had not yet done so. Clearly, the current relevant legal provisions are completely misguided and must be corrected, returning to the correct practices of the past. Any criminal must show their face during escort, trial, or public activities, and must not wear any head covering or mask, to publicly display his or her crimes. This deters existing and future criminals, facilitates public recognition of offenders, and also enhances the public's sense of justice.</p>
19	<p>In the course of a crime, if a perpetrator, criminal organization or criminal State destroys any evidence, the seriousness of the crime will no longer be</p>

	determined by the evidence provided by the perpetrator but by the victim State and the victims themselves. Any record provided by the criminal or criminal country about large-scale massacres must be considered from the starting point of the plan, or it will be considered destruction of evidence. Anyone who directly or indirectly orders the destruction of evidence, and those who carry it out, can be subjected to severe punishment, and must be severely punished for crimes against humanity.
20	Any righteous organization has the right to combat, in any manner, the criminal members, criminal organizations, and their protectors within countries that commit large-scale crimes like Myanmar and protectors of massive crimes. Any country or individual has the freedom to provide any kind of weaponry or equipment until the criminals and their organizations are eliminated.
21	All Burmese politicians or military officers and members of their families or descendants who have contributed to Myanmar's grave criminal situation by disregarding the Panglong Agreement are prohibited from engaging in government, military, police, intelligence, judicial, media, or financial industries, and cannot hold government positions. They are permanently banned from running for any parliamentary, presidential or government office. They are also permanently prohibited from running for or holding any leadership positions in any non-governmental organization.
22	Any criminal state as defined by this agreement will be stripped of its voting rights in international judicial institutions for 5000 years.
23	Any criminal state as defined by this agreement will lose its voting rights in any international organization, including the United Nations, for 5000 years.
24	Any criminals or their descendants who are involved in the crimes stipulated in this agreement will be permanently barred from holding positions such as Chief Justice, Deputy Chief Justice, Supreme Court Jury, Prosecutor General, Deputy Prosecutor General, members of the Public Prosecutor Committee, Chief Prosecutor, Prosecutor, and Senior Prosecutor of the Supreme Court.
25	Any criminal or their descendants who are involved in the crimes stipulated in this agreement will be forever prohibited from holding any formal or informal position in any international judicial institution or in the United Nations.
26	Prior to signing a compensation agreement with the victimized country and paying all agreed compensation in accordance with the agreement, no country, institution or enterprise may engage in investment activities in the criminal State. They must not violate ethical principles by constructing any infrastructure for the criminal nation, including roads, railways, or ports, without considering the still-grieving victims.
27	After the signing of this consensus, or following the formation of a governmental consensus by the United Nations or after a declaration by the United Nations, any country where large-scale crimes such as fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, torture and

	forced organ harvesting, and human trafficking have been committed since 1950 and have yet to be held accountable, must sign the first compensation agreement with the victim country and the victims within six months, and it must be implemented immediately. If the compensation plan does not begin to be implemented, all investment or construction of infrastructure in the criminal State by the countries that have signed this consensus must be immediately and completely halted.
28	Any country that refuses to sign this agreement should be considered as intending to instigate or protect future large-scale fraudulent behavior, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, torture, forced organ harvesting, and human trafficking.
25	Criminals from the offending country and their descendants, or their companies, should be completely and permanently barred from controlling any company in any countries outside their own through investment or economic activities.
26	A comprehensive and permanent ban should be enforced on criminals, their descendants, their companies, subsidiaries or their overseas counterparts from the offending country from leasing or purchasing land in any country.
27	Within the next 50,000 years, it is completely and permanently prohibited that the sum of land purchased or obtained by criminal countries or their citizens, descendants, companies, subsidiaries, or overseas researchers in any third country exceed 0.01% of the total territory of that country. For the land exceeding the above - mentioned quota, it must be transferred to others within eight months. If no buyer is found, all rights and interests will be deemed to be automatically forfeited.
28	Trials should be conducted in the victimized countries for criminals and criminal nations. The trials should not be held in the criminal countries. The jury system from the United States should be used, composed of ordinary citizens from the victim countries' territories. There are three specific requirements: First, the jury must be ordinary civilians from the county-level areas of the affected countries. Second, these civilians should not have received higher education. Third, they must hold the nationality of the victim country and have never changed their nationality. In addition, jury members should be between the ages of 18 and 75, with no age limit for victims. The jury shall consist of 60 persons, with any final punishment measures beyond the compensation and penalties prescribed in this consensus decided by the jury. Multiple prosecutions can be held by multiple victimized countries against the criminal nation and the criminals.
29	In criminal countries where large-scale crimes have occurred, the legal age for marriage must be at least 28 or 30 years old for men and at least 28 or 30 years old for women in order for them to get married and have children.
30	Any citizen of the criminal nation with a large-scale crime, or their descendants, or the descendants of their companies, or the descendants of any family business with assets or market value exceeding \$100 million, must

	sell their surplus assets within 60 working days, with priority given to selling to citizens who hold only the nationality of the given country.
31	All rewards and bonuses obtained in the activities of combating the large-scale crimes described in this consensus are exempt from personal income tax and inheritance tax.
32	Once a country or individual is involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this consensus, any institution or financial institution must disclose within five working days the funds or assets held by the criminal country, offender or criminal organization, as well as the corresponding list. Any bank, financial institution, individual, or organization that assists the offender or the criminal country or relatives of the offender in hiding assets in violation of this consensus, should be fined five times the value of the hidden assets and all personal and family assets of the criminal individual should be confiscated. It only allows to retain the minimum living allowance of that country. Violators and their descendants should be permanently prohibited from engaging in any financial, governmental, legal, police, security, military, or related work.
33	All those who plan, command, implement, and protect the large-scale crimes mentioned in this consensus, either as a criminal nation or as an offender, must stand trial in the victim's country. If a criminal destroys evidence of a crime or conceals the truth of a crime, no evidence of innocence, mitigation, or leniency provided by the criminal themselves or their defense attorney should be considered or accepted. Courts and juries may not believe any statement given by the offender on behalf of themselves or their group for their own interest. These criminals cannot have any defense attorneys and all evidence must be based on evidence provided by the victims or others. No country or region can harbor these types of criminals against humanity. The offender's country of origin or hiding place must hand them over to the victim's country within two weeks. Otherwise, the victim's country or any other country can target and attack the hidden offender, including military strikes.
34	If the offender is confirmed to be hiding in a sheltering country, the costs incurred will be borne by that country. If that country refuses to bear the costs, the United Nations has the right to freeze any assets of that country or its citizens globally. If the offender has destroyed any evidence of the crime or has concealed the facts of the crime, any evidence provided by the offender or defense attorney for acquittal, mitigation, or leniency will not be considered or accepted. If a lawyer mitigates his/her crimes, but it is proven otherwise, it indicates that the lawyer has lost the basic human rights standards, moral bottom line, and legal bottom line. The attorney and the criminal must at least be sentenced to the same level of crime, if it is the death penalty, the lawyer must be sentenced to death. Courts and juries may not believe any statement made by the offender or his/her interested party for the defense that is beneficial to the offender or his/her group. These offenders cannot be referred to as suspects before trial. Any bribery that results in

	lenient sentencing or the offender being acquitted will double the offender's liability. Any accountability system is not limited or restricted by time.
35	Any criminal State that fails to adequately compensate victims and their families, as well as the victim country, will be considered barbaric and uncivilized. Countries that have not signed agreements to fully compensate victims and their families, and countries persecuted in genocide, as recognized by victims, will be regarded as barbarous and uncivilized. No country, company, institution, or individual shall build roads, railways, or ports for such a criminal state.
36	<p>Since 1900, any criminal State that has perpetrated any one of the crimes of massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, or harvesting live organs against the public of another country, cannot serve as a permanent member of the UN or of any regional organization for the next three thousand years. Any politician from any country who proposes such a country will automatically be regarded as evil and without a moral bottom line.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
37	<p>Since 1900, according to this global consensus, any country, its descendants, or overseas descendants of those with citizenship who participated in mass killings, cannot own global media with the potential to influence other countries. If they currently hold these rights, the media control rights of other countries must be sold to other ethnic groups in that country, with priority given to ethnic groups of victims of mass killings. This transaction must be completed within three months. This provision should form a consensus among the governments of various countries and become part of the UN Declaration.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
30	Any citizen of the criminal nation with a large-scale crime, or their descendants, or the descendants of their companies, or the descendants of any family business with assets or market value exceeding \$100 million, must sell their surplus assets within 45 working days, with priority given to selling

	to citizens who hold only the nationality of the given country.
31	All rewards and bonuses obtained in the activities of combating the large-scale crimes described in this consensus are exempt from personal income tax and inheritance tax.
32	Once a country or individual is involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this consensus, any institution or financial institution must disclose within five working days the funds or assets held by the criminal country, offender or criminal organization, as well as the corresponding list. Any bank, financial institution, individual, or organization that assists the offender or the criminal country or relatives of the offender in hiding assets in violation of this consensus, should be fined five times the value of the hidden assets and all personal and family assets of the criminal individual should be confiscated. It only allows to retain the minimum living allowance of that country. Violators and their descendants should be permanently prohibited from engaging in any financial, governmental, legal, police, security, military, or related work.
33	All those who plan, command, implement, and protect the large-scale crimes mentioned in this consensus, either as a criminal nation or as an offender, must stand trial in the victim's country. If a criminal destroys evidence of a crime or conceals the truth of a crime, no evidence of innocence, mitigation, or leniency provided by the criminal themselves or their defense attorney should be considered or accepted. Courts and juries may not believe any statement given by the offender on behalf of themselves or their group for their own interest. These criminals cannot have any defense attorneys and all evidence must be based on evidence provided by the victims or others. No country or region can harbor these types of criminals against humanity. The offender's country of origin or hiding place must hand them over to the victim's country within two weeks. Otherwise, the victim's country or any other country can target and attack the hidden offender, including military strikes.
34	If the offender is confirmed to be hiding in a sheltering country, the costs incurred will be borne by that country. If that country refuses to bear the costs, the United Nations has the right to freeze any assets of that country or its citizens globally. If the offender has destroyed any evidence of the crime or has concealed the facts of the crime, any evidence provided by the offender or defense attorney for acquittal, mitigation, or leniency will not be considered or accepted. If a lawyer mitigates his/her crimes, but it is proven otherwise, it indicates that the lawyer has lost the basic human rights standards, moral bottom line, and legal bottom line. The attorney and the criminal must at least be sentenced to the same level of crime, if it is the death penalty, the lawyer must be sentenced to death. Courts and juries may not believe any statement made by the offender or his/her interested party for the defense that is beneficial to the offender or his/her group. These offenders cannot be referred to as suspects before trial. Any bribery that results in lenient sentencing or the offender being acquitted will double the offender's

	liability. Any accountability system is not limited or restricted by time.
35	Any criminal State that fails to adequately compensate victims and their families, as well as the victim country, will be considered barbaric and uncivilized. Countries that have not signed agreements to fully compensate victims and their families, and countries persecuted in genocide, as recognized by victims, will be regarded as barbarous and uncivilized. No country, company, institution, or individual shall build roads, railways, or ports for such a criminal state.
36	<p>Since 1900, any criminal State that has perpetrated any one of the crimes of massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, or harvesting live organs against the public of another country, cannot serve as a permanent member of the UN or of any regional organization for the next three thousand years. Any politician from any country who proposes such a country will automatically be regarded as evil and without a moral bottom line.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
37	<p>Since 1900, according to this global consensus, any country, its descendants, or overseas descendants of those with citizenship who participated in mass killings, cannot own global media with the potential to influence other countries. If they currently hold these rights, the media control rights of other countries must be sold to other ethnic groups in that country, with priority given to ethnic groups of victims of mass killings. This transaction must be completed within three months. This provision should form a consensus among the governments of various countries and become part of the UN Declaration.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
38	Provisions for the defense, trial, conviction, identification and compensation of offenders committing massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, human trafficking, or harvesting live organs should be incorporated into the criminal laws of each country according to this global consensus. Each UN contracting country should amend their national or

	<p>regional laws within six months after formally forming a government consensus.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
39	<p>For any country where crimes such as large - scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, or live - organ harvesting occur, if the total number of victims exceeds 10,000 within any five - year period, the victim country may station troops in the criminal country, and all costs of the troop - contributing country shall be borne by the criminal country.</p> <p>If there are multiple victim countries, troops are allocated according to the number of victims in each country. The location of the stationed troops is designated by the country of the victims. If the stationed troops are threatened, they can take any action. Any actions of the stationed troops are not bound by the laws of the criminal country, but only by the laws of the victim country.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
40	<p>All personal and family property of the criminals involved in this consensus, as well as the property of relatives or illegitimate children sponsored by the criminals, must be confiscated and compensated to the victims.</p>
41	<p>Any medical personnel involved in forced organ harvesting and illegal use, once found participating in such illegal activities, their professional qualifications shall be immediately terminated, and their descendants shall forever be forbidden from engaging in the medical profession, becoming civil servants, government officials, judicial professionals, or military personnel.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
42	<p>Even if the offender involved in this consensus is deceased, all of his or her personal and family assets must be confiscated and compensated to the victims, whether transferred to their relatives, spouses, descendants, illegitimate children, or lovers.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
43	<p>If a county or region with a population of up to 5 million people experiences a case of missing children or adults, human trafficking, organ harvesting, or death, and at least 100,000 people believe the outcome is unjust and the public widely suspects the investigative process or results of the police, and the police themselves cannot resolve the issue, as long as three countries among the top 50 in global GDP raise objections, the police of the country where the incident occurred should invite law enforcement personnel from</p>

	<p>those three countries to participate in the investigation within three days. Each country will send four representatives, and all expenses will be borne by the country where the incident occurred. The third country and the victim's family members will have access to all case materials.</p> <p>If a county or region experiences cases of missing or abducted children or adults, organ harvesting, or death, and the public widely suspects the investigation process or outcome of the police, and the police themselves are unable to resolve it, with at least 50,000 people believing that the outcome of the case is unjust, as long as three countries in the top 50 in the world GDP rankings raise objections, the law enforcement authorities of the country where the incident occurred should invite three law enforcement personnel from each of the three countries to participate in the investigation of the case within three days. The costs will be borne by the country where the incident occurred, and both the third country and the families involved should have access to all case-related information.</p> <p>The country where the incident occurred must provide all conveniences to allow police officers from three countries to arrive in that country within the next three days. The country where the incident occurred must take all measures to protect the health and safety of relevant personnel.</p>
44	<p>Anyone who uses internet media or self-media to whitewash criminals or criminal groups or criminal countries engaged in telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, torture, organ harvesting, human trafficking, or massacre, and misleads or deceives the public, if found, after being pointed out twice or warned twice, continues the aforementioned acts, will be treated as participating in all the aforementioned criminal activities along with the whitewashed criminals. Judicial institutions must calculate and punish the crimes committed by them cumulatively.</p>
45	<p>Any county or region with a population of 1-5 million, including Myanmar, that experiences 5 cases of child abduction or trafficking, 300 cases of telecommunication fraud, 8 cases of kidnapping, disappearance or trafficking in persons, torture, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, or illegal harvesting of organs within a year. The person responsible, the head of security, and the police chief of that county or region must be removed from their posts. After dismissal, their official position must be demoted by at least three levels, and officials must be held legally accountable. For counties or regions with larger populations, punishment rules shall be calculated proportionally. Cases that are promptly stopped are not included in punitive statistics.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
46	<p>Any county or region with a population of 1-5 million in any country, including Myanmar, within 2 years, As long as there are 5 cases of abduction or trafficking of children, 300 cases of telecommunication fraud, 8 cases of</p>

	<p>population kidnapping, disappearance, or trafficking, 5 cases of organ harvesting, where at least 80% of the major criminals cannot be captured, the main responsible person, the main person in charge of security work, and the police chief of the county or region must be removed from their positions. After dismissal, their official positions must be demoted by at least three levels, and the legal responsibilities of the officials must be pursued. For counties or regions with larger populations, sentencing rules shall be calculated proportionally.</p>
47	<p>If belated justice is considered justice, then what about evil? In fact, what we are largely lacking is not belated justice, but justice in the present moment. What is justice in the present moment? Justifiable self-defense is justice in the present moment. If justice cannot be served in the present, it lacks courage and true justice. If justice always arrives late, how can justice in the present be tolerated? Where do we begin to ensure security for individuals, children, women, and families, peace in the world, and continuous global harmony?</p> <p>What we lack most today is justice in the present, and yet, we are required to pay an excessive cost, even at the expense of the victims' lives. The entire society ignores the devastating harm inflicted on victims and their families by those who implement and establish the legal system, yet they do not take any responsibility or face any punishment. The legal system itself is severely lagging behind in its response to heinous crimes. In Myanmar, there are large-scale incidents of kidnapping, rape, gang rape, force the victims to be sex slaves, torture, organ harvesting, and massacre occurring every year. Where is justice from the International Court of Justice in The Hague? Where are the judges who uphold justice in the International Court of Justice? How long have they been asleep? Do they still receive salaries? In ancient China, judges who did not perform their duties were imprisoned or executed. You are law enforcement officers, and you should have a better understanding of the law than ordinary people. Shouldn't you be the first to be punished?</p> <p>Therefore, any urgent defenses and further action against the criminals involved in this consensus are justified. This includes any urgent action taken by those who show bravery in the face of righteousness. These actions should be commended and considered innocent. Regardless of the age of the offender, as long as they commit crimes, they are criminals. Even if they are still minors, they are still criminals, and their guardians are equally guilty. All the provisions of this consensus can be applied to punish their crimes. No judiciary in any country can deem the defensive actions of those involved in this consensus as guilty. Otherwise, if such law enforcement judgments occur, the relevant law enforcement personnel and lawyers can no longer engage in any law enforcement work. Criminals are the minority, and only by cracking down on and eliminating minority criminals can the security of the vast majority of good people be ensured.</p>
47	<p>In any country, should a telecommunication fraud hub emerge and is not dismantled within a month after being established, legal responsibility must</p>

	<p>be pursued against the leaders of that region and the judicial bodies. Those at the management level of the aforementioned institutions must be relieved of their posts immediately. The individuals concerned and their descendants shall be prohibited from holding any public service or government position, as well as from joining the military, the police, the security forces or similar organizations, whether on a permanent or temporary basis, and they shall be barred from working in the financial and economic sectors.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
48	<p>It is prohibited for any country or region that has ever been involved in crimes related to large-scale public consensus to operate offline or online gambling businesses or gambling venues. Violators should be sentenced to at least ten years' imprisonment.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
49	<p>Any country that refuses to sign this Consensus or Convention will be considered as a country attempting to commit or protect massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, or organ harvesting crimes, and plunder the wealth of victims.</p> <p>Any country opposing the core terms of this consensus or convention will be considered a country that disrupts the international moral order and crimes against humanity.</p> <p>Any politician opposing the core terms of this agreement or convention will be considered a politician who disrupts the international moral order and is against humanity.</p> <p>Any politician who opposes the core provisions of the agreement or convention that prevent the country from signing should force himself, his wife, son and daughter to experience the torture inflicted by all criminals in Myanmar for six months.</p>
50	<p>For criminals or criminal suspects who commit fraud, torture, rape (including gang rape), homicide, or trafficking in human beings, any lawyer is prohibited from providing any defence services. In court, only offenders or criminal suspects themselves are allowed to defend. If a lawyer is found to have turned the guilty of such criminals into the not - guilty or turned felonies into misdemeanors, the lawyer's professional qualification will be revoked, he or she will be permanently prohibited from engaging in this profession, and he or she will be sentenced to imprisonment for at least two years.</p>
51	<p>Gambling, a lifestyle that avoids labor, is a rather barbaric way of life driven by the desire to get rich overnight through luck and deceit, akin to a Ponzi scheme. Many victims, once lured into Myanmar, are coerced by fraud groups to gamble in casinos, making the profits of fraudulent kidnapping groups appear legitimate. Some victims lose all their money within minutes and are</p>

	<p>forced to borrow high-interest loans to continue gambling. After losing again, they are left with no choice but to sell their bodies at the casino or even undergo forced organ harvesting. This has become commonplace in Myanmar. If gambling is not globally prohibited, especially in countries where telecommunications fraud or civil wars occur, as well as in impoverished nations, crime will be difficult to eradicate. Gambling in Myanmar sustains the military expenditures of local warlords.</p> <p>If the politicians of the United Nations and various countries genuinely desire peace and goodness in this world, and if they truly confront the objective fact that Myanmar's casinos have claimed countless lives, they should swiftly enact legislation and establish a global covenant. First, the personal and family assets of all public officials, military personnel, police officers, security agencies, bank employees, financial institutions, and individuals associated with casinos in any country that operates casinos must be publicly disclosed. Second, it is imperative to permanently prohibit the operation of casinos in any country afflicted by telecommunications fraud, civil war, or poverty. Existing casinos must be completely shuttered within two weeks of the signing of this covenant. Third, a global timetable must be established to close all casinos worldwide within a period of ten years. Fourth, to address the gambling problem in countries where a significant portion of the population is fond of gambling, one can consider adopting Hong Kong's horse racing and betting system, enhancing management standards, strictly limiting betting amounts, prohibiting cross-border betting or gambling, and mandating an annual percentage of donations to be provided to charitable organizations or charitable funds.</p>
52	<p>The world should establish a morally upright and ethical global community. Consequently, criminal activities such as defrauding other countries of their wealth should not serve as a means for illegal profit for certain nations and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should promptly reach consensus and establish conventions to prevent and address the above-mentioned issues. Since 1990, any country engaged in large-scale telecommunications fraud against another country's public, provided the defrauded wealth exceeded \$3 billion, should be prohibited from serving as a permanent member of the United Nations or any regional organization for the next 3000 years. If defrauded wealth exceeds \$10 billion, the prohibition extends to the next 10,000 years. If defrauded wealth exceeds \$20 billion, the ban extends to the next 20,000 years. If defrauded wealth exceeds \$30 billion, the ban extends to the next 30,000 years. If defrauded wealth exceeds \$40 billion, the prohibition extends to the next 40,000 years. Any politician from any country nominating such a criminal country as a permanent member of the council will automatically be considered a morally bankrupt and evil politician without any ethical standards. Once nominated, such bad politicians must be deemed to automatically resign from all government positions in their respective countries.</p>

53	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has built a telecommunications fraud base since 2000, if victims from any other country are defrauded, kidnapped, tortured, raped, gang-raped, turned into sex slaves, trafficked, disabled, organs harvested, buried alive, or slaughtered, all criminals must be handed over to the victim country for trial. The trial can only take place in the region or city where the victims' families are located in the victim country. If any criminal destroys evidence or the course of the crime, they are prohibited from having a defence lawyer. If any criminal destroys evidence, all crimes will be doubled. For crimes committed abroad, the penalty will also be doubled. Any criminal who attempts to evade trial, the victim State or other justice-presiding countries or armed organizations may use weapons authorized by the United Nations to strike back.</p> <p>If a defense attorney commits perjury, both the attorney and the legal team must bear the same responsibility, face criminal punishment, and disclose all personal and family assets of the legal team.</p>
54	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>A country's assets do not belong to any political party, and it is prohibited for politicians of political parties in any state to waive claims on behalf of the state, its public, or victims against a criminal state or war criminal state that has committed large-scale crimes. Waiting for such claims goes against fundamental human ethics and rational logic, seriously violates the human rights of others, and is completely unsubstantiated from a legal standpoint. National assets belong solely to all citizens with the nationality of that country, and victims' property belongs only to the victims themselves, not to politicians, political parties or governments. Not holding a criminal state accountable for severe crimes and looting of property, and not forcing the</p>

	<p>return of all wealth, constitutes a major crime against the good people of that nation, a crime against human peace, a crime against those who diligently create wealth, and encourages the criminal state to initiate crimes. It also encourages a criminal State or a war criminal State to unlawfully accumulate wealth. Accordingly, the following global convention must be established:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prohibit any state's politicians from renouncing claims for compensation and reparations against the criminal State or war criminal State that has committed large-scale crimes on behalf of the State or its nationals or victims. 2. To prevent possible direct or potential interest deals between the politician and their family with the criminal state, creating material conditions for the politician's descendants, if such proposals are presented by politicians, the entire direct lineage relatives and all direct lineage of those relatives, and the blood-related collateral relatives' family property will unconditionally belong to the victims once the politician's opinion becomes a fact. 3. Due to the significant impact on the descendants of victims, if the third generation of the proposing politician is alive at the time, three consecutive generations of that politician's family must compensate the victims and restore the national property loss. Only after full restitution is made to the victims can they live freely; otherwise, the three generations of the politician who made the proposal must only enjoy the most basic living standard of the country, and they will be prohibited from flying in airplanes and traveling on luxury cruise ships. If there has been a high-minded family style since 1900, characterized by treating their own, their family members', and relatives' wealth with disdain, compensation to victims would naturally be voluntary. If not, it indicates extreme hypocrisy in the family, and the descendants of such a person should be banned from engaging in politics or holding any civil service or legal positions for a thousand years. 4. Any compensation that is disproportionate to loss and suffering is invalid, even if it was signed under external pressure in the past.
55	<p>Any state that legalizes organized crime (underworld organizations, or Mafia-like, or mobs, or gangland) is a barbaric and despicable nation, an uncivilized country, and a country without religious beliefs. It should never have voting rights in the United Nations and the Security Council, nor can it become a permanent member of the United Nations or the Security Council. Even if the legitimacy of organized crime is revoked in the future, the country should not become a permanent member of the United Nations for 300 years after the revocation, and should not be allowed to become a permanent member of the Security Council. In the future, any politician who proposes that a country with legalized organized crime or where such crimes are permissible should become a permanent member of the United Nations or the Security Council will be defined as an evil, contemptible and inferior anti-humanist politician. This evil country does not allow voting rights in the United Nations or any organization.</p>
56	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the</p>

current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.

Since 2000, any country that has committed the following crimes without fully compensating the victimized nation must accept the following sanctions and use them on any official occasion:

A country that has built numerous telecommunication fraud parks to carry out large-scale telecommunications fraud, extortion of property, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, organ trading, torture, or massacres, if within any consecutive 5-year period, the number of people involved reaches one hundred thousand, or the total wealth obtained from fraud reaches \$10 billion(calculated according to the currency value of 2023), it must be re-named a SR or SRM or RSM or ST or STM or TSM nation, and is prohibited from changing its name for 1000 years. For example, Myanmar must be renamed SR- Myanmar, SRM-Myanmar, RSM Myanmar, ST-Myanmar, STM-Myanmar, or TSM -Myanmar in any international occasion, including United Nations conferences and international sports events.

Even if Myanmar is disintegrated into several countries, these countries must inherit the prefixes of the above names. For example, if Myanmar is divided into three countries (AAA, BBB, CCC), and even if they try to escape the crime against humanity committed by Myanmar, they must be renamed as SR-AAA or SRM-AAA or RSM-AAA or ST-AAA or STM-AAA or TSM-AAA; SR-BBB or SRM-BBB or RSM-BBB or ST-BBB or STM-BBB or TSM-BBB; SR-CCC or SRM-CCC or RSM-CCC or ST-CCC or STM-CCC or TSM-CCC.

The republican form of government is a fair and just system, capable of achieving justice by engaging in and resolving political affairs and disputes peacefully. Republicanism emphasizes the public nature, fairness, and impartiality of government. Moreover, the positive connotations of democratic and free nations need no elaboration.

A wicked country that dares to carry out large-scale crimes without scruple, such as long-term brutal kidnappings, brutal torture, raping and gang-raping women, turning girls into sex slaves, live-harvesting human organs, and massacring kidnapped innocent people, must have its country name renamed. A country that does not commit large-scale crimes still has a country name with the thinking of normal people. Otherwise, it is a crime against humanity. Any politician, lawyer or citizen who opposes this proposal should consider what qualifications you have to raise objections. Why not legislate from the perspective of victims? If you do not legislate from the perspective of victims and quickly control crimes, it shows that you have lost the empathy that

legislators must have.

Therefore, you and all your family members must first experience three years of torture in Myanmar, being raped and gang-raped, being pregnant and giving birth after being gang-raped, being a sex slave, being forced to dig coal in a coal mine with primitive tools, having human organs harvested alive, or the pain of having family members killed. If you are still alive and not incapacitated by torture, then come to discuss legislation on this issue. Otherwise, you are a Don Quixote-like figure, a Wang Ming and Bo Gu in China, a Ma Hu and You Niao-like figure, a masked parrot who has never experienced the torture of multiple social hardships from middle school to university and does not know the ordinary hardships and pains.

If you deliberately demand legislation according to your will, in the future, all losses and compensation for victims will first be borne by you and all your family members and descendants with unlimited liability. If one victim dies, you must be executed after a public trial. If ten victims die, you and your children, your wife, and your parents must be executed after a public trial. If there are not enough members of your family, your immediate relatives must be executed. All personal and family property will be confiscated and compensated to the victims. If you are a corrupt official who comes to power with the support of your Democratic Party, your evil political party must also bear full compensation liability. All members must compensate the victims with their personal and family property. When the amount of compensation is insufficient, your country must compensate the victims.

If you do not have the ability to control crime, or empathy, and are even more unwilling to let you and your family members experience the pain of being victimized, but you still want to interfere in legislation, you are very harmful to society and should be sent to prison, deprived of all your political rights, and reflect on your own stupidity and ignorance.

Any country which has committed the aforementioned crimes and has not yet fully compensated the victims and the affected nation shall be prohibited from calling itself a "communist country," "democratic country," "free country," "progressive party", "democratic progressive party", "just country," "liberal democratic country," or "republic"; to prevent such a country from deceiving the public and other nations and undermining world peace.

In the aforementioned countries involved, any ruling party that refuses to sign written apologies and fails to provide full compensation is prohibited from calling itself the "Communist Party," "Socialist Party," "Social Party," "Democratic Party," "Republican Party," "Liberal Party," "Liberal Democratic Party," "Liberal Republican Party," "Republican Liberal Party," "Justice Party," "People's Party," "Democratic Republican Party," or "Republican Democratic Party," or "Justice Party." Furthermore, such ruling parties are prohibited from using any name containing the words "Republic," "Free," "Socialist,"

	<p>"Democratic," "Socialist," "Liberal," "Country," "Communist," or "Justice." Through these actions, a political-vigilance (politicalvigilance) is created both in the country and globally to prevent said political parties and their nefarious, unscrupulous politicians from deceiving the public and other nations, undermining global peace, with the goal of reducing war and achieving peace. The name involved in the case must be completely changed within three months.</p> <p>The above-mentioned methodologies for solving crime should be considered by the United Nations or the World Peace Organization as one of the methods for maintaining world peace and sustainable development. The United Nations should take the initiative to formulate relevant conventions as soon as possible.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
57	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects the crimes of mass rape or gang rape crimes stipulated by this Convention, or that is a state of war criminals or their citizens or descendants, will be prohibited from participating in the writing of any history books or historical textbooks for the next 1,000 years. The aforementioned publications from such a country can only be written by a specialized editorial team organized by the country with a larger number of victims and must be used compulsorily by everyone in that country or their descendants unless every country in the world agrees by vote. In the case of crimes committed since 1900, any event that results in the rape or gang rape of 5,000 innocent civilians in another country within a single event, 20,000 within a year, or 80,000 within any consecutive 8-year period, will be subject to this provision.</p> <p>Any nationals or women of aggressor or criminal States who wage aggressive wars are not covered by this Convention as a whole, and the entire population of those criminal States is guilty, with virtually no innocent civilians.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>

58	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects criminals involved in mass rapes or gang rapes as defined in this Convention, as well as their state or war criminals, citizens, or descendants, shall be prohibited from participating directly or indirectly in the establishment of any press, news, or media entity in any third country for the next thousand years, unless every country globally agrees by vote. This clause applies to any country where crimes since 1900 have resulted in 5,000 innocent civilians of another nation being raped or gang-raped in any single incident, 20,000 within one year, or 80,000 within any consecutive 8-year period.</p> <p>Any nationals or women of aggressor or criminal States who wage aggressive wars are not covered by this Convention as a whole, and the entire population of those criminal States is guilty, with virtually no innocent civilians.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
59	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country that commits or protects criminals involved in mass rapes or gang rapes as stipulated by this Convention, or a State guilty of war crimes, or its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in any international women's awards or from being awarded any international women's prizes for the next thousand years, unless every country in the world agrees by vote. This provision applies to any country where crimes committed since 1900 have resulted in 5,000 innocent civilians of another nation being raped or gang-raped in any single incident, 20,000 within one year, or 80,000 within any consecutive 8-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
60	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p>

	<p>Any nation which commits or protects criminals who commit offenses involving mass rape, gang rape as covered by this Convention, or is a state or war criminal, its citizens or their descendants, shall be prohibited from possessing legislative powers for the next thousand years and be forbidden from participating in legislation. Legislation in such a State shall be carried out only by a dedicated legislative team organized by States with a higher number of victims, and it must be used compulsorily by all persons in that State or their descendants. This clause applies to any State in which crimes committed since 1900 have resulted in 5,000 innocent civilians of another nation being raped or gang-raped in any single incident, 20,000 within one year, or 80,000 within any consecutive 8-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
61	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects criminals who commit offenses involving large-scale telecommunications fraud, or is a state or war criminal, its citizens or their descendants, shall be prohibited from possessing legislative powers for the next thousand years and be forbidden from participating in legislation. The nation's legislation shall be performed only by a specialized legislative team of nations with more victims and enforced among all people or their descendants. This clause applies to any State where crimes committed since 1900 caused 5,000 innocent civilians of another nation being raped or gang-raped in any single incident, 20,000 within one year, or 80,000 within any consecutive 8-year period, or where the total amount of fraud has reached ten billion U.S. dollars in any 5-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized</p>

	<p>people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
62	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country that implements or protects the criminals involved in large-scale telecommunication fraud as per this convention, or is a state of criminals or war criminals, shall be subject to the following measures if a religious organization within that country has engaged in creating conflicts, fraud, massacres of civilians of victim states, looting of property, extortion, rape, mass rape, kidnapping, the implementation of torture, or the extraction of organs, or has supported or protected criminal organizations or members of large-scale crimes: the religious organization must be globally regarded as a group or gang that is always ready to commit crimes under the guise of religious beliefs. The country must confiscate the property of the religious organization within its territory, remove all the leaders of the organization from their positions, and the organization must be declared illegal within that country for the next thousand years. It is prohibited for any member of the organization to conduct or participate in any religious gatherings, either within the country or globally, and to use any speech to induce the public. The personal and family properties of all members must be publicly disclosed in real-time for inspection by anyone. This clause applies to any crimes that has occurred since 1950 which resulted in 5,000 innocent civilians of another nation being raped or gang-raped in any single incident, 20,000 within one year, or 80,000 within any consecutive 8-year period, or in any instance where the total amount defrauded reaches \$10 billion in any 5-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
63	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any criminal state or nation of war criminals that has committed crimes involving mass fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, trafficking in human beings, harvesting of live organs, massacres including biowarfare, as</p>

	<p>covered by the Consensus, will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next 10,000 years. Moreover, if such a war criminal State, having committed any of the aforementioned crimes against the public of another nation since 1900, has not so far provided compensation for the losses of the victims, it will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next ten thousand years.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
64	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any criminal nation or war criminal State that has committed any crime against the public of another country, including large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, harvesting live organs, massacres, or the use of biochemical weapons as covered by this consensus, will be prohibited from owning or holding shares in any newspapers or media outlets abroad for the next thousand years. Moreover, if such a war criminal State has not compensated victims for their losses for crimes involving large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, live organ harvesting, massacres, or biochemical weapons since 1900, it will be prohibited from owning or holding shares in any newspapers or media outlets abroad for the next two thousand years.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
65	<p>Considerations of Philosophy and Methodology for Severely Cracking Down on Crimes of Robbery and Rape of Women and Preventing Incompetent and Unethical Individuals from Becoming Officials or Decision-Makers</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of</p>

world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.

Any evildoer who attacks women with the intent to rob, rape, or harm them, the woman's husband, or any third party upholder of justice may execute any necessary counterattack. Regardless of the degree of harm inflicted on the perpetrator, the defender is not guilty. If the criminal uses a knife or any other weapon, or if the criminal's fighting ability is superior to that of the victim or any person with a sense of justice, the victim and their family, or any person with a sense of justice, will not be convicted for using a vehicle or other means to attack the criminal. If the criminal's family insists that punishing the rapist is a crime, the criminal's family must be subject to criminal punishment.

Chairman Mao Zedong, a great Chinese philosopher and military strategist, once profoundly pointed out that: "What is leadership? What is the relationship between leadership and foresight? Foresight is seeing the trend of the future in advance. If there is no foresight, can it be called leadership? I say it cannot be called leadership." Politicians are typically those who hold leadership positions, and if they lack foresight, these politicians not only fail to create value for the public but also create crises. They must be promptly removed from government institutions and replaced by sober, morally upright, and capable individuals. If anyone voices opposition, the decision-makers must bear legal responsibility and joint economic compensation for any subsequent mistakes. This to some extent limits incompetent individuals from seeking leadership positions and harms the country and the public.

Politicians, lawyers, or judges, as leaders in their respective fields, must possess foresight; otherwise, they cannot assume leadership or propose policies.

Anyone who proposes erroneous policies that fail to protect victims, cause greater harm to victims, impede the strict punishment of criminals, or provide criminals with more opportunities to commit crimes must bear adequate responsibility and compensation for the consequences. If any politician, lawyer, or judge disagrees with this proposal, under the principles of empathy and equality in the judicial system, any past victim can find three individuals willing to rape the wife or daughter of the dissident politician, judge, or lawyer. If they can completely single-handedly protect their wife or daughter from being raped and gang-raped, and if more than half of the state's voters support them, this convention will be void for that part of the state's electorate. Once any voter has suffered such harm, all responsibility and compensation will be borne jointly by the criminal, politician, lawyer, and judge. For other voters who do not agree to cancel this convention, it will continue to be enforced.

In all cases where women or children are harmed or women resist harm,

	<p>if judicial officials, politicians, or civil servants give advice, issue commands, or make judicial rulings that are favorable to the criminals and result in aggravated harm to the victimized women or their protectors, once the victims have suffered substantial aggravated harm, the aforementioned judicial personnel, politicians, or civil servants shall be permanently prohibited from holding any position in judicial or governmental institutions and permanently prohibited from engaging in any political activities, and they must be dismissed within five working days.</p>
66	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for severely cracking down on evil criminals and protecting children</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any evildoer who attacks children with the intent to rob, rape, harm, or kidnap them, the child's parents, or any third party upholder of justice may execute any necessary continuous counterattack. Regardless of the degree of harm inflicted on the perpetrator, the defender is not guilty. If an attacker wields a knife or any other weapon, the defender is not guilty of using a vehicle to hit the attacker. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
67	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 2000, any criminal country that has built ten or more telecommunication fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre must fully compensate the victims and affected countries after they have completely eliminated such fraud centres. If officials from any country meet or hold discussions with officials from the offending country, whether in person or online, all official global media must label it a meeting with officials from one</p>

	<p>of the world's leading fraudulent nations. Otherwise, that country or media outlet will be considered an accessory to the fraudulent nation.</p> <p>It is prohibited for any third party or government to waive claims on behalf of victims without written and video authorization from all victims in that country. Any government's waiver of claims is inhumane and condones crime. Any politician who proposes to waive claims is inhumane, condones crime, and must be prohibited from participating in any international political activity, as such crimes include inhumane torture, rape, forced sterilization, mutilation, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or conventions.</p>
68	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that has built ten or more telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, after completely eliminating such zones and failing to compensate victims and affected countries in full, must be prohibited from receiving total annual investments exceeding \$10,000 from any country or organization. For countries with five telecommunications fraud zones, the total annual investment limit is \$50,000, for countries with three zones, the limit is \$60,000, and for countries with one zone, the limit is \$80,000.</p> <p>It is prohibited for any third party or government to waive claims on behalf of victims without written and video authorization from all victims in that country. Any government's waiver of claims is inhumane and condones crime.</p>

	<p>Any politician who proposes to waive claims is inhumane, condones crime, and must be prohibited from participating in any international political activity, as such crimes include inhumane torture, rape, forced sterilization, mutilation, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or conventions.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
69	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that has set up telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, it is necessary to establish a UN convention and international consensus to restrict the number of international flights in order to promote the fight against large-scale crime. For countries with ten or more telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region worldwide shall not exceed 3 per year. For countries with 5-9 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region worldwide shall not exceed 5 per year. For countries with 3-4 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region worldwide shall not exceed 6 per year. For countries with 1-2 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region in the world must not exceed 8 per year. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the</p>

	<p>future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>
70	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that constructs a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, a United Nations convention and international consensus must be established to restrict the behavior of its special personnel, in order to promote the fight against large-scale crime. Universities or colleges in any country are prohibited from admitting politicians, officials, civil servants, criminals, and any of their relatives from the criminal country for study. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>

71	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, even if the country has completely eliminated the fraud centers or fraud park, as long as it has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, and as long as it has not transferred all criminals to the affected country, the following restrictions must be imposed: a United Nations convention and international consensus must be established to restrict politicians, public officials, criminals and their relatives from that country, in order to urge the country to crack down on large-scale crime. Any university or college in any country must prohibit the admission of politicians, public servants, criminals, or any of their relatives from that country for the next 100 years. Any citizen of the country of criminals who enters any university or college in any other country must publicly disclose and declare all his or her personal and family assets, even if he or she holds dual nationality. People with dual citizenship must undergo even stricter scrutiny. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
72	<p>Spanish actress with 250,000 followers went on a bike trip to India with her husband. They were then robbed, assaulted, and gang-raped by 7 men while camping, causing immense pain and trauma to both of them.</p>

Over the past few decades, there have been frequent cases of women disappearing into public places, being kidnapped, gang-raped, tortured, and held captive for long periods, forcibly impregnated, and used as baby-making factories, with babies becoming organ factories. This has become a common occurrence, as criminal organizations not only rape women but also exploit them for profit through childbearing. The situation for babies born under these circumstances is even more tragic, as they are essentially treated as corpses. However, the current legal system severely hinders efforts to combat these criminals and deter rapists, failing to effectively protect women and children and instead being lenient towards criminals. This has led to rampant crime in Myanmar, with many women being raped every day. The fairness and justice of the law are far behind the atrocities, and this not only represents a dereliction of duty by the legal authorities at the top of the food chain, but also the greatest crime against humanity. If so many women are still being raped in this society and laws are not significantly amended, the lawmakers responsible for these laws should similarly be sentenced to death or long-term imprisonment.

Therefore, it is extremely necessary to quickly amend existing laws to form the following global consensus and United Nations convention: Any rapist of women, if beaten to death or injured by a justice-minded individual in an emergency, will not be held legally responsible. If the family of the criminal seeks justice, they will be held equally guilty and sentenced as accomplices. In addition, the principal perpetrators and accomplices of rape must be sentenced to death, and accomplices must be sentenced to at least thirty years in prison. Because kidnapping and raping women can result in the birth of a baby, the victim's breastmilk can bring substantial profits to the criminal gang. Given the high incidence of family-related crime, the personal and family assets of the criminal and their close relatives within three generations must be made public. Anyone who fabricates rape or causes harm to innocent individuals will be severely punished.

The international community and the United Nations should also reach consensus and agreement on the following issues: in India, judicial institutions are responsible for putting hoods on captured criminals. If a woman encounters these criminals on the street without knowing that they are repeat gang rapists, and is approached by them, losing the chance to escape, the responsibility should be shared by the judges, judicial institutions, and law enforcement agencies that authorized the use of hoods on criminals. These judicial officials are fully aware of the high likelihood of repeat offences by such criminals, yet they help conceal their faces, failing to adequately warn potential victims. This not only proves that these judicial officials are guilty, but also that their crimes must be considered more serious, as they are well aware that the reoffending rate of these criminals is higher. If judicial officials are unwilling to take responsibility, it shows that they are completely unfit for their judicial positions and unable to lower the crime rate. They must be

	<p>banned from practicing in the judicial industry, their positions revoked, and the Indian judicial system restructured. The use of hoods on criminals must be prohibited, and criminals must be publicly disclosed for everyone to be fully aware.</p> <p>The Indian government has confirmed that in 2018, on average, a woman in India was raped every 15 minutes. On February 10, 2020, at the graduation ceremony of Gargi College in New Delhi, more than a thousand attackers broke into the campus from outside the school, smashing and looting. Although there are currently no reports of casualties, many female students have been brutally raped. The international community and the United Nations should also form a consensus and convention on the following issues: in the event of a large-scale rape of female university students, the police must shoot and kill the criminals at the first opportunity to deter other criminals, otherwise the police will be punished for aiding and abetting rape.</p>
73	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter:</p> <p>Since 1994, if in any city, county or district, the total number of missing children in the past 30 years exceeds 1,000, with a clearance rate of less than 60 per cent and a safe recovery rate of less than 60 per cent, the personal and family assets of all civil servants in that area must be fully disclosed within three days of the incident. Officials in the area should not be promoted until over than 80 per cent of missing children have been recovered. Leading officials in the city should be demoted and held accountable.</p> <p>The personal and familial assets of any criminal, as well as those of their relatives up to three generations, must be disclosed.</p>
74	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The personal and family assets of any individual involved in large-scale trafficking in human beings, abduction of children, rape, gang rape, telecommunications fraud, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, burial, or massacre crimes, as well as those of their relatives up to six generations, must be disclosed. Judicial authorities must conduct rigorous scrutiny of them. All illegal and unidentified assets must be fully confiscated.</p>
75	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter:</p> <p>Any case involving murder in a rape or gang rape, regardless of whether the</p>

	perpetrator is an adult or a minor, all criminals must be sentenced to death uniformly.
76	The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: From now on, if any city, town, or county experiences a missing child case that remains unsolved, all officials in that area should be temporarily prohibited from promotion until the case is resolved.
77	The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: The responsibility for bullying on campus rests with family members and guardians, who must be held accountable. If a student who is bullied dies, as long as the perpetrator is over 12 years old, they must bear legal responsibility. Direct murder carries the death penalty. Guardians should be sentenced to at least 2-5 years in prison. If the crime occurs at school, the school should also assume some oversight responsibility. Any act that results in the victim being disabled requires the perpetrator's guardian to be sentenced to at least 1 year in prison and to compensate the victim.
78	The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention. Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 200,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 100 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years. This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years. Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be

	<p>prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
79	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 100,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 20 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years. This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 2,000 years and</p>

	<p>are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
80	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 50,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 10 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 1,000 years. This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 1,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic</p>

	<p>country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
81	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 100,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 50 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years. This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult</p>

	<p>to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
82	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 1000,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 20 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years. This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next 5,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 5,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
83	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying</p>

	<p>of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 10,000,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 50 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years. This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next 10,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 10,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
84	<p>The incompetence or injustice of judges often brings disaster to the victims. The United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish a convention on the following issues:</p> <p>Any group of criminals who first seek violence against innocent civilians, especially innocent women, using steel pipes and iron rods to strike the victim's vital areas such as the head, such attacks are likely to lead to future strokes, and the resulting injuries cannot be considered minor. Offenders should not be punished with just public security detention, but should be sentenced to at least one year or more in prison. When the victim encounters an attack by multiple criminals, the victim cannot measure the force of the</p>

	<p>counterattack before retaliating. The primary goal is to knock down and subdue the criminals, and the victim may retaliate against the criminals with any available weapon. Regardless of the degree of injury to the offender, the victim is not guilty. If the victim's resistance is instead defined as mutual combat or guilt, the judge should be sentenced for the errors in the sentence given to the victim. If the judge insists that their judgment is accurate and fair, they must act as victims themselves, with others acting as criminals, and experience an attack, so that the judge can experience the defense and reaction after being attacked. If either party is injured during this process, they are responsible for their own injuries. If the judge is wrong, they are no longer fit for the job and should be removed from their position. In any event, all personal and family property of all personnel in the judicial institution must be fully disclosed within three days. The judge and court compensated the victim for their losses.</p>
85	<p>Criminal organizations that defraud other countries of their wealth should not be used as a means of illicit profit by certain countries and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and address the above-mentioned problems:</p> <p>Since 1990, any criminal country that defrauded the public of another country on a large scale, as long as the fraud exceeded \$100 billion, shall be prohibited from serving as a permanent member of the United Nations or any regional organization for the next 5,000 years. Any political leader of a country proposing that the criminal state become a permanent member of the UN will automatically be seen as a bad, evil politician with no moral boundaries, a criminal politician, a thief, an extremely bad person.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 5,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
86	<p>Criminal organizations that defraud other countries of their wealth should not be used as a means of illicit profit by certain countries and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and address the above-mentioned problems:</p> <p>Since 1990, any criminal country that defrauded the public of another country on a large scale, as long as the fraud exceeded \$10 billion, shall be prohibited from serving as a permanent member of the United Nations or any regional organization for the next 2,000 years. Any political leader of a country proposing that the criminal state become a permanent member of the UN will automatically be seen as a bad, evil politician with no moral boundaries, a</p>

	<p>criminal politician, a thief.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
87	<p>Philosophical and methodological considerations for preventing serious judicial injustice</p> <p>History has proven that in any government, there are always corrupt elements. These criminals, who cause serious harm to innocent civilians, must be severely punished.</p> <p>Serious judicial injustice is the root cause of the occurrence of malignant cases, and must be corrected with strong measures to deter law enforcement officials from committing crimes. The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus on the following issues and establish conventions:</p> <p>If there is evidence that the suspect was not present at the scene in a case, completely contradicting the logic of the criminal investigation, the judge should not make a wrongful judgment. The reasons for the suspect's crime could not be established, but the judge disregarded the facts and maliciously convicted him, resulting in the victim's wrongful imprisonment. In such a case, the relevant judicial personnel are equally guilty, and their prison sentences should be the same as the victim's. If the victim is wrongly sentenced to death, once the error is corrected, the judge should be sentenced to at least 80 years in prison or the death penalty. In addition, the personal and family assets of the relevant judges should be confiscated to compensate the families of the victims or be turned over to the national treasury. The personal and family assets of all individuals in the relevant unit, as well as those of relatives within three generations, must be made public. All family members are permanently blacklisted from the credit system, and all family members and immediate relatives are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service system.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
88	<p>A country experiencing large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, human trafficking, and criminals exploiting legal loopholes, leading to a situation where individuals commit crimes for personal gain, benefiting their entire family or even the entire clan. They also bribe the protective umbrella of the criminal state. The criminal state utilizes internet water armies to spread rumors about the implementation or protection of the aforementioned crimes, whitewashing their crimes of murder. Anyone spreading rumors online will be held equally accountable with the most</p>

	<p>serious offender in a large-scale crime. They must be sentenced to the same term, and all assets of their families and three generations of relatives must be disclosed and confiscated, leaving only four years of basic living expenses. Second, law enforcement must impose travel restrictions on offenders. If the offender or his family members leave their place of residence in another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station. Third, offenders and their family members are prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed train. Fourth, the offender will be permanently blacklisted by the credit system, and all family members and direct relatives will be permanently barred from working in the civil service, military, police, security, or banking systems.</p>
89	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If a country experiences large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape and gang rape, live burial, trafficking in human beings, and massacres, with more than 100 victims, and if the criminal country uses online water armies to spread rumors to defend or protect the above crimes, whitewash their murderous acts, create a false sense of security in the area knowing the killings, laying the groundwork for future criminals to defraud and kill more people, then anyone who spreads rumors online is equally guilty as mass murderers. They must be sentenced to death, the entire property of their families and three generations of relatives must be disclosed, and all the property of the criminals' families must be confiscated, leaving only three years' worth of basic living expenses. Second, law enforcement must impose travel restrictions on offenders. If the offender or his family members leave their place of residence in another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station. Third, offenders and their family members are prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed train. Fourth, the offender will be permanently blacklisted by the credit system, and all family members and direct relatives will be permanently barred from working in the civil service, military, police, security, or banking systems.</p>
90	<p>For intermediary companies or intermediaries who, in the name of job - offering, deceive victims into going to Myanmar or going to Myanmar via a third country or countries where telecommunication fraud is rampant, and finally result in the victims being kidnapped, forced to conduct telecommunication fraud, tortured, raped, gang - raped, used as sex slaves,</p>

	<p>having their organs harvested while alive, buried alive or massacred, as long as there is one victim, the intermediaries shall be publicly tried and sentenced to death immediately, and all assets of the intermediary companies shall be confiscated, and all personal and family properties of the criminals shall be confiscated. Any property transferred to any third party shall be confiscated. Any criminal suspected of the above - mentioned crimes shall not be allowed to wear masks or cover their faces at any time. Lawyers are prohibited from defending the above - mentioned criminals. Such criminals are glib - tongued and good at luring kind - hearted people into trouble, and only the criminals themselves are allowed to defend themselves in court. Any act of a lawyer providing help for reducing or evading their crimes is considered as knowing the law but breaking it, and the lawyer must be subject to double criminal penalties. All criminals who are not executed will be exiled to remote and cold areas permanently.</p> <p>Criminals and their three - generation relatives will be blacklisted for life. Their properties must be made publicly available on a permanent basis. Offenders must be subject to travel restrictions, report to the police station when leaving their place of residence, and are prohibited from taking planes or high - speed trains. All family members and their three - generation relatives are permanently barred from entering the civil service system and from engaging in relevant work in the financial, judicial, security, and military fields.</p>
91	<p>Any country where large-scale crimes listed in this table occur within its territory shall have its voting rights in any international organization, including the United Nations, revoked for 1,000 -10,000 years.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
92	<p>In criminal countries where large-scale crimes occur as mentioned above, the legal marriage age and childbearing age of all criminals and their immediate relatives must be at least 30 years old. Otherwise, they are prohibited from receiving any medical or old-age insurance, including those provided by the government and private companies.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
93	<p>For offenders involved in large-scale criminal offences as described in this article, any mental illness cannot constitute a reason to protect the offender from committing crimes. Anyone who attempts to reduce or evade criminal punishment on the grounds of mental illness will be given double criminal punishment and all personal and family property will be confiscated.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
94	<p>In dealing with the punishment for large-scale crimes, for criminals who order</p>

	<p>or carry out torture on victims, the victims or victims of such cases shall impose double the time of torture punishment for the criminal and family members who benefit from the criminal's crime, so as to warn criminals who are preparing to commit fraud and kidnapping and carry out torture in the future. All criminals will lose all their personal and family assets. All offenders will be deprived of the right of residence in their place of origin and be exiled to cold and remote areas.</p> <p>For any offender who kills more than 10 victims, all family members of the offender will be killed, and all personal and family property of all offenders will be confiscated. For every criminal who kills 30 innocent victims, after a public trial, three generations of the criminal's family members will be killed, and all personal and family property of all criminals will be confiscated. Executing a small number of vicious criminals in exchange for regional social tranquility and peace. All offenders must be severely punished by flogging six times within half a year, with five lashes on the buttocks and legs of the offender each time. The crimes of all other offenders shall be determined by the victims. All offenders will be deprived of the right of residence in their place of origin and be exiled to cold and remote areas. The actions of all descendants of criminals will be monitored within 1,000 years. All finances and family property must be made public, and they are prohibited from taking high-speed trains and airplanes. All those who advocate leniency for criminals must experience the torture implemented by criminals for six months or be punished as victims. If the criminal law formulated is too lenient, resulting in an increase in such crimes, victims or their families can demand the confiscation of all personal and family property of the lawmaker and be sentenced to corresponding prison terms according to the years and degree of victimization. There will be no bail for any reason.</p> <p>Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, the power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
95	<p>Allowing organ transplantation is one of the main reasons for the disappearance of children, students, and adults, one of the frequent occurrences of illegal abduction, and one of the reasons for the illegal removal of human organs from wounded or sacrificed soldiers.</p> <p>Life is about quality and health, not necessarily length. Prevention leads to health, as does the choice of appropriate treatment methods in the early stages of illness. The vast majority of organ transplants can be avoided. The United Nations must establish a global convention to prohibit organ transplants and any harvesting of human organs. Any major offender involved in the live removal of human organs must be sentenced to death, and all personal and family property must be confiscated. All violators and all personnel from the involved institutions must disclose all personal and family assets within one week. All violators will be included in a credit blacklist, banned from taking high-speed trains and planes for the next 100 years, and</p>

	<p>required to report to the police before leaving any city. For the next 3,000 years, all direct relatives of the offenders are prohibited from working in government institutions, financial institutions, military, or security agencies. Those currently employed in these institutions must resign within two weeks. Modern medicine is heading in the wrong direction by implementing human organ transplants. This has led to large-scale kidnapping, illegal imprisonment, telecommunications fraud, and gang rape in Southeast Asian countries, including Myanmar. Once the value of the victims has been almost completely extracted, harvesting their organs becomes the final method by which criminals obtain huge profits. Most victims whose organs are harvested are thrown into the sea or buried alive. Banning human organ transplants would help in seeking medical methods that do not involve organ transplants to prevent and treat related diseases, and it would also be more conducive to the purification of global moral and ethical standards.</p> <p>The person in charge and legal representative of medical institutions engaged in the illegal harvesting of live organs, as well as the actual controller, major shareholder and second largest shareholder of such institutions, shall all be sentenced to death within three months after a public trial. There shall be no probation or bail for any reason.</p> <p>Anyone who knows about the above-mentioned criminal acts but fails to report them to the judicial institutions in a timely manner shall be sentenced to two years' imprisonment. There will be no probation or bail.</p>
96	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>When large - scale crimes occur in Myanmar, the International Court of Justice in The Hague has not, as an international judicial institution, severely cracked down on Myanmar's long - existing civil war, large - scale telecom fraud, torture, rape and gang - rape, homicide, human trafficking, or restrained Myanmar's ugly politicians. The Hague Court has done nothing. If this court had existed in ancient Chinese dynasties, all inactive judges would have been executed. In the international community, where empathy has regressed for 2,000 years, the Hague Court still exists, which is very bad. The criminal liability of the Hague Tribunal must be investigated and the court must be abolished as soon as possible.</p>
97	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100</p>

	<p>years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Internationally, within the next 10,000 years, nationals or descendants of war criminal countries or criminal countries such as Japan, Myanmar, Indonesia, Vietnam, and India that have committed large-scale crimes must be prohibited from serving in any international judicial institutions.</p>
98	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>In any country where large-scale crimes involved in this table occur, the property of all persons in that country must be fully disclosed within one month. It should start with all government officials, employees, military personnel, and criminals in that country. The property of all individuals, families, and their six generations of relatives must be disclosed.</p> <p>Anyone who leaves or emigrates from the criminal country within three years before the entry into force of this consensus must fully disclose his or her personal and family property as of the date of departure and at present. Otherwise, it is considered illegal, and any country can freeze all their assets.</p>
99	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The strange societies of various countries around the world today: Female middle - school students in a country were raped by refugees in a refugee settlement. After being brainwashed by the social system, instead of</p>

	<p>demanding severe punishment for the criminal refugees, the reason these middle school girls remain silent about being sexually assaulted by refugees is astonishingly that they don't want to ruin the reputation of the refugees. Even more strangely, judicial institutions do not severely punish criminals either.</p> <p>In any country where such incidents occur, if the government of that country does not correct its mistakes and severely punish criminals within one month, it will be regarded as that the president, prime minister, president of the Senate, president of the House of Representatives, the highest chief procurator of the national procuratorate of that country, and the director of the national police bureau of that country have lost their governing ability and enthusiasm and have automatically resigned because they are unable to protect vulnerable groups. The ruling party or coalition of ruling parties in that country is prohibited from nominating any candidates to participate in the election in the next five presidential or prime ministerial election cycles. Once the United Nations votes to adopt this international consensus and forms a United Nations convention or issues a United Nations declaration, all countries must amend their various constitutions within one month.</p>
100	<p>Since 2000, any country that has connived at crime within its territory and has obtained more than \$10 billion in wealth from other countries through large-scale telecommunications fraud within any three years (calculated according to the value of the U.S. dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is regarded as a country where all the people commit crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in this country. As long as this evil country cannot make full reparation to the victim countries and victims or their relatives and return the looted wealth, then in the next 1,000 years, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be regarded as civilians. The label given to this country by the international community is: This country is a country without religious beliefs, a country without morality, a country without ethics, a country without conscience, a country with correct laws, and this country is a country controlled by cult beliefs. This country is a country where people believe in cults. For the next three thousand years, this country is forbidden to hold any international religious or moral and ethical conferences. The ruling party of this country is prohibited from being called the Democratic Party or the Republican Party or the Progressive Party or the Socialist Party or a party with the above names.</p>
101	<p>Since 2000, any country that has connived at crime within its territory and has obtained more than \$20 billion in wealth from other countries through large-scale telecommunications fraud within any three years (calculated according to the value of the U.S. dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is regarded as a country where all the people commit crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in this country. As long as this evil country cannot make full reparation to the victim countries and victims or their relatives and return the looted wealth, then in the next 3,000 years, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be regarded as civilians. The label given to this</p>

	<p>country by the international community is: This country is a country without religious beliefs, a country without morality, a country without ethics, a country without conscience, a country with correct laws, and this country is a country controlled by cult beliefs. This country is a country where people believe in cults. For the next three thousand years, this country is forbidden to hold any international religious or moral and ethical conferences. The ruling party of this country is prohibited from being called the Democratic Party or the Republican Party or the Progressive Party or the Socialist Party or a party with the above names.</p>
102	<p>Since 2000, any country that has allowed crime within its territory and obtained more than \$10 billion in wealth from other countries through large-scale telecommunications fraud in any three years (calculated according to the value of the U.S. dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is regarded as a country where the whole people commit crimes. If religious groups and organizations in this country do not take to the streets to demonstrate or protest against the moral decline and lack of faith of the people, then the religious organizations in this country cannot be regarded as religious organizations, but only as organizations for eating. Anyone or any institution can ridicule their false religious beliefs. All religious statues or utensils ever used by this religious organization are regarded as ordinary objects and can be destroyed by anyone.</p>
103	<p>Since 2000, any country that has allowed crime within its territory and obtained more than \$10 billion in wealth from other countries through large-scale telecommunications fraud in any three years (based on the value of the U.S. dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is regarded as a country where all the people commit crimes. If religious groups and organizations in this country do not take to the streets to demonstrate or protest against the moral decline and lack of faith of the people, but instead support criminal organizations or the umbrellas of criminal organizations in various ways, then the religious organizations in this country cannot be regarded as religious organizations but only as accomplices of cult organizations and criminal organizations. Anyone or any institution can combat their false religious beliefs. All religious statues or utensils ever used by this religious organization are regarded as cult objects and can be destroyed by anyone. The leaders of this religious organization are suspected of serious crimes. The leaders of religious organizations and all offenders shall be severely punished in accordance with the offences of large-scale crimes involved in this table. Any person who supports the activities of criminal organizations that support live organ harvesting, live slaughtering or live burial, or the activities of criminal organizations that support gang rape, the leaders of religious groups and main criminals shall be sentenced to death. The rest shall be sentenced and exiled to remote and cold areas and permanently prohibited from returning to their places of origin. At the same time, this country is regarded as a country without religious beliefs, but as a country that believes in cults.</p>

	<p>This country has lost morality, conscience and ethics. Its immigrants are likely to be a risk factor for future conflicts and wars. The number of immigrants from this criminal country to other countries must be strictly limited. It is strictly forbidden for the number of immigrants in any country to exceed 0.1% of the number of deaths in the Nanjing Massacre in China committed by the Japanese invaders.</p>
104	<p>Since 2000, any country that has allowed crime within its territory and obtained more than \$20 billion in wealth from other countries through large-scale telecommunications fraud in any three years (based on the value of the U.S. dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is regarded as a country where all the people commit crimes. If religious groups and organizations in this country do not take to the streets to demonstrate or protest against the moral decline and lack of faith of the people, but instead support criminal organizations or the umbrellas of criminal organizations in various ways, then the religious organizations in this country cannot be regarded as religious organizations but only as accomplices of cult organizations and criminal organizations. Anyone or any institution can combat their false religious beliefs. All religious statues or utensils ever used by this religious organization are regarded as cult objects and can be destroyed by anyone. The leaders of this religious organization are suspected of serious crimes. The leaders of religious organizations and all offenders shall be severely punished in accordance with the offences of large-scale crimes involved in this table. Any person who supports the activities of criminal organizations that support live organ harvesting, live slaughtering or live burial, or the activities of criminal organizations that support gang rape, the leaders of religious groups and main criminals shall be sentenced to death. The rest shall be sentenced and exiled to remote and cold areas and permanently prohibited from returning to their places of origin. At the same time, this country is regarded as a country without religious beliefs, but as a country that believes in cults.</p> <p>This country has lost morality, conscience and ethics. Its immigrants are likely to be a risk factor for future conflicts and wars. The number of immigrants from this criminal country to other countries must be strictly limited. It is strictly forbidden for the number of immigrants in any country to exceed 0.02% of the number of deaths in the Nanjing Massacre in China committed by the Japanese invaders. If any country finds that the number of immigrants from the criminal country in that country exceeds the specified number, it may expel immigrants from the criminal country within three months by any means.</p>
105	<p>For companies providing virtual phone services without implementing real-name authentication and facilitating fraudsters, if there is a death of a victim, the person in charge shall be sentenced to death and must be executed within three months without any delay for any reason. As long as there is property loss for the victim, all personal and family property of the person in charge shall be confiscated, and only living expenses for five years at the local</p>

	<p>minimum living security standard may be left to his family. If the gains obtained by the person in charge of providing services to fraudsters are transferred to his relatives, the personal and family property of his relatives shall be confiscated. Companies that illegally provide telecommunications services to criminals shall be fined according to the amount of money defrauded. If the victim is not dead but is raped, gang-raped, tortured, subjected to live organ harvesting, or disabled, the person shall be sentenced to eight years in prison, and all personal and family property shall be confiscated. Only living expenses for five years at the local minimum living security standard can be left to his family. If there are multiple victims in the above situations, the prison term shall be calculated in an accumulative way, and there shall be no probation or bail. If the victim is kidnapped, the prison term of the person in charge is the same as that of the kidnapped victim. If there are multiple kidnappings, the prison term shall be calculated in an accumulative way, and there shall be no probation or bail.</p> <p>Telecom company salespersons who handle virtual phone services for telecom fraudsters without implementing real-name authentication or intentionally not conducting real-name verification. As long as there is death of a victim, the salesperson must be sentenced to death and must be executed within three months without any delay for any reason. All personal and family property shall be confiscated, and only living expenses for five years at the local minimum living security standard can be left to his family. If the victim is not dead but is raped or gang-raped, tortured, subjected to live organ harvesting, or disabled, the person shall be sentenced to ten years in prison, all personal and family property shall be confiscated, and only living expenses for five years at the local minimum living security standard can be left to his family. If there are multiple victims in the above situations, the prison term shall be calculated cumulatively, and there shall be no probation or bail. If the victim is kidnapped, the prison term of the salesperson is the same as that of the kidnapped victim. If there are multiple kidnappings, the prison term shall be calculated in an accumulative way, and there shall be no probation or bail. All losses of the victim shall be compensated by the person in charge and the handler in a ratio of 2:8. The personal and family property of all six generations of relatives of all offenders must be fully disclosed within one week after the police and judicial institutions take compulsory action.</p>
106	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and</p>

	<p>develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>As long as the criminal country or war criminal country that has committed large-scale crimes has not fully and adequately compensated the victims and the victimized countries for all losses and severely punished all criminals, any country, company, organization or individual is prohibited from providing any form of loan, borrowing, technology transfer or technology transfer service to the criminal country or war criminal country involved in this article. Otherwise, any country may freeze the assets of countries, companies, organizations or individuals that violate this rule.</p>
107	<p>For those involved in the trading of newborns in medical institutions, as long as the baby is harmed, all criminals must be sentenced to death, and all personal and family property of offenders shall be confiscated. Only living expenses for five years at the local minimum living security standard can be left to their families. Personal and family assets of the three generations of relatives of offenders must be permanently disclosed. Criminals are prohibited from living in their places of origin and are exiled to remote and cold areas. Any institution or individual who prevents the victim from viewing the medical historical records will be immediately dismissed from office. For those who hold positions, they will all be demoted to the most ordinary staff members and their medical insurance will be cancelled for three years. If it is finally confirmed that the records are related to the criminal acts of the criminals, all those who prevent the victim from viewing the historical records will be sentenced to two years' imprisonment. If the criminals continuously prevent the victim from viewing the historical records for various reasons, resulting in a continuous extension of time, his or her sentence will be calculated on the basis of that time. If it is ten years, their prison term will be ten years. There will be no probation or bail, and their medical practice qualifications will be revoked. The descendants of all offenders are prohibited from working in government institutions and medical institutions for 1000 years. Those who fabricate or modify medical records will be punished in the same way as above.</p> <p>If the baby is not harmed and is recovered within three days, all offenders must be sentenced to three years in prison. Personal and family assets of the three generations of relatives of offenders must be permanently disclosed. Criminals or their descendants are prohibited from engaging in medical work, government work, or civil service work for three hundred years.</p>
108	<p>The victim country may use any weapon to strike telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres in the other country and carry out any decapitation or comprehensive strike, including the use of bombers, attack aircraft, missiles, thermobaric bombs or fuel-air explosives. Any innocent person must stay three kilometers away from the telecommunications fraud park. The cost of the attack is borne by the criminal country.</p>
109	<p>The evil countries involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this</p>

	<p>article must be disintegrated and reorganized as soon as possible so that there can be sustainable peace in the world. The assets of all politicians suspected of crimes and the personal and family property of their main supporters will be completely confiscated and distributed equally to innocent citizens who support reorganization and were originally in the country.</p>
110	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Immigration to other countries is a latent means and tool for evil countries without conscience and empathy or countries with criminal records to commit crimes, invade, plunder wealth and annex the territory of other countries. It is an important factor leading to an increase in crime rates. It is the basis for evil countries to carry out long-term evil plans under the slogan of freedom and human rights. Farmers in China's three northeastern provinces were once deeply harmed and plundered by Japanese immigrants.</p> <p>The number of immigrants from the evil countries involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this article in any other country is prohibited from exceeding 0.01% of the number of deaths in Nanjing during the Nanjing Massacre carried out by the Japanese invaders. Those who have immigrated must be repatriated to the criminal country.</p>
111	<p>Surgical doctors, persons in charge, legal representatives, actual controllers, major shareholders and second largest shareholders of medical institutions engaged in human organ transplantation from illegal sources, as well as the recipients of organs from illegal sources, shall all be sentenced to 10 years' imprisonment after a public trial. There shall be no probation or bail for any reason, and all personal and family property shall be confiscated. Anyone who knows about the above crimes but fails to report them to the judicial institutions in a timely manner shall be sentenced to two years' imprisonment. There will be no probation or bail. Those who report the criminal situation to the judicial institutions in a timely manner shall be rewarded with 20% of the confiscated property of the criminals and must be redeemed within half a year. All offenders will have their medical qualifications revoked. All offenders and their descendants are prohibited from working in any government institution or medical institution for the next 1000 years.</p>
112	<p>A wicked country that dares to carry out large-scale crimes without scruple, such as long-term brutal kidnappings, brutal torture, raping and gang-raping</p>

	<p>women, turning girls into sex slaves, live-harvesting human organs, and massacring kidnapped innocent people, must have its country name renamed. A country that does not commit large-scale crimes still has a country name with the thinking of normal people. Otherwise, it is a crime against humanity. Any politician, lawyer or citizen who opposes this proposal should consider what qualifications you have to raise objections. Why not legislate from the perspective of victims? If you do not legislate from the perspective of victims and quickly control crimes, it shows that you have lost the empathy that legislators must have.</p> <p>Therefore, you and all your family members must first experience three years of torture in Myanmar, being raped and gang-raped, being pregnant and giving birth after being gang-raped, being a sex slave, being forced to dig coal in a coal mine with primitive tools, having human organs harvested alive, or the pain of having family members killed. If you are still alive and not incapacitated by torture, then come to discuss legislation on this issue. Otherwise, you are a Don Quixote-like figure, a Wang Ming and Bo Gu in China, a Ma Hu and You Niao (马户, 又鸟) like figure, a masked parrot who has never experienced the torture of multiple social hardships from middle school to university and does not know the ordinary hardships and pains.</p> <p>If you deliberately demand legislation according to your will, in the future, all losses and compensation for victims will first be borne by you and all your family members and descendants with unlimited liability. If one victim dies, you must be executed after a public trial. If ten victims die, you and your children, your wife, and your parents must be executed after a public trial. If there are not enough members of your family, your immediate relatives must be executed. All personal and family property will be confiscated and compensated to the victims. If you are a corrupt official who comes to power with the support of your Democratic Party, your evil political party must also bear full compensation liability. All members must compensate the victims with their personal and family property. When the amount of compensation is insufficient, your country must compensate the victims.</p> <p>If you do not have the ability to control crime, or empathy, and are even more unwilling to let you and your family members experience the pain of being victimized, but you still want to interfere in legislation, you are very harmful to society and should be sent to prison, deprived of all your political rights, and reflect on your own stupidity and ignorance.</p>
113	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must</p>

	<p>change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If the international community and the United Nations do not take restrictive measures against evil countries that are fond of committing fraud and establish international conventions or United Nations conventions, mankind will inevitably face large-scale wars and nuclear wars in the future.</p> <p>Since 1950, if telecommunications fraudsters from any country have defrauded other countries with an average annual total of \$5 billion in any three consecutive years, it shall be regarded as carrying out the Nanjing Massacre. The total number of immigrants and descendants of this criminal country in any other country in the next 5,000 years shall be prohibited from exceeding 0.01% of the number of Chinese killed in the Nanjing Massacre committed by the Japanese invaders. If the average annual total amount of fraud reaches \$6 billion in any three consecutive years, the total number of immigrants and descendants of this criminal country in any country shall be prohibited from exceeding 0.005% of the total number of Chinese killed in the Nanjing Massacre. The legal age for marriage and childbearing of the citizens of this evil country must be raised to 30 years old before they are allowed to have children legally. Otherwise, any country or organization shall be prohibited from providing medical insurance, commercial insurance, and old-age insurance to citizens of that country and their descendants.</p> <p>If the total population of this evil country exceeds 100 million, the marriage and childbearing age of its citizens, overseas immigrants or overseas descendants must be raised to 36 years. Otherwise, any country or organization will be prohibited from providing medical insurance, commercial insurance and old-age insurance to citizens of that country, their overseas descendants or their immigrants. For countries where the number of immigrants exceeds the above-specified limit, these immigrants shall be sent back to the country of the fraudster. Otherwise, any medical insurance and old-age insurance shall be prohibited from being provided.</p>
114	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since the year 2000, for any act of mixing chemically extracted paraffin oil or white oil into edible vegetable oil, regardless of whether the paraffin oil or white oil meets edible standards or not, as long as the scale of sales exceeds 50 tons, the legal representatives, major shareholders, the principal offenders</p>

	<p>and the main actual operators of the company shall be put to death without exception, and all their personal and family properties shall be confiscated. The personal and family assets of the nine generations of relatives of all offenders must be fully disclosed within two weeks and remain publicly disclosed permanently. For other offenders, they shall all be sentenced to 10 years' imprisonment, their eligibility to live in their place of origin shall be revoked, and they shall be permanently exiled to the coldest regions. The credit records of all offenders and their descendants shall be blacklisted. For 500 years, their descendants are prohibited from high-speed trains, bullet trains, cruise ships and airplanes, from working in any government institution, and from working in professions related to finance, law, security, chemistry, medicine, and the military. All offenders are only allowed to defend themselves, and any lawyer is prohibited from defending them. Any informant will receive 20% of the offender's property. If multiple persons file the same report at the same time, they shall jointly enjoy the rewards obtained from the report, and the transfer shall be dealt with directly by the court that tries the offender.</p>
115	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that, although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for more than 100 years, the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any evil official in any country who, by means of disguised forms, imposes criminal penalties on or imprisons the leaders or members of drug trafficking groups or drug traffickers who have fought hard against drug trafficking on the charge of violating human rights in the fight against drug trafficking, regardless of whether they have served as presidents or prime ministers in the past, must be sentenced to death. Their personal and all family property of three generations shall be confiscated, and all family members of such evil officials must be exiled to remote and cold areas. Any lawyer is prohibited from defending them. The personal and family property of the nine generations of the criminal's family members shall be fully disclosed and permanently disclosed. They are prohibited from engaging in any political activities and from working in any civil servant field within 5,000 years. They are also prohibited from working in any government agency, for example, even working as cleaners, security guards, cafeteria staff or maintenance workers in government agencies is absolutely prohibited. Those who violate these regulations shall be sentenced to more than ten years' imprisonment. Anyone who preserves property for such criminals shall also</p>

	be regarded as committing a crime and all their personal and family property shall be confiscated.
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Myanmar is not only a failure of state - building and systems, but also a haven for global crimes and must be restructured.

34.16. The necessity of restructuring the chaotic world and the obligations, responsibilities, opportunities, and rewards of Europe and America

Myanmar is a legacy of British colonial rule. It is also a loose - knit country formed by Myanmar's politicians and military deceiving the original inhabitants of northern Myanmar, which originally belonged to China, through the Panglong Agreement. Once these deceiving Myanmar politicians and military tricked the original inhabitants of northern Myanmar into forming a new country, they showed their true colors. They did not allow the original inhabitants of northern Myanmar to withdraw from the Union of Myanmar even after the agreement expired. Peoples with different cultures, customs and beliefs, and people in northern Myanmar who were highly moral, influenced by traditional Chinese culture and not yet polluted by the outside world at that time, could not accommodate the Burmese people who had low moral standards and completely lacked integrity. This has led to a 70-year civil war in Myanmar, with countless deaths. During the anti - Chinese massacre in Myanmar in 1967, at least 400,000 ethnic Chinese were killed by the Burmese.

In the 21st century, Myanmar has the most telecommunications fraud parks in the world, and is the world's largest center for large - scale kidnappings, rape and gang - rape, torture, and live organ harvesting. On December 12, 2023, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime released the latest "2023 World Drug Report", which shows that in 2023, Myanmar has replaced Afghanistan as the world's largest opium - producing country. These drugs are transported to Japan and Australia, and smuggled to European and American countries via Bangkok, Singapore, Hong Kong, and New Delhi. Among them, Amsterdam in the Netherlands is the world's largest drug distribution market.

Politicians and plutocrats in the United States may collectively have a serious epidemic, instigating the government to issue decrees allowing Americans to consume cannabis products. Nowadays, young people using drugs can be seen everywhere on some streets in the United States. If the opium problem in Myanmar is not solved, more and more Americans will become like the people of Qing Dynasty China, turning from healthy people into disabled people. In the 19th century, American merchants also sent a large number of drugs to China, and later it was almost the largest drug - exporting country.

The United States is the most powerful country in the world. It should not lead countries and the United Nations to turn global governance into a crisis - ridden, anxious sea level with rough waves under typhoon force-12. Instead, it should lead countries to turn places where humans live into beautiful and peaceful gardens after governance. Britain colonized the world. During World War II, Britain was forced to give up its colonies, leaving many problems around the globe. Britain should bear part of the responsibility for the global chaos of the 20th and 21st centuries and the liability

for compensation. Some countries in the world that frequently have armed conflicts, countries with serious racial discrimination against indigenous peoples, and evil countries that massacred large numbers of innocent civilians and plunder all their wealth, must require the criminals and their associates to compensate all the losses of the victims and victimized countries. If indigenous peoples and victims demand it, these countries must be reorganized. In particular, the evil countries that had carried out massacres and refused to compensate the victims must be reorganized. The United States and peace - loving people around the world can reap the rewards from institutional change and progress. It can be seen from the discussion in this text that Marx's understanding of the human social system is too superficial. The simple and confrontational classification of social systems is one of the reasons for ideological confrontation between different countries. Since, according to Marx's classification, Israel under the capitalist system has a kibbutz society similar to communism and can exist, this may be one step closer to Marx's theory than China's current system. Since the United States has a close relationship with Israel, like a father - son relationship, and supports Israel whenever it encounters a crisis, then there is even less reason for the United States to confront China. Moreover, China once saved the United States like a weak chicken.

There is no absolute difference in social systems between China, the United States, and Europe. There is no need for the United States and Europe to regard China as a country with inconsistent ideologies. The Chinese are very friendly to foreign friends with good intentions and saved the fledgling United States at the beginning of its founding. Back then, the United States was blockaded by Britain and Spain and was on the verge of collapse. Some American merchants sailed the American merchant ship "Empress of China" across the Pacific Ocean, arriving at Guangzhou, a trading port in China, to conduct trade with local Chinese merchants. They returned to New York in May of the following year. It was the Chinese government that, despite Britain's warnings, established trade relations with the United States. Moreover, when American merchants had insufficient funds, some Chinese merchants even allowed American merchants to take the goods back to the United States first and pay when they returned to China the next time. If China had not traded with the United States, the United States would have perished after being defeated by Britain and Spain, and there would be no United States today.

Most of the time in the 20th and 21st centuries, the U.S. government has been controlled by a group of fools who only shout about war and create conflicts and have no idea how to govern the country and the world to make it a better place. The reason why American and European politicians do bad things without scruples is the failure of the system! This is a great failure of the system. This is a great failure of the social system. Just like in Western medicine, when encountering severe tonsil infections, patients' tonsils are removed. Especially for children with inflamed tonsils due to colds and fevers, they are also surgically removed. The philosophical views, values, and methodologies of many Western politicians today are as stupid and barbaric as the tonsillectomy in Western medical treatment guidelines or expert guidelines, almost completely mindless actions, leaving patients with unavoidable sequelae. If any

politician doesn't believe it, you may randomly select ten patients aged 5 - 60 with severe tonsil infections due to colds and fevers, and ask the academicians of what you consider the best hospitals or universities in the United States to diagnose. If the academicians think surgical removal is necessary, see if the author of this paper can control and relieve patients' symptoms without any surgical operation within 24 hours and make the patients recover quickly afterwards.

From another perspective, the systems of China and other countries are products of historical processes. There is no need for the world to form two opposing groups in the ideological field because of Marx's theory. It is inappropriate to regard any theory as dogmatism. Chairman Mao repeatedly emphasized not to dogmatize Marxism. Why do American politicians dogmatize Marx's theory of the social system? Is this wisdom or stupidity? Among the top 100 universities in the world, the majors of philosophy, politics, history, economics, and management in American universities rank first globally.

History repeats itself. China is the only country in the world with a written record of ancient history in chronological order. China has a ten - thousand - year - long written history. Why haven't American philosophers, historians, statesmen, economists, and management experts recognized that China's current social system and that of the United States are products of the same kind dynasty but from different eras? This has led to long - term tensions in China - U.S. relations. Some Western politicians or leaders have long - term myopia and color - blindness. In many communities in Israel, everyone works and enjoys the fruits of labor, and the distribution system implemented is similar to communist distribution, according to the need system, which is more radical than the regional systems in China. However, Western politicians do not attack Israel's system and ideology, but attack China's ideology. These ideological differences are fabricated by Western theories.

34.17. Disintegrate evil and rebuild civilization: The mission of safeguarding human conscience.

In the development of human society, peace and justice have always been the core values pursued by humanity. However, when there are certain countries dominated by an extremely evil social system and then carry out a series of heinous crimes such as large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, riots, inhumane violations of women and children, live organ harvesting, burying civilians alive, waging war and massacres, this is not only a disaster for the people of their own country but also a serious threat to global human society. It is of crucial necessity to disintegrate and reorganize such evil countries and to establish a new social system with empathy, conscience and civilization.

First of all, from the perspective of humanitarian disasters, the harm caused by these evil acts is immeasurable. Every kidnapped person experiences fear and despair. Every victim of torture endures double torture of body and soul. As vulnerable groups, the rape and gang-rape of women and children is a serious trampling of humanity's moral bottom line. The anti-human act of harvesting live organs completely treats people as tools and ignores the dignity of life. Burying civilians alive is the most brutal

deprivation of the right to life. War and massacres have destroyed countless families and caused lives to disappear. The pain and trauma caused by these acts devour the human conscience like an abyss and immerse the whole world in sorrow. If such evil countries are not disintegrated, this humanitarian disaster will be endless and more innocent lives will be dragged into the dark abyss.

Secondly, from the perspective of social order, large-scale telecommunications fraud undermines the principle of trust in economic exchanges and puts the social and economic system at risk of collapse. Riots disrupt the normal operation of society and make the original orderly living environment chaotic. A country full of these evil acts has completely deviated from the direction of civilization in its social system and has become a hotbed of crime and violence. This chaotic social order will spread like a virus, affecting surrounding countries and regions and undermining the stability and harmony of the international community.

Moreover, from the dimension of international peace and development, wars waged by such evil countries have seriously damaged the international order, consumed a large amount of resources and hindered the global development process. Under the impact of their evil acts, international relations have become tense and fragile, trust between countries has been destroyed, and cooperation is difficult to carry out. In the long run, the whole world will fall into a vicious cycle of unrest. Therefore, disintegrating these evil countries is the key to preventing disasters from continuing to spread. And establishing a new social system is the fundamental way to reshape hope. The new social system should be based on empathy, so that people can understand and feel the pain of others and thus avoid harmful acts; be guided by conscience so that people follow moral guidelines in their actions; take civilization as the goal and build a social environment that respects life, is fair and just, and is harmonious and orderly. Only in this way can we fundamentally eliminate the root causes of these evil acts, bring human society back to the right track of peace and development, safeguard the dignity and value of human civilization, and create a beautiful world without fear and violence for future generations. Some countries that have experienced or are currently experiencing anti human disasters must be disintegrated and reorganized, such as Japan, India, Myanmar, Vietnam, Indonesia, the Philippines, etc.

In the development process of human society, the number of college graduates today has increased significantly since 1950. However, since 2000, there has been a serious regression in global ethics. Conflicts and wars continue, and people are in a predicament. This highlights that humanity urgently needs to at least choose a social system with empathy and establish a negative feedback mechanism in such a society to make timely adjustments when there are bad signs. It can effectively prevent the emergence of evil forces and promptly crack down on criminal acts. Only in this way can wars be reduced and the world return to peace and stability and get out of the current chaotic predicament. Marx identified six social systems, but his classification is too simple. Social systems vary due to differences in leadership concepts, selection

methods, represented interests, moral levels, empathy, philosophies, and political/economic theories. In addition, Marx's naming of the socialist social system brought great difficulties and differences in understanding and cognition to later practitioners, and provided opportunities for those who create ideological confrontations between the East and the West. Therefore, considering the complexity and diversity of human society from philosophical, methodological and historical perspectives and reclassifying human social systems will help the public identify the advantages and disadvantages of social systems and help eliminate this ideological opposition in the hearts of people around the world. At the same time, according to different characteristics, moral levels and whether they are pirate-plundering countries, the public can quickly identify the systems of these countries and choose, avoid, change or eliminate the social systems of some countries. Finally, this article reclassifies human social systems like an encyclopaedia from historical and philosophical perspectives.

This paper also further expands Marx's classification theories and methods of human social systems from the perspective of historical materialism, hoping to promote all villages, groups, ethnic groups, regions, and countries to move towards better social systems. The public of all countries should work together to promote the reform and improvement of the social system and create a better tomorrow for the future of humanity. There is only a desolate and oxygen-deficient Mars where one cannot survive. Even if you can be transported to Mars by a spaceship, you can't avoid reality.

34.18. The rise and fall of a country's economy and the politicians and political parties that build its social system

The rise and fall of a country's economy is closely related to its social system. Whether a country's economy can develop sustainably depends on its social system and related support systems. However, the social system and auxiliary systems of the country are determined by political parties, politicians, their supporters and opponents. The economic development of a region depends on national and regional systems. The development of a tourism behavioral economy depends not only on resource attributes but also on the creativity brought by the country's economic system and regional system. The improvement of the living conditions of the rural poor and economic development depend to a large extent on the systems and economic policies formulated by politicians, political parties and government. In the fluctuations of the market, this is ultimately manifested as rural behavioral economy and agricultural behavioral economy. **The economies of the United States, Europe, and almost all countries in the world, in addition to the characteristics of the market economy or market-oriented economy, are also prominently manifested as politician behavioral economy, political - party behavior economy, political behavioral economy, and government behavior economy.** Internationally, relevant new economic disciplines should be established to explore relevant issues, especially politician behavioral economics, political -party behavioral economics, political behavioral economics, and government behavioral economics. To address rural poverty and

sustainable development, more efforts are needed to establish and study rural behavioral economics and agricultural behavioral economics.

34.19. The cultural, moral and civilized foundation for China to construct the current system. The unique culture shapes the Chinese people's simplicity, kindness, and public spirit - a set of images or videos.

34.19-1. A benevolent and disciplined military is the guarantee of the social system of China

"Three Big Disciplines and Eight Points of Attention" is a fixed command in the form of a military song, and it has become a unified discipline for the entire army. This highlights that China is not a country that favours aggression against other nations.

The military song "Three Big Disciplines and Eight Points of Attention":

Revolutionary soldiers must always remember, the three major disciplines and the eight points for attention.

First, all actions must follow orders, only with unified steps can we achieve victory.

Second, do not take a needle or thread from the masses, the people support and like us.

Third, all confiscated items must be turned over to the public, working hard to lighten the burden on the people.

We must adhere to the three major disciplines and never forget the eight points for attention.

First, speak with a good attitude, do not be arrogant and respect the masses.

Second, trade at fair prices, no bullying in buying or selling.

Third, return borrowed items when done using them, do not lose them.

Fourth, if something is damaged, compensate in full without any deductions.

Fifth, no hitting or cursing, eliminate warlord behavior decisively.

Sixth, protect the crops of the people, pay attention to them everywhere during marches and battles.

Seventh, no harassing women, eliminate thuggish behavior.

Eighth, no mistreating prisoners of war, no hitting, cursing, or searching their pockets.

Everyone must conscientiously follow the rules, and be vigilant against violations.

Remember every aspect of revolutionary discipline, and love people everywhere as soldiers of the people.

Forever advance in defending the motherland, welcomed and supported by the people nationwide.

China has a unique and benevolent and highly disciplined military in the world, which is one of the foundations for China to realize the improved and optimized version 4.0 of the equal-field system.

India has an army steeped in evil ideology. India has occupied large areas of Chinese territory. It has a penchant for annexing the territories of other countries and using police and military forces founded on cult - like ideologies to suppress the people of the annexed ethnic groups.

Although Vietnam is nominally ruled by the Communist Party, it is actually an

extremely evil political party and country. China has provided free aid to Vietnam for at least 26 years, and the amount of free aid now amounts to at least \$2 trillion. After Vietnam's reunification, it began to slaughter overseas Chinese or descendants of China, killing 1.5 million people and forcing every displaced person to pay 12 taels of gold, otherwise they would be killed or thrown into concentration camps.

34.19-2. The unique culture shapes the Chinese people's simplicity, kindness, and public spirit - a set of images or videos.

China has a very high and broad - based foundation of morality, conscience, and empathy for implementing the improved or optimized version 4.0 of the Equal Field System. This can be reflected in many aspects, whether it is from the founding chairman, the premier, and the team they led, or from ordinary people. The following screenshots can reveal many issues. Western cultures and civilizations are fabricated by Western missionaries by plagiarizing, fictionalizing, and forging Chinese culture and technology in batches. Figures such as the Queen of Egypt, Alexander the Great, Shakespeare, Picasso, Aristotle, Socrates, Plato, Euclid, Archimedes, etc. are fictional characters created by accumulating Chinese ideas, stories, and technologies. Moreover, ancient Egyptian civilization, ancient Greek civilization, ancient Roman civilization, ancient Indian civilization and Mesopotamian civilization were all forged by the West. China has a history of at least 10,000 years. China was the first to reach the American continent, and Native Americans are descendants of the Chinese. A large number of unearthed cultural relics can verify this. Western missionaries like to produce fake cultural relics. People with backgrounds in chemistry, materials science, pharmacy, and medicine can tell at a glance that cultural relics unearthed in the West are basically worth only a few hundred to a thousand RMB at most. It will take a long time for Western societies to implement China's system. China has no intention at all regarding what social system the West is adopting.

No country in the world has as many touching stories of mutual assistance and selfless dedication as China, in any era. This is the cultural heritage, this is civilization, this is the religion embedded in the heart. Many Westerners believe that going to church to pray or participate in religious festivals is a religious belief, but no country's kindness reaches the level of the Chinese people, religious belief should not be very narrow formalism of going to church to pray, but kindness and empathy engraved in the heart, and disdain and struggle against evil forces. Several mainstream religions in the West were built after the 16th century and can be mathematically proven.

Fig. 232. In 1942, the leader of China and creator of the new social system, Mao Zedong, gave lectures in front of the cave where he lived, wearing clothes with many patches.2021-03-13. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwSVUNd/i@c.aajpq:/10/08>

The leader of China and creator of the new social system, Mao Zedong:

A great philosopher, a great thinker, a great logician,
a great military strategist, a great strategist,
an outstanding calligrapher, and an outstanding poet.

A Chinese leader and pioneer of the new social system who often wears patched

clothes and pants.

The world owes him a Nobel Prize in Literature, a Nobel Prize in Physics and a Nobel Peace Prize, because Mao Zedong's ideology has prevented war in China for the past few decades.

The bold and unrestrained poetry of Su Dongpo, a literary giant in Chinese history during the Song Dynasty, has been unmatched for nearly a thousand years. In modern times, only Mao Zedong's the poem "Spring in the Qin Garden" "Snow" can compare in its boldness. Outstanding poetry like this comes once in a millennium.

Fig. 233. In his later years, Chairman Mao's body grew larger, causing his cotton undershirts to shrink easily. Eventually, these clothes became too small for him to wear.

The hope for the future of the world lies in inheriting Chinese culture. Wuhan 202001-20240427-0930-1005-1020

However, since the Chairman did not want to discard them, the staff would sew two pieces together to make one, or three pieces together to make two, then add extra material to make them larger so that Chairman Mao could continue to wear them. 2024-02-26. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwSquLd/06/04Yzg:/l@p.qr>

Fig. 234. Among the many relics of the great Chinese leader Mao Zedong, there is a pajama that has been worn for over 20 years and has been patched with 73 patches. [A pajama with 73 patches. Do you know whose it is?2021-06-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwSxJ8y/kPx:/08/26h@O.xF>]

In the past 200 years of world history, which leader's philosophy, logic, literature, and strategic level can surpass Chairman Mao Zedong?

Fig. 234-1. When officials rise to high office, they often forget about the suffering of ordinary people.

Chairman Mao Zedong's head nurse, Wu Xujun, recalled: "In the late 1960s, Chairman Mao presided over a national conference of regional secretaries. The meeting was almost over, but it was not time for dinner yet. Wang Dongxing asked Chairman Mao for permission: 'Should we get something for everyone to eat?' The Chairman said: 'Sure, but don't overdo it. Just give each person a small bowl of noodles.' I found it strange at the time. After the meeting, **I saw the Chairman looking quite pleased. I asked him: 'Chairman, today's attendees are all senior leaders. Why did you only give them a small bowl of noodles? Isn't that stingy?' The Chairman smiled and said: 'Precisely because they are all senior leaders, who dares to let them go hungry on a regular day? By not allowing them to eat their fill here, I want them to remember the taste of hunger. When officials rise to high positions, they often forget about those who suffer.** That's why, even though the old man has been gone for over forty years, the people still love him so much."

[A person's official position can easily forget those who suffer at the bottom# The sentiment of great men.2024-05-14. <https://v.douyin.com/i2Qyvxs7/> 02/01 UyG:/R@x.FU]

Fig. 234-2. Chairman Mao managed a large China, yet he lived extremely simply. Among the clothes he usually wore, there was a button that was mended, and its color was inconsistent. No leader of other countries could be like that.

[The great leader Chairman Mao will live in the hearts of the people forever.2024-10-27.<https://www.douyin.com/note/7430406550746844425>]

A good social system needs to be designed by great people and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self - discipline.

Fig. 234-2. Premier Zhou Enlai lived a simple life. A Zhongshan suit would be worn by him for more than ten years. The first - ever premier of the People's Republic of China after its founding.

2024-10-08. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7423217528639343881>

Fig. 234-31. Premier Zhou's life was a life of frugality. He never cared about personal enjoyment. Especially regarding food and clothing, he always had strict requirements and strictly prohibited extravagance and waste. The first - ever premier of the People's Republic of China after its founding.2021-02-12. <https://www.douyin.com/video/6927285440315673869>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self - discipline.

Fig 235. The magical Chongqing Sichuan River Gorge, the uncanny work of nature, the highway hanging on the steep cliffs, how did it form in the end! #The uncanny work of nature #Natural wonders #Cliffs #Mountain roads. 2024-03-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqrtB7q/N@j.Px FhO:/ 10/05>

Construction based on rural behavioral economy

Fig 236. The magical Chongqing Sichuan River Gorge, the uncanny work of nature, the highway hanging on the steep cliffs, how did it form in the end! #The uncanny work of nature #Natural wonders #Cliffs #Mountain roads. 2024-03-02.

<https://v.douyin.com/iFqrtB7q/N@j.Px FhO:/ 10/05>

Construction based on rural behavioral economy

Fig 237. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Construction based on rural behavioral economy

One shot, watching the cement roads connecting every household in the deep mountains of 100,000 mountains, it's like a heavenly road, shocking #away from the hustle and bustle of the city #100,000 mountains #mountain roads #beautiful countryside #healing scenery. 2024-03-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqyxYN3/> 05/05 m@q.EH oDU:/

Fig 238. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Construction based on rural behavioral economy

One shot, watching the cement roads connecting every household in the deep mountains of 100,000 mountains, it's like a heavenly road, shocking #away from the hustle and bustle of the city #100,000 mountains #mountain roads #beautiful countryside #healing scenery. 2024-03-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iFqyxYN3/> 05/05 m@q.EH oDU:/

这里就是很多人驱车千里赶来

Fig 238-1. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Developing rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. [Xiangxi, Hunan Province. 2024-04-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iYUffMCu/xSy:/04/28r@R.kc>]

Fig 238-2. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Construction based on rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. North Panjiang Guanxing Highway. [Experience the North Panjiang Highway in Guizhou Province, thrilling and thrilling. 2024-02-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iY9FVjeW/04/25P@K.jcHll:/>]

Fig 238-3. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Construction based on rural behavioral economy. [The winding mountain road built on cliffs in Guizhou Province has scared away many young drivers. Do you dare to challenge it# Thrilling stimulation. 2024-03-01. <https://v.douyin.com/iY9Ff7v6/> lvf:/ 12/28 x@F.Ul]

Fig 238-4. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Construction based on rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. **Zhenfeng North Panjiang Canyon Highway**. [Inventory the stunning self driving highways around Guiyang. These stunning self driving highways around Guiyang. The ordinary path can also be extraordinary. 2023-11-12. <https://v.douyin.com/iY92m3n2/Xzg:/z@G.vS10/21>]

Fig 238-5. The most basic work done by the Chinese government to solve rural poverty is to build roads to almost every household. Construction based on rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy.

[Guizhou Province Expressway Scenic Video. 2024-04-06.
<https://v.douyin.com/iY92t1Db/08/30K@w.seoqR:/>]

Fig 238-6. A road that has deterred countless veteran drivers from other places! The most thrilling road in China is built on vertical cliffs, and local villagers have to ride it for 3 hours every time they go home# Panshan Highway # Eighteen Bend Mountain Road # thrilling # incredible# Construction based on rural behavioral economy and tourism behavioral economy. 2024-06-14.

<https://www.douyin.com/video/7380201340057799975>

The transportation infrastructure projects leading to rural areas in China that can only be completed with national transfer payments. This is a part of political party behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, tourism behavioral economy and rural behavioral economy.

If you have enough courage and technology, perhaps you can choose the right time to experience one of China's most dangerous highways.

Fig 238-7. A road that has deterred countless veteran drivers from other places! The most thrilling road in China is built on vertical cliffs, and local villagers have to ride it for 3 hours every time they go home# Panshan Highway # Eighteen Bend Mountain Road # thrilling # incredible#2024-06-14. <https://www.douyin.com/video/7380201340057799975>

The transportation infrastructure projects leading to rural areas in China that can only be completed with national transfer payments. This is a part of political party behavioral economy, government behavioral economy, tourism behavioral economy and rural behavioral economy.

“受人之托 忠人之事”

1999年，娶了救命恩人遗孀的战地记者
卢宇光：他托我照顾妻儿

“你愿意嫁给我，让我照顾你吗？”

如今，儿子和女儿均在中国上学
品格坚毅，勤奋好学
战友的儿子也始终尊称卢宇光为爸爸，从未改变

Fig 239. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

In 1999, Chinese war journalist Lu Yuguang, as a correspondent, reported from the battlefield during the Second Chechen War in Russia. During his coverage, he encountered a Russian special forces soldier and the two formed a bond, looking out for each other and enjoying each other's company along the way. However, due to the intense conflict, the vehicle they were traveling in hit a landmine. In order to protect Lu Yuguang, the special forces soldier sacrificed himself by shielding him from the

incoming shrapnel. Before his death, the soldier entrusted Lu Yuguang with taking care of his wife and child, a request to which Lu Yuguang agreed.

After the war ended, Lu Yuguang tirelessly searched for the soldier's family and eventually found them. The special forces soldier left behind a wife and a one-year-old son. It was a heart-wrenching moment for Lu Yuguang and the soldier's family upon learning of his sacrifice. As promised, Lu Yuguang vowed to take care of them for the rest of his life. Over time, a deep bond developed between Lu Yuguang and the soldier's widow, leading to a marriage. They later had a daughter together, whom Lu Yuguang treated as his own. Despite the cultural differences and the inherent risks faced by a war journalist, Lu Yuguang's wife became apprehensive and fearful, ultimately leading to a peaceful divorce.

After the divorce, Lu Yuguang brought the two children back to China and supported their higher education. Despite their separation, Lu Yuguang continued to provide regular financial support to his former wife, honoring his commitment to the fallen Russian special forces soldier.

Today, the son and daughter display strong character, resilience, and a diligent attitude towards learning. The son of the special forces soldier continues to refer to Lu Yuguang as his father, and this has never changed.

[Entrusted with a loyal person's task, one should repay it with a gushing spring for a mere drop of kindness. How many people in this world can truly achieve this? Perhaps that is also why Lu Yuguang is respected both in Russia and abroad. #vision #kindness #emotions. <https://v.douyin.com/iJW9nsnd/>]

Fig 240. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

Lu Yuguang is not only the chief journalist of Phoenix TV in Moscow, but also a war correspondent on the Russian battlefield. Since we cannot prevent war, let us tell the world the truth about war. [Revealing the truth, understanding history, and paying tribute to Lu Yuguang. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWytb8w/>]

Fig 241. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

[Russian special forces sacrificed their lives in honor of saving Chinese war correspondent Lu Yuguang! Leave a last word: "Take care of my family." In order to repay the favor and take better care of the benefactor's widow, Lu Yuguang has married and lived a happy life# China Russian Friendship# Touching# Passing Positive Energy # Songs to Others. <https://v.douyin.com/idAeTs16/WmQ:/04/10o@Q.Kw>]

Fig 242. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

Lu Yuguan has a deep bond of camaraderie with Lieutenant General Gerasimov, the director of the Russian Defense News Bureau. This is not only because Lu Yuguan possesses abundant experience as a war correspondent, but also because he embodies the Chinese values of loyalty, gratitude, and kindness. His unique professional integrity has earned the respect of the Chinese people in Russia. Lu Yuguan, driven by his passion and belief in journalism, strives to spread the truth to the world because he cannot stop the war. Ignoring personal danger, he navigates fearlessly through gunfire and explosions.

From General Konashenkov (Игорь Конашенков), the author can still feel a strong breath of righteousness, wisdom, bravery, courage, insight, kindness, and gratitude, even on his tired body, which is rare among Western generals. If General Konashenkov has the opportunity to become President of Russia in the future, it may be of great help to the stability of Russia and the continuity of global peace.

[Character Story: Chinese war reporters, in order to repay their kindness, married the widow of Russian special forces and now break up peacefully. Their son and daughter followed him back to China. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWaPYkA/>],[Chinese war reporters, in order to repay their kindness, married the widow of Russian special forces and now break up peacefully. Their son and daughter followed him back to China. June 27, 2022.

Fig 243 A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

[Character Story: Chinese war reporters, in order to repay their kindness, married the widow of Russian special forces and now break up peacefully. Their son and daughter followed him back to China. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWaPYkA/>]

Fig 244. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

The son of a seventy-five year old grandmother in North Donetsk was killed and left alone. She doesn't know how to live in the future. [In this short lifetime, we will eventually lose. <https://v.douyin.com/iJWGkFtV/>]

Fig 245. A true Chinese person's friendliness is not just verbal or superficial, but comes from the heart and deep down in their bones.

When the battlefield is in danger, the most selfish are Western journalists [Reporter # personally experienced. Sharing Lao Lu's Journalist Experience Here#<https://v.douyin.com/iJ7Lxf5a/>]

Fig. 246. After the snowstorm, the highway was blocked all night, and the nearby villagers came early in the morning... 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdSQ2xG/c@A.gO IIV:/ 07/28>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self - discipline.

Fig 247. Residents along the highways in various parts of Hubei are providing free hot water and food for stranded drivers on the highway! Three years ago, people from all over the country helped Hubei, and the people of Hubei are not cold! Natural disasters have no mercy, but people do! Let's get through this difficult time together! #Hubei #Human warmth #Positive energy #Going home for the Spring Festival2024-02-05.<https://v.douyin.com/iNdap1d9/> 10/31 s@E.hb Vlp:/

Fig 248. Thank you for the love meal sent by my fellow Jishou people. It's the first time I've eaten bacon this year. #The joy of traffic jam on highway. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdmH5XR/Q@x.sR01/08Rkc/>

Fig 249. Only free delivery, not for sale! Villagers near the Macheng section of Hubei Province climb onto the highway to deliver meals #Huanggang #Highway #Seeking Beauty Huanggang. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd9MfNp/03/26OxF:/r@r.rR>

Fig 250. Blizzard can't stop people from returning home for the Spring Festival. The true feelings of the villagers are touching. There is true love everywhere, because we are a family that loves and cares for each other. # Broadcasting video #Human warmth #Touching moments #Positive energy #Heartwarming. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdtDJJW/10/14BtE:/W@M.JV>

Fig 251. Thank you, Hubei. # Original Video #Real Outdoor Life #Have a Seafood Dinner Outdoors. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdnQ2md/goQ:/02/06/Q@K.Wz>

Fig 252. Kind-hearted people from Jingmen, Hubei spontaneously sent free food to those stranded on the highway. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdW6Ly8/> 04/05 a@N.jp trR:/

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 253. The ice and snow are ruthless, but Huanggang has love. In the year of the great epidemic, the whole country saved Hubei. In the face of the snow disaster, the people of Hubei know how to be grateful! Without a call or command, the people of the old liberated area came together and sent water and food to the people of all ages for free! The people of beautiful Hubei have beautiful hearts of China! Wish peace. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd7AXwq/t@e.OKndN:/03/13>

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Fig 256. Episode 83 | On February 5th, in the Macheng section of the Daguang Expressway in Hubei Province, villagers delivered hot meals to drivers stuck in traffic for free, knocking on windows one by one and asking, "Do you need food?" #I want to give you a thumbs up #Hubei freezing rain and snow disaster #Hubei Expressway.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdvFJgF/D@h.oQ GvF:/03/14>

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Fig 259. Peasant friends once again moved people across the country to tears # nostalgia memory # rural life # Tiktok records rural life # my rural life # snow in my hometown. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdcve1R/> 12/31 m@Q.kc Hvf:/

Fig 260. Peasant friends once again moved people across the country to tears # nostalgia memory # rural life # Tiktok records rural life # my rural life # snow in my hometown. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdcve1R/> 12/31 m@Q.kc Hvf: /

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self - discipline.

Fig 261. High-speed icebound, there is love in the world, ordinary farmers around the area distribute food for free. This is the simple farmers of China. The traditional virtues of the Chinese nation are so great and lovely. Farmers are often our angels. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNd3yTVC/06/18fba:/t@R.KW>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 262. #Highway Traffic Jam during Spring Festival# Grandpa Delivers Hot Water from a Long Distance# Warm Chinese New Year # Macheng, Hubei. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdTL52t/04/20V@y.GVHli:/>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 263. Do you know what this is about? The people nearby the Hunan Expressway have given their best to warm the heart of the wandering children passing by. The wandering children are still warm in their hearts, but what about our local officials? I would like to give my fellow villagers a big thumbs up. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdKLYGm/rRK:/S@Y.MW> 09/05

Fig 264. A catering team in Xiaogan, Hubei set up seven large pots near the highway and cooked eggs, noodles and steamed buns for passengers for free. 2024-02-05. https://v.douyin.com/iNdEfQQN/gbn:/07/29_g@B.go

Fig 265. This year, I went back to my hometown to celebrate the New Year, with many touching scenes, which brought tears to my eyes! Let's remember their faces. This year, although we have encountered a freezing and snowy weather that we haven't encountered in many years. The warm scene on the highway makes the people of the whole country feel even more familiar!

Long live the great unity of the Chinese people! Long live the Chinese peasant uncles.
2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR1T3cN/f@b.aA03/28kca/>

Fig 266. In times of crisis, loyalty is seen. The party member commando team delivered supplies to thousands of stranded vehicles at the west exit of Jishou Expressway. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdehr4/k@p.dN09/14 HVL:/>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 267. Wind and snow protection, warm return journey】 Due to the snow and ice weather, the masses were trapped in the Jiazhuoyuan section of the highway in Gong'an County. The nearby villagers spontaneously organized free cooking and hot water delivery, just to let the stranded masses eat hot meals. #Warm-hearted mutual aid under heavy snow and ice traffic jam #Ice and snow road surface #Warm-hearted moment. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdaCeA/KWz:/12/01 X@m.qr>

Fig 268. Wind and snow protection, warm return journey. Due to the snow and ice weather, the masses were trapped in the Jiazhuyuan section of the highway in Gong'an County. The nearby villagers spontaneously organized free cooking and hot water delivery, just to let the stranded masses eat hot meals. #Warm-hearted mutual aid under heavy snow and ice traffic jam #Ice and snow road surface #Warm-hearted moment. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdaCeA/KWz:/12/01 X@m.qr>

Fig 269. Wind and snow protection, warm return journey. Due to the snow and ice weather, the masses were trapped in the Jiazhuoyuan section of the highway in Gong'an County. The nearby villagers spontaneously organized free cooking and hot water delivery, just to let the stranded masses eat hot meals. #Warm-hearted mutual aid under heavy snow and ice traffic jam #Ice and snow road surface #Warm-hearted moment. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRdaCeA/KWz:/12/01 X@m.qr>

Fig 270. Passenger: I cannot repay your kindness, but I wish them a happy wedding and a healthy baby. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR8MGed/> ipq:/ n@Q.kP 08/22

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self - discipline.

Fig 271. Passenger: I cannot repay your kindness, but I wish them a happy wedding and a healthy baby. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR8MGed/> ipq:/ n@Q.kP 08/22

Fig 272. Episode 18 | Cold Snow and Warm Hearts: Passengers Trapped in the Yingcheng Section of Xiaohong Expressway Are Rescued in Time #Blizzard #Safety. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR8GLoG/HiC:/g@o.qR07/30>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

常德高速因积雪致司机受困

正在家中办喜事的男子带队
爬上高速路给受困人送饭菜

Fig 273. Episode 25 | On February 4th, snow caused drivers to be trapped on the Changde Expressway in Hunan Province. A man was celebrating a wedding and led a team to the side of the highway to deliver hot meals to the trapped people. Source: @YiYeZhiQiu. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRLX3pC/> usR:/ E@h.bA 11/14

Fig 274. Ice and snow are merciless, but villagers are the most close. # Villagers' hanging basket sent relief supplies and received warm letters. # Big V said #Big V said hotspot @Jingshi Live.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRLGv9w/> mQx:/ 01/08 j@p.da

Fig 275. Villagers in Xiantao, Hubei, spontaneously used hanging baskets to deliver supplies to stranded high-speed returnees, receiving a warm response: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNgPCu/Nws:/03/30g@O.Kj>

Fig 276. Villagers in Xiantao, Hubei, spontaneously used hanging baskets to deliver supplies to stranded high-speed returnees, receiving a warm response: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNgPCu/Nws:/03/30g@O.Kj>

Fig 277. Villagers in Xiantao, Hubei, spontaneously used hanging baskets to deliver supplies to stranded high-speed returnees, receiving a warm response: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNgPCu/Nws:/03/30g@O.Kj>

Fig 278. But do good deeds and don't ask about the future! I hope everyone on the highway can get home safely! Little things like this really didn't expect to bring so much heat. Thank you very much for all the villagers' efforts, and I am also honored to be a Chinese daughter. #Record True Life. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRNHFLu/>

Fig 279. The high-speed stranded people received help and sent a thank-you letter using a "basket" to express their gratitude. The reply said: "The most beautiful people in Hubei!" #Blizzard #Heartwarming #Hubei @Villager Su Junjie. 2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRFXWku/F@u.fbJCU:/06/01>

Fig 280. The snow is merciless, but people are not. # Highway #Love Knows No Boundaries #Returning Home for Spring Festival. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRf3X/w@s.EU>

Fig 281. 2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRFECnn/06/10m@D.HI.NWZ:/>

Fig 282. Compassion is the highest virtue in all morality. 2023-12-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNR63XJy/MJi:/01/06x@s.eb>

Fig 283. Episode 1 | Warming the stomach and the heart! More than a dozen citizens in Jishou, Hunan, spontaneously sent hot food to people stranded on the highway (Source: @happy) #The atmosphere of the Spring Festival begins with the Spring Festival transportation home #What is the New Year? # 2024 is a beautiful Chinese New Year.2024-02-05. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdwRc6n/lvS/> 10/30 c@N.JI

Fig 284. #On the third day of delivering hot water on the highway, two children who were delivering hot water on the highway ran countless times. The hot water came, friends # Hunan Expressway Positive Energy.2024-02-06. <https://v.douyin.com/iNRweWeH/01/11 mdn:/L@J.II>

Fig 284-1. Anhui Jinzhai is not only a famous tourist destination, but also the most unique and famous "Lu'an Piangua" tea producing area in China. The people here are very simple, and despite the cold and snow, they walk two kilometers and do their best to help drivers and passengers trapped on highways, providing free boiled water, instant noodles, milk, and other food. [2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iNdkFRV/m/e@O.XZ> 03/11 RKJ:/]

The approximate English meaning of Chinese songs in the video:

This is the call of the heart

This is the dedication of love

This is the spring breeze of the human world

Fig 284-2. Xiaochang County, Hubei Province. After heavy snow, the highway was congested, and nearby villagers brought free food and hot water.

[2024-02-04. <https://v.douyin.com/iN8WUXNb/> x@f.BT 03/22 CHv:/]

The rescued personnel wrote a poem:

Snow drifts over Hubei, making roads impassable,
yet the warmth of people's hearts is as thick as spring.
Selfless dedication displays true feelings,
as delivering coal in the snow reveals genuine merit.
If only the whole world could be like this,
with deep affection as boundless as the skies.

English belongs to phonetic writing and originated from Chinese. After translating this poem into English, it cannot accurately express the complex and true meanings of Chinese.

Fig 284-3. [Caring individuals in Jingshan City, Hubei Province set up large pots of noodles, eggs, and other food for stranded individuals at the entrance and exit of the highway. 2024-02-06. <https://v.douyin.com/iN67JKR2/> N@J.vs kCU:/ 09/07]

Jingshan City is the location of the Qujialing Culture over 4000 years ago. It has over 500 rivers, 72 springs, and three major waterfalls.

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 285. #Xinjiang #Gansu #Zhangye City. The city of Zhangye has provided a warm welcome to stranded tourists during the extreme weather in Xinjiang, showing a "charity in time of need" attitude. Source: @Yangtze River News #Extreme Weather #Moment of Touching. 2024-02-18. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwfY3wD/> 09/21 J@v.SY hBG:/

Fig 286. #This is the best tourism promotional video. The strong winds and heavy snow affected more than 20,000 tourists and stranded them in Guazhou. Only 50,000 people in the small county were receiving them. Before the farewell, the official apologized for the poor hospitality. Please forgive us. 2024-02-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwyQEgq/ufO:/J@v.Sy> 11/05

Fig 287. In Guazhou, Gansu Province, there is a history of the Guiyi Army, and today there is a love in the snow. No matter how the times change, the simplicity and kindness of Gansu people will never fade. #Where is Guazhou? # A heart-warming scene in the snowstorm #Guazhou, Gansu Province, is worth seeing.2024-02-25. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwyVcqX/F@H.vF> 04/02 IPK:/

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self - discipline.

Fig 288 Chinese people #Guazhou #positive energy. 2024-02-20. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwf3ST1/05/26t@R.KwZmQ:/>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 289. The entire city of Guazhou in Gansu received 25,000 tourists stranded due to the snowstorm, including residents, businesses, and government agencies. I# Thank you.2024-02-21. <https://v.douyin.com/iNwPM2gX/06/11> PKw:/ J@v.Fu

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

超2万名游客受风雪影响滞留瓜州

5万人小县倾城倾心接待!

Fig 290. Recently, the strong wind and snow affected more than 20,000 tourists stranded in Guazhou, and the small county of 50,000 people warmly received them! #Warm Heart #Passion #Unity (Source @Yuyechengfeng CCTV13, The Paper).2024-02-22.<https://v.douyin.com/iNwyHGDU/v@S.Lw pda:/ 07/06>

Fig 291. As the weather improves, more than 20,000 people stranded in Guazhou have left one after another. Guazhou has issued an apology for any inadequate hospitality..2024-02-20.<https://v.douyin.com/iFuuRjnX/N@W.zg07/31Wzt:/>

Fig 291-1. The founding major general and commander of a large military district borrowed money from a nanny, which in no way diminished his noble character.

In May 1985, General Zhang Zhixiu suddenly said to the nanny, "I promised to send the children of this martyr to college, but I have a little financial shortfall. Can you lend me some money and I will pay you back next month when I receive my salary?" The nanny immediately handed over the money with tears in her eyes and said, "Your family's finances are not abundant, yet you support so many people. Can you report this to the organization?" The general laughed heartily and said, "Family problems should not be made public!" Then he sincerely said, "As a member of the Communist Party, we have the responsibility to give to the people, but no right to ask for anything in return."

2024-03-29. <https://v.douyin.com/iFwWpWwL/Wmq:/01/06 i@P.Kj>

Fig 291-2. Monument: Prototype of the character: Hu Jun (1889-1935), head of the logistics department of a division of the Red Fourth Army. During the Red Army's Long March over the snowy mountains, he sacrificed his life due to the severe cold while marching, and was known as the "logistics head who froze to death."

The text "Monument" revolves around the theme of a monument and narrates the touching story of a logistics chief of the Red Army who, while marching, gave his own cotton coat to a comrade and died of the severe cold. It praises his selfless and altruistic spirit, and his spirit can be regarded as a model.

2023-07-28. <https://v.douyin.com/iFwv7wSa/Y@M.wS 08/14 XMj:/>

Fig 291-3. Kuang Renong, the founding major general. "Red Army generals who fainted from hunger while guarding their own grain bags"

After the start of the Long March, Kuang Renong had been the deputy head of the supply department of the Red 5th Division, and began to follow the troops in their transfer. In August 1935, the main force of the Red Army was preparing to cross the grassland, and Kuang Renong was transferred to the head of the supply department of the Red 13th Regiment. In order to secure provisions for the troops to cross the grassland, Kuang Renong led his supply troops to nearby farms to buy grain.

Unfortunately, due to the sparse population in the area, the procurement of provisions did not go smoothly, and the troops set off without being able to procure enough food. Unable to complete the task of procuring provisions, Kuang Renong took out the

rations allocated to himself and said, "I was unable to procure enough food, so I will give my rations to the larger force to distribute to the comrades."

The comrades all understood that their failure to procure enough provisions was not the fault of the supply department. In order to shake off pursuers, the troops had to take the risk of crossing the grassland and begin a difficult journey. As the head of the supply department, Kuang Renong carried a bag of grain and followed the troops across the grassland.

During the process of passing through the swamp grassland, Kuang Renong did not eat a single grain of food. He dug for wild vegetables, ate tree bark, and grass roots. He even looked carefully through horse dung, to see if there were any leftover grains, and picked them out.

As the grain in Kuang Renong's bag dwindled, he did not eat a single grain, but gave everything to the soldiers. After several days of not eating any provisions, only eating wild vegetables and grass roots, Kuang Renong's face grew pale. As he walked, he suddenly felt dizzy and collapsed to the ground. One of the soldiers in the supply department saw their leader collapse and quickly helped him up, realizing that the leader had passed out of hunger.

The soldier took out a piece of dried beef from Kuang Renong's bag and put it in his mouth, reviving him. When Kuang Renong woke up and saw the dried beef in his mouth, he uncharacteristically became angry. He said to the young soldier, "Comrade, the supplies of our department are meant for the troops, how can I eat them?"

This is the selfless Kuang Renong, responsible for the logistics of the troops, and held himself to extremely high standards. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, Kuang Renong served as the secretary of the logistics department of the East China Military Region, continuing to adhere to the revolutionary tradition of hardship and simplicity. He never bought new clothes, wearing patch upon patch, and took pride in it.

2023-06-09. <https://v.douyin.com/iFw3BRoy/05/22f@o.qe> Euf:/

Fig 291-4. A little red army soldier who, while traversing through the swampy meadows, would rather starve than admit to being hungry in extreme difficulty, and also cares for their injured leader.

One late afternoon in late August 1935, on the vast grassland, Red Army soldiers were struggling to march forward. Dark clouds covered the sky, and heavy rain was about to come.

Chen Gong, the leader of the officer team, re-injured his leg and fell behind the troops. He was leading a tired and thin horse, taking slow steps forward. Suddenly, he saw a young Red Army soldier, who was only eleven or twelve years old, also falling behind. He quickly caught up to him.

When he approached the young soldier, Chen Gong noticed that the boy was wearing tattered clothes, had a pale face, and his grass sandals were already worn out, with his small feet frozen and swollen. Chen Gong asked him, "What's your name, kid? Can't walk anymore? Let me give you a ride on the horse for a while."

The young Red Army soldier replied, "My name is Nine-and-a-Half, I have much stronger endurance than you. You go on ahead."

Chen Gong sternly said, "Kid, you must ride for a while!"

The young soldier stubbornly replied, "I can walk. Or else, let's have a race with your horse."

"Then let's walk together."

"No, you go first. I have to wait for my companion, I'll surpass you in a while!"

Chen Gong had no choice but to hand over the last bit of barley flour from his bag of provisions to the young soldier and said, "Eat it!"

The young Red Army soldier patted his own bulging bag of provisions and said, "You see, I have more than you."

Chen Gong looked at the young boy's bag of provisions and indeed, it was full. He felt that the young soldier was not lacking in food and could recover after a little rest, so he relaxed and continued to lead the horse forward.

Chen Gong's mind was never at peace. After a long time, he suddenly realized that Nine-and-a-Half had never caught up.

It was impossible for Nine-and-a-Half, who looked pale and was stumbling, to have so much food in his bag of provisions. Chen Gong realized that something was wrong and shouted, leaping onto his horse and galloping back along the way.

When he found the young soldier, he had collapsed on the grassland.

Comrade Chen Gong struggled to lift the young soldier onto the horse, and his hand touched the young soldier's bag of provisions. The bag was hard, as if it contained something. He took it out and found a piece of charred ox kneecap, with several bite marks on it.

Comrade Chen Gong understood everything. At that moment, the young soldier stopped breathing.

Comrade Chen Gong held the young soldier tightly, full of self-blame. Later, at General Chen Gong's home, there was always an extra pair of chopsticks and a bowl on the table every Chinese New Year, in memory of the young soldier.

2024-01-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iFKf1gLr/03/15VLw:/d@a.NJ>

2022-05-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iFKaHXAK/i@P.KjRkp:/10/28>

Fig 291-5. Chairman Mao Zedong's ex-wife, the first female Red Army to go up to the Jinggang Mountains, was bombed by Nationalist planes during the Long March. In order to save the injured soldiers lying on stretchers, she threw herself on top of them and was hit by many shrapnel. In a situation completely without anesthesia, she performed surgery to remove some of the shrapnel, leaving a bowl-deep scar on her back. In the end, seventeen pieces of shrapnel were only found in her ashes. 2022-09-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iFKHPvMj/05/17 e@b.Nj RXz:/>

Fig 291-6. Chizhi Bing, a one-legged soldier who had undergone amputation three times, was lying on a stretcher with 17 shrapnel wounds on his body. He was protected from the bombing of Nationalist planes by He Zizhen, the wife of Chairman Mao Zedong.

In 1935, the then political commissar of the Red Army, Zhong Chibing, was seriously injured at the Lou Mountain Pass. His injuries were so severe that the doctors recommended amputation. Due to continuing to fight after being injured, the bone that was hit by the bullet shattered. With limited medical supplies, the surgery had to be conducted under extremely difficult conditions, using only a knife and a broken carpenter's saw. The surgery had to be performed three times, each time under excruciating circumstances. Zhong Chibing endured immense pain during the surgeries, but his strong will allowed him to remain silent. Even when the doctors suggested he call out if the pain was unbearable, he chose to silently endure. The first amputation only removed part of his leg below the knee, but later the doctors had to perform another surgery to remove the rest of his right leg below the knee to prevent infection. Unfortunately, due to extremely poor medical conditions, the wound became infected for a second time, contrary to their hopes.

In a situation where there was no other choice, the doctor was forced to perform a third amputation, this time cutting off the entire right leg from the root. Enduring three amputation surgeries in half a month caused Zhong Chibing to experience repeated pain, and although he ultimately saved his life, he lost his right leg forever.

After the three amputation surgeries, Zhong Chibing became a wounded person with half a leg missing. However, even after the surgery, Zhong Chibing's wound remained severely infected, leading to persistent high fever and unconsciousness. In difficult conditions, doctors performed multiple surgeries and ultimately pulled Zhong Chibing back from the brink of death.

Although Zhong Chibing managed to save his life, the wound on his right leg was difficult to heal. Faced with the daunting task of the Long March, both the commander of the Red 12th Regiment and the Red First Army, Peng Dehuai, hesitated about whether to let Zhong Chibing continue with the army. However, Zhong Chibing expressed a strong willingness to follow the Red Army, regardless of his weakness and disability. In August 1935, Zhong Chibing set out from Luhua, northwest of Sichuan, and began the arduous Long March of climbing snow-capped mountains and crossing grasslands. When he encountered cliffs that were impassable by litter, he would prop himself up with a crutch and push forward. With every step, the wound on his leg would cause intense pain. His guards later recalled, "Commissar Zhong never let anyone carry him over the snow-capped mountains. He crawled bit by bit, often falling from high places. Later, when his injuries slightly improved, he let his comrades tie him to a horse for the march." After crossing countless mountains and rivers, Zhong Chibing arrived in northern Shaanxi with the army in October 1936, bringing an end to the Long March.

After the establishment of New China, in 1954, during the Spring Festival tea party, Guizhou warlord Wang Jialie, as a democratic person, attended the symposium with Zhong Chibing. At that time, Wang Jialie did not know that General Zhong Chibing had been disabled in battle with his own troops. He walked up to Zhong Chibing and bowed deeply, asking, "May I ask, General, what is your surname? How did you lose your right leg?"

Zhong Chibing smiled and said, "I am surnamed Zhong, named Chibing. My legs were borrowed by your honorable army's double gun soldier at Loushan Pass. I don't know when sir will return them?"

The words made Wang Jialie feel deeply ashamed, and he clasped his hands together, saying, "I have long heard of your great name, General, please forgive my past mistakes and continue to guide me."

Years later, Zhong Chibing did not dwell on past mistakes, saying, "Mr. Wang, this is all in the past. History has turned a new page. In the future, we will work together and contribute to the development of Guizhou."

Moved by this, Wang Jialie tightly grasped Zhong Chibing's hand and said, "General Zhong, you truly have the bearing of a great leader. I greatly admire you."

On September 27, 1955, Zhong Chibing was promoted to the rank of major general and was honored with the First-Class 81 Medal, the Second-Class Independent

Freedom Medal, and the first-class Liberation Medal.

[In 1935, Zhong Chibing sawed his leg three times, and He Zizhen blocked the gun for him. Mao Zedong: "Carry the Long March together." 2023-03-16. https://www.360kuai.com/pc/9a9f67d9d3429972a?cota=3&kuai_so=1&sign=360_57c3bbd1&refer_scene=so_1];

[2023-09-02. <https://v.douyin.com/iFK9fwpM/07/28e@o.qr iPx:/>]

Fig 291-7. **The "Eight Females Jumping into the River."**

Eight young women sacrificed themselves by jumping into the river after fiercely battling the Japanese invaders to cover the breakout of the anti-Japanese alliance army.

Cold Cloud (1915-1938), from Huachuan County, Heilongjiang Province, after the Japanese invaded China, she joined the 5th Army of the Northeast Anti-Japanese Allied Forces in 1937. Leading female soldiers, she bravely faced the powerful and cruel Japanese invaders, enduring the harsh tests of nature. Relying on her loyalty to the country and faith in victory, she fought to drive the savage Japanese invaders out of China, engaging in long-term battles between mountains and rivers.

In October of the same year, on the banks of the Wusihun River, a tributary of the Mudanjiang River, she deliberately exposed her position to engage in fierce combat with the Japanese puppet army, in order to cover the breakout of the majority of the anti-Japanese Allied forces. After firing her last bullet and throwing her last grenade, she and 7 female warriors from her unit sacrificed themselves by jumping into the river, known as **the "Eight Females Jumping into the River."**

At the time of the sacrifice, the oldest, Cold Cloud, and An Shunfu, were 23 years old, while the youngest, Wang Huimin, was 13 years old. Their average age was less than 20, the same age as students in the sixth grade of elementary school to just graduating from university. At the height of their youth, like fresh flowers, they withered in the flames of the evil Japanese invasion of China, submerged in the rushing waters of the Wusihun River. However, their lives are forever immortalized in their heroic sacrifice, their young and beautiful faces forever remembered in history, their unyielding spirits immortalized in a timeless monument.

[The "Eight Females Jumping into the River."2023-11-03. <https://v.douyin.com/iFEj4CYL/SIC:/m@q.Eu 08/30>];

[The "Eight Females Jumping into the River."2018-10-21. https://www.sohu.com/a/270275737_425345]

Table 33-1."The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" creates ten world records.

1	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion in Chinese history.
2	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion in world history.
3	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion in World War II history.
4	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion by women in world history.
5	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion by female warriors in World War II history.
6	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by women in world history.
7	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by women in World War II history.
8	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by the youngest women's team in World War II history.
9	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against Japanese invaders by the youngest girls' warrior team in World War II history.
10	"The Eight Young Girls Jumping into the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance against invasion by the youngest girls' warrior team in modern history.

Fig 291-8. Nine brave and tenacious women, each with their own unique characteristics. In the midst of this battle, one of China's most talented and hardworking writers sacrificed her life to rescue these girls, and a renowned musician also perished.

If Hollywood directors are preparing to make a unique, justice-driven, vibrant and youthful film idolizing those who fearlessly fight against evil forces, in order to promote everlasting peace in the world, they should carefully consider this subject matter. Not only is it an unparalleled theme in Chinese history, but also an extraordinary and profoundly moving story in the annals of world history. The

unique plot in this film will help at least achieve high attendance in China.

2022-09-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iYc47Sh6/> ztr:/ 12/18 b@n.qE

What qualifications do we have to forgive the evil Japan for our ancestors?

Table 33-2."The Nine Women Drowning in the River" creates 18 world records.

1	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous resistance by female warriors during World War II.
2	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of brave women resisting Japanese aggression in world history.
3	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of courageous women fighting back against Japanese invaders in World War II.
4	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is an unprecedented story of a group of brave women resisting Japanese aggression in World War II.
5	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most evil beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
6	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most brutal beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
7	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most savage beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
8	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most shameless beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
9	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most hypocritical beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
10	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most despicable beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
11	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most inhumane beastly nature of the Japanese people in World War II.
12	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the Japanese people's talent for pretending to be polite in World War II.
13	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the Japanese people's talent for pretending to be civilized in World War II.
14	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the Japanese people's talent for hiding their true intentions in World War II.
15	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is the story in World War II history that best reflects the most inhumane and beastly nature of the Japanese people.
16	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is the story in World War II history that best reflects the Japanese people's penchant for torturing and abusing prisoners of war.
17	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is the story in World War II history that best reflects the Japanese people's penchant for torturing and abusing women.
18	"The Nine Women Drowning in the River" is a story that best reflects the most evil, brutal, savage, shameless, hypocritical, despicable, anti-human,

pretending to be polite, pretending to be civilized, adept at hiding true intentions, and inhuman nature of Japan in World War II.

Fig 291-9. "Seven sisters" who jumped off cliffs and died for their country.

Seven women soldiers of the Chinese Expeditionary Force fought until they ran out of ammunition and food. They would rather die than surrender, jumping off cliffs and dying for their country.

Salute to the female heroes. Salute to the female heroes.

2023-02-28.<https://v.douyin.com/iYcVmu9R/I@P.KW CUI:/> 11/26

Fig 291-10. "Seven sisters" who jumped off cliffs and died for their country.

Seven women soldiers of the Chinese Expeditionary Force fought until they ran out of ammunition and food. They would rather die than surrender, jumping off cliffs and dying for their country.

Salute to the female heroes! Salute to the female heroes!

In 1942, seven female interpreters were surrounded by the Japanese army during their retreat. Radio is crucial for war. Seven female soldiers, in order to prevent the leakage of confidential information, collectively sounded the hand grenade and died in the end of the world# Passing Positive Energy # Paying tribute to women and not letting men down # Remembering History # Paying tribute to heroes # Like our heroes

2023-02-28.<https://v.douyin.com/iYcVmu9R/> |@P.KW CUI:/ 11/26

唯一的湖南隆回（司门前镇）籍开国少将白天，逝后十年，家乡人才知：

我们隆回县也有一位开国少将！

他战功卓越，却婉拒毛主席、朱总司令说服领中将衔。彭德怀元帅追着他打，骂道：“我是你的入党介绍人，原是国军少将，跟共产党干了近三十年，授中将怎不行？连主席的话都敢不听！”到56年才勉强领少将衔。但白将军对家人一直秘而不宣。73年逝世前对家人说：“司门前人是我的乡亲，全国人民都是我的乡亲。”

Fig 291-11. In 1956, General Wei Wei was promoted to the rank of Major General, but he never told his family about the promotion. It wasn't until ten years after his death that his hometown of Longhui County discovered that there was a founding major general from their county.

Wei Wei, who repeatedly refused the rank of Lieutenant General, finally agreed to be appointed as a Major General, showing his indifference to fame and fortune and his noble character, which is rare in other countries around the world.

Originally named Wei Wei, he was appointed as the Chief of Staff and Deputy Commander of the 93rd Army of the Nationalist Army in 1939.

In 1940, he joined the Eighth Route Army and changed his name to Bai Tian.

In 1955, at the ceremony of conferring ranks in the new China, it was decided to appoint Bai Tian as Major General. However, Bai Tian refused directly without even thinking about it. He believed that after joining the Communist Party, he had mostly worked in administrative positions, and that his achievements did not "deserve" the rank of Major General.

In order to persuade Bai Tian to accept the rank of Major General, many leaders, including Chairman Mao, personally visited him. However, Bai Tian simply said, "In any case, I will not accept the rank of Major General!"

Marshal Peng Dehuai had a good personal relationship with him and scolded him loudly, "You were already a Major in the Nationalist Army, and now they want to give you the rank of Major General, isn't that excessive? Why are you so stubborn?!"

However, Bai Tian still refused. This made Marshal Peng angry, and he immediately picked up his riding crop and waved it towards Bai Tian, saying, "You dare not listen to me and Chairman Mao? Are you trying to make me angry?!"

Seeing Marshal Peng become angry, Bai Tian quickly hid behind a table, and the two of them ended up circling the table. After a while, they both stood panting, staring at each other, neither willing to concede.

After a while, Bai Tian sighed and knew that if he didn't agree to Marshal Peng's request, he wouldn't let him off. So he reluctantly said, "I will accept the appointment, but I will only accept the rank of Major General."

2024-03-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iYef4gTR/Hli:/w@s.Rk> 04/26

Fig 291-12. In 1919, **Xu Rumei** was born into an intellectual family in Wenchang County, Hainan. Her father was a well-known lawyer in the area, and the family was well-off. Xu Rumei was the only daughter in the family and received a good education from an early age. **Her father named her "Rumei," hoping that she would be as proud and**

resilient as the plum blossom.

After the evil Japanese invasion of China, Xu Rumei joined the resistance against Japan. Following the Japanese invasion of Hainan Island, they began to sweep through and commit mass killings. Wherever the Japanese army went, buildings were burned down and the property of the people was looted. Countless civilians fell under the swords and guns of the Japanese army. During a mission, 24-year-old Xu Rumei was betrayed by a traitor who informed the Japanese army, leading to her and several comrades being surrounded by the enemy. While trying to break out of the encirclement, her comrades sacrificed themselves one by one, and Xu Rumei was also seriously injured. Because of her injuries, she left a trail of blood, which allowed the Japanese army to track her down, and she tragically fell into their hands.

The evil Japanese soldiers took Xu Rumei back to a nearby village and subjected her to intense interrogation, trying to force her to reveal the whereabouts of the guerrilla group and the injured. Xu Rumei refused to confess, but was tortured by the enemy. Later, the Japanese army tied Xu Rumei to a tree and tortured her to force her to disclose hiding place of the guerrilla group and the organization's deployment. When **Xu Rumei still refused to confess, the inhumane Japanese soldiers resorted to a cruel method - they brought 11 long iron nails and pierced Xu Rumei's body, nailing her to the tree, causing blood to flow profusely.**

Xu Rumei could no longer speak, but in order to vent their anger, the Japanese soldiers released dogs to attack her body, creating a scene so bloody that it made the villagers present covered their faces and wept.

After Xu Rumei's sacrifice, a miraculous human-shaped tree emerged at the site later.

[She is a female hero in the war against Japanese aggression. She was tortured to death by being nailed to a tree with 11 steel nails. Later, the tree miraculously grew in the shape of a human, and people called it the Hero Tree, paying tribute to the hero. #SaluteToTheHero.2021-09-23. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdjTtWP/02/20TL:/Z@Z.md>]; [How tragic was her sacrifice? She was nailed to a tree by the Japanese army with 11 long nails and was also torn apart by a wolf dog. 2024-01-07. <https://baijiahao.baidu.com/s?id=1787406044218231916&wfr=spider&for=pc>]

网友提问：

为什么解放军那么受欢迎爱戴？

关于朝鲜战争，美国记录了各参战国对平民的暴行，但最后一句是：只有中国没有伤害无辜平民。美军有被俘后反审讯的训练，讲课时第一句就是：“不要认为你会幸运的被中国军队捕获”

一位美军战俘躲在山洞里，惊讶的看见了志愿军战士比比划划的用手语向朝鲜老百姓买白菜，在美军的印象里，这玩意儿还用买？拿过来吃就是了，于是美军十分顺滑的向志愿军投降了。（美军士兵詹姆斯·乔治·温纳瑞斯自己回忆的）他们是真的想投降，只是不敢投朝鲜人民军。人民军都不虐待战俘的，直接当场毙了。

抗战结束后，阎锡山留了一部分投降的日军当自己的王牌，解放战争里这支日本雇佣军被解放军包围，走投无路，派人试探性地问解放军这边：“我们这边还有妇孺，能不能保证所有人的生命安全？”我军回答：你什么时候听说过八路军虐待俘虏？日军一想确实是这个道理，马上投降了。

Fig 291-13. One netizen asked: **Why does the PLA receive so much love and respect?**

Regarding the Korean War, the US documented atrocities committed by various warring countries against civilians, but the last sentence was: Only China did not harm innocent civilians. The U.S. military has training for resisting interrogation after being captured, and the first thing taught in the class is: "Don't think you will be lucky to be captured by the Chinese army."

A U.S. soldier who was a prisoner of war hid in a cave and was surprised to see a volunteer soldier of the Chinese army using sign language to buy cabbage from North Korean villagers. In the impression of the US military, would this cabbage still need to be bought? The U.S. military usually just takes it and eats it, so the U.S. soldiers very smoothly surrendered to the volunteer army. (Recollection of US soldier James George Wrennery)

They really wanted to surrender, but they dared not surrender to the Korean People's Army. The People's Army does not mistreat prisoners of war, they just kill them on the spot.

After the war, Yan Xishan left a portion of surrendering Japanese soldiers as his ace

card. During the War of Liberation, this Japanese mercenary force was surrounded by the People's Liberation Army, with nowhere to go. They sent someone to tentatively ask the PLA: "We still have women and children on our side, can you guarantee everyone's safety?" Our army replied: When have you heard of the Eighth Route Army mistreating prisoners of war? The Japanese soldiers realized this was true, and immediately surrendered.

2024-03-31. <https://v.douyin.com/iYe5yXNB/XMj:/g@o.Qk> 04/26

Fig 291-14. Anti-Japanese hero Zhao Yiman

Evil Japanese invaders tortured Zhao Yiman for nine months before her execution, breaking her ribs and causing at least 24 fractures throughout her body, with some bones even piercing her skin.

But Zhao Yiman remained silent throughout, refusing to give the Japanese any information about the Northeast Anti-Japanese Alliance forces. Her resilience left the Japanese invaders stunned.

At the time, even the Japanese army doctor said that her body's ability to endure pain

had exceeded the limits of human physiology, something that medical science could not explain.

[Anti-Japanese female hero Zhao Yiman. Do not forget the past painful history. Today's peaceful and prosperous era is exchanged by countless ancestors with blood and life. We should strive to be strong and pay tribute to the heroes. #Do not forget national humiliation #Zhao Yiman #remembering history.2024-02-17. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdr4yPu/N@j.Pk dan:/ 08/29>]

Fig 291-15. The most beautiful female teacher in the Wenchuan earthquake

Yuan Wenting (September 6, 1982 - May 12, 2008), from Shifang City, Sichuan Province, was at the Democratic Center Elementary School in Shifang Shigu Town when the Wenchuan earthquake occurred. The school building was severely damaged and collapsed instantly. In order to minimize casualties among the children, she repeatedly

rushed into the classrooms and carried out one child after another with her delicate hands. After her last attempt, the teaching building collapsed, and her youth was forever frozen at the age of 26. She saved a total of 13 children's lives.

2024-03-06. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdUPNdd/N@W.zt> 08/29 QxS:/

山西“铁娘子”王光

1943年，日军对我岳南根据地进行残酷的“钳形合围”“铁滚扫荡”，扬言要变根据地“无人区”。王光担任一区反“扫荡”总指挥。10月一天，她率上寨民兵掩护群众转移，不幸被敌人抓获，受尽酷刑，仍坚贞不屈，最后被灭绝人性的日军开膛破肚挖去心脏，壮烈牺牲，年仅23岁。

Fig 291-16. Wang Guang, the "Iron Lady" of Shanxi, in 1943, the Japanese army carried out a brutal "pincer encirclement" and "iron sweep" against the Yuennan base of our guerrilla region, threatening to turn the base into a "no man's land." Wang Guang served as the overall commander of the first area to resist the "sweep." One day in October, she led the militia to protect the people and transfer them, but unfortunately she was captured by the enemy, subjected to cruel torture, and still remained unwavering.

In the end, she was brutally killed by the inhumane Japanese army, who carved out her heart. She sacrificed herself at the young age of 23.

[Wang Guang, an anti-Japanese heroine, was born in 1920 in Shanxi# Salute to Heroes # Remember History # Never Forget National Shame # Character Stories # Love China 2023-12-30. <https://v.douyin.com/iYdUTqSB/> BGI:/s@e.BT 02/21]

Fig 291-17. The blind soldier from Shangganling carried his broken leg comrade on his back and launched the final charge towards the US military # Salute to the hero. 2023-10-19. <https://v.douyin.com/i2Bj7oW/> 11/11 trE:/J@i.cn

Fig 291-17-1. The video clearly shows **the poor moral quality of Western soldiers** and the excellent qualities of Chinese soldiers, arousing the love of the Chinese people for high-quality Chinese soldiers. 2024-03-12. <https://v.douyin.com/i2SL8GCf/> 11/10 O@X.ZZ qEh:/

Fig 291-17-2. Video of disaster relief. In April 2024, PLA soldiers rushed to aid the flood-hit areas in northern Guangdong. These are the sons and daughters of the Chinese people in uniform. Where there is disaster, there they are. Salute to the frontline rescuers. May everyone return safely. Disasters are ruthless, but there is love on earth. When one place is in trouble, support comes from all sides. 2024-04-24. <https://v.douyin.com/i2S2byBH/Qkp:/K@w.FB 10/05>

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Fig 291-17-3. 2024 Flood Control and Disaster Relief in Northern Guangdong# The most beautiful Chinese soldiers# 2024-04-30. <https://v.douyin.com/i2SjJHfu/> 04/17 vfO:/ Q@x.sR

A good social system needs to be designed by great figures and implemented and realized by outstanding individuals and the public with conscience, empathy, and good self-discipline.

Definition of Social system:

From a historical perspective, both Marx and past sociological theories have overlooked the composition of human society. This neglect has resulted in the prolonged inability of human society to eradicate groups that commit large-scale crimes. Instead, a series of systems have been established to protect such criminal groups, harming victims, kind-hearted individuals, and those with a sense of justice. This has resulted in a blurring of the lines between justice and evil in human society, resulting in the continued occurrence of large-scale heinous crimes and wars of aggression.

Human society is composed of humans and evil humanoid creatures that can speak the human language. Further speaking, human society is made up of kind-hearted people, people with a sense of justice, neutral humans, people lacking empathy, groups that fabricate and invent religious beliefs to commit large-scale crimes (including manufacturing drugs such as opium and trafficking drugs such as opium), evil people, evil races, and groups of humanoid criminals with an appearance just like that of humans. The human social system is inevitably formed in the struggle where some groups commit injustices, plunder wealth, massacre kind-hearted groups and commit evil crimes, while other groups pursue justice, fairness, power, wealth and resist evil.

The process of the evolution of human social civilization is a process of mutual struggle between kind-hearted people and those with a sense of justice on one hand, and groups of evil criminals on the other. It is a process in which kind-hearted people, those with a sense of justice, and neutral people are enslaved, defrauded, kidnapped, tortured, plundered, raped, gang-raped, poisoned with drugs, buried alive, and massacred by people lacking empathy, evil people, evil races, and criminal humanoid creatures. It is a process in which kind-hearted and justice-minded people, after awakening, strive to protect themselves and their kind, and resolutely eliminate and wipe out evil people, evil races, criminal humanoid creatures that look like humans, criminal races, or criminal countries. It is also a process in which kind-hearted and justice-minded people continuously guide the moral evolution of neutral people and those lacking empathy, and constantly combat and reform evil people. Reducing and eliminating evil humanoid creatures that commit heinous crimes is not a crime, nor is it anti-human; rather, it is a process of purifying human society. Conversely, protecting and tolerating these evil humanoid creatures, as well as the groups or nations formed by them, constitutes a grave crime against victims, kind-hearted individuals, and those with a sense of justice.

The social system refers to the general term for one or more systems that reflect and maintain a certain social form or social structure and achieve the inevitable results of that society. It includes the economic, political, legal, cultural, educational and other systems of society.

A vivid description of the definition of the social system: the general term for one or more systems that lead to what the trunk, branches, leaves and flowers of a society look like and what kind of fruit will inevitably be borne.

Definition of Warvigilance:

Warvigilance runs through the whole process of the development of war, starting from the study of the possibility of the emergence of war. In the pre - war stage, through various means, the analysis is mainly focused on the profound political, economic or financial reasons, the moral and conscience status of the country's politicians and voters, the national situation, population factors, immigration factors, religious factors, geographical factors, environmental factors, meteorological factors, military equipment, weapons and ammunition, war - related technologies, the possibility of war, the scale and development trend of war, the possibility of the end of war, possible casualty situations, the handling of prisoners of war, war - related medical care, compensation for casualties, post - war handling, relevant interest relationships, and the formulation of relevant policies for war suppression.

The definition of National Democracy or Country's Democracy or Democratic Country:

The purpose of any activity of any ruling party in a country must be to serve the whole people. Democratic electoral activities and governance that are not responsible for all the people of the country, but only for the election and governance of one or more political parties, cannot be regarded as true democracy. Local or regional democracy cannot be equated with national democracy. In today's world, politicians are used to describing local democratic election activities, or governance activities of members of a single political party, or governance monopolized by two or three parties in combination, or governance activities of the government in which only the high - funded contributors in presidential or prime - ministerial elections can participate as democracy, but none of these are true democracy.

A country with the following behaviors is not a democratic country:

Voters support politicians, political parties or countries that commit or protect large-scale heinous crimes (such as large-scale telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, burying people alive, massacring, plundering the property of civilians, or manufacturing and trafficking drugs like opium, etc.). However, the voters who voted in support of such acts, the politicians, the political parties, and the country itself do not bear all civil and criminal responsibilities, and their descendants continue to enjoy the benefits brought about by the commission of large-scale heinous crimes. Such a country is nothing but an evil criminal country, not a democratic one. The above-mentioned voters and their descendants, politicians and political parties are nothing but a community of criminal groups. Any so-called democratic election in that country is an attempt to select from criminal groups the leaders or organizations that are more capable of committing or protecting the commission of large-scale heinous crimes and reaping the benefits therefrom.

After the politicians and political parties supported by the voters come to power and gain control of the country, they disrupt the country's economic or social order, causing the moral level of the country's people to decline and the number of serious criminal cases to increase. However, the voters who voted in support of such actions, the politicians, and the ruling political party do not bear civil and criminal

responsibilities. Such a country is nothing more than a country that gathers around the center of interests, rather than a democratic one. The above-mentioned voters, politicians, and political parties in that country are merely a community of interest groups.

After the politicians and political parties supported by the voters come to power and hold the power of the country, they do not keep their election promises and formulate wrong policies in the fields of politics, economy, judiciary and other aspects. The public are unable to effectively control or reverse the situation in a timely manner. However, the voters who voted in support of the above actions, the politicians, and the ruling political party do not bear civil and criminal responsibilities. Such a country is nothing but a country that gathers around specific interests, rather than a democratic one. The above-mentioned voters are merely the "cannon fodder" for politicians, political parties or plutocrats to carry out or complete the so-called democratic elections in form.

A nation where the government funds rewards for its citizens to commit mass rape or gang rape of numerous women, yet the perpetrators are neither prosecuted, punished, nor executed, and the victims are unable to receive adequate compensation, all under the guise of so-called religious beliefs.

A society or country where the government protects government officials who have committed serious misdeeds or serious illegal acts, or who bully civilians or vulnerable groups, more than it protects the interests of the common people.

A society or country that protects the wealthy or the plutocracy who have committed serious illegal acts or severely bullied civilians or vulnerable groups more than it protects the interests of the common people.

A society or country where the judicial system tends to protect those in power, the plutocracy, or the wealthy groups.

A so-called racial society or country with religious beliefs formed by stealing a large number of books, forging a large number of cultural relics and books, fabricating history, and inventing a religion.

A country constructed by people who fabricate religion and religious beliefs.

A country where the mainstream media often creates fake news to deceive the public.

A country where the mainstream media often fabricates false news to deceive the public, yet the media and those responsible are not severely punished.

An evil country that illegally occupies the territory of other countries and refuses to return it, except for the lands of the criminal countries in World War II.

An evil and extremely wicked religious nation that has been conducting large-scale telecommunications fraud activities against the citizens of a permanent member of the United Nations (For example, the US) for four consecutive years, defrauding an average of at least \$5 billion annually since 2000.

An extremely evil religious country that has continuously carried out large-scale telecommunications fraud activities against the people of a permanent member of the United Nations (For example, the US), with the cumulative number of defrauded people being at least three million since 2000.

A nation whose entire populace and government spent over 70 years collectively fabricating evidence of being bombed by atomic weapons in order to fraudulently obtain the Nobel Peace Prize.

The standards of a civilized society are as follows:

Definition of Civilization or Civilized Society:

Respect life and severely punish criminals. Let the weak not be fearful, the strong not be arrogant, power not be haughty. Let the incompetent voluntarily step aside. Let the immoral occupy fewer public offices. Let the mediocre make fewer decisions. Let the virtuous and capable not waste their talents. Let the wicked be afraid to do evil. Let the kind people be safe. Make society fairer and more just. Make society full of vitality and let people have inner peace. Let there be education in childhood, learning in adolescence, medical care when sick, support and guarantee when unemployed, support for the elderly. Basic family housing does not need to be taxed. Everyone respects each other. Let the operation of the government be based on a negative feedback mechanism.

Politician or statesman behavioral economics (Behavioral economics of politician or statesman):

Politician or Statesman behavioral economics is a discipline that uses psychology, behavioral science, or behavioral economics as its foundation to study, analyze, clarify, predict, and evaluate the economic problems, behaviors, phenomena, or laws of politician or Statesman in the process of implementing national governance. It aims to guide or promote the adjustment of stakeholders' behavior and the formulation of relevant political, economic policies or public policies.

Political vigilance (Political vigilance): Political vigilance runs through political activities all the time. Starting from political activities, it mainly uses various methods to analyze and identify the causes of relevant social, cultural, customary, religious, political, economic, financial, military, and people's livelihood activities and changes, evaluate the benefits, harms, and risks of relevant political activities, prevent them from being wrongly pushed towards directions that harm society, and establish an effective negative - feedback mechanism through dealing with abnormal issues, so as to establish a civilized society, resolve contradictions and conflicts, promote social harmony and stability, enable people to live and work in peace and contentment, ensure the normal progress of all kinds of work, and facilitate the healthy development of the economy.

Definition of super-large criminal country-type underworld society: A society that commits large-scale crimes, such as large-scale telecommunication fraud, large-scale rape and gangrape crimes, large-scale kidnapping of women, students and children to be used as sex slaves, large-scale torture of the kidnapped, large-scale live organ harvesting from the kidnapped, large-scale massacre of victims, or build telecommunication fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zone for a large number of

criminals, or annex another country with military force, or not abiding by agreements, constantly launching civil wars and annexing the territories of indigenous peoples who hoped for normal rights, or constantly waging civil wars, oppressing and wiping out ethnic minorities who are trying to obtain normal rights, or seize the territory that historically belonged to other countries, or the heinous crimes of forcing sex slaves to give birth to babies, setting up human milk factories, and creating sources of newly born human organs such as corneas and skin, or accumulates a population advantage through the large-scale immigration or long-term immigration of these individuals, drives away the original inhabitants, seizes part of the territory of other countries, attempts to seize the entire territory of other countries, or annex another country with military force, or seize the territory that historically belonged to other countries, but in the name of a country or ethnic group, has seemingly legal military and police institutions, can legally purchase weapons from other countries, and can be protected by the rules of the United Nations! It also legally uses various weapons to attack people's armed organizations that fight criminal gangs that are committing large-scale crimes.

Definition of a super-large criminal religious organization or religious group: It places religion or religious beliefs above the morality, ethics, conscience, and empathy that normal, kind-hearted people possess. It takes advantage of the so-called religious beliefs and the freedom of religious belief, uses religious doctrines to numb individuals, gathers individuals who share the same so-called specific religious belief, raises the so-called anti-racism slogan, commits large-scale crimes (such as large-scale telecommunication fraud, or large-scale rape and gang rape crimes, large-scale kidnapping of women, students and children to be used as sex slaves, large-scale torture of the kidnapped, large-scale live organ harvesting from the kidnapped, large-scale massacre of victims, or build telecommunication fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zone for a large number of criminals, or not abiding by agreements, constantly launching civil wars and annexing the territories of indigenous peoples who hoped for normal rights, or constantly waging civil wars, oppressing and wiping out ethnic minorities who are trying to obtain normal rights), or accumulates a population advantage through the large-scale immigration or long-term immigration of these individuals, drives away the original inhabitants, seizes part of the territory of other countries, attempts to seize the entire territory of other countries, or annex another country with military force, or seize the territory that historically belonged to other countries, or it has already annexed another country by military force since the establishment of the United Nations, or takes advantage of the so-called democratic election rules and the so-called democratic voting advantage brought by a large population to seize the political power or the right to speak of other countries, and forcibly changes the culture or customs of the original inhabitants. Such religious organizations or religious groups are evil.

	The redefinition of the United Nations???
1	The United Nations is not really a very bad organization or institution??

	It has continuously protected countries that commit large-scale crimes. Since its establishment, large-scale criminals and wars have kept emerging. What's even more outrageous is that it legalized crimes committed by countries, leaving victimized countries unable to carry out comprehensive strikes! It is an institution that protects the crimes of religious groups under the pretext of protecting extremely large-scale religious beliefs. Aren't these so-called countries that commit evil large-scale crimes actually super-large criminal gangs? Should they still exist?
2	It is an institution that has long maintained the organizational structure of countries that commit large-scale crimes to be stable and legal and their military forces to exist legally.
3	It is an institution that has difficulty in restraining crimes but is able to protect countries that commit large-scale crimes and fully safeguard the organizational structures and military forces of such countries.
4	It is an institution that can legally protect the leaders of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes and an institution that can prevent the armies of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes from being immediately attacked and eliminated by victimized countries.
5	It is an institution that can prevent the criminals of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes from being immediately attacked and eliminated by victimized countries.
6	It is an institution that can protect criminal groups that commit large-scale crimes from being immediately attacked and eliminated by victimized countries.
7	An institution where a victimized country has been defrauded by criminal groups with the nature of the underworld in countries that commit large-scale crimes, yet the victimized country still has to pay membership fees, even though these criminals have caused the citizens of the permanent members of the United Nations to lose an average of \$5 billion annually for four consecutive years and the victims are unable to recover their losses.
8	<p>The criminal countries that commit large-scale telecommunications fraud crimes have repeatedly attempted to become permanent members of the UN Security Council, and the United Nations has even held meetings to discuss and vote on this issue many times. Should such evil things still be discussed and voted on in meetings?</p> <p>Isn't this era an obviously absurd world constructed by countries that commit large-scale telecom fraud crimes?</p> <p>You may have encountered the most shameless ethnic groups and races, but have you ever seen one that is even more extremely shameless than this? India, which has defrauded the United States and Canada of at least \$5 billion annually on average for four consecutive years, has constantly proposed to become a permanent membership in the UN Security Council. Hasn't the United Nations become an organization that includes members of the underworld? Isn't it strange that India is so shameless? Could an ancient civilization have been born in such a region? Does this make sense? Isn't it fabricated by false</p>

missionaries? Does morality, ethics, conscience and empathy still exist in today's world? Ancient India was in the region of present-day Pakistan. India should change its country name and stop using it to deceive the global public.

However, the United Nations has actually tried to hold meetings to discuss granting the status of permanent membership to countries that commit large-scale crimes. **Why not revoke the right to propose, vote and elect of such criminal countries that commit large-scale crimes based on their crimes.** For every \$1 million defrauded from victims of large-scale fraud crimes, the criminal country's right to propose, vote and make decisions in any international organization shall be revoked for one year; for every \$100 million defrauded from citizens of other countries, the above rights shall be revoked for 100 years; **if the cumulative amount of fraud against citizens of other countries reaches \$10 billion, the above rights shall be revoked for 10,000 years.**

How could President Joe Biden of the world's leading power shake hands with Narendra Modi, the head of a super-large underworld gang that is constantly committing large-scale fraud crimes against the United States? Aren't you afraid of soiling the hands of a leader of a major power? When it comes to large-scale crimes, India has absolutely no moral bottom line. U.S. security agencies and the media should work together to conduct statistics to see when the number of Americans harassed by Indian telecom fraud will increase from the current 50 million to 100 million in the future.

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